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EDITORIAL NOTE

Zamfara International Journal of Education (ZIJE) is the official Journal of the Faculty of Education, Federal University Gusau, Zamfara State, Nigeria. The Journal publishes article of diverse fields of interest in education. Papers reporting original research and extended version of already established conference and journal articles are welcomed. Papers for publication are selected through peer review process to ensure originality, relevance and readability. ZIJE is published bi-annually June and December.

The aim and scope of the journal is to provide an academic medium and an important reference for the advancement and dissemination of information that supports high level learning, teaching and research in the fields of education.

This edition, Volume 3, Number 5, October, 2023 is poised to present research reports in the following fields of education: Educational Foundations, Science Education, Educational Psychology, Curriculum & Instructional Technology, Guidance & Counselling, Philosophy & History of Education, Sociology of Education, Entrepreneurship Education, Special and Inclusive Education, Physical & Health Education, Religious Education, Gender Studies, Peace & Security Education among others. The articles in this volume are academic and professional discourse written by reputable scholars in their areas of specialization.

The Board remain indebted to its editorial members for the ceaseless support given towards successful publication of the Journal. In the same vein, we acknowledge quite sincerely the assistance and support of our esteemed consulting editors for ensuring the credibility of this edition. Also worthy of appreciation are the authors and their immense contributions to this publication.

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The Editorial Board of Zamfara International Journal of Education (ZIJE) calls for scholarly articles for review and possible publication in its next edition (Volume 4). ZIJE publishes articles that emphasize on research development and application within the field of Education. All manuscripts are reviewed by editorial review committee. Contributions must be original, not previously or simultaneously published elsewhere, and are critically reviewed before they are published. Papers, which must be written in English Language, should have good grammar and proper terminologies. Also note that prospective articles are subjected to plagiarism assessment to estimate the percentage of originality of the papers. Hence, plagiarism threshold of $\leq 20\%$ is recommended.

Editorial Guidelines

1. Manuscripts including references, appendices, tables and diagrams should be double-spaced and single coded on A4 paper with generous margins (at least 1”/2.5cm).
2. Title should be explicit and not more than 19 words.
3. Title page should be arranged as follows: Title, author(s) full name, affiliation, full addresses, email addresses and phone numbers.
4. Abstract should be single line and not more than 250 words.
5. For conceptual papers, the body should have appropriate headings where necessary.
6. For empirical papers, it should be presented in the following order: Introduction, Objectives of the study, Research Questions and/or Hypotheses, Methodology, Results, Discussion of Findings, Conclusion and Recommendations.
7. Acknowledgement (if any).
8. Quotations of more than 40 words should be indented and typed single spacing with indication of the pages where the quotes were lifted.
9. In-text citations should follow the APA 7th edition format.
10. References should be in range with 7th edition of APA Style.
11. Each table and figure should be presented within the manuscripts, with a brief and self-explanatory title.
12. All text within the table should be clearly legible, and all graphics and legends should be easily distinguished when printed in black and white.
13. Tables should be in horizontal lines only, with only blank space to separate columns.
14. Tables and figures that may be included in the main text of the paper should be numbered separately, in the sequence that they are mentioned in the text.
15. Figures should be saved in a neutral data format such as JPEG, TIFF or EPS.

Submission of Manuscripts & Assessment Fee

Manuscripts should be submitted directly to the Editor-in-Chief or Publication Editor through the following e-mail address: zijefugusau@gmail.com. Articles can be submitted between the periods of January to April ending for June publication, while July to October ending for December publication. Assessment fee for manuscript is #5,000.00 only.

Dr. Abubakar Sadiq Haruna

Publication Editor

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Adult Education as a Tool For Effective National Security and Sustainable Economic Development In Nigeria

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Abstract

In recent years, Nigeria, like many other African countries have been battling with various degrees of civil unrest, ranging from communal clashes, ethno-religious intolerance occasioned with political violence. National security is described in this paper, as freedom from or resilience against potential harm caused by others. In all the violent conflicts, youth have been the willing tools in the hand of politicians or religious zealots in causing troubles in the land. The reason is premised on the high rate of unemployment and underemployment among the youths which is fallout of faulty educational system that renders Nigerian youth's unemployable in the labour market. The economic predicaments of the Nigerian youths have made them ruthless in crimes and unethical behaviours. It is an established fact that qualitative education can reduce incidences of insecurity and restiveness among the youths, if not totally eradicated. Education, this paper revealed is a major weapon of progressive social change. The paper therefore examined the relevance of adult education and various problems it faces in Nigeria which, if not solved, constitutes hindrance to successful sustainable security and economic development in Nigeria.

Keywords: Adult Education, Effective Security, Sustainable Economic Development

Introduction

Nigeria as a nation is presently grappling with gross underdevelopment, killings, kidnappings, murder, poverty, inequality, hunger, banditry and gross insecurity, violence, ethnic conflicts and religious crisis (Ogechi, 2021). There is also no gainsaying that Nigeria is currently facing serious security challenges, that have put every citizen on the edge including those at the helm of affairs and even the security operatives saddled with the responsibility of securing lives and properties. Hardly can citizens sleep with their two eyes closed as a result of constant attacks on various communities. In the last ten years, there have been a dramatic twist on the wave, dynamics and sophistication of insecurity in Nigeria (Ubong, et. al., 2019). Insecurity that used to be one of the lowest concerns in the hierarchy of Nigeria's social problems has now assumed an alarming proportion. A time we thought that corruption and power failure have the crown of our problems, insecurity in the country has now taken the centre stage (Seji, et. al., 2020). Boko Haram activities, Fulani Herdsmen invasion of communities, money ritualists, internet fraudsters ("yahoo boys"), fake prophets and other secret gangs have created undue hardship, confusion, loss of control, and lack of trust among citizens all gearing towards insecurity (Rabiu & Muhammad 2013).

Education generally plays a key role in overall human development and as well as the backbone of any country's sustainable national growth and development be it security or economic development. Education is usually associated in most countries of the world with formal learning, just the education of children and the young ones alone leaving out the adult members of the communities and cities, the vulnerable and all other marginalized groups. Whereas, United Nations declaration 2030, stated that the right to education is a human right that must be enjoyed by all, irrespective of age and where located (Ogechi 2021) Education should be for all as it is deemed a universal thing and that it must be inclusive, equitable, of good quality and one that promotes lifelong learning for all. The essence of education is further established that education is a public good, a fundamental human right and a basis for achieving, for guaranteeing the realization of other rights (United Nation

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2015). The above implies that for any type of development to be sustainable, secured and maintained, education must reach all, ignorance must be wiped out and illiteracy must be subsided. Adult education must therefore play a key role in the nation's socio-economic development to curtail the problems of insecurity.

Adult Education and sustainable economic Development in Nigeria

Adult education as an integral part of education plays a key role in sustainable development, promotes economic growth, as well as social, and environmental dimensions to sustainable development and creates favourable conditions for empowering citizens globally for development. Adult Education is a learning process whether formal, informal and non-formal which the adult engages in for skills acquisition, knowledge, better information equipment and development. Adult Education can generally be taken as any form of learning undertaken by men, women and youths in the formal or non-formal school system. The main targets of adult education are specifically (girls and boys over 15 years of age, the migrants, the normads, drop out, less privileged, physically challenged, professionals, workers and educationally disadvantage people in the society among others) (Ubong et al 2019). Although literacy continues to be emphasized, adult education also includes computation of figures, problem solving, acquisition of skills and numerous forms of knowledge impartation (Ogechi, 2021). Adult Education emphasizes all forms of functional education programmes for youths and adults outside the formal school system (Aderinoye 2007). Such education programmes include basic literacy programme, post literacy programme, continuing education programme, and vocational education programme (FRN Blue Print 2008). These adult education programmes are geared towards human and national development which encompasses security and economic development. Nzeneri (2010), quoting a UNESCO working document, sees adult education in a more encompassing way as the entire body of organized educational process, whatever the content, level and method, formal or otherwise, whether they prolong or replace initial education in schools, colleges and universities as well as apprenticeship, whereby persons regarded as adults by the society to which they belong develop their abilities, enrich their knowledge, improve their technical or professional qualifications and bring about changes in their attitude or behaviour in the two fold perspectives of full personal development and participation in balanced and independent social, economic and cultural development of the society. The above opinion is broad and encompassing in that, it does not only define adult education but it also defines its content and scope.

Adult education provides employers in different sectors of the economy with qualified and sustainable skills and manpower which service the economy and provide basis for rewarding the adult members (Okemakinde and Ogunyinka 2016). Farhey (2010) observes that: "people who are more educated know why they are not supposed to make prejudice comments and consequently disguise their prejudices". Adult education, by solving the problem of injustice, deprivation and oppression brings peace and harmony among adult members of the country and hence ensures sustainable security and economic growth and development. It will by no means solve the current problems of kidnapping, youth restiveness and insurgency in the country if properly annexed. Fasokun (2006) observes that: adult education is concerned not with preparing people for life, but rather with helping people (adults) to live more successfully as useful and acceptable members of their societies and contribute meaningfully to the overall development of those societies. Hence, the benefits of adult education to the overall development and the security challenges in any nation and to individuals cannot be over-emphasized by bringing peace and tranquility.

Adult Education and Effective National Security in Nigeria

The issue of security is not alien as it has been the central focus of primitive society. In the same vein, Audu et. al., (2014), argued that since the end of the cold war, there appears to be shift from viewing security from state-centric perspective to a broader view that places emphasis on individuals, in which national security also encapsulates human security, human right and national development. National security according to Iredia (2011), simply mean, the capacity of a state to overcome challenges confronting her. Iredia (2011) also opined that national security is not limited to military might, defense or law enforcement; it covers basic dimensions like job, water and food security. National security is also seen as a state or condition in which most cherished values of a country and the people are permanently protected and continuously enhanced. The concept of security also denotes the condition or feeling of safety from harm or danger. It also means the defense and protection of values acquired. Security has to do with freedom from danger or threat to a nation's ability to protect and develop itself, promote its cherished values, legitimate interests and enhance the well-being of its people. Internal security implies freedom from danger to life and prosperity. Audu, et al (2014), explained security as any mechanism devised to alleviate the most serious threats that prevent people from pursuing their cherished values. While, according to Mezieobi (2012) the term security brings to mind issues that pertain, predominantly, to one or a combination of the following whenever it is discussed:

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1. The defence and protection of national integrity or Nigeria's sovereignty, territorial and political jurisdictions from external and internal interferences or intervention;
2. Personal safety of members of political class who are in control of the helm of affairs of governance, in addition to safeguarding or protecting their office, hence the incredible allocation of funds for security services;
3. The security agents or forces, civil defence corps protecting the lives and properties of the mass of the defenseless citizenry against the menace of the men of the underworld;
4. Forestalling or deterring possible internal attacks or crises and subjugating insurgency;
5. Keeping the security agents on active security alert and readiness at all points in time;
6. Checkmating impending or actual internal threats to state or national security or anti-social behaviours by those who are deliberately undermining or sabotaging government efforts;
7. Checkmating social problems such as Boko-Haram saga and youth militancy, kidnapping/abduction that may pose threat to state and national security and detract the political cadre in control of state affairs from active commitment to their functions; and
8. By making the environment free from insecurity to attract international investment.

This is in line with Robert McNamara's earlier quoted assertion on the relationship between growth, national development and peace and security. From the above, security therefore can mean the state of being free from danger, risk or threat. It covers freedom from anxiety, fear, the safety of a state or organization against criminal activities and attacks like terrorism, theft or espionage (Ogheneakoke, 2014). The security interests of any nation therefore include safety of lives and properties, economic, physiological, mental well-being and the freedom to pursue the attainment of objectives without hindrance. Hence, insecurity implies a state of vulnerability to attacks, danger or threats to a people, their properties, cherished values and the inability of the nation to protect its citizenry. Alemika (2016) postulated that insecurity can be classified into several dimensions with the most significant dimensions as:

1. Physical insecurity- violent personal and property crimes;
2. Public insecurity- violent conflicts, insurgency and terrorism;
3. Economic insecurity- poverty, unemployment;
4. Social insecurity- illiteracy, ignorance, diseases or illness, malnutrition; water borne disease, discrimination and exclusion;
5. Human right violations- denial of fundamental rights by state and non-state actors in different states; and
6. Political insecurity- denial of good and social democratic governance

The dimensions of security as highlighted above are interwoven and cannot be treated in strict isolation as explicated by Anan (1998) cited in (Joshua, Dominic and Ibieta 2016) that: "Security" today means far more than absence of conflict knowing that lasting peace requires a broader vision encompassing areas such as education, health, democracy and human rights, protection against environmental degradation and the proliferation of deadly weapons. Also, there cannot be security amidst starvation, peace cannot be without alleviating poverty, and freedom cannot be built on the foundations of injustice. These pillars are understood as people-centered concept of human security which is interrelated and mutually reinforcing.

Condoleezza Rice, former Secretary of State of the United States of America posited that quality education of a nation is a direct function of a country's national security (Joshua, et al 2016). This relationship springs from the role education plays in providing the knowledge base for technological training, advancement and human capital development. Thus, education is as important as national security. The Boko Haram insurgency has become a festering sour because the Nigerian military are fighting 21st Century Islamic military insurgency with nineteenth Century military education (Ejirika, 2014). In the Nigerian context, internal security particularly from 2007 till date seems to be elusive (Joshua et al 2016). Some of the indicators of insecurity in Nigeria include; ethno-religious conflicts, violence, kidnapping, terrorism among others. Insecurity has taken different dimensions in the various regions in Nigeria. For instance, in the Niger Delta region (South-South), the militants slugged it out with oil companies in the area, killing and destroying oil company's properties as well as Federal Government properties especially from 1999-2007 (Joshua et al 2016) In Jos, Plateau State (North Central), the Hausa and the indigenes have been at war from around 2002 till date. In South-East, kidnapping, ritual killing, herdsmen -farmers clashes and armed robbery has been the nature of insecurity in the region same with the South-West region of the country.

Boko Haram insurgency has been the greatest challenge to internal security in the North-East, North-West and North Central from 2009 till date (Joshua et al 2016). Fear, apprehension and jitteriness have become the lot of Nigerians. Consequently, huge amount of fund is always allocated to security by government for the purpose of addressing these threats of insecurity (Ogechi 2021). A cursory glance at the Nigerian daily newspapers will convince one of the states of insecurity in the country. Youth restiveness, kidnapping, bombing, arson, militancy, insurgency inter alia, have become the order of the day

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(Ogheneako, 2014). National growth, economic development and human capital development have all been hampered by this social problem. Robert McNamara, a onetime president of the World Bank, once observed that no country can develop under an environment of insecurity. Also, argued that peace and stability, are necessary condition for growth and development. In the Nigeria context, Mordi (2013) noted that the nation's growth and stability have been truncated by the on-going mayhem and destruction of lives and property in different parts of the country by the menace of Boko-Haram in the Northern states, the militants and kidnappers in the south-South; among others. Food production has been grossly affected and on the decline as farming and agricultural activities have been hampered, while oil exploration, exploitation and export have been negatively affected in the North and south-south, respectively (Omoroge, 2012). In all these cases of insecurity, youths are the prominent figure in the crusade of crime. Such youths either lack requisite education that render them jobless, unemployable, poor and disenchanting; or are educated and are still jobless. Poor youth find it difficult to resist temptation to commit crime, provided such will open way to meet their immediate needs. In other word, education and national security are inexorably linked together. Little wondered that strength, security and wellbeing of any society rest squarely on the quality of education.

Effective Security and Sustainable Economic Development in Nigeria

Effective security is a prerequisite for sustainable economic development. Effective security is one that endures and lasts, one that will not roll back or recede, even in the face of threatening reversal waves. It is a kind of development which can assure the security and protection of the environmental and its resources presently and subsequently (Ogechi 2021). When the security of any nation is threatened, the economic development of such is grossly affected. Sustainable development is an amalgam of two component words; namely "sustainable" and "development". A clearer understanding of each of these two component words is necessary to make this discourse more meaningful. The literary meaning of "sustainable" is that which can continue or be continued for a long time; capable of being maintained at a set level, keep up assumed role competently (The American Heritage Dictionary, 2000; The 21st Chambers Dictionary, 2001; Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English, 2003; Hornby, 2005) in Ogechi, (2021). Establishing relationship between adult education and security for sustainable economic development, require peace and harmony to function. Sustainable security and economic development through education foster healthy and safe environment where people can thrive and function in a sustainable way. Viewed from this perspective, security is one of the most basic needs of people no matter the age bracket or status and also the territorial environment.

In Maslow's hierarchy of needs, security and safety is ranked second to physiological needs. This is a motivational theory in Psychology with a five-tier model of human needs. This theory assumed that lower needs in the hierarchy must be satisfied although not totally, before individuals can attend to higher needs. These needs are: physiological, safety, love and belonging, esteem and self-actualization. However, these needs have been further divided into two: deficiency needs and growth needs. Deficiency needs arise due to deprivation leading to insecurity and economic deprivation if not met. The most basic need of an individual is physical survival and this is what motivate and control human behaviour. Individuals' inability to satisfy deficiency needs causes insecurity, youth restlessness and other social vices rampaging the society most especially in Nigeria.

Modern day research in social sciences and education also requires that theoretical and rational foundation be provided for overall conceptualisation of critical phenomena and issues in the society for proper clarification. Hence, Moronkola (2006) in Ogunyinka, (2014) opined that a theory is a set of formulations designed to explain and predict facts and events that can be observed. Thus, for the purpose of this paper, Maslow's Theory of Hierarchy of Needs is adapted for clarity of purpose and to buttress the inability of the society to meet the basic human needs propounded by Maslow leading to restiveness, kidnapping, high rate of unemployment among the youths causing high rate of insecurity in Nigeria.

Figure 1: Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs :(Mcleod, 2018)

According to the theory, basic needs must be met by an individual before moving to the next level of needs. However, the inability of most of the youths to meet the physiological and safety needs in the society is causing the high rate of insecurity in the country. People want to experience order, peace predictability and be in control of their lives (Mcleod 2020). Therefore, security is also a political issue on account of the key decisions that need to be made by country's authorities to regard a particular issue as a priority. Ensuring security is regarded as one of the most fundamental objectives and functions of country. Generally, it depicts protection against military attacks, but it includes security from terrorism, economic security, food security, cyber security, and territorial/environmental security, maintenance of independence and sovereignty of the nation and security for natural disaster. Security becomes the core fulcrum on which revolves all other developmental indices of a state or nation. The economic, social, political and indeed every other dimension of development are all anchored on security.

In realization of this fact the Nigerian constitution regards security as the fundamental objective of state policy. It is also observable that the governments adopt some measures which include political, economic, military, civil, diplomacy, dialogue and other intelligent tactic to safeguard the security of the nation. In all, adult education provides the skills, needed information, education, debate forum, knowledge, sensitization and creativity to develop new approaches that are necessary for sustainable security and economic development. A paradigm shift is only possible through critical, conscious and innovative exposure of citizens to adult education that is more encompassing.

Causes of Insecurity in Nigeria

Ogheneakoke (2014) identified a plethora of factors as causes of insecurity in Nigeria. These include, but not limited to, the following: Corruption, Marginalization, Social inequality, Ethnicity, Poverty and greed, Loss of value system, Religious intolerance, Foreign infiltration – insurgency, Bad leadership, Youth unemployment, Porosity of our borders, Falling standard of education, Poor judiciary system, Cultism and cult activities, High value for material things, Manipulation of electoral processes by political parties, Lack of trust on security agents, and Human right abuses among other causes.

Implication of Insecurity in Nigeria

The socio-political and economic landscape in Nigeria has been blighted by the endemic twin evil of crime and violence (Seji et al 2020) The abysmal failure of successive administrations in Nigeria to address challenges of poverty,

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unemployment and inequitable distribution of wealth among ethnic nationalities, ultimately resulted in anger, frustration, agitation and violent crimes against the Nigerian state by individuals and groups. Such crimes include militancy, kidnapping, bombing, armed robbery, destruction of government properties, among others. The activities of various militia groups consequently resulted in low income for government from oil revenue, moderating the gross domestic product growth (GDP) rate, low participation of local and foreign investors in economic development and insecurity of lives and properties of the citizens (Seji D.O. Omoroje, Philip Onyekachukwu Egbule, 2020).

The cost of life and material resources to insecurity in the country since the past few years is unquantifiable. According to Human Rights Watch, a security monitoring agency, between 2009 and 2012, about 2,000 lives had been lost to militia insurgency; within the first nine months in 2012, 815 people were killed in 275 suspected attacks, and more than 60 police stations were attacked in 10 Northern states, excluding the bombed police headquarters in Abuja. Tens of dozens are still nursing various degrees of injuries. The data base of orphans and widows caused by the rampaging sects has grown vastly, swelling the numbers of internally displaced persons (IDPS). Money from some international organization and funds raised locally from governmental, non-governmental agencies, charitable organizations and individuals that is supposed to be channeled to human capital development has been deployed for the rehabilitation of families of the casualties and the renovation of properties destroyed. Yearly, unspecified millions of naira is being paid as ransom for the release of victims of kidnappers: not forgetting the Central Bank of Nigeria's N100 million cash donation, N200 million donation from the combined efforts of the opposition governors, and the \$50,000 (USD) from the Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN), America chapter, to reduce the suffering of the victims of regional militia (Seji et al 2020).

As Nigeria struggles with the army of unemployed youths of about 24%, companies in their numbers are closing down operations in Boko-Haram ravaged North and oil-rich South-South, and relocating to other African countries for loss of lives and properties (Seji et al 2020). And the few remaining companies operate on skeletal bases. Construction workers and expatriates providing specialized services on various projects in these regions have fled for safety. This development has multiplied the number of unemployed youths roaming the street which has become an easy tool for violence. This scenario has not only deepened the existing unemployment rate but also paints a gloomy picture of poverty. Education is the bedrock of social economic development (Freire, 1970) .in Ogechi (2021) The Islamic militants have serially attached students and facilities in educational institutions in different Northern states of the country (Chibok Girls and Burnin Yadin Boys Government Schools) (Seji et al 2020). Over time, a lot of schools have shut down their academic programmes as a result of insurgency, banditry and kidnapping. These have drastically impacted the teaming number of students seeking admission into academic institutions at all levels. For example, University of Maiduguri, one of the most affordable universities in Nigeria which is known for turning down admission of students because of quality and to avoid overcrowding of facility, now solicits for admission through different media outreach. Also recently, a respondent survey shows that many students have vowed never to participate in the compulsory one-year National Youth Service Corps (NYSC) programme if posted to the Northern part of the country (Seji et al 2020). Those who were inadvertently posted to the North redeployed immediately after three weeks of mandatory camping. This development therefore defeats the core mandate of setting up the Act of NYSC in 1973 (FinIntell, 2013).

Roles of Adult Education in Checkmating Insecurity in Nigeria

There is a significant relationship between National security and education, a cursory look at the personality of Boko-Haram Islamists and bandits in the Northern region of Nigeria reveals high level or rate of illiteracy among them (Seji et al 2020). It is in the light of this that the Emir of Kano, HRM Lamido Sanusi, admonished the elites of the region to establish schools, instead of building mosques. Also, in a bid to help reduce the rate of illiteracy the past administration of President Goodluck Jonathan established Nomadic education and Al-Manjeri schools in the Northern region. UNESCO (2008) stated that "No development can be possible without humans, and no humans can reach development without quality education". It is in light of this, that Anadi (2008) opined that for a nation to be developed and secured, there must be a very considerable proportion of trained educated citizens in that nation not only to act as doctors, engineers, teachers, agriculturist, scientists, and the likes, but also to create a new class sufficiently large and hence, sufficiently strong to establish its own values of justice, security, selection on merit, flexibility, empiricism and efficiency. For this to be actualized, the education system (primary, secondary and tertiary levels) must be practical and functional. Therefore, quality education is the primary agents of national security and development for bringing the vision of society into reality. "For example, if the militants, Boko-Haram, armed robbers and kidnapers were properly nurtured with quality formal, informal and indigenous education from the grass root level, all the security threats/challenges such as terrorism, riots/civil unrest, demonstrations, intolerance, cult-related criminal acts,

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religious intolerance, armed robbery, intra and inter-ethnic strife, drug trafficking, human trafficking, kidnapping, hijacks and many other vices threatening lives and properties would not have been in existence” (Osakwe, 2013).

However, in order to make adult education a tool for achieving effective security and sustainable economic development in Nigeria, the following suggestions are made:

1. Adequate allocation should be made for education in the National budget to meet the UNESCO International benchmark of 26 percent to make more funds available for education and ultimately for adult education. Adult education practice should be reviewed constantly, organized and systematized in order to develop a more coherent and useful agenda for adult education to give it the needed respect among other disciplines.
2. There should be more awareness through mobilization and advocacy because many interested learners are not aware of the existence of adult education centres and even the programmes, they are supposed to enroll in.
3. There should be establishment of more centres of adult education in the six geo-political areas of the country so that every individual will have easy access to education and not have need to travel long distances to acquire skills and knowledge needed for security and development.
4. Basic and Post literacy programmes should be free in all the states of the Federation and the programmes should be based on the learners’ needs and aspirations.
5. Upward review of facilitators’ remuneration should be in accordance with the minimum benchmark as set by the Non-Formal Education blue print that facilitators should be paid minimum wage as their remuneration or allowances.
6. Only qualified persons with Nigeria Certificate in Education and specialization in adult education should be employed as facilitators in the Non-Formal Education centres. More capacity building programmes (pre-service, in-service and on-the-job training) for Adult and Non- Formal Education personnel at all levels should be put in place.
7. There should be regular and effective monitoring of programmes at all levels and there should be capacity building for monitoring and evaluation of officers through short-, medium- and long-term training programmes, workshops, conferences amongst others.
8. People will have good perception of adult education programmes, if they are timely, relevant and innovative and if these programmes reflect practical and real-life situation. The negative perception will change to positive one, when there is effective management and administration of adult education programmes.
9. The introduction of peace education as an integral part of the adult at this critical period of Nigeria's nation-hood is quite imperative and if properly designed and developed, it will help to control the rising cases of insecurity and armed conflicts in some parts of Nigeria.

Conclusion

Adult education being life-long and life wide learning activities provide programmes that address any particular issue. With peace education sustainable development is achievable which invariably will lead to economic development. The goal of peace education is to curb violence by resolving conflicts in a non-violent manner to share limited resources equitably and live within the limits of sustainability. When people develop sound mind and right sound attitude, there will be harmony tranquility, peace, accord and acceptability without fear. Farmers can go to farm, fisher men to rivers, traders to markets, students go to school without fear, workers work and come back home, free movement and transportation of goods and services, value of life is restored and economic is invariably developed.

Recommendations

1. This paper therefore suggests that a revitalized adult education is a tool that could be used in achieving human capacity for sustainable security and economic development in Nigeria.
2. Through Adult Education programmes, the much needed technical and vocational knowledge, skills, values and attitudes needed by the adult populace for sustainable development are achieved. In addition, also, adult education will enable people to become well-informed, capable of thinking critically and owning their destiny through active participation.
3. Successful and sustainable development cannot be achieved when majority of the populace is illiterate.
4. Thus, the political will to encourage adult education especially in areas of funding would only be achieved through a deliberate and sustained effort by government to ensure that the percentage of fund allocated to education in the yearly national budgets meet the international bench-mark of 15-25 per cent as recommended by UNESCO in 2018 among several other measures discussed to revitalize Adult Education.

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Assessment of Administration, Planning and Supervision among Government Secondary School Principals in Dala Educational Zone of Kano State

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Abstract

This paper assessed administration, planning and supervision among government secondary school principals in Dala educational zone of Kano State. Three objectives and corresponding research questions guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consists of all public secondary school Principals in Dala Educational zone, during the 2022/2023 academic session. 55 (35 Male and 20 Female) principals constitute the sample size of the size, this was arrived at using multi-stage sampling technique. The instrument was validated and reliability coefficient of 0.741 was obtained using Cronbach alpha reliability test. The conclusion was made as effective motivation and supervision of educational and planning is necessary for good outcomes of secondary schools. The recommendations Government should provide periodic training, seminars, and workshops on planning for principals.

Keywords: Administration, Supervision, Educational, Planning, Principals.

Introduction

Educational institutions including Secondary Schools are designed to achieve specific goal of preparing individuals as good and responsible citizens. Olajide (2016) asserted that principals are key administrators in secondary schools through whom their competencies would influence teachers to achieve secondary educational goals. Principals could play their roles effectively towards the attainment of the objectives of secondary schools when they possess the requisite competencies, leadership, talents, administrative efficiency, managerial skills, planning skills and the competency to motivate teachers to pursue such effort, which could help in achieving stated secondary educational goals. As an administrator, every principal is expected to provide professional guidance to teachers in order to improve the conditions which affect learning and growth of students and teachers. In discharging their administrative roles, principals may help teachers to perform their jobs in preparing lesson plans; good use of instructional materials or aids, keeping and maintaining of school records, provision of required instructional materials to teachers among others (Fika, Ibi & Aji 2015). Educational planning is an element of the educational and leadership management in educational institutions that includes ambition of general and specific objectives and priorities from educational strategies and existing resources to predict the future of different circumstances. This is corroborated by DeMathers et al, (2020) who argued that the main beliefs, values, knowledge, teaching and educational management practices by the school administration reflect their educational effects and the outcome on tis educational institutions (Kaufman, 2020). Nwabueze, (2016) is of the view that the principals provide good leadership for proper direction and effective coordination with the school to develop and maintain effective educational administration and Planning programmes and promote the improvement of teaching and learning in the school. The principals have the responsibilities for the organization of the school, development of instructional programme, assigned of duties to members of their staff, general operation of the school facilities and whole school supervision (Wallace Foundation (2013). The role of the secondary school principal has changed dramatically over the past two decades. Once seen primarily as instructional leaders, principals are now increasingly being viewed as government agents, responsible for implementing government policies and agendas. This shift has been driven by a number of factors, including the rise of standardized testing, the increasing focus on accountability, and the growing emphasis on school choice. As a result of these changes, principals are facing a number of challenges, including balancing the demands of multiple stakeholders, managing an increasingly complex bureaucracy, and maintaining a focus on student learning amidst competing priorities (McKenna, 2018).

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Education deals with knowledge acquisition, training and development of the individual to be able to contribute positively. Education embraces not only school experiences but also indirect or incidental influences which help us to learn, which activities affect our characters, behaviors and perceptions. Ogunode, (2020) sees education as an enabling agency by which Africans could restore their self-confidence, and make those who doubted the humanity of Africans begin to revise their views and learn to respect Africans. From the above education is a form of training given to the individual that makes him useful in the communities. Administration has an infinitive form to administer, which means to manage. It also derives from the Dutch Language “administratie” which meaning ranges from administration to management of organizational activities. Some experts provide definitions for the term. Administration is the overall determination of policies, setting of major objectives, identification of general purposes, and laying down of broad programs and project. Administration is the guidance, leadership and control of the efforts of the groups towards some common goals. <https://www.hashmicro.com>.

Educational administration is a process that includes the combined operation through which a country is maintained in good working conditions. It is a process of utilizing appropriate material in such a way as to promote effectively the development of human qualities. It includes all those techniques and procedures employed in operating the educational organization in accordance with established policies. It is the totality of resources which are made available and made effective for accomplishing the purpose of an enterprise. Educational administration includes functions like planning, organizing, financing, directing, supervising, inspecting and evaluation. It is also concerned with elements like setting up of goals of education, review, feedback and innovations (wordpress.com). Nwankwoala, (2016) defines the term as a broad umbrella encompassing a number of processes such as planning, coordinating, controlling, and being involved in other management processes and contribute to formulation of policies. In order, to achieve these goals, the head of the educational organization plans carefully various programmes and activities. The educational organization may be a school, college or university. The head organizes these programmes and activities with cooperation from other teachers, parents, and students, motivating them and coordinating the efforts of staff members as well as directing and exercising control over them. The head evaluates the performance and progress of staff in achieving the purpose of educational programme, provides feedback to them and brings modification in the plans and programmes of the institution when required. The totality of these processes, which are directed towards realizing or achieving the purposes of the school is called educational administration.

Planning is considered one the basic processes that emphasis importance in improving the policies, ways, and means, which are organized to choose the best possible solutions to reach certain objectives in light of the different organizational resources. Orefice and Guraziu (2018). The concept of educational planning has developed within a comprehensive framework of steps, procedures and methods used to achieve these objectives and to ensure the degree of achievement of the objectives in the process comprehensive pre-vision of all the elements of the educational process Ismail et al, (2021). And it was not on a specific aspect of the educational process but rather it concerned with the educational aspects in the educational institutions. Yemini et al, (2018). Furthermore, it is applied to education at all levels and its forms and stages, regular and non-formal and addresses the categories of society in educational institutions, educational circular, effective teaching methods, teacher preparation, technological means and others. Aderonum, et al. (2021) defined educational Administration as “essentially a service, activity or which the fundamental objectives of the education process may be more fully and efficiently realized. Educational administration broadly means running of education institutions, which involves guidance, leadership and controlling of the efforts of individuals in the achievement of the goals of the institutions. Okoroma (2016), outline the objectives of educational administration are as to provide proper education to students to ensure adequate utilization of all resources; ensure professional ethnics and professional development among teachers; organize educational programmes for acquainting students with the art of democratic citizenship; mobilize the community; organize co-curricular activities effectively for developing talents of students and work efficiency of educational teachers. He further stated to include get the work done; prepare students for taking their places in vocations and of life and train the students in developing scientific attitude and objectives outwork among them towards all aspects and activities of life and to ensure quantitative improvement of education. Motivation is an internal process. Maslow stated (Sutrisno and Sunarsi, 2019) that the motivation is to create the driving force behind the stimulation of work to collaborate, work effectively, and integrate into their job satisfaction efforts. However, Matsso and Dahlqvist (2013), assert that motivation is an essential tool for improving and retaining employee performance in Dala Educational Zone, Kano State.

Educational Administration and Planning of Principals activities are very paramount importance in the secondary school education, which requires adequate planning by the principals for the improvement of quality assurance which lead to the attainment of educational goals/objectives including academic excellence, discipline, high enrolment, good administration and excellence outcome of the school results. Therefore, lack of effectiveness of supervision by principals such as regular lesson

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plan check as well as scheme of works, lack of monitoring of staff activities, lack of observing teachers attitudes, mentoring teachers on modern teaching methods and facilities, lack of incentives for those who observed, lack of regular training, workshop and seminars, lack of adequate training and resources: Many principals in Dala Educational Zone lack the necessary training and resources to effectively administer, plan, and supervise their schools. This can lead to a number of problems, including ineffective leadership, poor decision-making, lack of accountability, poor communication: There is often a lack of communication between principals and their staff. A lack of trust, lack of collaboration, lack of shared goals in effective use of data: Principals often do not effectively use data to inform their decisions. Poor resource allocation, ineffective interventions, lack of progress Low morale: There is often low morale among teachers in Dala Educational Zone. This can be due to a number of factors, including poor leadership, low pay, lack of resources, High turnover: There is a high turnover rate of principals in Dala Educational Zone. This can lead to: lack of continuity, lack of institutional knowledge, lack of stability by the principals are the major problems that study needs to overcome. In line with the above, this paper intends to assess administration, planning and supervision among Government Secondary School principals in Dala educational Zone of Kano State.

Objective of the Study

The aim of the research is to assess administration, planning and supervision among Government Secondary School principals in Dala Educational Zone of Kano State and the specific objectives are as follows;

1. Determine the extent of supervision on improving secondary school administration among principals in Dala Educational zone of Kano State.
2. Determine the extent of motivation on improving secondary school administration among principals in Dala zone of Kano State.
3. Determine the extent of interpersonal influence on improving administration among principals in Dala Educational zone of Kano State.

Research Questions

1. What is the extent of supervision on improving secondary school administration among principals in Dala Educational zone of Kano State?
2. What is the extent of interpersonal influence on improving administration among principals in Dala Educational zone of Kano State?
3. What is the extent of interpersonal influence on improving administration among principals in Dala Educational zone of Kano State?

Methodology

This study adopted descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consists of all public secondary school Principals in Dala Educational zone, during the 2022/2023 academic session. 55 (35 Male and 20 Female) principals constitute the sample size of the study, this was arrived at using multi-stage sampling technique. The instrument of data collection was structured questionnaire which was validated by 3 experts. The instrument was validated and reliability coefficient of 0.741 was obtained using Cronbach alpha reliability test. The data collected for this study were coded into statistical package of social sciences (SPSS), 25.0. The package was used to calculate mean and standard deviation.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the extent of supervision on improving secondary school administration among principals in Dala Educational zone of Kano State?

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Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Influence of Supervision on Principal Administration and Planning in Dala Educational zone of Kano State, Nigeria?

S/N	ITEMS	N	MEAN	SD	REMARK
1	The principal supervises instructional activities to improve teacher's competencies	88	3.58	1.251	Agreed
2	The principal supervision improves identification of areas of strength and weakness.	88	3.75	1.215	Agreed
3	The supervision provides adequate control measure and properly established by principals.	88	3.47	1.219	Agreed
4	The supervision help in avoiding wrong decision and mistake from the teachers.	88	3.76	1.238	Agreed
5	The principal supervision improves teachers' self-confidence and ability to perform duties effectively.	88	3.62	1.234	Agreed
6	The supervision improves decision making process.	88	3.73	1.173	Agreed
7	The supervision upgrades the level of performance of subordinate.	88	3.58	1.126	Agreed
8	The supervision helps in analysis of problems and skillful use of logic and good judgment.	88	3.66	1.234	Agreed
GRAND TOTAL			3.64		

Source: Field Study 2023.

The output of the descriptive statistics presented in table 1 revealed that all items of the variable of Influence of Supervision on Improving Principal Administration in Dala zone of Kano State, Nigeria were having a mean score of above 3.0. The mean scores of secretarial professions ranging from 3.47 to 3.58. The grand mean of supervision on improving school administration is 3.63 which is above the benchmark of revised four-point Likert scale. The results indicated that the respondents agreed with statements that supervision influence the performance of Principals administration in Dala zone of Kano State, Nigeria.

Research Question 2

What is the extent of motivation on improving secondary school administration among principals in Dala zone of Kano State?

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Influence of Motivation on Principal Administration and Planning in Dala Educational zone of Kano State, Nigeria?

S/N	ITEMS	N	MEAN	SD	REMARK
1	Stimulating and providing guidance by the principal display improve the school administration.	88	3.59	1.222	Agreed
2	The principal encourage the staff by encouraging their effort.	88	3.48	1.303	Agreed
3	The exchanging ideas and opportunity arouse teaching and no teaching attention.	88	3.69	1.190	Agreed
4	Without tangible reinforcement staff cannot charge their duties at the right time.	88	3.74	1.121	Agreed
5	Reward and punishment are the measure for improving school administration by the principals.	88	3.70	1.991	Agreed
6	The division of labor by the principal improve the quality of leadership in the school	88	3.69	1.269	Agreed
7	It was too easy to share my decision content with subordinate in order to improve the leadership.	88	1.32	1.032	Disagreed
8	The principal felt control of the leadership style in the school	88	3.69	1.269	Agreed
GRAND TOTAL			3.36		

Source: Field Study 2023

The output of the descriptive statistics presented in Table 2 indicates that only one items of the variable on the influence of Motivation on Improving Principal Administration in Dala zone of Kano State, Nigeria disagreed with mean score of 1.32,

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while other items agreed were having a mean score of above 3.0, the mean scores of motivations on improving principal administration ranging from 1.32 to 3.74. The grand mean of motivation on improving principal administration is 3.36 which are above the benchmark of revised four-point Likert scale. The result indicates that the respondents agreed with statements of Influence of Motivation in Improving Principal Administration in Dala zone of Kano State, Nigeria.

Research Question 3

What is the extent of interpersonal influence on improving administration among principals in Dala Educational zone of Kano State?

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of Influence of Interpersonal skills on Improving Principal Administration in Dala zone of Kano State, Nigeria?

S/N	ITEMS	N	MEAN	SD	REMARK
1	Good planning improves level of positive relationship among the staff.	88	3.48	1.219	Agreed
2	The duties assign to staff create room for good relationship between staff and principals	88	3.68	1.189	Agreed
3	The principal is responsible for improving healthy relationship between staff in the schools	88	3.63	1.217	Agreed
4	Friendly and responsible relationship improve good administration by the principal.	88	3.14	1.333	Agreed
5	The principal is responsible for an attending staff improve complain improve the school administration.	88	3.29	1.297	Agreed
6	Maintaining temper and remain cool even in chaos situation improve principal administration.	88	3.68	1.248	Agreed
7	The frequent get together with subordinates improve the principal administrations.	88	3.62	1.336	Agreed
8	The team work is element of improving principals' administration in the school	88	3.70	1.991	Agreed
GRAND TOTAL			3.38		

Source: Field Study 2023

The output of the descriptive statistics presented in Table 3 indicates that all items of the variable on the of Influence of Interpersonal skills on Principal Administration in Dala zone of Kano State, Nigeria agreed were having a mean score of above 3.0, the mean scores of Interpersonal skills on Improving Principal Administration in Dala zone of Kano State, Nigeria relevancy of secretarial profession in public institution ranging from 3.13 to 3.68. The grand mean of interpersonal skills is 3.07 which are above the benchmark of revised four-point Likert scale. The results indicated that the respondents agreed with statements of interpersonal skills improving principal administration.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of research question 1 indicate that the respondents agreed with statements of Influence of Motivation and Supervision on Principal Administration and Planning in Dala Educational Zone of Kano State, Nigeria. This is in line with finding that there are effective principal's supervisory roles that encourage teacher's job performance. Nakpodia (2011) who noted that teacher's performance in Secondary schools is significantly dependent on the capacity of the principals effectively conduct adequate and valuable supervision which validates the importance of discipline, record keeping and teaching aids. Supervision refers to the activities that are directed towards improving the conditions sounding the growth of the students and teachers. The role of principals as a supervisor is to improve, encourage, coordinate and direct teachers towards personal and institutional goal attainment. Supervision of teachers by principals is a prerequisite to enhance professional standard in teaching profession.

The findings of research question 2 revealed that respondents agreed with statements of Influence of Motivation on Principal Administration and Planning in Dala zone of Kano State, Nigeria. This is in line with findings of there are lack of motivation of teachers on secondary schools' administration and planning in Dala educational zone of Kano state by encouraging poor planning on record keeping, causing poor planning of periodic workshops and conferences in schools. This

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brings hazy preparation of budget, causes poor teaching, because of poor teaching plan, breeds role conflict amongst staff, causes inadequate and poor facilities and instructional materials, there are school insecurity, poor maintenance of equipment, poor educational administration and planning of extracurricular activities and leads to poor classroom supervision. This is in line with Ikediugwu and Chukwumah (2015) who stated that probably the reason for poor infrastructure, inadequate staffing, inadequate funding and poor-quality assurance owing to various training limitation could be adduced to poor strategic management skills of the principals who have not dutifully motivated to put things in place. Therefore, poor educational administration and planning breeds mismanagement and mal administration in secondary schools. Principals should try as much as possible to see that effective and proper training and motivation is carried out in the schools to avoid all these negative influences on their schools.

The finding of the research question 3 indicates that that the respondents agreed with statements interpersonal skills on principal administration and planning. This in line with Mustapha (2019) and Wang Pollock and Hausemen (2019), whose findings rated principal's interpersonal relationship at the most important source of the principal administration. This corroborates Di Benneto and Afered (2017), who arrived within the school community is a crucial determinant of attainment of educational goals and principal's administration. This means that a positive interpersonal relationship fosters not only principal's administration but in their entire life.

Conclusion

The successful administration, planning and supervision among government secondary school principals in Dala educational zone of Kano state that the provision of necessary regular training, and working materials should be provided by the government. Encourage principals to use data to inform their decisions and the government review that teachers' salaries and allowance for effective administration to take place. An effective educational and planning is necessary for good outcomes of secondary schools. Practicing good administration and planning in schools helps in maximizing fund resources, human and material resources to meet the demands of education in order to achieve the desired goals with the given time. Also, good administration planning is required to get full cooperation of staff in the schools and the need to change, improve and adapt the educational system to suit our needs. With all these things in place, good school administration is guaranteed. Provide principals with the necessary training and resources: Principals need to be trained in effective leadership, decision-making, and data analysis. They also need to be provided with the resources they need to do their jobs effectively. Improve communication between principals and their staff: Principals need to establish open and honest communication with their staff. This can be done through regular meetings, one-on-one conversations, and surveys. Address the factors that contribute to low morale among teachers: Principals need to create a positive and supportive work environment for their staff. They also need to advocate for better pay and resources for teachers. Take steps to reduce principal turnover: Principals need to be given the support they need to be successful in their roles. This includes providing them with training, mentorship, and resources.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Government should provide periodic training, seminars, and workshops on planning for principals.
2. Government should place experience and high level of education as conditions for principal ship. This will improve successful administration and planning in schools.
3. Principals should have to establish interpersonal relationship to teachers and good communication skills in their schools.
4. Government should provide adequate funds to secondary schools to enable principals engage comfortably in the administrative responsibilities.

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Assessment of Admission Exercise and Political Interference at Secondary School Level of Education in Kebbi State

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Abstract

The paper Assessment of Admission Exercise and Political interference at secondary school level of Education: A case Study of Kebbi State, with one objective of the study as to examine the Admission Exercise and Political interference at secondary school level of Education in Kebbi State, and a research question as to how does political interference affect the students' admission exercise in government secondary schools in Kebbi State? as well a single null hypothesis was formulated to know whether there is difference in the opinion of the respondent and the title of the research. A case study survey research design was adopted for the study, being descriptive in nature, with a population of the study consists of 5177 comprising all government secondary schools education stakeholders in Kebbi State during the 20/20 academic session, a sample size of 376 stakeholders was used, which comprises of (18 principals, 327 teachers, 10 school based management committee members and 10 quality assurance officials), five points Likert questionnaire titled Assessment of Admission Exercise and Political Interference at Secondary School Level of education (AAPISSLE) was used as an instrument or collection of data collection, a reliability test of the instrument was conducted coefficient of 0.81 was obtained using Cronbach alpha reliability test.84,data was analysed using descriptive statistics such as frequency count, percentages, mean scores, tables and charts. ANOVA was used to test hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance for the study. At the end findings revealed that there is political interference in education in the admission exercise of government secondary schools in Kebbi State, it was concluded that politics interfere into educational system of the state, a recommendation was made that government should give the state ministry of education free hand to exercise its official mandate according to the law.

Keyword: Political, interference, student admission, secondary school.

Introduction

The civilian administration in Kebbi State made tremendous effort to develop educational sector through enhanced budgetary allocation to bring back the lost glory. Despite all the efforts, improvements of academic performance of secondary school education in the state are still low Haliru (2018). This could be due to improper leadership in the administration of state educational system, manifestation of this can be observed from the insufficient teaching and learning facilities, infrastructural conditions as well as distortion in the educational settings that were in existence since the time Kebbi State was under Sokoto State, one of which is closure of Science and Technical Education Board despite the fact that the Edict establishing it has not been amended by the state legislature, Report of the committee on the Improvement and Development of Education in Kebbi State (February 2013). Contract for the supply of educational facilities were awarded without consulting the real stakeholders: students, teachers, parents and community needs etc, Report of the committee on the Improvement and Development of Education in Kebbi State (February 2013). This is why most of the time resource allocation is not commensurate with school's requirement, posting of teacher is lopsided, as well as poor placement of students' admission, accordingly some schools are overstaffing while others were understaffed especially between rural and urban secondary schools in the state Haliru (2018). Secondary school in urban areas have more than 100 students per class as against the provision made by National Policy on Education (article 113 (a)) of not more than 35 to 40 students per class, Report of the committee on the Improvement and Development of Education in Kebbi State (February 2013). The criteria for student's

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admission were not strictly adhered to, because students are placed on request from their parents hence overcrowding of students in urban secondary schools Haliru (2018).

Admission of student into secondary school should be an exercise that supposed to be conducted by expert in the field of education, that will take into cognizance of so many factors such as socioeconomic background of the child, especially where the contribution of government is absent or become very minimal, the accessibility of schools (geographical location), consideration on ability/capacity of the child, which is normally identified after an evaluation by the experts, that will help them to identify whether or not a child could be good in science, art, social science and or technical, and above all there should be no biasness in all this activities Haliru (2018). Research conducted by Osuji (2011), reveals that there is disparities between urban and rural schools, between schools owned by the state government and the federal government and that of private agencies. There is also a serious gap in terms of enrolment between male and female as well as in the case of admission figures and resources available In Kebbi State because of nature of schools in the rural areas no qualified teachers, no conducive environment for teaching and learning parents normally refuse to take their children to the school admitted especially in the rural areas thereby moving them the urban area especially State Capital. Secondly, another factor is because of the involvement of politics in the education sector almost all the major villages in each of the 21 Local Governments has either two or more, Day or Boarding Secondary Schools. This is in line with what Muhammad (2013) as: the decision to locate a school is based on other consideration such as place of origin of the policy maker and the political strong hold of the policy maker and the political strong hold of the party in government, for instance it is quite common in Nigeria for a commissioner and other political office holder to go to a ceremony and announce the sitting of a new school in the locality without asking the educational planner to determine the viability of such as school. Because of the above reason many parent especially less privileged would want their ward to be at home because of two factors; to spend less in sending the child to school and to have some assistance for their personal issues. That brings about in balance in admission plan of the State Ministry of Education.

The admission of student in Kebbi State into secondary schools is based on the following criteria by Directorate of Quality Assurance, Kebbi State Ministry of Education (2016).

1. Result of the student during BECE (Basic Education Certificate Examination) otherwise known as Junior Leaving Certificate Extermination result, which will determine which area a child understands better of sciences, commercial, art, social science and or technical that will give the committee saddled with the responsibility of admission idea as to which school a child should be admitted to. And for Junior Secondary School (JSS) Students are to be selected from various primary schools in the state, with regards to his/her performance at the Common Entrance Examination to any Day/Boarding Secondary School in the state.
2. The geographical proximity (where you Leave) of child to the school which he/she is to be admitted to, this is in consideration of socioeconomic background of the parent.
3. For Physically challenged children, because the State has only one School for the Special Needs and it's located in the state capital, parents who do not want their child to be far from them for special care and the special need does not include hearing and vision can be admitted in any nearby school in the state.
4. Parents need not to apply for the admission.

Globally secondary education denotes two processes. First, Access; This means universal provision of secondary schools and universal enrolment of children in the age group of 13 to 18 groups. All children in the age group of 13 to 18 should have access to secondary schools. There should not be any discrimination on grounds of sex, religion, place, or socio-economic status. Second Access: By simple providing access to secondary schools, we cannot claim that we have universalized secondary education. Along with access to schools we should make adequate provisions in the schools so that children can experience success in secondary education. Adequate number of trained teachers, qualitative learning and teaching materials, aids and equipment, classrooms, as well as a balanced admission of students etc. should be provided in each and every school to facilitate successful completion of secondary education. Success is to be determined in terms of attainment of Minimum Levels of Learning which means most of the students would acquire most of the competencies. Thus, political involvement in education, should not be a reason why a child should be denied proper placement in terms of admission based on the observed capacity, without which it will have its future consequences to the society Muhammad (2013). In view of the above, the researcher intends to find out if there is any research conducted in this research area, but was able to find a studies conducted by Muhammad in 1991 Educational Facilities and Needs of Secondary Schools in Sokoto State, which was before the creation of Kebbi State, secondly is the research conducted by Dada (2008) titled Influence of Politics in Administration of Secondary

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Schools in Kebbi State the third study conducted in the area related to this study is by Jega (2004) unpolished PhD thesis titled Influence of Politics in Administration of Secondary Schools in Kebbi State, study in School Mapping and Rationalization also a study by Haliru (2018) on school mapping politics in the activities of secondary schools in Kebbi State was also reviewed by the researcher. In all four studies it was realized that not a single one was directly focused on admission exercise in the area thereby giving the researcher an opportunity to conduct this study as Assessment of Admission Exercise and Political interference at secondary school level of Education: A case Study of Kebbi State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

Assess impact of political interference on admission exercise into government secondary schools in Kebbi state, Nigeria.

Research Questions

To what extent does political interference affect admission exercise into government secondary schools in Kebbi state, Nigeria.

Hypotheses

There is no significant difference between political interference on admission exercise into government secondary schools in Kebbi state, Nigeria

Methodology

A case study survey research design was adopted for the study, which is descriptive in nature and according to Ishaya in Haliru (2018) is appropriate for a study that involve large population of respondents. The aggregate total population of the study is 5177 which include 274 principals, 4538 teachers, 274 school based management committee members, 91 quality assurance officials. Sample size is 365 (7%) respondents which comprises of 18 principals, 327 teachers, 10 school based management committee members and 10 quality assurance officials, and this is based on research advisors (2006). Purposive sampling technique was adopted by the researcher which afforded the researcher a chance to select 2 educational zones which is (30%) out of the 6 educational zones the justification of the selection of these two zones is because of the preponderance of schools in the zones. Using random sampling technique 9 schools were randomly selected from each zone, 9 principals, 5 quality assurance officials, 5 SBMC members. Teachers were chosen based on population in the schools, 102 teachers from Argungu educational zone and 125 from Birnin Kebbi Educational zone. Research instrument for this study was titled Assessment of Admission Exercise and Political Interference at Secondary School Level of education (AAPISLE) questionnaire with Likert five points scale option which include; strongly agree, agree undecided, disagree and strongly disagree. The questionnaire consists of section one personal data of the respondent section two 10 option statement for testing hypothesis. A reliability test of the instrument was conducted using Cronbach alpha .84. Data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency count, percentages, mean scores, tables and charts. Inferential statistics such as ANOVA was used to test hypothesis for the study. Since the instrument is structure along a modified five-point Likert scale, decision mean of the research is 3.0 which is term as weighted mean, it is to be used as decider as whether to accept or reject the research question. Thus, anything less than 3 the score is rejected and above is accepted. This is shown below. SA = 5 points, A= 4 points, UD= 3 points, D= 2 points, SD= 1 point $\frac{5+4+3+2+1}{5} = \frac{15}{5} = 3.0$

Results

Research Question

To what extent does political interference affect admission exercise into government secondary schools in Kebbi state, Nigeria.

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Table 1. Mean Score of Respondents on the Assessment of Admission Exercise and Political interference at secondary school level of Education: A case Study of Kebbi State

S/N	Item statement	Respondent	N	Mean
1	Age of a student is considered during admission exercise due to political interference in education in government secondary schools in Kebbi state	Principals	18	4.3
		Teachers	327	4.2
		SBMC	10	3.8
		Q/Assurance	10	4.4
2	Religion is considered in students' admission due to political interference in education in government secondary schools in Kebbi state	Principals	18	3.7
		Teachers	327	4.1
		SBMC	10	4.5
		Q/Assurance	10	3.4
3	Political interference in education affects student's entrance examination before admission into government secondary schools in the Kebbi state.	Principals	18	3.9
		Teachers	327	4.0
		SBMC	10	4.1
		Q/Assurance	10	3.7
4	There is ethnic consideration in the admission of students into government secondary schools in the state due to political interference in education.	Principals	18	3.5
		Teachers	327	4.1
		SBMC	10	5.0
		Q/Assurance	10	4.5
5	Urban secondary schools are over populated due to the political interference in education during admission of student into government secondary schools in the state	Principals	18	4.1
		Teachers	327	4.1
		SBMC	10	4.5
		Q/Assurance	10	3.8
6	Rural schools are less populated due to political interference in education during admission into government secondary schools in the state.	Principals	18	4.2
		Teachers	327	4.1
		SBMC	10	4.4
		Q/Assurance	10	4.4
7	There is admission imbalance as a result of political interference in education into government secondary school in the state.	Principals	18	3.2
		Teachers	327	3.8
		SBMC	10	4.2
		Q/Assurance	10	4.4
8	Geographical proximity is considered during admission due to political inference in education on government secondary schools in the state.	Principals	18	4.4
		Teachers	327	4.1
		SBMC	10	3.0
		Q/Assurance	10	3.6
9	Availability of space is considered during admission due to political inference in education in government secondary schools in the state.	Principals	18	4.3
		Teachers	327	4.1
		SBMC	10	5.0
		Q/Assurance	10	4.5
10	Unqualified students are offered admission due to the political interference in education in government secondary schools in the state.	Principals	18	3.8
		Teachers	327	4.1
		SBMC	10	4.7
		Q/Assurance	10	4.2

Source: Field survey (2022)

From table the result show that, item 1 revealed that principals having mean score of 4.3, teachers 4.2, SBMC officials 3.8 and Quality Assurance (Q A) 4.4. It indicated that the statement was accepted by the respondents. Item 2 indicated that principals have mean score of 3.7, teaches 4.1, SBMC 4.5 and QA 3.4, which implies acceptance. Item 3 was also accepted with the mean score for principals 3.9, teacher 4.0, SBMC 4.1 and QA 3.7. Item 4 was accepted by all the respondents with the mean score of 3.5, 4.1, 5.0 and 4.5 for principals, teachers, SBMC and QA representatively. Item 5 had mean score for principals 4.1, teachers 4.1, SBMC 4.5 and QA 3.8, which indicated acceptance. Item 6 showed that principals had mean score of 4.2, teachers 4.1, SBMC 4.4 and QA 4.4. Item 7 was accepted by principals, teachers, SBMC, and QA, with the respective mean

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scores of 3.2, 3.8, 4.2 and 4.4. Item 8 have the mean score of 4.4, 4.1, 3.0 and 3.6 for principals, teachers, SBMC and QA, accordingly. Item 9 have the means score of 4.3, 4.1, 5.0 and 4.5 for principals, teachers, SBMC and QA respectively and was accepted. Similarly, item 10 was accepted with the corresponding mean score of 3.8, 3.1, 4.7 and 4.2 for principals, teachers, SBMC and QA. It was revealed therefore that political interference in education has serious impact on students' admission exercise in government secondary schools in Kebbi State?

Hypothesis Testing

H0₁: There is no significant difference in the opinion of principals, teachers, quality assurance officials and SBMC representatives on the Assessment of Admission Exercise and Political interference at secondary school level of Education: A case Study of Kebbi State.

Table 2. ANOVA on the Assessment of Admission Exercise and Political interference at secondary school level of Education in Kebbi State

Admission exercise	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2.447	3	0.816	0.871	0.456
Within Groups	337.945	361	0.936		
Total	340.392	364			

Source: Field survey 2022

Table shows the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the opinion of respondents on the political interference in education on students' admission exercise in government secondary schools in Kebbi State is retained. Reason for this is because the calculated significant value (p) of 0.456 is higher than 0.05 alpha level of significance set for the study. This implies that the responses of the respondents were in agreement.

Discussion of Findings

The findings further revealed that Assessment of Admission Exercise and Political interference at secondary school level of Education: A case Study of Kebbi State, Reasons being politics has influence over geographical proximity to schools, over population of urban secondary schools, as well as having less population in the rural schools, It was also reveal that politics influenced the availability of space for setting up secondary school. It further revealed that politics influence admission of unqualified students which is also as a result of influence of politics on the students' entrance examination before admission, age is also being influence by politics. These findings are in agreement with the opinion of Osuji (2011), which reveals that there is disparities between urban and rural schools, between schools owned by the state government and the federal government and that of private agencies. There is also a serious gap in terms of enrolment between male and female as well as in the case of admission figures and resources available

Conclusion

In conclusion, based the research conducted it was observed that the level at which politics interfere into educational system of the state is beyond imagination, in which in the real sense one may not expect, because education as a system if it's not allowed to function under a guiding principle, the danger or consequences of such action is going to manifest in the future which may not be in the interest of the society. This is because the findings observed that interference has reach the level at which, a politician asking the head of an organisation in charge of teachers' administration to force the head teacher of a school to accept his child on admission even if he did not qualify for the entrance examination, to be admitted in such institution else he will be sanction.

Recommendations

The research recommends that government should give the State Ministry of Education free hand to exercise the its mandate officially according to the law, given proper admission with consideration of factors associated with admission criteria.

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Assessment of Causes of Mental Health Challenges among Retirees in Ifelodun Local Government Area of Kwara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Mental health problem has gained research interest in the recent years among researchers. Mental health underlies the extent to which individual functions cognitively, emotionally, socially and physically. The retirees had been statistically found to have decreased quality life due to psychological conditions that can be clinically diagnosed and treated. Thus, the study examined "causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area, Kwara State". Descriptive design was adopted for the study and multi-stage sampling method of purposive, stratified and simple random sampling technique. The samples of the study comprise of one hundred and twenty (120) retirees in Ifelodun local government area, Kwara State, Nigeria. The researchers used "Causes of Mental Health Challenges Questionnaire (CMHCQ)" to elicit relevant information from the respondents for the study. The instrument was subjected to test re-test reliability statistical method and result from this exercise yielded 0.86 reliability coefficient. Frequency counts and percentages were used for demographic data. The null hypotheses formulated were analysed using t-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at .05 level of significance. The findings of the study indicated that the major causes of mental health challenges are; absence of functional intervention programme, brain malfunction/defect/injury and financial unpreparedness. The hypotheses tested revealed no significant difference in the causes of mental health challenges as expressed by retirees in Ifelodun local government area, Kwara State based on gender and religion but significant difference was noticed based on year of retirement. Based on the outcomes of the study, some recommendations were made.

Keywords: Causes, Mental-Health, Challenges, Retirees.

Introduction

The lives of the retired civil servant individuals in Nigeria have been characterized by multifarious mental-health challenges in a continuum of tormenting experience with little or no assistance to alleviate their pains. It is on records that many of the retired civil servants in Nigeria have experienced one form of mental-health condition or the other after their retirement, which has hindered the quality of life that they had previously enjoyed while they were in active service. Mental-health has been regarded as a state of an individual emotional, psychological and social well-being. It is a state of balance in someone's psychological, physiological and social life that has resulted in experience of mental wellbeing, quality life and emotional stability over a long span of time in an individual's life. To live happily within and outside oneself, is primarily a function of maintenance of good mental health which could be linked to harmonious relationship between the soul and the body of any living man. Wang (2022) affirmed that since the mid of 20th century, the understanding of people about mental health has gone through a certain transformation process which has diverted their focus from a mere understanding of illness to wellness, which has formed the basic requirement for getting rid of illness from the body, and to the desire of comprehensive positive mental functioning. Galderisi, et al. (2017) stated that the definition of mental health which was proposed by the World

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Health Organization (WHO) has been centred around a hedonic and eudemonic perspective of human existence, in which a major role is assigned to an individual's well-being and productivity. However, well-being in this term is regarded as a desirable goal for majority of human beings, and its inclusion in the of mental health definition raises some concerns among scholars. According Galderisi, et al. (2017), people's well-being includes emotional, psychological and social well-being, and it evolves around positive feelings (such as, happiness and satisfaction), positive attitudes towards self, personal responsibilities and towards other people around oneself and a positive functioning (such as, social integration, actualization and coherence). Summarily, mental health can be regarded as a state of well-being in which an individual realizes his or her own potentials, has the ability to cope with the normal stressors of life, ability to work productively and fruitfully, and ability to make a contribution to one's own community. Mental health is a comprehensive system that is so related to people's physical health, lifestyle and socioeconomic status, which underpins the overall wellness and functionality of anybody. Unfortunately, the widespread use of the word mental health has been restricted to absence of mental illness in an individual, in a number of societies. This therefore calls for a comprehensive approach to its definition, diagnosis and treatment.

Wang (2022) stressed that mental health as the ability in an individual to handle normal life stresses, realizing his or her potential and the ability to integrate into the community that he or she belongs. However, there is little agreement on this definition according to Galderisi, et al. (2017). Patel, et al. (2013) observed that the lack of consensus on mental wellness is still a major obstacle for integrating mental health initiatives into global health programmes and primary healthcare services across the globe, and recently there are agitations that mental health might not be something that can be achieved generally, rather, it could be assigned to an ability of an individual to adapt and to manage self successfully in the face of life challenges which has shown a trend of changing the definition of mental health from a universal standard to a comprehensive ability that are strongly related to individual differences in term of personal characteristics. Galderisi, et al. (2017) affirmed further that mental health is a dynamic or active state of internal equilibrium that allows anybody to use his or her innate abilities in harmonious relationship with the universal values or standards of his or her society. The above authors also stressed that the maintenance of mental health entails processing of basic cognitive or mental ability and social skills, ability to recognize things accordingly, expression of, and adapt to one's own emotions, as well as empathic understanding of other peoples' feelings, flexibility in behavioural dispositions and ability to cope with adverse life occurrences, function appropriately in certain social conditions, and having harmonious relationship between body and mind. All of the aforementioned attributes represented important components of good mental health which have all contributed, to a varying degree, to the state of internal equilibrium.

The concept of mental health cannot be exclusively arrived at and as such, no universally agreed definition available for the construct, but a real definition of course, must be focused on the ability of an individual to pay attention, remember things and organize information, solve problems, make decisions, and use one's own repertoire of verbal/non-verbal abilities to communicate and interact with other people in the society (Galderisi, et al., 2017). Mental health problem or mental health illness refers to such a condition in the life of an individual which affects his or her cognition, emotion, and behaviour. In the middle of last century according to Wang (2022), mental disorders did not have a broad classification and patients, meanwhile, its definition was only depending on diagnosis alone. However, due to the aggressively increase in the number of patients that were experiencing mental health challenges in every society, existing medical resources seems not enough to cater for their treatments, the new classifications were highly needed to identify patients based on their needs, experiences and peculiarities and give them a corresponding treatment based on identified variables (Haruna & Mayanchi, 2023). Nowadays, the definition of mental illness has indeed moved from a partial one to a more holistic perspective or it has moved away from a simple concept about a disease, to a more comprehensive understanding of health challenges in some individualistic and general perspectives. There are difference causal factors of mental health problems which individual may experience at any given time. Many of which have gained empirical evidences nowadays, although such empirical evidences are scarce in Nigeria. Different theories have been proposed to explain the reason why people have mental health challenges. Among such theories are; "Social Causation Theory (Jon Ivar & Steinar, 2003) and Rational Emotive Behavioural Theory (REBT) of Albert Ellis. The Social Causation Theory believed that individual's social environment accounts for his or her mental health conditions. Another theory that explains the reasons why people develop psychological disorder is "Rational Emotive Behavioural Theory" (REBT) which was propounded by Albert Ellis. The theory is also known as ABC Theory. This theory maintains that the reason why some people develop mental health problems was largely due to the belief formed over time by such an individual on certain event of his or her life and that not the event per se that directly leads to the psychological condition. Ellis referred to event that befell individual as activating agent, which does not directly link to consequence (A-B-C), but directly link to belief formed from the event that occurs in the life of an individual. Across literature, the leading causes of mental health challenges are factors such as; experience of childhood abuse, traumatic experience, experience of social and neglect or isolation and loneliness,

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discrimination and stigmatization, social disadvantage, poverty and overwhelming debts, bereavements, severe or long-term stress, long-term physical health problem among other causal factors.

Retirement is regarded as the exit of an individual from active service usual at a fixed period of time or age such as 35 years of service or 60-year-old depending which one comes first, one when an individual is no longer capable of rendering effective service due to a particular condition. Retirement in a public or private organization is a legal, authorized and formal ending of work life and it is a shift from active involvement in the world of work to the active world of leisure Temilola (2022). The above author stated that just as retirement makes a period of transition in the lives of people, the nature of retirement is in itself experiencing of a period of transition as well and as a result of lack of applicable and sustainable interventions, many people have experienced a variety of psychosomatic challenges, and some of them show signs of psycho-phobic reactions. According to Temilola (2022) in Nigeria, both the public and private sectors regard retirement as the most intractable or difficult experience, and it has even come to the point that retirement challenges have made post-retirement life so terrible that many Nigerian workers are being feverish and fearful of going for retirement. According to Ugwu and Idemudia (2023), the psychological implication of retirement is under emphasized. The above authors maintained further that a proactive personality negatively predicted retirement anxiety, and that social comparison (opinion) mediated the relationship between proactive personality and retirement anxiety (financial preparedness and social alienation), and that social comparison (opinion and ability) mediated the relationship between proactive personality and retirement anxiety. They stressed further that retirees in Nigeria faced with complex challenges which include; financial unpreparedness, social alienation, and uncertainty. Temilola (2022) affirmed in his study that insufficient financial resources due to lack of retirement planning and absence of income generating activities represented the topmost post-retirement challenges that the older retirees are often faced with. The above author also maintained that reduced in the levels of physical activity combined with old age constituted one of the major causes of health challenges among his study participants. Another major post retirement challenge discovered by Temilola (2022) was the absence of functional government interventions for the retirees. However, it appears as if retirement is a curse that usually associates with a painful and provocative experience only in many Nigerian societies. Daramola, et al. (2019) in another empirical endeavour discovered that there are usually three main challenges confronting this age group. The first of these challenges according to the above authors was poverty, due to loss or reduction of earning power, while the second one was the increasing prevalence of chronic diseases among the retirees and older population in Nigeria, with the accompanying increased healthcare utilization and financial burdens on them. They also observed that elderly people's abuse has been gaining attention as a major social problem among researchers. According to them, tackling this menace requires a multidimensional approach, joint collaborations and involvement of a number of stakeholders, hinging on strong political will and political commitment on the part of government, which is critical for effective implementation of any policy at all. Daramola, et al. (2019) maintained further that it is essential to engage all stakeholders including; governments, institutions, organizations, civil society groups, private sector, community leaders, youth and youth groups, health-care providers, researchers, caregivers, families, older people, and the general public towards capacities building among populace for translating the internationally agreed policy frameworks into practical effects by ensuring that older persons such as retirees in Nigeria, do enjoy income security, gain access to health care and not being subjected to any form of abuse or inhuman treatment.

Ejeh, et al. (2019) reported that emotional health problems are common or prevalent among retirees, but they are often remaining undetected and untreated. According to them, emotional health problems occur to the retirees as a result of challenge that is experienced by them, and complex interaction of social, psychological and biological factors play the major role. Their study unveiled that there were significant relationships between depression and retirees' demographic factors of gender, age and educational level with 5% of the variation experiences of depression among retirees. There were also significant relationships between anxiety and retirees' demographic variables of gender, and age, level of education, place of residence and income level with 7% experiences of anxiety. There were also significant relationships between stress and retirees' demographic factors of gender, age, and educational level, but no significant relationships found between place of residence and stress, with 6% experiences of stress found among retirees. According to World Health Organization (2017) statistics, over 20% of the adult population who have aged 60 and above suffer from one form of mental or neurological disorder (excluding headache disorders) and 6.6% of all disability (disability adjusted life years (DALYs) among people over 60 years is attributed to mental and neurological disorders. These disorders in older people account for 17.4% of Years Lived with Disability (YLDs). The most common mental and neurological disorders in among this age group According to WHO statistics are dementia and depression, which affect approximately 5% and 7% of the world's older population, respectively. Anxiety disorders affect 3.8% of the older population, substance use problems affect almost 1% and around a quarter of deaths from self-harm are among people aged 60 or above. Substance abuse problems among older people are often overlooked or misdiagnosed. It is crystal

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that the previous studies reviewed in this work left a gap behind to the best knowledge of the researchers, in the sense that none of them has investigated exactly the problem of the present study. Hence, the present study focused on assessment of the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun LGA., Kwara State, Nigeria.

Research Objectives

This study stands on the following objectives:

1. To asses causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area, Kwara State.
2. To determine whether there is any significant difference in the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area, Kwara State based on gender.
3. To determine whether there is any significant difference in the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area, Kwara State based on religion.
4. To determine whether there is any significant difference in the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area, Kwara State based on year of retirement.

Research Question

The following research question was raised and answered in this study:

What are the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area, Kwara State?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were raised and tested in this study:

1. There is no significant difference in the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area, Kwara State based on gender.
2. There is no significant difference in the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area, Kwara State based on religion.
3. There is no significant difference in the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area, Kwara State based on year of retirement.

Methodology

The researchers adopted the descriptive survey research design. This type of design allows researchers to describe a phenomenon under study as they occur without an influence from the researchers. Descriptive survey method however, also the researchers to make observation of certain thing under study, collect relevant information about such phenomenon are describe them objectively. In this context, the researchers are not allowed to manipulate any variable. The population of this study comprised all retired civil servants in the state ministries and parastatals, retired teachers and retired local government staff in Ifelodun Local Government of Kwara State. This covers a total number of 854 retirees captured in the field survey carried on by the researchers from nine districts that formed Ifelodun local government area of Kwara State (these districts are; Idofian, Omupo, Ora, Share, Agunjin, Ile-Ire, Igbaja, Okeode and Oro-Ago). A multi-stage sampling technique which involved purposive, stratified, and simple random was used in selecting sample for this study. At stage one, only retirees that exist the public service or retired from active service from 2013 till-date (that is; 10 years ago), were purposively selected to avoid third party responses which might occur as a result of over age on the part of the respondents. At stage two, stratified sampling technique was used to select sample of this study based on some category of demographic characteristics such as gender, religion and year of retirement. Lastly, simple random sampling technique was used to select 120 participants from four (4) districts selected to participate in this study selected represents 14.05%. This figure is in line with Krejcie and Morgan sample size recommendation which suggests 10% as an adequate representation of a fair larger population like the population of this study.

A researchers self-designed and structured questionnaire which was titled "Causes of Mental Health Challenges Questionnaire (CMHCQ)" was used to elicit information on causes of mental health challenges as expressed by retirees in Ifelodun LGA., Kwara State. The instrument has two distinct sections: That is; section A and section B. Section A elicits personal data of the respondents such as gender, religion and year of retirement, while the section B consists of 20 items on the respondents' perception of the causes of mental health challenges. The 4-point Likert-type rating scale response format was used for respondents to make their precise responses to each item on the instrument which was tagged (CMHCQ). In order to ascertain the validity of the instrument of this study, some draft copies of the instrument were given to five seasoned lecturers in the Department of Counsellor Education, University of Ilorin for vetting. Minor corrections were observed on the instrument in the course of its vetting which were some few spelling and typographic errors that were later corrected before the final draft of the instrument. The instrument was re-presented to the same lecturers who vetted it earlier and it was affirmed

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been valid. In order to ascertain the reliability of the instrument, test re-test reliability method was used. By this means, the instrument was administered on twenty (20) retirees within the study locale who did not form part of this study again, but possessed similar characteristics of the population of the study. After a period of four (4) weeks, the same instrument was re-administered on the same set of retirees. The two set of scores obtained on the two occasions were later correlated using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) statistical method. The reliability co-efficient (r) value of 0.86 was obtained at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the instrument is reliable for the study. Frequency counts and percentages were used to analyze the demographic data of the respondents of this study such as gender, religion and year of retirement.

The research question set for the study was answered with items analysis using Mean scores benchmark of 2.50. The researchers used Four Point Likert-Type Rating Scale format in the following order: Strongly Agree (SA) = 4 points; Agree (A) =3 points, disagree (D) =2 points, and Strongly Disagree (SD) =1 point. The highest score that any participant can score is 4 and the lowest is 1. However, the average score is calculated thus: $1+2+3+4 = 10$, and $10/4 = 2.50$. However, any item that its mean score is above 2.50 would be considered as high causes of mental health challenges among the respondents, while those below it would be considered as low causes. Any item that its mean score falls on 2.50 which is average mean score would be considered as neutral response. The three (3) null hypotheses formulated for the study were tested with t-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

The data obtained were analysed using frequency counts and percentage, mean rank order for descriptive data while t-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) statistics were used to test the three (3) null hypotheses formulated for the study.

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents Based on Gender, Religion and Year of Retirement.

S/N	Variables	Frequency	Percentages (%)
1.	Gender		
	Male	84	70.0
	Female	36	30.0
	Total	120	100.0
2.	Religion		
	Christianity	68	56.7
	Islam	45	37.5
	ATR	07	5.8
	Total	120	100.0
3.	Year of Retirement		
	2013-2017	74	62.0
	2018-2023	46	38.0
	Total	120	100.0

Source: Field Survey

Table 1 presents the distribution of respondents based on gender, religious affiliation and year of retirement. The total number of respondents who participated in this study was 120. Based on the gender of the respondents, 84 (70.0%) were male and 36 (30.0%) were female. On the basis of religious affiliation of the respondents 68 (56.7%) were Christianity, 45 (37.5%) were Muslims and 7 (5.8%) were from other African Traditional Religion background. Lastly, based on the year of retirement of the respondents, those who had retired between 2013 and 2017 were 74 (62.0%), while those who had retired between 2018 and 2023 were 46 (38.0%).

Research Question 1: What are the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun LGA., Kwara State, Nigeria?

Table 2: Items Analysis of Causes of Mental Health Challenges among Retirees in Ifelodun LGA., Kwara State, Nigeria

S/N	Items	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Experience of abuse/inhuman treatment/discrimination	2.94	0.88	High
2	Genetic factor/hereditary factor	3.04	0.86	High
3	Reduced level of physical activities	2.98	0.76	High
4	Poor nutrition/hygiene	3.10	0.98	High

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5	Absence of functional intervention programme	3.34	1.26	High
6	Poor access to functional healthcare	2.85	1.04	High
7	Childhood abuse at the early stage of life	2.58	0.74	High
8	Brain malfunction/defects/injury	3.28	1.32	High
9	Bereavement (e.g., loss of close relation)	2.82	1.08	High
10	Persistent domestic violence	3.02	0.77	High
11	Poverty/financial burden	2.80	0.93	High
12	Financial unpreparedness	3.20	1.36	High
13	Poor interpersonal/family relationship	3.08	1.20	High
14	Increasing future uncertainty (e.g., nonpayment of gratuity)	2.96	1.02	High
15	Absence of income generating activities	2.76	0.87	High
16	Increasing prevalence of diseases due to old age	2.66	1.13	High
17	Social alienation/isolation/neglect	3.06	1.24	High
18	Post-traumatic experience (e.g., witness of assassination)	2.64	0.79	High
19	Substance misuse/drug abuse	3.01	0.94	High
20	Reduced or lack of adequate sleep	2.68	0.85	High
Grand Total		2.94		

Source: *Field Survey, 2023*

The table 2 shows the mean and standard deviation of items on the causes of mental health challenges as expressed by the retirees in Ifelodun LGA., Kwara State, Nigeria. There are twenty items altogether on the (CMHCQ) questionnaire that were statistically analysed. Item 5 with a statement "absence of functional intervention programme" has the highest mean score of 3.34, item 8 with a statement "brain malfunction/defects/injury" has a mean score of 3.28 and item 12 with a statement "financial unpreparedness" has a mean score of 3.20 respectively. From the table presented above, it is crystal clear that all items on the table were factors that responsible for mental health challenges among the retirees in Ifelodun local government area., Kwara State, Nigeria as none of the items was rated below 2.5 which was used as the benchmark for decision making.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area., Kwara State based on gender.

Table 3: Mean, SD and t-test Result Showing Difference in Causes of Mental Health Challenges among Retirees in Ifelodun LGA., Kwara State Based on Gender

Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	Cal. t	Crit. t	p-value	Decision
Male	84	54.04	6.82	118	0.82	1.96	0.126	Retained
Female	36	36.84	4.64					

Source: *Field Survey*

Table 3 shows that for a degree of freedom (df) of 118, the calculated t value of 0.82 is less than the critical t-value of 1.96, with a corresponding p-value of 0.124 which is greater than 0.05 level of significance. This indicates that there was no significant difference in the opinion of retirees in Ifelodun local government area., Kwara on the causes of mental health challenges based on gender. Hence, the hypothesis one which stated that there is no significant difference in the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area., Kwara State based on gender is retained.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area., Kwara State based on religion.

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Table 4: ANOVA Result Showing Difference in the Respondents' View of Causes of Mental Health Challenges among Retirees in Ifelodun local government area., Kwara State Based on Religion.Source:

Source	Df	SS	Means Square	Cal. F-ratio	Crit. F-ratio	p-value
Between Group	2	106.168	54.084			
Within Group	117	5268.355	45.028	0.84	3.00	0.556
Total	119	5345.360				

Field Survey

Table 4 shows that the calculated F-ratio of 0.84 is less than the critical F-ratio of 3.00 ($p = 0.556 > 0.05$). This means that there was no significant difference in the opinion of retirees in Ifelodun local government area., Kwara on the causes of mental health challenges based on religion. Thus, the hypothesis two which stated that there is no significant difference in the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun LGA., Kwara State based on religion is accepted.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference in the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area, Kwara State based on year of retirement.

Table 5: Mean, SD and t-test Result Showing Difference in Causes of Mental Health Challenges among Retirees in Ifelodun local government area, Kwara State Based on Year of Retirement

Year of Retirement	N	Mean	SD	Df	Cal. t	Crit. t	p-value	Decision
2013-2017	74	62.16	7.24					
2018-2023	46	48.94	6.84	118	2.08	1.96	0.001	Rejected

Source: *Field Survey*

Table 5 shows that for a degree of freedom (df) of 118, the calculated t-value of 2.08 is greater than the critical value of 1.96, with a corresponding p-value of 0.001 which is less than 0.05 level of significance. This indicates that there was significant difference in the opinion of retirees in Ifelodun local government area, Kwara on the causes of mental health challenges based on year of retirement. Hence, the hypothesis three which stated that there is no significant difference in the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area, Kwara State based on year of retirement is rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study revealed that absence of functional intervention programme, brain malfunction/defect/injury and financial unpreparedness are the major causes of mental health challenges among the retirees in Ifelodun LGA., Kwara State, Nigeria. The first finding stated above is in line with the findings of Temilola (2022) whose study discovered similar outcome in its findings. The second finding of this study is also in agreement with the findings of Aminu, Yahaya, Adigun, Aminullahi and Adio (2021) who study also comes up with the same result that one of the major reasons why people have psychological problem such as depression is as a result of brain injury. The third finding of the present study is also in tandem with the findings of Ugwu and Idemudia (2023) whose recently conducted study unveiled the same empirical outcome. The agreement in the present findings and the previous ones might not be surprising in the sense that all the studies were locally conducted and as such they are home based studies with closeness in some characteristics of the respondents.

Hypothesis one tested revealed that there was no significant difference in the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun LGA., Kwara State based on gender. The finding is in consistence with the finding of the study of Ejeh, Achor and Ejeh (2019) who had earlier discovered the same thing in their empirical analysis. Hypothesis two unveiled that no significant difference occurred in the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area., Kwara State based on religion. The finding is in agreement with the finding of a study conducted by of Aminu, Yahaya, Adigun, Aminullahi and Adio (2021) which maintained that respondents were not differ in their responses on the causes of depressive disorder on the basis of religion.

The result of hypothesis three indicated that there was significant difference in the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area, Kwara State based on year of retirement. This finding is in consistence with the findings of study of Daramola, Awunor and Akande (2019) and Ejeh, Achor and Ejeh (2019) whose different empirical

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findings indicated that age has significant implication in the experience of challenges that were bedeviling retired class and elderly population of Nigeria.

Conclusions

The findings identified absence of functional intervention programme, brain malfunction/defect/injury and financial unpreparedness as the leading causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area., Kwara State, Nigeria. The result of the hypotheses revealed that there was no significant difference in the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area., Kwara State, Nigeria based on gender and religion but discovered a significant difference in the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area., Kwara State, Nigeria based on year of retirement.

Recommendations

In line with the findings of the study, it is recommended among other things that:

1. There should be provision for different functional intervention programmes that will make life conducive for all retirees after retirement irrespective of where they had worked.
2. Mental healthcare should be strengthened in every nook and cranny of the country to allow easy access to preventive, and treatment intervention programmes at very low or no cost for all citizens.
3. The workers should be trained on how to plan for retirement and be assisted to achieve such plans.
4. Irrespective of gender and religious backgrounds of the retirees, they should be encouraged to seek assistance or help on their mental health challenges.
5. The people who had been long retired (for instance, above five years) should be given a close monitoring and adequate attentions by all concerned stakeholders for improved living standard.

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Assessment of Out-Of-Service Teachers in Teaching and Learning of Mathematics at Primary School Level in Lere Educational Zone, Kaduna State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study aims at investigation of the Assessment of out-of-service teachers in teaching and learning of Mathematics at Primary School level in Lere Educational Zone, Kaduna State, Nigeria. A descriptive survey research design was used for the study and a self-developed questionnaire named Upper Primary School Teacher Questionnaire (UPSTQ) with nineteen (19) items were used for data collection with 0.65 reliability index. The instruments were validated by three experts whose rank are senior lectures and above, two from Department of Science Education, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria and one from Department of Mathematics, Federal College of Education Zaria. Three (3) objectives, three (3) research questions and three (3) null hypotheses, respectively were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance to guide the conduct of the study. The Population of the study consists of all upper basic primary school teachers in Lere Educational Zone during the 2021/2022 academic session. A sample size of 37 Upper basic primary school teachers were used for the study. Data collected were analyzed using frequency count and simple percentages. It was discovered that, there was no significant area(s) in the primary school Mathematics curriculum where the teachers find it difficult to teach or require further training before they can adequately teach the topics. Based on the findings, it was recommended that regular workshops and seminar should be organized either by ministry of education or relevant governmental and non-governmental organizations to address identified difficult areas where the teachers felt incompetent to teach.

Keyword: Mathematics, Teaching and learning, Teachers

Introduction

The foundation of any planned program mostly determines its quality, effectiveness and the extent to which its objectives can be realized. The ability to analyze, synthesize and comprehend a given concept lies on the mastery of its foundation. Education is systematically organized and subjects are generally intersected, concepts or topics are specially linked from simple to complex as pre-requisite. In primary schools, the subjects are served as the base or foundation to which further studies may be place on and a preparation for life challenges. Odili (2006), defined Mathematics as the science of quantity and space, "it is a systematized, organized and exact branch of science". It is a creation of human mind, concerned primarily with ideas, processes and reasoning. Ashcraft and Kirk (2010), indicated that mathematics is the language of science and foundation of rational development and productivity. Akine (2017) remarked that as long as mathematics are in the classroom and isolated from acquiring mathematics experiences, they are more likely to need some updating. Harmit (2017) defined mathematical updating as the mathematical knowledge and skills needed by mathematics teachers to provide their students with up-to-date preparation for the current technology of the world of work. Mathematics teachers need periodic in-service training to update their competence in their areas of specialization. It seems most teachers at primary schools denied these opportunities of re-training. Some of the objectives of primary school education as stipulated in National Policy on Education (FRN, 2013) include;

1. Inculcation of permanent literacy and numeracy,
2. Laying a foundation for national development,
3. Giving the child opportunities for developing manipulative and scientific skills

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At all levels of education, the primary school is still the first level of educational ladder (Okeke, 2016). He further maintained that; primary school is a preparatory ground where the background knowledge is rooted and built up for other academic endeavor. Specifically, the objectives of primary school mathematics curriculum include;

1. Developing positive attitudes of the pupils toward mathematics and appreciation of both the practical and aesthetic aspects,
2. To develop problem solving abilities and a facility for application of mathematics to everyday life,
3. To enable the child to use mathematical language effectively and accurately,
4. To enable the child, acquire an understanding of mathematical concepts and process to his/her appropriate level of development and ability,
5. To enable the child to acquire the proficiency in fundamental mathematics skills and in recalling basic number acts.

This indicates that; there is need to lay a sound foundation of mathematics knowledge at primary school so as to ensure the realization of its objectives. The primary school level is often considered to be the most important years of child school career (Lawrence, 2015). Teachers are the curriculum implementers; therefore, every teacher should act as architect, composer, movies director, stock broker, ship captain, and prospector (Aminu et al, 2016). This will put the pupils at ease, develop in them positive attitude towards the learning of mathematics and thus, increase their performance.

Despite the vital roles played by mathematics in scientific and technological development of the nation, its teaching and learning are faced with some problems that make most students to perform poorly in the subject. According to Onifade (2016), academic performance is an important aspect of learning but retaining what is learnt seems to be more important. This might have resulted from weak and erroneous foundation they receive at early stage as a result of difficulties faced by the teachers who are not scientifically based or are not specialized in mathematics in some selected upper basic primary school classes, which made them to teach the topics poorly, wrongly, partially, or even skip or ignore some of the topics. Akinsolu (2010), observed that teachers are vital pre-requisites for students' attainment of educational goals and objectives. Similarly, Ashimole (2011), emphasized that teaching and learning depends largely on teacher, and that it is on teachers' number, quality and devotion that rest the effectiveness of all educational arrangements, development and growth. The teacher is ultimately responsible for translating educational policies and principles into actions based on practice during interaction with the pupils. This is because no education can go beyond the quality of its teacher. This observation becomes a challenge and this is why the current effort is being embarked upon to verify the claim. Therefore, the need to investigate on Assessment of out-of-service teachers in teaching and learning of Mathematics at Primary School level in Lere Educational Zone, Kaduna State, Nigeria cannot be over emphasized.

Objectives of the Study

The purpose of this study was to investigate on the 'Assessment of out-of-service teachers in teaching and learning of Mathematics at Primary School level in Lere Educational Zone, Kaduna State, Nigeria'. The study aimed to determine the effectiveness of teaching mathematics subject at upper primary schools by out-of-service teachers, where one teacher has to teach all the subjects offered by the pupils irrespective of his/her area of specialization.

Specifically, the study aimed to;

1. Find out if there exist challenges encountered by the out-of-service teachers teaching mathematics at upper basic primary schools in Lere educational zone.
2. Find out difficult topics encountered by out-of-service mathematics teachers at upper basic primary school level in Lere educational zone.
3. Assess relationship between out-of-service teachers and pupils' performance in mathematics at primary school level in Lere educational zone

Research Questions

The following research questions were asked to guide the conduct of the study;

1. what are the challenges encountered by the out-of-service teachers in teaching of mathematics at upper primary school level in Lere educational zone?
2. What are the difficult topics encountered by the out-of-service mathematics teachers at upper basic primary school in Lere educational zone?
3. What is the relationship between out-of-service teachers and pupils' performance in mathematics at primary school level in Lere educational zone?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study;

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1. There are no significant challenges encountered by out-of-service teachers in teaching mathematics at upper basic primary school level in Lere educational zone.
2. There is no significant difficult topics encountered by out-of-service mathematics teachers at upper basic primary school level in Lere educational zone
3. There is no significant relationship between out-of-service teachers and pupils' performance in mathematics at primary school level in Lere educational zone.

Methodology

The research design used for this study was a descriptive survey. Data were collected from the selected sample of the study. The Population of the study consists of all upper basic primary school teachers in Lere Educational Zone during the 2021/2022 academic session. A sample size of 37 Upper basic primary school teachers were used for the study. Data collected were analyzed using frequency count and simple percentages. It was discovered that, there was no significant area(s) in the primary school Mathematics curriculum where the teachers find it difficult to teach to teach or require further training before they can adequately teach the topics. A questionnaire named; Upper Primary School Teachers Questionnaire (UPSTQ) with nineteen (19) items was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three experts whose rank are senior lecturers and above, two from Department of Science Education, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria and one from Department of Mathematics, Federal College of Education Zaria. Their corrections were noted and incorporated. The reliability of the instruments was tested using test re-test reliability test and was found to be 0.65 which implies that the instrument is reliable. The administration and collection of the questionnaire were done by the researcher with the help of the heads of the schools. Questionnaires were distributed and collected latter through the head teachers of the schools. Forty-eight (48) questionnaires were distributed while only thirty-seven (37) were returned. These questionnaires were sorted based on identical opinions of the respondents for easy tabulation. For analyzing hypotheses, the row data collected through the method of research instrument were processed and prepared for presentation as tabulated evidences. The technique used in constructing these tables include; frequency and percentage calculations. Thus, all the conclusions about the findings of this study were made on the bases of percentage of the responses recorded. The tables were prepared to serve as the main frame-work around which the analyses, conclusions and recommendations were made.

Result

Research Question 1:

What are the challenges encountered by the out-of-service teachers in teaching of mathematics at upper primary school level in Lere educational zone?

Table 1: Frequency and percentage of teachers having problems in teaching some selected topics at upper primary school.

S/N	TOPIC	NUMBER OF TEACHERS	PERCENTAGE (%)
1.	Probability	1	03.0
2.	Geometry	2	05.4
3.	Angles	2	05.4
4.	Weight	1	03.0
5.	Measurement	2	05.4
6.	Division	5	14.0
7.	Word Problem	6	16.2
8.	Numbers base	1	03.0
9.	Ratio	4	11.0
10.	Proportion	1	03.0
11.	Expansion	1	03.0
12.	Roman numerals	1	03.0
13.	L.C.M. (Least Common Multiples)	1	03.0
14.	Counting in millions	1	03.0
15.	Percentage	4	11.0
16.	Algebra	1	03.0
17.	Indices	2	05.4
18.	Quantitative reasoning	4	11.0

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19.	Order of operation	2	02.7
20.	Capacity	4	11.0
21.	Fraction	2	05.4
22.	Factorization	1	03.0
23.	Construction	1	03.0
24.	Shapes	2	05.4
25.	Plain Figures	2	05.4
26.	Scale drawing	1	03.0
27.	Data collection and Presentation	2	05.4
28.	Measure of central tendency	1	03.0
29.	Binary numbers	3	08.1
30.	Volume	1	03.0
31.	Height	1	03.0
32.	Money	2	05.4
33.	Decimal	2	05.4

The result from table 1 reveals that; teachers rate themselves having no problem to teach more than 90% of the upper primary school curriculum content since none of the topics indicates 50% of the teachers having problem to teach.

Research question 2

What are the difficult topics encountered by the out-of-service mathematics teachers at upper basic primary school in Lere educational zone?

Table 2: Frequency and percentage of Teachers having difficulty in teaching some selected topics at upper primary school

S/N	TOPIC	NUMBER OF TEACHERS	PERCENTAGE (%)
1.	Probability	1	03.0
2.	Geometry	2	05.4
3.	Angles	2	05.4
4.	Weight	1	03.0
5.	Measurement	2	05.4
6.	Division	5	14.0
7.	Word Problem	6	16.2
8.	Numbers base	1	03.0
9.	Ratio	4	10.8
10.	Proportion	1	03.0
11.	Expansion	1	03.0
12.	Roman numerals	1	03.0
13.	L.C.M. (Least Common Multiples)	1	03.0
14.	Counting in millions	1	03.0
15.	Percentage	4	10.8
16.	Algebra	1	03.0
17.	Indices	2	05.4
18.	Quantitative reasoning	4	11.0
19.	Order of operation	2	02.7
20.	Capacity	4	11.0
21.	Fraction	2	05.4
22.	Factorization	1	03.0
23.	Construction	1	03.0
24.	Shapes	2	05.4
25.	Plain Figures	2	05.4
26.	Scale drawing	1	03.0
27.	Data collection and Presentation	2	05.4

Assessment of Causes of Mental Health ... (Aminu, et. al., 20203) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10408112>

28.	Measure of central tendency	1	03.0
29.	Binary numbers	3	08.1
30.	Volume	1	03.0
31.	Height	1	03.0
32.	Money	2	05.4
33.	Decimal	2	05.4

The result from table 2 reveals the percentage of the teachers having difficulty in teaching some selected topics in the upper primary school mathematics curriculum. However, the items listed were those items which the teacher said they are having problem to teach thus, they need further training before they can competently teach the topics. Those who require this training were mainly those teachers who find themselves to teach the subject of mathematics and do not specialize in mathematics.

Research question 3

What is the relationship between out-of-service teachers and pupils' performance in mathematics at primary school level in Lere educational zone?

Table 3: Frequency and percentage of teachers supporting and not supporting teacher far class

S/N	Names of Schools	Teachers' Frequency	Supporting	Percentage (%) of Supporting	Not supporting	Percentage (%) of not Supporting
1.	L.G.E.A. Pri. Sch. Rahama	3	3	100	0	0
2.	L.G.E.A. Pri. Sch. Saminaka B.	3	3	100	0	0
3.	L.G.E.A. Pri. Sch. U/mele	1	1	100	0	0
4.	U.B.E. Pri. Sch. Kafannuwa	1	1	100	0	0
5.	U.B.E. Pri. Sch. T/wada	3	1	33.3	2	66.7
6.	U.B.E. Pri. Sch. Nasarawa	2	2	100	0	0
7.	U.B.E. Pri. Sch. Badarawa	2	2	100	0	0
8.	L.G.E.A. Pri. Sch. U/Jumare	2	2	100	0	0
9.	L.G.E.A. Pri. Sch. Abadawa I	2	2	100	0	0
10.	U.B.E. Pri. Sch. Abadawa II	2	2	100	0	0
11.	U.B.E. Pri. Sch. Domawa	1	1	100	0	0
12.	U.B.E. Pri. Sch. Lagga	1	1	100	0	0
13.	U.B.E. Pri. Sch. Kwaftara	1	1	100	0	0
14.	U.B.E. Pri. Sch. Sabon-birni I	2	2	100	0	0
15.	Central Primary School U/Bawa	3	3	100	0	0
16.	U.B.E. Pri. Sch. Nasarawan- jaja	1	1	100	0	0

Table 3 reveals that about 93.3% (28 out of 30) of the teachers support the policy of every teacher should teach his/her area of specialization. One of their reasons among others was that; pupils will have an effective teaching ones the teacher is competent in his subject matter. This indicates that only 6.3 % (2 out of 30) of the teachers support the policy of teacher per class. Their reason among others was that; the teacher will have enough time to access his/her students without any interruption by other teachers. The researcher remarks here that; it is possible for a teacher to be competent on a particular subject matter and not on others, no matter how intelligent the teacher is. Therefore, the researcher is in line with those teachers who support the policy of every teacher should teach his/her area of specialization.

Discussion of Findings

The findings reveal the topics where the teachers are having problem to teach as shown in Table 1. These topics were similar to those topics where the teachers rate themselves as the areas, they are having difficulty to teach as shown in and Table 2. Thus, the teachers require further training before they can teach these topics competently. Although the teachers listed about thirty-three topics out of the upper primary school mathematics curriculum as those topics, they are having difficulty to teach, the majority of the teachers support the policy of every teacher should teach his/her area of specialization. Attached to this, many teachers are just being involve in to teaching mathematics so they have little or no background experience. This is a clear manifestation of the poor pre-service training they had. Thus, the problem faced by the teachers ranges from poor teaching of most of the topics, act of skipping some topic/selecting the simple arithmetic such as Addition, Subtraction, Division and Multiplication in the upper primary school mathematics curriculum. In fact, through discussion with teacher by the researcher, some of the teachers identify only Addition and Subtraction as topics they can manage to teach. This appears to be a great problem to the performance of the pupils since the background of the subject will not be there.

Conclusions

Based on the findings from this study, the researcher concluded that the ability of the teachers has been discovered to be very okay since majority of the teachers perceive themselves very competent to teach at least more than 50% of the upper primary school curriculum content.

Finally, it is concluded that, poor performance among primary school pupils may not be as a result of difficult topics faced by the teachers in Lere educational zone, Kaduna State, Nigeria. Thus, poor performance may be as a result of out-of-service teachers since about 93% of the teachers support the policy of every teacher should teach based on his/her area of specialization.

Recommendations

Based on the findings from this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Regular workshops and seminar should be organized either by ministry of education or relevant governmental and non-governmental organizations to address identified difficult areas where the teachers felt incompetent to teach.
2. Re-fresher training should be organized by the state ministry of education on regular bases as the content of mathematics is dynamic in order to improve the level of effectiveness of the achievement of the stated objectives of the content.
3. Specialist in mathematics education should be employed as a matter of urgent need by the Kaduna State government so as to carter for the need of the Pupils in order to improve their performance in mathematics and to reduce level of complications faced by the teacher.

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Assessment of Provision and Management of Internet Services among Federal Universities in Northwest, Nigeria

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Abstract

The rapid evolution of the internet has significantly transformed higher education globally. Nigerian universities, like many institutions worldwide, are embracing the digital age by providing internet services to enhance learning, research, and administrative operations. This paper assessed the provision and management of internet services among Federal Universities in North-west, Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The population of the study consisted of 19120 (42 management staff, 6447 teaching staff, 12344 non-teaching staff and 287 students' representatives) from all the Federal Universities in North-west, Nigeria. The sample size for the study was 557 stakeholders (comprising 129 teaching staff, 248 non-teaching staff, 152 students' representatives and 28 management staff). Hence, this was arrived at using multi-stage sampling technique within all the states in North-west, Nigeria. A closed ended questionnaire adapted from Maina (2016) titled "Assessment of the Provision and Management of Students Internet Services Questionnaire" was used for data collection. The descriptive statistics of frequency count and percentages were used for the analysis of the research question and decision mean of 3.0 was used to determine acceptance or rejection of the item statement as structured in the instrument to answer the research questions. Inferential statistics of Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings from the study revealed that although internet service is provided and managed in Federal Universities in North-west, Nigeria, but there were issues of lack of adequate maintenance of the internet facilities. It was concluded that internet services in Federal Universities are poorly managed. Therefore, the study recommended among others that more effort should be geared towards ensuring that there are adequate measures put in place for regular maintenance of existing internet facilities among Federal Universities in North-west, Nigeria.

Keywords: Internet services, Management, Stakeholders, Provision.

Introduction

The internet has revolutionized education, offering vast resources and collaborative opportunities that enhance teaching, learning, and research in higher institutions globally. Nigerian universities have recognized the importance of internet access in advancing education and are making efforts to provide reliable connectivity. Indeed, the Internet is an inseparable part of today's educational system. The academic community increasingly depends on the Internet for educational purposes; University students are increasingly using the Internet as an information resource while in search of information for academic assignments, playing online games, streaming videos, online shopping and such others. Thus, the emergence of the Internet has had a profound impact on society in general and on library and information services in particular (Allison, 2016). Majority of academic and research institutions provide and manage Internet service for staff and students to enhance teaching and learning. Students also use the Internet for social communication which helps them expand and build new relationships. Allison (2016) reported that, students use the Internet more than 5 hours per day, more than 25% of those are in their 20's, and they rather browse the Internet on their smartphones, than on laptops or school property computers. Students utilize the Internet to speak with lecturers and colleagues, for research and to get access to library resource. Therefore, Internet serves as a useful tool in support of the various educational activities that ranged from research to teaching. Affum (2022) opined that internet help students to access journals and articles which otherwise are not made available in the libraries. The author remarked further that, increase in internet use was very useful in the improvement of students learning outcome. Similarly, Jackson, (2011) cited

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in Ahmad (2022) also noted that, the Internet will level the educational playing field due to its availability to everyone, everywhere, and any time irrespective of gender, race/ethnicity, income or other socio-demographic characteristics. In the same line of thinking Siraj (2015) opined that internet enhances easy communication in the academic community. Thus, the Internet is a vital tool that will propel university education to greater heights as the world move further into the knowledge-based economy.

Universities worldwide now invest a lot on internet access because it reduces the time between the production and utilization of knowledge; improves co-operation and exchange of ideas with fellow researchers in other institutions, regions or countries, furthers the sharing of information; and promotes multidisciplinary research. Oso and Adesina (2017) highlighting the importance of internet services stated that having access to internet allows students to keep up with information that might not make it into textbooks or might be outdated by the time it is published in a traditional format. The internet provide easy access to information and help students to do their assignments with just only search on the search engine and also give them the opportunity to exchange ideas and information from different locations at the same time (Affum 2022). Thus, survival in academics without the Internet can be very difficult. The Internet harbors applications used in online data repositories, library catalogues, journals, news services, student and financial administration systems, online supported or solely online conducted teaching, as well as in digital communication with fellow students' and lecturers. Other contemporary uses of Internet by students include purchasing, entertainment, and even dating. Consequently, studies have been carried out in many places to understand how University students' and staff use the Internet, the purposes for which the students' and staff use the Internet, the search engines used, their internet skills as well as problems that hinder efficient internet use among others. Chan and Fu (2015) observed that the internet is very useful to university students' and staff in Nigeria because it enables them to have access to timely, accurate and relevant information that cannot be obtained from library shelves. The authors remarked further that, Internet searching helps University students to boost their intellectual development and job preparation. Hence, due to the endless nature of information resources on the Internet, libraries are increasingly investing in provision of Internet services and resources to enable their clients have better access to the information. However, Aguolu (2012) in Ahmad (2022) asserts that resources may be available in the library and sometimes there may be identified bibliography relevant to one's area of interest, but the user may not be able to locate the material. Constraints to effective utilization of internet have been identified by researchers in varying degrees (Omotayo, 2016; Siraj 2015; Bassey 2019; Affum, 2022). In relation to the internet access challenges, Omotayo (2016) found that the major barriers to efficient Internet use by students include slowness of the server and payment for the access time. Similarly, Bassey (2019) reported that were not easily accessible to students due to malfunctioning of some facilities, irregular power supply and the negligence of the management in subscribing to the internet services. Luambo and Nawe (2014) also observe that the slow Internet connections attributable to small bandwidth is a major factor hindering Internet access and use in Africa.

Indeed, the mode of acquiring and disseminating information for university education has changed from just physically available prints to a combination of physical and e-materials with virtual reality. As a result of that Akintunde (2012) in Ahmad (2022) opined that, any attempt to have meaningful academic communication can be successful only by the use of ICT which presents information in real time and space. Youngsters especially students' and researchers spend most of their time in cybercafé because the service is not adequately available in the university community, they risk travelling a further distance to transact one business or another on the internet. These members of the university community use the Internet for the resources it provides. Internet services according to Ikoro (2012) in Ahmad (2022), include e-mailing, world wide web browsing, telephoning, and telex/video conferencing and others. Available also in the internet are social media resource such as audio broadcasting, news and discussion/chart group, face-book YouTube and twitter resources. In relation using those resources available on the internet Cisse (2014) noted that students' and researchers are disposed to access maximum information and communicate at world level. Thus, they can debate democratically and freely while being exposed to happenings in their fields of activities as well as other subjects. Chifwepa (2013) discovered a high use of internet by the staff of the University of Zambia where 35 out of 37 staff made use of internet. Their major motivation for such use was convenience (82.91%); usefulness (80.05%); free access to information and software (71.4%); and ease of use (68.6%). In Nigeria, findings from the study of Oso and Adesina (2017) indicated that the government provides internet services in the institution but teachers and student cannot regularly access the services due to negligence of the school management in terms of regular subscription to the internet services, lack of upgrade and maintenance of the available facilities. While Jagdoro (2014) in his own research ascertained that 45.2% of graduate students access the Internet at the cybercafé in the university where only 8.2% used the library Internet facilities. A greater percentage (38.24%) did that only on monthly basis where 39.7% spent one hour on each visit.

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From the above assertions it appears that although internet services play a significant role in facilitating access to information and dissemination of information, something is lacking in the quality and quantity of such services in Nigerian Public universities. Therefore, it is against the background of that the researchers conducted an assessment on provision and management of internet services among Federal Universities in North-west, Nigeria.

Objective of the Study

The objective of the study was to:

To access the extent of provision and management of internet services among Federal Universities in North-west, Nigeria

Research Question

The following research question guided the study:

What is the extent of provision and management of internet services among Federal Universities in North-west, Nigeria

Hypothesis

The following research hypothesis was raised to guide the study:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the extent of provision and management of internet services among federal Universities in North-west, Nigeria.

Methodology

The researchers adopted descriptive survey research design for the study. The population of the study was 19120, (which comprised 42 management staffs, 6447 teaching staff, 12344 non-teaching staff and 287 students' representatives) in all the Federal Universities in North-west, Nigeria. The sample size for the study was 557 (comprising 129 teaching staff, 248 non-teaching staff, 152 students' representatives and 28 management staff). The sample was derived from Research Advisor (2006). A closed ended questionnaire adapted from Maina (2016) was used to generate the relevant data for the study. Questionnaire was titled "Assessment of Provision and Management of Internet Services Questionnaire (APMISQ). A 5-point Likert scale was used such as Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD) Undecided (U). The reliability of the Questionnaire was established through pilot test using test re-test method. Result from the two tests were subjected to Pearson Product Moment Correlation test in order to determine the reliability Coefficient of the study, a reliability coefficient of 0.68 was obtained at 0.05 level of significance. The instrument was therefore declared reliable. Collection of data was done by the researchers with the help of research assistants. The description statistics: frequency count and percentages were used for bio-data of the respondents and decision mean of 3.0 was used to determine acceptance or rejection of the item statement as structured in the instrument to answer the research questions. Inferential statistics of Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Result

Research Question

What is the extent of provision and management of internet services among Federal Universities in North-west, Nigeria.

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Table 1: Mean Scores of Respondents on Provision and Management of Internet Services in Federal Universities of Northwest Geographical Zone, Nigeria.

S/N	Item statement	Category of Respondent	Strongly Agreed	Agreed	Undecided	Disagreed	Strongly Disagreed	Number	Mean
1	There is Internet service in the University	Management staff	22	5	1	22	-	49	3.6
		Teaching staff	13	90	8	-	-	110	4.0
		Non-teaching. staff	17	80	3	-	14	108	3.9
		Students	82	10	-	7	-	107	4.3
2	The internet service works every day for the benefit of students	Management staff	12	19	-	8	10	49	3.3
		Teaching staff	21	80	-	5	5	110	4.0
		Non-teaching. staff	53	15	2	37	7	108	3.8
		Students	50	37	-	12	8	107	4.0
3	The university internet is used for research by students to improve their academic achievement.	Management staff	20	10	-	8	11	49	3.4
		Teaching staff	60	41	4	6	-	110	4.4
		Non-teaching. staff	58	27	7	12	8	108	4.1
		Students	56	34	4	9	4	107	4.2
4	University makes provision for free wireless in the campus	Management staff	13	22	-	12	3	49	3.6
		Teaching staff	60	10	7	30	4	110	3.8
		Non-teaching. staff	62	30	-	20	2	108	4.3
		Students	65	17	-	22	2	107	4.1
5	University provides modem to students to enable them get access to the Internet service.	Management staff	6	3	1	37	2	49	2.6
		Teaching staff	5	20	11	73	2	110	2.5
		Non-teaching. staff	10	30	-	70	4	108	2.2
		Students	28	5	-	54	10	107	2.3
6	The University internet is easily accessible.	Management staff	20	8	-	10	11	49	3.3
		Teaching staff	54	-	1	25	30	110	3.2
		Non-teaching. staff	55	32	-	27	-	108	4.2
		Students	85	6	-	9	7	107	4.4
7	The University is linked to internet service	Management staff	6	10	4	10	19	49	2.4
		Teaching staff	100	10	-	31	20	110	4.5
		Non-teaching. staff	43	2	-	13	4	108	2.3
		Students	66	7	-	34	10	107	4.0
8	Students are patronizing e-library for their research.	Management staff	16	10	1	13	9	49	3.2
		Teaching staff	39	50	-	6	17	110	3.8
		Non-teaching. staff	61	27	-	9	7	108	4.0
		Students	84	6	-	12	5	107	4.4
9	The internet service is well managed	Management staff	14	28	-	4	3	49	3.9
		Teaching staff	28	58	5	5	15	110	3.7
		Non-teaching. staff	51	30	-	23	-	108	3.8
		Students	87	10	-	8	2	107	4.5
10	The management supervises the internet facilities regularly	Management staff	10	20	-	17	2	49	3.3
		Teaching staff	15	63	5	19	9	110	3.5
		Non-tech. staff	61	3	6	40	3	108	3.8
		Students	44	45	-	16	2	107	4.0
11	Spoiled facilities are replaced promptly	Management staff	12	19	-	8	10	49	3.3
		Teaching staff	21	50	-	20	20	110	3.3
		Non-teaching. staff	40	10	2	55	7	108	3.3
		Students	57	30	-	12	8	107	4.0
12	The computers in the E-Library are well maintained	Management staff	20	10	-	19	-	49	3.6
		Teaching staff	60	31	4	6	10	110	4.1
		Non-teaching. staff	40	27	7	30	8	108	3.6
		Students	46	44	4	9	4	107	4.1

Source: Fieldwork, 2022

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Table 1 revealed the views of Management staff, Teaching staff, non-teaching staff and Students on provision and management of internet services in Federal Universities of North-west zone. Item 1 revealed opinions of the respondents on Whether there is Internet services in the University. From the responses of the respondents, the item statement was accepted by the respondents with the mean scores of 3.6, 4.0, 3.9 and 4.3 respectively. Item 2 showed the views of respondents on whether the internet service works every day for the benefit of students. The mean scores of the respondents showed that the item was accepted by the respondents with the mean scores of 3.3, 4.0, 3.8, and 4.0 for Management staff, teaching staff, non-teaching staff and Students respectively. Item 3 was on whether the University internet is used for research by students to improve their academic achievement. The opinions of the respondents showed that the item statement was accepted that is Management staff had a mean score of 3.4, Teaching staff 4.4, non-teaching staff had 4.1 and Students had 4.2. Item 4 was on whether University makes provision for free wireless in the campus. The mean scores of 3.6, 3.8, 4.3 and 4.1 were obtained from the responses of the respondents, implying that the respondents accepted the item statement. Item 5 is on whether University makes provision for free wireless in the campus. The item was also accepted by the respondents with the mean scores of 3.6, 4.5, 4.2 and 3.0 for Management staff, Teaching staff, non-teaching staff and Students. Similarly, item 6 was accepted by the respondents with the mean scores of 3.3, 3.2, 4.2 and 4.2 for Management staff, Teaching staff, non-teaching staff and Students respectively. Item 7 was to find out whether the University is linked to internet service. The mean score showed that the item was accepted by all the categories of the respondents with the decision means of 3.3, 3.3, 3.9 and 3.2 for Management staff, Teaching staff, non-teaching staff and Students respectively. Item 8 was on whether Students are patronizing e-library for their research. The item statement was accepted by the respondents with the mean scores of 3.2, 3.8, 4.0 and 4.4 respectively. From item 9, the decision mean of the respondents were found to be 3.9, 3.7, 3.8 and 4.5, meaning the item was accepted by the respondents. Item 10 was on whether the management supervises the internet facilities regularly, the Item was accepted by all the respondents with the mean scores of 3.6, 4.0, 4.2 and 3.7 respectively. Item 11 was on whether spoiled facilities are replaced promptly. The item was accepted by all the respondents with the mean scores of 3.3, 3.5, and 4.0 respectively. Item 12 was on whether the computers in the E-Library are well maintained. The item was accepted by the respondents with the mean scores of 3.6, 4.1, 3.6 and 4.1, respectively. From the analysis of Table 1, it was established that internet services are provided in most of the Federal Universities of Northwest Geographical Zone, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Testing

H01: There was no significant difference between the extent of provision and management of internet services among Federal Universities in North-west, Nigeria.

Table 2: Summary of the One Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on the extent of Provision and Management of Internet Services among Federal Universities in North-west, Nigeria.

Dialogue	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	9.558	3	3.186	2.211	0.085
Within Groups	496.960	372	1.373		
Total	506.518	374			

Source: Fieldwork, 2022

From table 2, the F-value is 2.311 and the P-value is 0.085 at 0.05 level of significance. Since the P-value is greater than the level of significance set for the study, the hypothesis is therefore retained. Thus, there is no significant difference in the opinions of respondents on Perception of Stakeholders (respondents) on Provision and Management of Internet services in universities of northwest geographical zone, Nigeria. This means Internet services were provided in the Federal Universities of North-west zone, but there were issues of inadequate maintenance of the facilities.

Discussion of Findings

It was revealed by the findings of this study that Internet services are provided in most of the Federal Universities in North-west, Nigeria, but there are issues of inadequate maintenance of the facilities in the Federal Universities. This was revealed from the responses of the respondents to the structured questions given to them. The result from the analysis shows that there was a unanimous acceptance of all the item statements on the research question which indicated that Internet services

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are provided in most of the Federal Universities, findings also showed that there is inadequate maintenance of those facilities; responses from the participants shows among others that, there is Internet service in the Universities; The internet service works every day for the benefit of students; The Universities internet is used for research by students to improve their academic achievement; Universities makes provision for free wireless in the campus. The findings are in support of the findings of Chifwepa (2013) who discovered a high use of internet by the staff of the University of Zambia and their major motivation for such use was convenience (82.91%); usefulness (80.05%); free access to information and software (71.4%); and ease of use (68.6%). In Nigeria Jagdoro (2014), in his own research also, ascertained that 45.2% of graduate students access the Internet at the cybercafé in the university where only 8.2% used the library Internet facilities. A greater percentage (38.24%) did that only on monthly basis where 39.7% spent one hour on each visit. The outcome of this study also support the findings from the study of Oso and Adesina (2017) which indicated that, the government provides internet services in the institution but teachers and student cannot regularly access the services due to negligence of the school management in terms of regular subscription to the internet services, lack of upgrade and maintenance of the available facilities This finding has highlighted the fact that although internet services are provided in universities, lack of proper and regular maintenance is affecting the ability of students and staff to optimally utilize such services.

Conclusion

The paper concluded that, although, internet services are provided in most of the Federal Universities in North-west, Nigeria, but there are issues of inadequate maintenance of the facilities despite the prospects provision and management of internet services in Nigerian universities hold for transforming education, research, and administrative operations. Thus, challenges related to provision and management of the internet service must be addressed collaboratively by universities management, government, and all other stakeholders through strategic interventions and concerted efforts, in order to harness the full potential of the internet for the betterment of education and society at large.

Recommendations

1. The University management should increase access to Internet services in Federal Universities to meet both students and staff demand.
2. The University management should ensure that there are adequate measures put in place for regular maintenance of existing internet facilities in Federal Universities in North-west zone, Nigeria.

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Comparative Analysis Between Conditions of Service and Professional Commitment among Private School Teachers in Ilorin-South Local Government, Kwara State

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Abstract

This study investigated comparative analysis between conditions of service and commitment among private school teachers in Ilorin-south local government, Kwara State. Correlational research design was adopted for this study. Purpose of the study is to examine the relationship between teachers' conditions of service and commitment in private secondary schools in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria. Two research questions and five hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study comprise 13145 (7145 male;6000 female) private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State during the 2022/2023 academic session. The sample size of the study consists of 364(Male 200; female 164) private secondary school teachers selected using proportional sampling technique. A Researcher-designed questionnaire titled 'Teachers' conditions of service and commitment questionnaire (TCOSCOQ) was used for data collection'. Reliability coefficient of 0.85 was obtained. Percentage was used to answer the research questions while Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Statistic was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed there is significant relationship between teachers' conditions of service and commitment in private secondary schools in Ilorin south local Government area, Kwara State. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that teachers need to be committed to their responsibilities and to achieve this, their conditions of service must be favourable. The study therefore recommends among others that school owners should endeavour to pay teachers' salary regularly and ensure that teachers' salary are increase as and when due.

Keywords: conditions of service, private schools, teachers and commitment

Introduction

Teachers play an important role in educating the future members of a society through their work in school. They contribute to the future of their students either positively or negatively. The commitment of teachers is a key factor influencing the teaching-learning process. It is the psychological identification of the individual teacher with the school and the subject matter or goals, and the intention of that teacher to maintain organisational membership and become involved in the job well beyond personal interest. The greatest commitment of a teacher should be with the students and their learning. Students of highly committed teachers are more likely to learn faster and develop a positive attitude toward school than those of teachers with low levels of commitment. According to Nwadubueze (2013), there is no effective education without a committed teacher who is willing and ready to give his best to his students. A committed teacher is one that is not only concerned about his payment but also sees to it that his students get the very best meaning of what is been taught in class. Teaching is not a mission; it is a profession, and like any other, it requires a certain set of knowledge, competencies, skills, and behaviours. A teacher who is truly committed to students is one that puts students' learning and interests above everything else. It's a teacher who knows that the continuity of the work started with students during the term/semester or school year is essential and does their best to comply with the commitment they have made. The commitment of teachers should go beyond just communicating with their students in class but should include providing opportunities for students to keep in touch with them by way of classroom blogs, Facebook pages, and the like. For these teachers, answering a students' query by e-mail is not a hassle, but a pleasure. Communication is not only made easy but also very interesting not only on the part of the teacher but also on the part of the students. The education of students is at risk when teachers put up a lackadaisical attitude towards teaching the student. Teachers should not allow their personal problems or needs affect their classes. Even when they have to miss work, they should find a way to minimise the effects of their absence on students by: providing a detailed lesson plan for the substitute teacher; whenever possible, choosing a day in which their absence will jeopardise students' learning the least; if choosing the date is not possible, rearranging the content so that the most challenging aspects will be dealt with on a day they will be present. When students don't receive proper teaching from the teachers, their school fees and right are being tampered with. For teachers to be

committed to their job, there is need for proper conditions of service. Schools need to be very attractive and encouraging, if the realization of the effectiveness of the schools is of priority to the government and other stakeholders in education. This is very necessary because, if teachers' conditions of service are not favourable, the teachers are likely not to be committed and the achievement of school objectives may be jeopardized. In private secondary schools in Nigeria, the issue of teachers' conditions of service has been generating a topic of discussion, because teachers have the feeling that they are not well treated by their state government. For instance, in Kwara State private secondary schools, sometimes, teachers get their salary late. Not only that, there has been a serious complaint by private secondary school teachers in Kwara state and many other states of the federation over the new Minimum Wage. The governments in some states, including Kwara State, implemented the New Minimum Wage for teachers who are between Grade Level 1 to 6 but did Consequential Adjustment for teachers from Grade Level 7 to 17. This situation might not encourage the teachers, who were given consequential adjustment (Ademola, 2020).

Promotion of teachers has not been timely implemented in Kwara State, as government do not key in very well to their capacity building, by organizing different trainings or financially support them to attend within or outside the country. To this end, Samson (2020) stated that, compensation of teachers in private secondary schools in many states in Nigeria, especially in the areas of salary, promotion, training opportunities, fringe benefits and other incentives, has not been encouraging. This could make teachers worrisome and could consequently have a negative effect on the commitment of teachers. Olalekan (2017) posited that teachers' conditions of service and commitment are inseparable. If teacher conditions of service are favourable, their morale could be boosted towards high dedication to their official duties and this will eventually help the school to achieve effectiveness in its operation, especially in the aspect of students' academic performance. Sadam (2016) posited that the ultimate goal of any educational institution is to see that its students have excellent academic performance in their examinations. However, one of the ways of ensuring this in private secondary schools in Kwara State is by making teachers' conditions of service such as salary, promotion, capacity building and fringe benefits more attractive, as poor conditions of service could consistently dampen their readiness to making the schools effective. Obadare (2018) lamented that one of the factors responsible for ineffectiveness of private secondary schools in Nigeria is lackadaisical attitude of the governments towards ensuring high teachers' commitment by providing favourable teachers' conditions of service, especially in the aspects of salary, promotion, fringe benefits and professional development.

Teachers' professional commitment is the psychological attachment of teachers to their job resulting in personalizing assigned task by given it their all. It can be measured by affective, normative or continuance commitment. According to Abdulkareem (2016), affective commitment is the feeling of oneness or mental attachment to an organization. Continuance is that commitment one exhibits because of the cost of leaving or losing the job while normative is that commitment due to the similarity in ones ideology to the organization. These commitment leads to school effectiveness. School effectiveness means the extent to which the school has been able to achieve the stated goals, especially in the area of students' academic performance. Adedeji (2018) maintained that effectiveness of schools could be measured through discipline, neatness of the environment, mutual relationship among school members or between school members and members of the host community, judicious utilization of the available resources could also be used to determine effectiveness of schools. However, students' academic performance takes precedence over others, because it is through it that concrete measures could be derived. Gabriel (2019) asserted that, for several years, one could conclude that private secondary schools in Kwara State have not been effective. Evidently, the results derived from Senior School Certificate Examinations have not been encouraging enough as shown from the performance of students from 2012 - 2021 that 38.81%, 69.58%, 29.37%, 36.68%, 52.97%, 26.01%, 49.98%, 17.13%, 39.82% and 48.61% have five credits and above including English Language and Mathematics respectively. Dada (2017) asserted effectiveness of the private secondary schools, especially in terms of excellent students' academic performance, is the end result which every stakeholder in education has a keen interest in. For this to be well achieved, among other things which should be done, teachers' commitment should be enhanced through favourable teachers' conditions of service. It is against this backdrop that this study is set out to examine the relationship between secondary school teachers' conditions of service and commitment in Kwara state.

Effectiveness of secondary schools in Nigeria, in terms of students' academic performance has been a serious concern for the members of the private. This is because the results derived from West African Senior School Certificate Examination since few years back have not been encouraging. Findings in West African Senior School Certificate Examination from 2012 to 2021 revealed the following percentage of students' passes.

Table 1: Percentage of Students who made five credits and above including Eng and Maths

Year	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
%	38.81	69.58	29.37	38.68	52.97	26.01	49.98	17.13	38.82	48.61

Table 1 revealed that in the last ten years, it was only in the years 2013 and 2016 that the percentage of candidates who got five credits and above, including English language and General Mathematics in WASSCE reached average. However, this scenario is not encouraging and could be due to low teachers' commitment arising from ineffective teachers' condition of service. Thus it is important to investigate the commitment of lecturers as it relates to teachers' conditions of service in secondary schools in Ilorin-south LGA, Kwara State. Hence, this is the gap which this study intends to fill.

Objectives of the study:

The main purpose of the paper is to examine the relationship between teachers' conditions of service and commitment in private secondary schools in Ilorin South Local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria. The specific purposes of this study are to:

1. Examine the mean response on conditions of service among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria
2. investigate the level of commitment in among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria.
3. examine the relationship between teachers' salary and commitment in private secondary schools in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria.
4. find out the relationship between promotion and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria.
5. examine the relationship between capacity building and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria.
6. investigate the relationship between fringe benefit and teachers' commitment in private secondary schools in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the paper:

1. What are the mean response of conditions of service among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria?
2. What is the level of teachers' commitment in private secondary schools in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

There are one main and four operational research hypotheses postulated to guide the study:

Main Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between conditions of service and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria

Null Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between salary and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria.
2. There is no significant relationship between promotion and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria.
3. There is no significant relationship between teachers' capacity building and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria.
4. There is no significant relationship between fringe benefit and teachers' commitment in private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria.

Methodology

Correlational research design was adopted for this study. Geographically, the study covers private secondary schools in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria. The population of the study comprise 13145 (7145 male; 6000 female) private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State during the 2022/2023 academic session. The sample size of the study consists of 364(Male 200; female 164) private secondary school teachers selected using proportional sampling technique. A

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Researcher-designed questionnaire titled ‘Teachers’ conditions of service and commitment questionnaire (TCOSCOQ) was used for data collection. It is subdivided into two parts A and B. Section A consist of items designed to collect data on teachers’ conditions of service while section B is design to collect data on teachers’ commitment. The statements in section A of the instrument were based on highly favourable (HF); moderately favourable (MF); lowly favourable (LF) and not favourable (NF) response pattern while section B was based on the four (4) Likert scale of strongly agree (A), agree(A), disagree (D) and strongly disagree (SD). The instrument was given to three experts in the Department of Educational Management and the validity of the instrument was ascertained. Crumbach Alpha was used to ascertain the reliability of the instrument and 0.85 was obtained as the reliability index. This showed that the questionnaire was reliable. Descriptive statistics of percentages was used to answer the research questions while inferential statistics of Pearson product moment correlation statistic was used to test research hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the mean response of conditions of service among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria?

Table 2: Favourability of Teachers’ Conditions of Service in Kwara State Secondary Schools

S/N	Item	HF	MF	LF	NF
		F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)
1.	Payment of Salary	09(29.95)	214(58.79)	41(11.26)	00 (0.00)
2.	Promotion	23(6.32)	182(50.00)	141(38.74)	18(4.95)
3.	Staff Dev. Programmes	33(9.07)	42 (11.54)	157(43.13)	132(36.26)
4.	Fringe Benefit	157(43.13)	182(50.00)	25 (6.94)	00(0.00)
.	Percentage Average	22.12	42.56	25.02	10.30.

Source: fieldwork (2023)

Table 2 revealed that 22.12 percent of the respondents (on the average) were of the opinion that teachers’ conditions of service are highly favourable service among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, 42.56 percent were of the opinion that teachers’ conditions of service are moderately favourable service among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, 25.02 percent agreed that teachers’ conditions of service are lowly service among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State while 10.30 percent were of the opinion that conditions of service are favourable service among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria. Since the highest percentage of the respondents were of the opinion that teachers’ conditions of service are moderately favourable service among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, it is suffix to conclude that teachers’ conditions of service are moderately favourable service among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State.

Research Question 2:

What is the level of teachers’ commitment in private secondary schools in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria?

Table 3: Commitment among Secondary School Teachers in Ilorin- south local government, Kwara State

S/N	ITEMS	Positive Response		Negative Response	
		Frequency	%	Frequency	%
1	I will do my best to ensure the success of this school	288	79.12	77	20.88
2	If I am given another job elsewhere, I will choose this secondary school over any other	82	22.50	282	77.47
3	I feel attached to this school psychologically	88	24.18	277	75.82
4	It is better to stay in this school because of the uncertainties in leaving for another job	300	82.42	64	17.58
5	The cost that comes with leaving my school is much, thus I will stay committed to my present job	79	21.70	285	78.30
6	The job security associated with my job makes me to love the job	321	88.19	43	11.81

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7	The success of this school is of more importance to me than my personal interest	64	17.58	300	82.42
8	Sharing my knowledge with other people makes me happy	364	100	00	00.00
9	There is mental satisfaction derived from helping others through my work	364	100	00	00.00
Percentage Average (%)		59.52		40.48	

Source:

fieldwork (2023)

Table 3 shows that 59.52% of the teachers (on the average) responded positively that: they will do their best to ensure the success of their schools, will still choose their present job if offered another job, feel attached to their present job psychologically, stayed on their present job because of the uncertainties of leaving for another job, stayed committed to their present job because of the cost of leaving the job, love their job because of the job security, put the success of their school above their personal interest and derive mental satisfaction from helping others. However, 40.48% of the respondents (on the average) negatively responded. Since the number of teachers (respondents) that are in agreement is higher than those that disagreed, it is sufficient to say that teachers in private secondary schools in Kwara state are committed.

Hypotheses Testing

Main Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between conditions of service and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria

Table 4: Teachers' conditions of service and Commitment in Private Secondary Schools in Kwara State

Status	N	SD	r-value calculated	p-value	Remark
Teachers' conditions of service	364	1.94	0.68	0.001	Significant
Teachers' Commitment	364	1.81			

source: fieldwork (2023) **P<0.05 at 0.05 alpha level**

It can be deduced from table three that the p value of 0.001 is less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the hypothesis that states that there is no significant relationship between conditions of service and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria is rejected. Thus, there is significant relationship between conditions of service and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria

Operational Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant relationship between salary and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria.

Table 5: Teachers' Salary & Commitment in Private Secondary Schools in Kwara State

Status	N	SD	r-value	p-value	Remark
Teachers' Salary	364	1.97	0.61	0.000	Significant
Teachers' Job Commitment	364	1.81			

source: fieldwork (2023) **P<0.05 at 0.05 alpha level**

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It can be deduced from table four that the p value of 0.000 is less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the hypothesis that states that there is no significant relationship between salary and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria is rejected. Thus, there is significant relationship between salary and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant relationship between promotion and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria.

Table 6: Teachers’ Promotion & Commitment in Private Sec. Schools in Ilorin-south, Kwara State

Status	N	SD	r-value calculated	p-value	Remark
Teachers’ Promotion	364	2.00			
			0.66	0.002	Significant
Teachers’ Commitment	364	1.81			

Source: fieldwork (2023) **P<0.05 at 0.05 alpha level**

It can be deduced from Table 6 that the p value of 0.002 is less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the hypothesis that states there is no significant relationship between promotion and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria is rejected. Thus, there is significant relationship between promotion and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 3:

There is no significant relationship between teachers’ capacity building and commitment among private secondary schools teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria.

Table 7: Teachers’ Capacity Buildings and Commitment in Private Secondary Schools in Kwara State

Status	N	SD	r-value calculated	p-value	Remark
Teachers’ capacity buildings	364	24.99	2,11		
			0.58	0.000	Significant
Teachers’ Commitment	364	24.87	1.81		

source: fieldwork (2023)

P<0.05 at 0.05 alpha level

It can be deduced from Table 7 that the p value of 0.000 is less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the hypothesis that states that there is no significant relationship between teachers’ capacity building and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria is rejected. Thus, there is significant relationship between teachers’ capacity building and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 4:

There is no significant relationship between fringe benefit and teachers’ commitment in private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria.

Table 8: Fringe Benefit and Teachers' Commitment in Private Secondary Schools in Kwara State.

Status	N	SD	r-value calculated	p-value	Remark
Fringe benefits	364	1.89			
Teachers' Job Commitment	364	1.81	0.76	0.001	Significant

source: fieldwork (2023) **P<0.05 at 0.05 alpha level**

It can be deduced from Table 8 that the p value of 0.001 is less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the hypothesis that states that there is no significant relationship between fringe benefit and teachers' commitment in private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria is rejected. Thus, there is significant relationship between fringe benefit and teachers' commitment in private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The testing of the main hypothesis resulted in its rejection. Hence there is significant relationship between conditions of service and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria. This conforms to the observation of (Mazaki, 2009, as cited in Ademola, 2020), that teachers' conditions of service in schools is aimed at making teachers happy, healthy and duty conscious. Teachers' conditions of service have been found to be indispensable tools in increasing commitment of teachers and organizational effectiveness (Buitendach & de Wite, 2005, as cited by Ademola, 2020). Yousef (2008, as cited in Abdulkareem, 2016) noted that teachers' conditions of service and commitment are inversely related to such withdrawal behaviours as tardiness, absenteeism and staff turnover. The finding from the testing of hypothesis one revealed that there is no significant relationship between salary and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria. This finding is in agreement with that (Ejiogu, 2007, cited in Abdulkareem, 2016) that the typical low income earning teacher yearn is a sizeable salary increase that would significantly enhance their commitment and performance. Fabiyi (2007, cited in Abdulkareem, 2016) also ascertained that of all conditions of service, salary is the best predictor of teacher's performance, productivity and commitment. Fabiyi further stated that salaries of teachers are inadequate making it so difficult for teachers to meet the basic necessities of life, their salaries when compared with other employees with the same qualifications and experience, but are in other sectors of economy such as bankers; site engineers and nurses can be described as unfavourable.

The rejection of hypothesis two revealed that there is significant relationship between promotion and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria This conforms to the findings of Lambert, Hogan and Jiang {2008, cited in Samson, 2020) who observed that employees expect to work in the organizations which provide plenty of promotional opportunities for more challenging and responsible positions. If there is a good environment of promotion policies within the company, employees tend to work hard to earn the promotion, increase the productivity of their work, as well as develop a strong emotional bond with their workplace (Gaiduk *et al.* (2009, cited in Abdulkareem, 2016). Hence, there is a positive relation between organizational commitment and policies and practices concerning a promotion within the organization. The positive relation between promotional opportunities and lecturers' commitment has also been identified in higher education sector in particular. Malik *et al* (2010, cited in Adedeji, 2018) have conducted the research among university teachers in private sector of Pakistan and have found out that academics that are highly satisfied with the promotional opportunities they are provided with are also more satisfied with their job in general as well as more committed to their workplace.

The testing of hypothesis three showed that there is significant relationship between teachers' capacity building and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria. This finding goes in line with the finding of (Souza, 2009, as cited in Olalekan, 2017) that staff development and training should be an in-built and integral part of school system if teachers would perform their job well, motivated and get full satisfaction from their work. The provision of training and development programmes can significantly enhance confidence and motivation level of educators (Wati, as cited in Olalekan, 2017).

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Hypothesis four was rejected, thus there is significant relationship between fringe benefit and teachers' commitment in private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria. This finding is in conjunction with the finding of (Allender, Colquhoun, and Kelley, 2011, as cited in Abdulkareem, 2016) who found that the workplace health leads to the job motivation and satisfaction. Therefore, the academicians will be motivated and committed in their teaching when regularly receive unexpected benefits. Priti (2009 cited in Obadare, 2018) argued that the role of teachers' conditions of service activities is to promote economic development by increasing efficiency and productivity with the underlying principle is making workers give their loyal services ungrudgingly in genuine spirit of co-operation and the general well-being of the employee. In the same vein, (Ubom, 2002, as cited in Gabriel, 2019)), teachers place premium on variables such as salary, time and mode of payment of salaries, fringe benefits, promotional prospects of teaching and work environment as determinants of job satisfaction, which in turn affect their productivity in a positive manner.

Conclusion

Teachers are the most important resources among every other one within the school system. The teachers manipulate material, financial and physical resources in order to achieve the goals and objectives of the school. It is therefore necessary to ensure that they are committed to their job. Commitment of teachers in secondary schools is more of continuance and normative commitment but it is necessary to ensure that teachers are committed in terms of affective, continuance and normative. Teachers' conditions of service as a catalyst to teachers' motivation, job satisfaction and job commitment must be improved upon.

Recommendations

1. Government should also endeavour to pay teachers' salary regularly and ensure that teachers' salary is increase as and when due.
2. Principals should always try to assess staff training needs, plan training programmes and get sponsorship from government of private individuals if need be. The Government also need to make fund available to the school to carry out needed developmental programmes.
3. Government should ensure that promotions are done as and when due. Effort should also be made to ensure that promotion is based on merit and not on ascription or favourism.
4. Teachers should be given stipends for some extra work done as commendation to make then give more towards the achievement of school goals and objectives.

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Comparative Analysis Between Quality Assurance Mechanisms and Administration at Secondary School Level of Education in North-West, Nigeria

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Abstract

There are evidences of different views on the relationship between the various mechanism of quality assurance and school administration. Hence, this study examined the Co-relationships between Quality Assurance Mechanisms and administration at secondary school level of Education in North-west, Nigeria. The study adopted a correlation type of research design. Simple and stratified random sampling procedures were used to select the sample of the study. The population of the study consisted of 26,048 teachers from all the senior secondary schools in the North West, zone of Nigeria during the 2022/2023 academic session. The sample comprises of 1500 teachers from 75 secondary schools. Quality Assurance Mechanism Questionnaire (QAMQ), School Effectiveness Questionnaire (SEQ) and Qualifying Examinations results of the students were used to collect data for the study. The QAMQ and SEQ instruments were validated, and test-retest method of reliability was used to determine their reliability coefficients of 0.78 and 0.81 respectively. Two research questions guided the conduct of the study. The data collected for the study were analyzed using relevant descriptive (frequency counts and percentage score) and inferential (Pearson Product Moment Correlation) statistical tools. The study revealed a positive correlation between quality assurance mechanism, instructional supervision (0.745), in-service training (0.682), learning environment (0.825) and school administration. The study concludes that quality assurance mechanisms relate to the effectiveness administration of the schools. Therefore, it was recommended among others that the principals of the schools should sustain the tempo of supervision in schools in order to ensure better school administration.

Keywords: Education, Quality Assurance Mechanism and administration.

Introduction

Education which is a vital factor in economic and political development of any country is a process of acquiring the necessary skills needed to live a useful life as a member of the society where one lives. In any organization performing a given task, especially those engaged in human capital development like secondary schools, are in need of quality assurances. Quality assurance involves the achievement of educational programme standards which are established by institutions, professional organizations, and government. While quality assurance mechanisms are the processes by which the achievement of these standards is measured. Smith (2021) defined quality assurance as a planned and systematic review process of an institution or program to determine whether or not acceptable standards of education, scholarship, and infrastructure are being met, maintained and enhanced. Mensah, Okyere & Kuranchie, (2013) opined that quality assurance involves the evaluation of a system or a school and its operations against certain prescribed standards for self-assurance that ensure all devices are working to make output or results correspond to set objectives. Within the context of teaching and learning, quality assurance refers to the process of ensuring that practices and procedures or actions intended to enhance quality and excellence in the key areas of classroom lesson delivery and test administration are complied with. In the view expressed by Okeke-James, Igbokwe, Anyanwu, & Ogbo, (2020), quality assurance is the process of ensuring that the learners are maximally imparted with the skill and knowledge as was stated in national educational goals. Therefore, the increasing awareness of the importance of education to the upliftment of the individual and the society has made both the household and the nation devote a reasonable proportion of their earnings to acquiring qualitative education. Scheerens, (2016) defines school efficacy as the ability of a school to produce desired outcomes in terms of student learning, development, and achievement. It involves the school's capacity to efficiently utilize its resources, implement effective teaching strategies, and create a positive learning environment. School

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efficacy" refers to the belief or perception that a school, as a whole, has the capacity to successfully achieve its goals and objectives. It involves the collective confidence of the school community—administrators, teachers, students, and sometimes parents in the school's ability to create a positive and effective learning environment. This concept is often associated with the broader field of school effectiveness, which examines the factors that contribute to a school's success in promoting student learning and development. School efficacy is closely related to the concept of self-efficacy, which refers to an individual's belief in their own ability to succeed in specific situations. In the context of schools, the collective self-efficacy of the school community can significantly impact the overall effectiveness of the educational institution. Researchers often explore school efficacy in the context of school improvement efforts and interventions to enhance educational outcomes for students.

Quality assurance in education aims at preventing quality problems and ensures that the products of the school system conform to the expected standard. According to Okebukola (2017), quality assurance is an umbrella concept for a host of activities that are designed to improve the quality of input, process and output of an education system. Omopariola (2017) argues that quality assurance is the steady maintenance and improvement of the quality or standard of education in all areas of the school system. In Nigeria, secondary education prepares students for useful living within the society and preparing them for higher education. It is very pivotal in the educational system of the country because it is the bedrock which determines the academic and professional career of students. It is also of six-year duration comprising of three years each for junior and senior secondary school levels. In spite of the importance of secondary education system, concerns about the poor quality of secondary education graduates are on increase in Nigeria (Adeyemi & Adeyemi, 2020). For instance, the growing complaints by parents, heads of tertiary education institutions and the employers indicate that secondary school graduates are poorly prepared for the challenges ahead of them. Reporting on obstacles bedeviling the secondary schools' effectiveness, Abenga (2019), maintained that concerns expressed by government bureaucrats, politicians and the public in general is over what they perceived as lack of and/or inadequate quality assurance practices in secondary schools. Also, Olaleye and Jolaoso (2017) reported that the present state of achievement of secondary school students as measured by performance in external examination conducted by the West African Examination Council (WAEC) has been characterized by a declining trend, which caused a dissatisfaction of the general public.

In the North West zone of Nigeria, as in other geo-political zone of the country, inadequate quality assurance poses a serious challenge to school effectiveness of secondary schools. Thus, according to Ekundayo (2018), the ineffectiveness of the secondary schools in the three domains of learning has been attributed to several factors such as parental factor, teacher factor, societal factors and institutional factors. While the institutional factor considered here relates to the quality assurance mechanisms such as instructional supervision, in-service training and the learning environment that were put in place in the school system. In the same tone, Adeyemi & Adeyemi (2020) observed that the maintenance of factors such as curriculum, instructional materials, equipment, school management, teacher training and resources are some of the indicators of quality education. Quality assurance therefore has to do with compliance with standards set in ensuring that schools achieve the objectives for which they are established.

Instructional supervision as a key factor of quality mechanism in the school system is a service activity designed to help teachers do their job better so as to bring about effective operation of a good system. According Walker (2016) instructional supervision is a task of improving instruction through regular monitoring of teachers. The implication of this definition is that, a deficiency in this exercise may spell doom for the education system. Series of concerns has been raised over the level of both internal and external supervision in secondary schools in North-West geo-political zone of Nigeria. It appears that the principals of schools and heads of departments who are in charge of internal supervision are being found wanting in their assignments. Inadequate or haphazard supervision could result in teachers' lackadaisical attitude towards their job and consequently make school ineffective. Usman (2015) found a positive relationship between instructional supervision and teachers' performance and academic achievements of students in secondary schools. This in extension has implication for secondary schools' effectiveness.

In-service training is another factor of quality assurance mechanism that has impact on the level of effectiveness of a school. In-service training is an on-the-job training organized for teachers to help them develop their skills in their areas of discipline. It can be in the form of training organized by the agencies in charge of the school system in order to improve the professional development of the teachers. Contrary to studies of (Garba, 2014; Rahman, Jamani, Akhter, Chisthi, & Ajmal, 2015), which revealed positive relationship between in-service training and school effectiveness. There are evidences such as Alabi, (2016), Adeyemi, et al, (2019), Akomo, et al (2015) that revealed that some practicing teachers in secondary schools were not adequately equipped with the necessary skills for curriculum delivery. They emphasize that some do not know how well to present lessons in the classroom. Besides, few teachers that know how to identify relevant instructional materials do

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not know how to make effective use of the instructional materials. All these explained why performance of the secondary school teachers is declining and thus making the schools to be ineffective.

Another factor of quality assurance that could affect school effectiveness is learning environment. According to Omopariola (2017) learning can occur anywhere, but the positive learning outcomes generally sought by educational systems happen in quality learning environment. Thus, conduciveness of the school learning environment has been said to be potent factors influencing students' achievements in the three domains of learning and thereby result to school effectiveness. This view was also supported by many studies, for example, Etim, Iya, Akuegwu, Basil, Uchendu & Chika, (2019) that found positive relationship between school facilities and school effectiveness in the environment of learning while, Ogunode, & Agwor, (2020) also reiterated provision of adequate facilities for effective teaching and learning to take place.

In the dynamic landscape of secondary school education, the co-relationships between quality assurance mechanisms and administration play a pivotal role in shaping the overall educational experience. While quality assurance mechanisms are designed to ensure and enhance the educational standards, administrative practices act as the backbone of school management. However, there is a gap in our understanding of how these two crucial elements interact and influence each other in the context of secondary education. This research aims to delve into the complexities of this relationship, seeking to identify the key factors that contribute to effective co-ordination or potential conflicts between quality assurance mechanisms and administration at the secondary school level. By addressing this gap, the study seeks to provide insights that can inform policy decisions, improve educational practices, and contribute to the overall advancement of secondary education systems.

Objectives of the Study

This study was designed to investigate co-relationships between quality assurance mechanisms and administration at secondary school level of education in North-west, Nigeria. Specifically; the objectives of the study are as follows:

1. To determine the nature of the relationship between quality assurance mechanism (Instructional supervision, In-service training and Learning environment) and administration of Secondary schools' effectiveness in North-West zone of Nigeria.
2. To examine the significance of the relationship existing between quality assurance mechanism (Instructional supervision, In-service training and Learning environment) and administration of Secondary schools' effectiveness in North-West zone of Nigeria.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions.

1. What is the nature of the relationship between quality assurance mechanism (Instructional supervision, In-service training and Learning environment) and administration of Secondary school effectiveness in North-West zone of Nigeria?
2. Is there any significant relationship between Quality Assurance mechanism (Instructional supervision, In-service training and Learning environment) and administration of secondary schools' effectiveness in North-West zone of Nigeria?

Methodology

The design of this study was basically correlation type of research design. The population of the study consisted of 26,048 teachers from all the senior secondary schools in the North West zone of Nigeria during the 2022/2023 academic session. These schools cut across Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Sokoto and Zamfara States in the North-West geo-political zones of Nigeria. Multi-stage sampling procedure technique was used to select the sample. The first stage involved the use of purposive sampling to select four States due to security situations out of the seven states in North-west Nigeria. The states selected were Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano and katsina. For the second stage, a proportionate stratified random sampling procedure was used to determine the number of schools per state. Fifteen (15) schools were selected from Jigawa State, twenty (20) schools each from Kaduna, Kano and katsina States respectively to make up total number of Seventy-Five (75) secondary schools used for the study. The third and final stage involved the use of simple random sampling to select 20 teachers from each of the 75 senior secondary schools, making 1500 teachers in all.

Three instruments were used to gather the data for the study. The first instrument was tagged Quality Assurance Mechanism Questionnaire (QAMQ) and it comprises two sections. Section A elicited response on personal background information of the respondents while section B requested information about the influence of quality assurance mechanisms on administration of secondary school effectiveness. The second instrument which was tagged School Effectiveness Questionnaire (SEQ), also consisted of two sections A and B. Section A of the questionnaire elicited information on school variables such as location, type and level. Section B requested information about the influence of quality assurance mechanisms on affective and

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psychomotor domains of learning activities in the schools. The third instrument used for the study was a Qualifying Examinations results. It measured the students' performance which is also a factor of teachers' contribution to administration of secondary school effectiveness. Hence, this result was combined to the results of the analysis of the responses on Section B of the School Effectiveness Questionnaire (SEQ) to determine the administration of secondary school efficacy. Both (QAMQ) and (SEQ) instruments were structured along five point likert scale namely Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Neutral (N), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) weighted 5,4, 3, 2 and 1 point respectively positively demanding statement and reverse for the negative ones. The teachers who are the respondents were requested to indicate the extent of their agreement or disagreement with each item in the questionnaires. The instruments were validated by research experts in Educational Management, and Tests and Measurement in Bayero University Kano. The QAMQ and SEQ instruments were validated, and test-retest method of reliability was used to determine their reliability coefficients of 0.78 and 0.81 respectively were obtained using test-retest method. The data for the study were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The descriptive used include frequency counts and percentage score, while the inferential statistics used was Pearson Product Moment Correlation.

Result

Research Question 1

What is the nature of the relationship between quality assurance mechanism (Instructional supervision, In-service training and Learning environment) and administration of Secondary school effectiveness in North-West zone of Nigeria?

Table 1: Intercorrelation Matrix of Independent Variables (Quality Assurance Mechanisms) and Dependent Variables (School effectiveness)

Variables	Quality Assurance Mechanisms			School Effectiveness
	1	2	3	4
1	1.000			
2	.492	1.000		
3	.528	.420	1.000	
4	0.745	0.682	0.825	1.000

Key: 1 = Instructional supervision; 2 = In-service training;
 3 = Learning environment; 4 = School effectiveness.

Table 1 shows the intercorrelation matrix with the coefficient of correlation for each pair of the variables examined. The findings of the correlation matrix show the nature of the relationship between pairs of quality assurance mechanisms' variables ((instructional supervision, in-service training and learning environment) with respect to administration of secondary school's efficacy's variables (school effectiveness). The results presented in Table 1 shows that there existed positive correlation between quality assurance mechanisms' variables: instructional supervision (0.745), in-service training (0.682) and Learning environment (0.825) and school effectiveness.

Research Question 2:

Is there any significant relationship between Quality Assurance mechanism (Instructional supervision, In-service training and Learning environment) and administration of secondary schools' effectiveness in North-West zone of Nigeria?

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) Analysis of Pairs of Quality Assurance Mechanisms and administration of secondary School Effectiveness

Variable	No. of Cases	Calculated r_{xy}	Critical r_{xy}	Decision at $P < .05$
Instructional supervision (x) School Effectiveness (y)	1500	0.745*	0.250	S
In-service Training (x) School Effectiveness (y)	1500	0.682*	0.250	S

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Learning Environment (x)				
School Effectiveness (y)	1500	0.825*	0.250	S

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level

The results of the correlation coefficient analysis presented in Table 2 show that there exists a significant relationship between quality assurance mechanism of instructional supervision and administration of secondary school effectiveness (calculated $r_{xy} = 0.745$; critical $r_{xy} = 0.250$); a significant relationship between quality assurance mechanism of in-service training and administration of secondary school effectiveness (calculated $r_{xy} = 0.682$; critical $r_{xy} = 0.250$); and a significant relationship between quality assurance mechanism of learning environment and administration of secondary school effectiveness (calculated $r_{xy} = 0.825$; critical $r_{xy} = 0.250$).

Discussions of the Findings

The findings presented in Table 4.1 revealed that positive relationship exist between relationship between quality assurance mechanisms (Instructional supervision (0.745), In-service training (0.682) and Learning environment (0.825)) and administration of secondary school effectiveness. The observations from this study indicated that quality assurance mechanisms are strongly related to administration of secondary school effectiveness. Hence, each of the quality assurance mechanisms has strong relative effect on administration of secondary school effectiveness. There are some earlier studies that supported the findings here. Usman (2015) for instance, investigated the impact of instructional supervision on academic performance of secondary school students (a factor of school effectiveness) in Nasarawa State. He found a positive relationship between instructional supervision and school effectiveness. This implies that if instructions are well supervised through regular monitoring of teachers, improved school effectiveness will be the result. For the impact of in-service training on the level of effectiveness of a school, studies of Rahman et. al, (2015) and Garba, (2014) revealed positive relationship between the two variables. This present study therefore confirmed that if in-service training is provided for teachers, it will help in developing their skills in their area of discipline. The teachers will know how well to deliver their lessons and how to make effective use of instructional materials, thus making schools effective. While for the relationship between learning environment and school effectiveness, Walker, (2016) and Omopariola, (2017) in their different studies found positive relationship existing between learning environment and school effectiveness. Their findings revealed learning environment to be a potent factor influencing school effectiveness.

In seeking answer to the second research question that says: Is there any significant relationship between Quality Assurance mechanism (Instructional supervision, In-service training and Learning environment) and administration of secondary schools effectiveness in North-West zone of Nigeria? The study reveals that there is significant relationship between the pairs of quality assurance mechanisms (Instructional supervision, In-service training and Learning environment) and administration of secondary school effectiveness. The implication of these findings, for instance on the significant relationship between instructional supervision and administration of secondary school effectiveness is that effective supervision of the teachers' activities will invariably lead to effective administration of secondary school effectiveness. The reason for this is due to the fact that the secondary school principals and Heads of Department who are the supervisory agencies are up and doing in the schools. This finding thus, corroborates a similar study of Usman (2015), Alonge & Obiweluzor, (2015) and Walker (2016). Also, the significant relationship between in-service training and school effectiveness implies that if enough provision is made for teachers' in-service training and teachers are encouraged to attend, school effectiveness will be enhanced. This finding could also due to the fact that teachers' attendance and participation in various in-service training will bring about sustainable human capacity development which will invariably contribute to school effectiveness. This finding is in consonance with Garba, (2014), Rahman et. al (2015) and Omopariola (2017). While the observed significant relationship between learning environment and school effectiveness suggests that when the learning environment is conducive, when all learning resources are better put in place and well utilized by the teachers, better performance (factor of school effectiveness) are expected from the students. Hence, enhanced school effectiveness will be the result. This also suggests that learning environment has great influence on school effectiveness. This finding is in agreement with similar findings of Ahunanya & Ubabudu (2016) and Omopariola (2017). More so, this also agrees with the studies of Asiabaka (2018) and Adeyemi & Adeyemi (2020) that found positive relationship between school facilities and school effectiveness in the environment of learning.

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Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the conclusion drawn was that quality assurance mechanisms such as instructional supervision, in-service training, and learning environment has positive relationship to the effectiveness of the administration of secondary schools in Northwest, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made.

1. The Secondary School Principals and Heads of Departments as quality assurance agents should sustain the tempo of instructional supervision in schools in order to ensure better administration of secondary school effectiveness.
2. Secondary school principals should encourage teachers to attend and participate in-service training such as workshops, seminars and conferences. This is to enhance better human capital development and to improve upon the level of school effectiveness.

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Comparative Analysis of Funding of Students' Personnel Services in Public and Private Secondary Schools in Ilorin West Local Government

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Abstract

This study compared funding of students' personnel services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government. It adopted descriptive research design of survey type. The population for the study comprised all the 2,325 (female 1,327; male, 998) teachers in the 42 public secondary schools and 2,229 (female 1,219; male, 1,010) teachers in the 48 private secondary schools in the local government area in 2022/2023 academic session. Random sampling technique was used to select 21 public and 24 private secondary schools, while 10 teachers were randomly selected from each of the sampled schools to make a sample of 450. Questionnaire entitled "Funding of Students' Personnel Services Questionnaire" was used to collect data for the study. The questionnaire was validated, tested for reliability and found reliability coefficient of .81. Inferential statistic of t-test was used to test the hypotheses formulated. The findings of the study revealed that there was a significant difference between funding of students' personnel services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government ($p < .05$). The study concluded that funding of students' personnel services was performed better in private secondary schools than public in Ilorin West Local Government. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among other things that government should intensify its efforts in funding students' personnel services like proprietors of private schools, while the proprietors of private schools should not relent in giving personnel services a priority, in order to continually provide a supportive and conducive environment for students to learn and consequently boost their academic performance.

Keywords: Funding, Students' Personnel Services; Library Service, Guidance and Counselling Services, Co-curricular Services

Introduction

Funding is an important instrument for achieving the goals of education, regardless of the level. It is a very key necessity which significant determines school success (Salman, 2022). Funding could be adjudged as one of the factors which is responsible for variation in the effectiveness of schools in Nigeria (Adekola, 2022). A school that is well-funded is likely to operate better than the one that is funded poorly. However, one of the areas where school proprietors need to ensure adequate funding on, in order to achieve the goal(s) for which the schools are established is students' personnel services such as library services, information communication services, health services, guidance and counselling services, co-curricular services and

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the likes (Yusuf, et al, 2019). According to Odediji, et al. (2023), funding is the process of making money available for effective running of a private or public organization in order to actualize the stated goals. Elujekwute, et al. (2021) stated that funding refers to provision of financial resource for the success of an organization. Ogungbenle and Edogiawerie (2019) explained that funding is a crucial resource which schools need to achieve the stated goals. Adequate provision of funds is a strong base upon which the smooth operation of every aspect of any educational enterprise is built. Ahmed and Oweh (2013) submitted that inadequate funding is one of the problems facing educational system in Nigeria, irrespective of the level. Adewuyi and Okemakinde (2013) opined that considering the role which education plays in the socio-economic development of Nigeria, it is very crucial that both government and private investors in education ensure adequate provision of financial resource for schools. Nwafor, et al. (2015) maintained that all the stakeholders in education believe that the quality of funding made available to a school is a great determinant of the quality of its outputs. Odediji, et al. (2023) maintained that no secondary school can effectively operate without adequate funding. Apart from adequate provision of student personnel services, funding is required for the payment of workers' salaries, provision for and maintain infrastructural facilities and to keep the school at proper condition Adequate provision of funds for schools is very sacrosanct to the smooth to the actualization of schools' goals. However, one of the areas which adequate funding is needed for schools to achieve the stated goals is in the area of students' personnel services. According to Abdullahi (2017), students' personnel services can be defined as all activities carried out by managers, teachers and non-teaching staff in order to make school conducive for learning for students, make them happy, useful and become better citizens of the society in which they belong. Yusuf, et al. (2019) elucidated students' personnel services as various services which are provided for students by school management, with the purpose of helping them to succeed in their academic activities. This is necessary not only to ensure that students gladly learn but also ensure that the stated goals achieved. Ebirim, et al. (2014) maintained that students' personnel services are an important aspect of school system and they constitute the needs which would assist students to achieve their educational dreams. No educational system, irrespective of the level, cannot effectively operate without these services and their provision greatly support the success of the schools.

Usman (2015) asserted that the poor performance of students in secondary schools in Nigeria could be due inadequate provision of personnel services to students. Bradley et al. (2015) stated that adequate provision of students' personnel services makes students comfortable, and this helps in greatly contributing to not only the peace of mind but also effective learning of students. The aspects of students' personnel services which this study covered were library, guidance and counselling and co-curricular services. Onuoha and Chukwueke (2020) viewed a library as a systematized assemblage of sources of information resources made available for students for reference or borrowing, in order to boost their academic performance. In addition, school library serves as the channel for ensuring availability of physical or digital access to materials which help support students' effective learning. Agbo (2015) maintained that library services are very important because of its role in improving the academic development of students. Through library services, students have access to a pool of textbooks, newspapers, periodicals, magazines, journals, computers, films, recordings or videotapes which help to enrich their knowledge in their various subjects of learning and other aspects of learning. Nkamnebe, et al. (2017) noted that library services in general term cover reference services, lending services, referral services, document delivery, electronic mail services, current awareness services, selective dissemination of information, reprographic services, indexing and abstracting services, bibliographic services and online searching amongst others. If all these are adequately provided and students make effective use of them, it would help enhance their academic success. The findings of the study conducted by Verma (2015) revealed that school library plays an important role in the academic success of students. No educational institution is complete without effective library services provision for students. In addition, the findings of Strong (2013) showed that there was a significant relationship between library services and students' academic attainment and sustainable education in the United States of America.

Another aspect of students' personnel services which is highly needed to be given adequate attention in schools is guidance and counselling. Abdullahi (2017) stated that guidance and counselling services are a crucial aspect of students' personnel services. This is because it is a channel that is based on desirable advisory techniques, aimed at helping students to actualise their aspirations and goals. Through guidance and counselling, emotional problems, frustration or upheavals which are troubling the students' minds are removed. To buttress the importance of guidance and counselling services to students, the findings of the study conducted by Anagbogu, et al. (2013) revealed that there was a significant relationship between guidance and counseling services and academic success of students. Owan and Ekaette (2019) opined that guidance and counseling services are a significant aspect of students' personnel services. This educative act aims at helping students to develop competencies and skills that could assist them to make decisions that would make them live impactful lives and at the same time aptly make their contributions to the national development. Etebu, et al. (2016) submitted that guidance and counseling is an important component of educational system and so, it is very imperative that every school is provided with trained counselors

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saddled with the responsibility of dishing out professional guidance and counseling services to students, to make them solve any problem which could hinder their effective learning. Ali and Ogundele (2015) believed that it is very crucial for schools to have effective guidance and counselling services so as to provide the necessary support for students in the choice of career. Ogundele, et al. (2018) concluded that provision of real guidance and counseling services needs to be given an utmost consideration. The quality level of guidance and counseling services provided for secondary school students would enable them to fathom their potentials and able to take right decisions which would aid their academic success. Another aspect of students' personnel services which needs adequate funding is co-curricular services. Othoo and Omondi (2022) explained co-curricular activities as those activities sponsored or recognised by a school which are not part of the academic curriculum but are approved to be an indispensable part of school system. Co-curricular activities consist of sports, clubs or associations which are performed based on students' willingness. They are activities carried out outside the realm of students' academic activities. Bryant, et al. (2015) believed that co-curricular services are an essential aspect of students' personnel services. Through effective co-curricular services, students' overall development is enhanced. Hence, there is need for school managers to ensure the services are operated smoothly in schools. Chang and Shon (2015) asserted that the importance of co-curricular services in educational system cannot be over-emphasised. This is because the services help to meet the needs and aspirations of the students; foster unity among students; make students to be fit physically; changes the school tone; and prepares students for future tasks. To support the above claims, the findings of the study conducted by (2013) revealed that there was a significant relationship students' personnel services (co-curricular services) and academic performance of students.

Students' personnel services in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government needs to be given adequate attention in order to boost students' academic performance. However, despite the great contributions of students' personnel services to the academic success of students, seems not getting the due attention in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, especially in the aspects of library, co-curricular and guidance and counselling services (Sunday, 2021). For instance, some schools in this area do not have a building that could be regarded as the school library while the existing ones in other schools are seriously suffering from lack of professional librarian and lack or insufficiency of current adequate textbooks, magazines, newspapers, journals, internet facilities and other resources for students' self-study or research which help to enhance their academic performance. Not only that, some of these schools do not have sporting and other resources which could aid effective conduct of co-curricular services, in spite of its role in boosting physical and mental development of students (Adekunle, 2020). In addition, guidance and counselling services as integral as it is to education has gone to the state of redundancy in some of these schools, because of absence of well-equipped counselling unit (Adekola, 2021). All these challenges are majorly bothered on inadequacy of funds to these schools.

Some researchers had conducted studies related to this present study. For instance, Chidobi (2015) investigated management of student personnel services in public secondary schools in Enugu Education Zone for sustainability of quality human resources for national development. The findings of the study revealed that management of student personnel services in public secondary schools in Enugu Education Zone for sustainability of quality human resources for national development was average. Paul (2015) carried out student personnel management: A panacea for effective secondary school administration in Nigeria. The findings revealed that there was a significant relationship between student personnel management and effective secondary school administration in Nigeria. Akpan and Onabe (2016) investigated management of students' personnel services and sustainable secondary education in Calabar education zone of Cross River State, Nigeria. The findings of the study revealed that there was significant relationship between management of students' personnel services and sustainable secondary education in Calabar education zone of Cross River State, Nigeria. However, none of these previous studies compared the scenario of students' personnel services in both private and public secondary schools. Hence, this study was set out to compare funding of students' personnel services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, in order to determine the kind of attention given to this important aspect of education in the two school types. Determining the attention given to students' personnel services in the two school types would help to determine which school type performs better in that aspect, so that necessary improvement could be made where necessary, in order to boost students' performance academically. This is the gap which this study filled.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to compare the:

1. funding of students' personnel services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government;
2. funding of library services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government;

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3. funding of guidance and counselling services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government; and
4. funding of co-curricular services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised.

1. Is there significant difference between funding of students' personnel services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government?
2. Is there significant difference between funding of library services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government?
3. Is there significant difference between funding of guidance and counselling services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government?
4. Is there significant difference between funding of co-curricular services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government?

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were formulated.

1. There is no significant difference between funding of students' personnel services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government.
2. There is no significant difference between funding of library services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government.
3. There is no significant difference between funding of guidance and counselling services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government.
4. There is no significant difference between funding of co-curricular services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government.

Methodology

This study compared funding of students' personnel services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government. It adopted descriptive research design of survey type. The population for the study comprised all the 2,325 (female 1,327; male, 998) teachers in the 42 public and 2,229 (female 1,219; male, 1,010) in 48 private secondary schools in the Local Government Area. Random sampling technique was used to select 21 public and 24 private secondary schools, while 10 teachers were randomly selected from each of the sampled schools to make a total of 450 respondents. "Funding of Students' Personnel Services Questionnaire" was used to collect data for the study. The questionnaire was divided into the three sections (A: Library Services; B: Guidance and Counselling Services & C: Curricular Services). The researcher and two research assistants administered questionnaire to the respondents. The questionnaire was validated by three experts in the field of Educational Management, tested for reliability and found reliability coefficient of .81 was obtained. Inferential statistic of t-test was used to test the hypotheses formulated at 0.05 level of significance. Four hundred and twenty-two (public, 194; & 228, private) copies of the questionnaire retrieved were used for analysis. t-test was used to test all the hypotheses. Out of the 210 copies of the questionnaire distributed to respondents in public secondary schools and 240 copies distributed to respondents in private schools, only 194 and 228 copies were retrieved from public and private schools respectively.

Results

Research hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the funding of students' personnel services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government.

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Table 1: t-test Showing Significant Difference in the Funding of Students' Personnel Services in public and Private Secondary Schools in Ilorin West Local Government

School type	<u>X</u>	SD	p-va	p-value	Decision
Public	3.48	1.09		0.004	Ho ₁ Rejected
Private	4.41	0.83			

Field Report (2023)

Table 1 shows the p-value (0.004) that is less than the level of significance (0.05). Hence, the hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference in the funding of students' personnel services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government was rejected. This means that there was a significant difference in the funding of students' personnel services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government.

Research Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between the funding of library services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government.

Table 2: t-test Showing Significant Difference between the Funding of Library Services in public and Private Secondary Schools in Ilorin West Local Government

School type	<u>X</u>	SD	p-va	p-value	D Decision
Public	3.64	0.95		0.001	Ho ₂ Rejected
Private	4.16	1.27			

Field Report (2023)

Table 2 shows the p-value (0.001) that is less than the level of significance (0.05). Hence, the hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between the funding of library services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government was rejected. This means that there was a significant difference between the funding of library services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government.

Research hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference between the funding of guidance and counselling services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government.

Table 3: t-test Showing Significant Difference between the Funding of Guidance and Counselling Services in public and Private Secondary Schools in Ilorin West Local Government

School type	<u>X</u>	SD	p-p	p-value	Eci Decision
Public	3.30	1.11		0.027	Ho ₃ rejected
Private	4.64	1.53			

Field Report (2023)

Table 3 shows the p-value (0.027) that is less than the level of significance (0.05). Hence, the hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between the funding of guidance and counselling services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government was rejected. This means that there was a significant difference between the funding of library services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government.

Research hypothesis 4

There is no significant difference between the funding of co-curricular services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government.

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Table 4: t-test Showing Significant Difference between the Funding of Co-curricular Services in public and Private Secondary Schools in Ilorin West Local Government

School type	\bar{X}	SD	p-value	Decision
Public	3.51	1.20	0.011	Ho ₄ Rejected
Private	4.43	1.39		

Field Report (2023)

Table 4 shows the p-value (0.011) that is less than the level of significance (0.05). Hence, the hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between the funding of curricular services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government was rejected. This means that there was a significant difference between the funding of curricular services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study revealed that there was a significant difference between the funding of library services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government. The mean score of private schools (4.41) which is greater than that of the public schools (3.48) shows that funding of students' personnel services was better in private than public secondary schools. This finding agrees with the finding of Garuba (2017) that the provision of students' personnel services was better in private than public secondary schools in Ofu Local Government Area, Kogi State.

The findings of the study showed that there was a significant difference between the funding of library services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government. The mean score of private schools (4.16) which is greater than that of the public schools (3.64) connotes that funding of library services was better in private than public secondary schools. This supports the finding of Adaralegbe (2020) that the library services provision was better in private than public secondary schools in secondary schools in Akinyele Local Government Area, Oyo State.

The findings of the study revealed that there was a significant difference between the funding of guidance and services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government. The mean score of private schools (4.64) which is greater than that of the public schools (3.30) signifies that funding of guidance and counselling services was better in private than public secondary schools. This finding is in tandem with submission of Alarape (2020) that guidance and counselling services play a significant role in the life of every secondary school student but it is worrisome that attention which this aspect of students' personnel services receives in some public secondary schools in Niger State is not encouraging; as this is not comparable with the attention which the managements of some private secondary schools give to it in the state.

The findings of the study revealed that there was a significant difference between the funding of co-curricular services in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government. The mean score of private schools (4.43) which is greater than that of the public schools (3.51) shows that funding of students' personnel services was better in private than public secondary schools. This finding agrees with the finding of Garuba (2017) which revealed that the co-curricular services provided in private was better than public secondary schools in Ofu Local Government Area, Kogi State.

Conclusion

The study concluded that funding of students' personnel services was performed better in private secondary schools than public in Ilorin West Local Government; funding of library services in private secondary schools was given better attention than public in Ilorin West Local Government; funding of guidance and counselling services was done better in private secondary schools than public in Ilorin West Local Government; and funding of co-curricular services was given a better attention in private secondary schools than public in Ilorin West Local Government.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that:

1. government should intensify its efforts in funding students' personnel services like proprietors of private schools, while the proprietors of private schools should not relent in giving personnel services a priority, in order to continually provide a supportive and conducive environment for students to learn and consequently boost their academic performance;

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2. government should ensure that well-equipped library is provided for schools which do not have while the existing ones which are in the state of moribund should be renovated and well-equipped while the managements of private secondary schools should continue to give funding of library services proper attention in order enhance students' academic success;
3. there is need for government to give guidance and counselling services a more befitting attention, while the proprietors of private secondary schools continually strive in giving guidance and counselling its due attention, in the interest of students' academic success.
4. government should intensify more efforts in providing adequate financial support which would resuscitate effective provision of co-curricular services in public schools, while the private secondary school managements should not rest on their oars in the provision of adequate support to co-curricular services for the purpose of helping students to succeed academically.

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Effect of Audio-Visual Aids on Performance in Business Studies among Secondary School Students in Oredo Local Government, Edo State

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Abstract

The study examined the effects of audiovisual aids on performance in Business Studies among Secondary School Students in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State. The increased low academic performance of Students in this subject area has generated hot quest for investigation on the utilization of audio-visual aids by teachers of this subject. Two research questions and two corresponding null hypotheses guided the study. A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of this study comprised 758 (400 male and 358 female) Junior Secondary two (JSS11) Students during the 2022/2023 academic session in 35 public secondary schools in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State. The study sampled fifty (50), (25 males and 25 females) students from two (2) public Secondary Schools' Students during the 2022/ 2023 academic session local Government Area. A four-point rating scale questionnaire and Business Studies Achievement Performance Test (BSAPT) which were validated and reliability coefficient of 0.78 Was obtained using Kuder Richardson formula 20. Data collected from the study were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions posed, while t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings include that there is significant difference between audio-visual aids utilization and the academic performance in Business studies' students. And that there is significant mean difference in the academic performance of Male and Female Business studies students taught with audio-visual aids in Oredo Local Government Area. The study concludes that the students in Business studies in this Oredo Local Government Area are not being taught with adequate audio-visual aids. Hence, it recommended among others that Schools and educational institutions should invest in the acquisition and maintenance of audiovisual equipment and resources.

Keyword: Audio-Visual Aids, Academic Performance, Business Studies

Introduction

The recurrent and worsening low academic performance of students in external examinations as presented by the chief examiner of West African Examination Council (WAEC), in general and particularly the Business Study as a subject has attracted the attention of stakeholders in education. Though other variables that could enhance or inhibit academic performance are being regularly investigated, there are likelihood that the utilization of instructional aids may also be liable for the low understanding of concepts, hence poor academic performance. Traditional teaching approaches, primarily relying on textbooks and lectures, may not always capture the attention and engagement of students effectively. As a result, educators are increasingly turning to audiovisual materials to enhance the teaching and learning experience. According to Nwokedi & Ufodike (2016), the field of education in Nigeria has witnessed significant developments over the years, with an increasing emphasis on innovative teaching methods and the integration of technology in the classroom. The discipline of Business Studies plays a crucial role in equipping students with the knowledge and skills necessary for success in the business world. However, the traditional approaches to teaching Business Studies often rely on textbooks and lectures, which may not fully engage students or cater to their diverse learning needs. In recent years, there has been a growing recognition of the potential benefits of audiovisual materials in the teaching and learning process.

Audiovisual materials refer to the use of visual and auditory resources, such as videos, presentations, multimedia tools, and interactive technologies, to enhance the educational experience. These materials offer dynamic and interactive means of delivering content, making it more engaging, memorable, and accessible to students. Audio-visual materials arouse the interest of learners and help teachers in explaining the concepts easily and effectively. Lestage in (Job & Opeyemi, 2020), pointed out

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that technology can never replace the human mind, but it can help expand it. It is the duty of the teachers to use audio-visual materials relevant to the lesson and students; wrong use and selection of the teaching materials could be a wastage of time and energy for nothing. Mathew (2013) stated that it is the responsibility of the teacher to use audio-visual materials to make the teaching-learning process effective. Shamsideen (2016) asserted that teaching and learning activities are interesting when audio-visual materials are used effectively and efficiently in a classroom-teaching situation. It is a universal fact that children learn best by observing and copying the behaviors of adults. Sunder in (Okafor, 2018), stated that learning is more effective when sensory experiences are stimulated. Teaching materials stimulate the behaviors of the students toward learning. Sunder in (Okafor, 2018), stated that teaching materials strengthen teaching skills, attract and retain learner's interest and attention and make teaching learning process more interactive and knowledge centered. So, keeping in the mind views of different scholars there is keen need and importance of teaching materials to make the teaching-learning process result-oriented, easy, effective and interesting for both teachers and students; the present investigation is an attempt to ascertain the effectiveness of audio-visual materials in teaching-learning process (Prem, 2018). According to Job & Ado (2019), Resources could aid the understanding of students because it involves the use of cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains. The implication is that resources that best enhance the communication of particular lessons' ideas should be brought into the classroom during the course of teaching such ideas. The use of multimedia is therefore a better attempt at a better application of educational technology in the classroom.

Teaching involves various activities and attempts that are geared toward changing the behaviour of a learner in a specific context. Paul in (Eze & Ojuro, 2020), explained that change could be in attitude, knowledge, idea, skill or appreciation. Effective teaching of any subject will not only stimulate students' interest in the subject but also enhance their achievement in an examination. To achieve effective teaching and learning, there is need for availability and adequate utilization of instructional materials to be adequately available and utilized by teachers as they enable students grasp ideas better. Instructional materials are the different teaching materials or apparatus which a teacher employs to facilitate teaching and achieve stated objectives. Agun in Emeasoba and Igwe (2016) defined instructional materials as those materials which are helpful to teachers and students to maximize learning in various areas. The unique role of instructional materials in classroom teaching and learning is enormous. This means that method of teaching will be grossly incomplete where instructional materials are not utilized. Aransiola in Eze (2021), identified instructional materials for teaching business subjects to include textbooks, manuals, workbooks, magazines, pictures, films, models, simulators and stationeries. They consist of print and non-print items such as kits, textbooks, magazines, newspapers, pictures and recording videos that make the teaching and learning process interesting especially in the teaching of business studies (Effiong & Igiri, 2015). Business Studies is a dynamic subject which prepare students for the challenges of the 21st century by introducing them to the world of business and self-reliance. Business studies is integrated in nature which means that the subject is taught as a single subject with components. It is expository and discovery in nature which enable students to discover those skills and potentials that help individuals in future for life-long education. Hence, Umezulike and Okoye (2013) considered business studies as the key agent of economic and technological development either as a way of developing human capacity, increasing the shield of workforce for modernization, industrialization, and environmental development or as a matter of personal freedom and empowerment of the populace. According to Amoor in (Agun, 2018), business studies play significant role in the economic development of the society by providing knowledge and skills to the learners, thereby, enabling them to adequately impart knowledge into others, and handle sophisticated office technologies and information systems. The goal of business studies is primarily to produce competent, skillful and dynamic business teachers, office administrators and businessmen and women that will effectively compete in the world of work. If these objectives will be achieved, then efforts should be made to provide adequate instructional materials to Nigeria junior secondary schools in teaching of Business Studies and to encourage its effective use.

The use of instructional materials in teaching of business studies is very important because it provides a concrete basis for conceptual thinking, motivates students to learn and captures their imagination if used correctly. Instructional materials provide the teacher with interesting and compelling platforms for conveying information since they motivate learners to learn more (Adekunle, 2018). Furthermore, the teacher is assisted in overcoming physical difficulties that could have hindered his effective presentation of a given topic. According to Akude in (Job & Opeyemi, 2020), the influence of instructional materials in promoting students' academic performance is indisputable. The teaching of business studies in Nigeria secondary school needs to be properly handled. The materials used by teachers to teach and drive home their subject at the primary and secondary school levels of the education system are important in practical classroom interaction to successfully transfer knowledge from teachers to learners. Despite the emphasis placed on the usefulness of instructional materials in the teaching and learning process, most students still find it difficult to cope with the study of business studies. One possible reason for this could be the

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non-utilization of instructional materials that can easily convey the message of the lesson to the learners. Orji in Effiong and Igiri (2015) stated that teaching aid is the guidance of learning activities that a teacher uses to motivate and arouse students to learn. This implies clear that for effective learning to take place, students need to be properly guided by the teacher with concrete materials. According to Bongotons and Onyenwe (2016), one of the pillars of a successful implementation of effective business teacher education is the adequacy and utilization of teaching and learning materials. These materials are in form of facilities and equipment needed to foster skill development and allow for standards and quality in products. Unfortunately, one of the major challenges facing the junior secondary schools and indeed business studies is inadequate teaching and learning resources. Utilization of instructional materials is the act of using and applying the available instructional materials in the actual teaching/learning process. Where resources are supplied for instructional use, teachers are expected to utilize them to support a smooth and meaningful flow of instruction and promote understanding of the content being taught, (Nwabunwanne, in Enekwe, Vero & Osuji, 2020). The teacher who uses instructional materials should be able to manipulate and operate the available units: They should be able to use them to meet the learning needs of the particular learning or group of learners' they are dealing with. This is why Okafor (2013) pointed out that effectiveness of learning materials is determined by the way they are manipulated by teachers or instructors. Instructional materials are in various classes such as audio or aural, visual or audio visual. Audio instructional materials refer to those devices that make use of the sense of hearing only like radio, audio tape recording and television. Visual instructional materials are those devices that appeal to the sense of sight only such as the chalkboard, chart, slide and film strip. An audio-visual instructional material is a combination of devices which appeal to the sense of both hearing and seeing such as television, motion picture and the computer (Isola, 2018). This study focused on the extent of utilization of these instructional materials in teaching and learning of business studies such as projected visual materials, non-projected materials and computer assisted instructional materials. Projected visuals refer to media formats in which still images are projected onto a screen. Such projection is achieved by passing a strong light through transparent film (overhead transparencies, slides, and filmstrips), magnifying the image through a series of lenses, and casting the image onto a reflective surface (Reiser & Dempsey, Job & Opeyemi (2020). Projected visuals are instructional materials that summarize information and ideas through overhead projector, computer images, sound slide sets, multi-image presentations, filmstrips and opaque projections. Patrick in Boor (2016) noted that most students are initially less familiar with projected visuals than they are with flat pictures. They are valuable means of communicating certain information and have generally been found to aid the teacher and the learner by providing visual, audio information. They are aimed at supplementing and improving teaching and learning.

The use of projected media attracts inputs from the teachers and the students; however, they are not intended to end the work of teachers. The use of projected media increases the rate of learning by providing worthwhile experiences for learners. According to Orji in (Nwadike & Ufodike, 2016) projected visuals give instruction a more scientific base through providing a framework for systematic instruction planning. The method required by the teacher to make the teaching of business studies effective demands that the teacher should be very resourceful. Instructional materials are to be used to serve and meet many of education needs if only educators can access and effectively utilize them. Meziobi in Serhat (2021) revealed that the application of projected instructional visuals in teaching has been found to enhance instructions. Today, projected visuals are highly rated worldwide to be of great value in the teaching and learning process. Non projected visuals are those aids which are used without any projection which translate abstract ideas into a more realistic format. They allow instruction to move from verbal representation to a more concrete level. Non-projected learning materials are not technological but are the very basic stuff that has been used in classrooms for years. Like printed and duplicated materials, non-projected media include posters, cartoons, charts, pictures and graphs, and what students produce by themselves can provide powerful visual support for learning abstract ideas. The non-projected media can be presented in the classroom or used as a part of a class activity (Bello, 2015). They are particularly helpful with objectives requiring the identification of people, places or things. The number of a teacher's years of teaching experience can influence the use of instructional media. For instance, personal familiarity with instructional media influences its implementation, Barnard in (Effiong & Igiri 2015&) reported that the acquisition of computer skills is neither smooth nor linear and takes time and aspiration. Barnard further explains that the more experienced a teacher is with any form of instructional media, the more the teacher will appreciate it and implement it practically in the field. Despite the obvious usefulness of instructional materials in the teaching and learning process, most teachers still find it difficult to cope with the teaching of business studies.

The study leaned on constructivist theory of learning, which idea is based on learners being active participants in their learning journey, and knowledge is constructed based on experiences. As events occur, each person reflects on their experience and incorporates the new ideas with their prior knowledge. The theory asserts that Learners develop schemas to organize

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acquired knowledge, and this model was entrenched in learning theories as espoused by Dewey, [Piaget](#), [Vygotsky](#), [Gagne](#), and Bruner. The idea that students actively construct knowledge is central to constructivism, as they add (or build) their new experiences on top of their current foundation of understanding. As stated by Woolfolk in (Job & Opeyemi 2020) “learning is active mental work, not passive reception of teaching”. The theory of constructivism has many elements. These principles outline the theory as a whole and how they affect the learning of the students. The main points are listed below:

1. Knowledge is constructed. Every student begins the learning journey with some preexisting knowledge and then continues to build their understanding on top of that. They will select which pieces of the experience to add, making everyone’s knowledge unique.
2. Learning is a social activity. Interacting with others is vital to constructing knowledge. Group work, discussions, conversations, and interactions are all important to creating understanding. When we reflect on our past experiences, we can see how our relationship with others is directly connected to the information learned.
3. Learning is an active process. Students must actively engage in discussions and activities in order to construct knowledge. It is not possible for students to take on a passive role and retain information. In order to build meaningful ideas, there must be a sensory response.
4. [Learning is contextual](#). Isolation is not the best way to retain information. We learn by forging connections between what we believe and the information we have already. Learning also occurs in the situation within the context of our lives, or alongside the rest of our understanding. We reflect on our lives and classify the new information as it fits into our current perspective.
5. People learn to learn, as they learn. As each student moves through the learning journey, they get better at selecting and organizing information. They are able to better classify ideas and create more meaningful systems of thought. They also begin to recognize that they are learning multiple ideas simultaneously, for example, if they are writing an essay on historical events, they are also learning elements of written grammar. If they are learning about important dates, they are also learning how to chronologically organize important information.
6. Learning exists in the mind. Hands-on activities and physical experience are not enough to retain knowledge. Active engagement and reflection are critical to the learning journey. In order to develop a thorough understanding, students must experience activities mentally as well.
7. Knowledge is personal. Because every person’s perspective is unique, so will be the knowledge gained. Every individual comes into the learning activity with their own experiences and will take away different things as well. The theory of constructivist learning is based entirely around each individual’s own perspective and experiences.
8. Motivation is key to learning. Similar to active participation, motivation is key to making connections and creating understanding. Students cannot learn if they are unwilling to reflect on preexisting knowledge and activate their thought process. It is crucial that educators work to motivate their students to engage in the learning journey.

According to Serhat (2021), it is not enough to simply know the theory of constructivist learning, educators must also know how to implement it in their classrooms, as their goal is to create a welcoming environment that promotes active engagement in learning. In the theory of constructivist learning, instructors act as facilitators, hence, must promote collaboration and adjust their lessons based on the prior level of understanding of the class. Once they identify students’ existing knowledge, instructors must work to grow the understanding in those areas.

There are four key areas that are crucial to the success of a constructivist classroom:

1. The instructor takes on the role of a facilitator instead of a director.
2. There are equal authority and responsibility between the students and the instructor.
3. Learning occurs in small groups.
4. Knowledge is shared between both the students and the instructor.

Constructivism as a learning theory has several educational implications when it comes to the use of audio-visual materials in teaching.

The academic performance of Business Studies’ Students keeps nose-diving despite the various efforts of Governments at all levels emphasizing the importance of education in our society. Perhaps, the teachers of this subject may not have been utilizing Audio-Visual Aids to simplify their teaching. These teachers may hold the notion that the subject is a simple one that requires little or no preparation. To them, teaching Business studies involves merely talking to students about a given topic as may be taken from textbooks or a mere look at some pictures. Business studies teaching requires adequate instructional materials as may be needed in teaching the subject at any level of education. It is, however, worrisome to note that despite its usefulness to the teaching process, Business studies teachers may not have taken full advantage of audiovisual

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aids such that it is inappropriately selected and may not be regularly put to use. Based on the above hindrances, coupled with the fact that students do not retain for long or understand what they are taught without Audio-Visual Aids, the need to investigate the utilization of Audio-Visual Aids in the teaching of Business studies by teachers in junior secondary schools of Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State has become very crucial as none utilization of these instructional aids could demotivate the learners, hence poor academic performance.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To determine the academic performance of students taught Business studies using Audio-Visual Aids and those exposed to conventional teaching methods in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State
2. To determine the academic performance of Male and Female Students taught Business Studies using Audio-visual Aids in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State

Research Questions:

1. What is the Mean academic performance of Students taught Business Studies using Audio-visual Aids and those Exposed to Conventional Teaching Methods in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State.
2. What is the Mean Academic Performance of Male and Female Students taught Business Studies using Audio-visual Aids in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between mean academic performance of students taught Business studies using audio-visual Aids and those exposed to conventional teaching method in Oredo Local Government Area.
2. There is no significant difference between mean academic performance of male and female students taught Business studies using Audio-visual Aids in Oredo Local Government Area.

Methodology:

The design adopted in this study was a descriptive survey. According to Nworgu (2015), a survey research design is the one that aims at collecting data and describing in a systematic manner the characteristics, features or facts about a given population. The study was carried out in Edo State which is made up of 18 Local Government Areas with a total of 300 public secondary schools distributed in three senatorial districts namely, Edo South, Edo Central and Edo North. The Area of the study is Oredo Local Government Area. Oredo LGA functions as one of the 18 LGAs with its headquarters in the town of Benin City. The population of this study comprised 48 Business Studies subject teachers and 758 Junior Secondary Students in 35 public secondary schools in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State. Random Sampling technique was used to select the schools that formed the sample of the study. The sample for the study was twenty (20) Business Studies teachers from ten (10) public secondary schools and fifty (50) students from two (2) public secondary schools in Oredo LGA. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire titled "Questionnaire on Application of Audio-Visual Aids in Teaching and Learning of Business Studies (QAAATLBS)" and Business Studies Achievement Test (BSAT). The questionnaire contains forty (40) items and was structured on the basis of research questions on a four-point Likert scale of Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D), and Strongly Disagreed (SD). The BSAT consists of twenty (20) items of multiple-choice objective tests drawn from past BECE questions.

The Questionnaire on the Application of Audio-Visual Aids in Teaching and Learning of Business Studies (QAAATLBS) and BSAT were subjected to face and content validation by three experts in Business Education. These experts subjected the instruments to rigorous scrutiny in order to ascertain the clarity, relevance, adequacy, and other attributes which a good research instrument should possess. The researchers reconstructed the instruments based on the suggestions of the experts. The BSAPT was pilot tested in the school that was part of the population but was not used in the final for the study, and the results were carefully collated and used to determine the reliability coefficient. The split-half reliability for QAAATLBS was 0.78 while that of BSAT is 0.72 which was considered high enough for use. The researcher personally administered the questionnaire to the sampled teachers. After 40-50 minutes, all the copies of the questionnaire administered were completely filled and returned. Two schools were used for the treatment. In one of the schools, the researcher taught JSS 1 students Banking using Audio-visual Aids while in the second school, the students were taught without utilizing Audio-visual Aids. A week after the treatment, the BSAPT was administered, marked and the scores were carefully recorded for analysis. Mean ratings and standard deviation were used to analyze the data relating to the research questions. The data collected related to the hypothesis were analyzed using arithmetic mean(x), standard deviation (SD) and t-test statistical analysis. The results of the different groups were computed and used in testing the hypotheses. The level of significance adopted for the analysis was $p=0.05$ which

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formed the basis for accepting or rejecting each of the hypothesis. For decision rule, if t-calculated value is greater than the t-critical value, the null hypothesis is rejected (which means significant) and if the t- calculated value is less than the t-critical value, the null hypothesis is accepted (which means not significant).

Results

Research Question 1

What is the mean academic performance of students taught Business studies using Audio-visual Aids and those exposed to conventional teaching method in Oredo Local Government Area?

Table 1. Mean scores of academic performances of students taught Business Studies using Audio-visual Aids and those exposed to conventional teaching method in Oredo Local Government Area

S/N	The relationship between audio-visual utilization and the academic performance of students	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	Sd.	x_{avr}	Sd_{avr}	Decision
1	The integration of audio-visual aids in teaching improves students' academic performance in Business Studies.	10	8	2	0	3.4	0.68			
2	The use of audio-visual aids encourages active participation and involvement of students in the learning process.	7	8	3	2	3.0	0.97	3.46	0.67	Strongly Agree
3	Audio-visual materials make learning Business Studies more enjoyable for students	14	6	0	0	3.7	0.47			
4	Audio-visual aids help students retain information better compared to traditional teaching methods	12	7	1	0	3.6	0.61			
5	The use of audio-visual aids enhances students' motivation to study Business Studies	13	6	1	0	3.6	0.60			

From table 1 above, the average mean response is 3.46 with a Standard Deviation (Sd.) of 0.67. This implies a generally positive effect of audio-visual aids utilization on Business studies' students' academic performance in Oredo Local Government Area.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between audio-visual utilization and the academics performance of Business studies' students in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State.

Table 2: t-test analysis on the effect of audio-visual aids utilization and the academic performance of Business Studies students in Oredo Local Government Area

Group	N	Mean(x)	SD	Df.	Tcal	t.crit.	Std. error	Decision
Experimental	25	74.72	5.86					
Control	25	57.76	6.23	48	9.9147	2.021	1.711	Significant
Mean Diff.		16.96						

The result as shown in table 3 reveals that the mean performance scores for the experimental group is 74.72 with a standard deviation of 5.86 while the mean performance scores for the control group is 57.76 with a Standard Deviation (Sd.) of 6.23. The mean difference of the scores of experimental and control groups is 16.96. The result of the hypothesis 1 in the table 3 also indicates that t-calculated value of 9.9147 is greater than that of the t-critical value of 2.021. Therefore, the null hypothesis 1 is not accepted. This implies that there is significant effect of audio-visual aids utilization and the academics performance of Business studies' students in Oredo Local Government Area at 0.05 level of significance.

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Research Question 2.

What is the difference in the academic performance of Male and Female students in Oredo LGA taught with audio-visual instructional material?

Table 3: Mean difference in the academic performance of Male and Female students in Oredo LGA taught with audio-visual instructional material

S/N	Difference between the academic performance of male and female students taught with audio-visual instructional materials	SA	A	D	SD	X	Sd.	$x_{avr.}$	Sd_{avr}	Decision
1	I believe that audio-visual aids are equally beneficial for both male and female students.	14	5	1	0	3.7	0.59			
2	Audio-visual presentations facilitate a better understanding of subject content for male students.	12	8	0	0	3.6	0.50			
3	Audio-visual presentations facilitate a better understanding of subject content for female students.	10	6	4	0	3.3	0.80	3.1	0.90	Agree
4	Male students benefit more from the use of audio-visual instructional material compared to female students.	8	1	6	5	2.6	1.27			
5	Female students benefit more from the use of audio-visual instructional material compared to male students.	6	2	3	9	2.3	1.33			

Table 3 reveals that the average mean response is 3.1 with a standard deviation (Sd.) of 0.90. This implied that there are differences in the academic performance of Male and Female students in Oredo Local Government Area taught with audio-visual aids. However, while there is general agreement that audio-visual aids are equally beneficial for both genders and that they facilitate a better understanding for male students, there is more variability in opinions about their effect on female students' understanding.

Hypothesis 2.

There is no significant mean difference in the academic performance of Male and Female Business studies students taught with audio-visual aids in Oredo Local Government Area at 0.05 level of significance.

Table 4. t-test analysis of academic performance of Male and Female Business studies' students taught with audio-visual aids in Oredo Local Government Area

Gender	N	Mean(x)	SD	Df.	$t_{cal.}$	$t_{crit.}$	Decision
Male	10	70.20	5.69				
Female	15	77.23	3.66	23	4.0287	2.019	Significant

The result of hypothesis 2 in the table 4 indicates that the t-calculated value of 4.0287 is greater than that of the t-critical value of 2.019. Therefore, the null hypothesis 2 is not accepted. This implies that there is significant mean difference in the academic performance of Male and Female Business studies' students taught with audio-visual aids in Oredo Local Government Area at 0.05 level of significance.

Discussion of Findings

This study was carried out with the aim to determine the effect of audio-visuals aids utilization in teaching and learning of Business Studies in public secondary schools in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State. The data from table 1 indicates a generally positive effect of audio-visual utilization and the academic performance of Business Studies students in Oredo Local Government area. Which means integrating audio-visual aids improves academic performance, encourages active

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participation, makes learning enjoyable, helps retain information, and enhances motivation to study. The mean scores for each point support this positive perception. The findings suggest that audio-visual utilization is associated with positive effect of learning outcomes and experiences among Business Studies students in Oredo Local Government Area. This finding agrees with Enekwe, Vero & Osuji (2020), on their study – the challenges and possible solution to the utilization of audio-visual materials in teaching social studies in upper basic schools in Udi educational zone, Enugu. They submitted among others that students should be involved in the improvisation and use of audio-visual materials, as they learn more from what they do. It also validates the study of Eze & Ojuro (2020) on their study- to determine the utilization of instructional materials in teaching and learning of Business studies in secondary schools in Anambra State. The study affirmed that utilization of instructional materials by teachers should help students acquire skills. Effiong & Igiri (2015) also agreed that teaching aids is the guidance of learning activities.

The data from table 2 reveals varying effect on the academic performance of male and female students in Oredo Local Government Area taught with audio-visual instructional aids. While there is general observation that audio-visual aids are equally beneficial for both genders and that they facilitate a better understanding for male students, there is more variability in opinions about their impact on female students' understanding. Additionally, opinions are divided regarding which gender benefits more from the use of audio-visual aids, (Mathew, 2013, Agun, 2016, Nwakedi & Ufodike, 2016, and Serhat, 2021). Overall, the findings suggest that perceptions of the impact of audio-visual instructional material on gender-specific academic performance are mixed, with no clear consensus on whether one gender benefits more than the other. This indicates a need for further investigation and research to better understand the relationship between gender, audio-visual utilization, and academic performance in the context of Business Studies students in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State.

Conclusion

The study's results indicate a positive association between the use of audio-visual materials and the academic performance of Business Studies students. It was evident that integrating audio-visual materials enhances understanding, engagement, motivation, and retention of complex concepts. The analysis of gender-based differences in academic performance showed that while both male and female students benefit from the use of audiovisual materials, there are variations in the extent of benefit. This suggests the importance of considering gender-specific learning preferences and needs when designing instructional strategies involving audiovisual aids. Furthermore, the statistical analysis supported the rejection of the null hypotheses, confirming that there is a significant relationship between audio-visual aids utilization and academic performance, as well as a significant mean difference in the academic performance of male and female Business Studies students taught with audio-visual aids.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the present study, the following recommendations are offered:

1. Teachers should integrate audio-visual materials in their teaching in order to enhance understanding, engagement, motivation, and retention of complex concepts.
2. Teachers should consider gender-specific learning preferences and needs when designing instructional strategies involving audiovisual aids.

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Effect of Competency Based Instruction on Performance in Concept Stress Pattern among University Undergraduate English Students in Katsina State

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Abstract

This study is titled effect of competency-based instruction on performance in concept stress pattern among university undergraduate English students in Katsina state. The study was guided by the objective to determine the mean performance score of university undergraduate English students taught concept stress pattern using competency-based instruction and those taught using language laboratory instructions. Research question and hypothesis were in line with objective of the study. The study employed quasi-experimental research design (pre-test, treatment and post-test). One hundred and eighteen (69 Male and 49 Female) B.A. Ed. English 300 level students during the 2021/2022 academic session constituted the population of the study. Eighty students (40 Male and 40 Female) were purposively selected as samples. Stress Competency Performance Test (SCPT) was used as the research instrument. The instrument contains twenty-five multiple choice items and yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.96. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research question, while t-test was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Findings of the study revealed that students taught stress pattern using competency-based instruction performed significantly better than those taught using language laboratory instruction. The study recommended the use of competency-based instruction in teaching and learning of stress pattern in universities in Nigeria.

Keywords: Effect, Competency, Instruction, Performance, Stress

Introduction

For any language student at the university or any other citadel of learning for that matter, fluency in expression and competency are unique features that can never be dispensed with. In fact, the need for fluency and competency has always been the focus of meaningful language instruction in the Nigeria education system. Students at the universities who are being trained as prospective teachers are expected to demonstrate mastery and command of the language of instruction in order to be successful in classroom interaction and other relevant daily activities. Competency in language expression requires mastery of a number of concepts and content areas of which stress pattern is at the center stage. In Nigeria, English language is the official language of instruction in the institutions of learning. This implies that, students who study English in the universities are studying it as a second language. To this effect, mastery in the pronunciation of the correct stress pattern is consciously or unconsciously affected by the interference of the first language.

This interference is commonly noticed in pronunciation of the correct stress pattern in some words and sentences which are believed to be missing, mixed up or neglected in most indigenous languages in Nigeria (Kabir & Dada, 2021). On this note, it is pertinent to emphasize the relevance of stress pattern to the mastery and fluency in speaking. It is the stress pattern that determines how, when and where to put emphasis in pronouncing a word. Haigar (2020), Larry (2020) and Ibrahim (2023) lamented that fluency of expression in English could be realized with mastery of the stress pattern. Stress is the degree of emphasis or importance attached in pronouncing a particular syllable in a word. Contrary to the way some syllables in a word and some words in a sentence are pronounced with more emphasis than the others in English language, to many indigenous languages in Nigeria, this is not the case. Most indigenous languages in Nigeria use tone and mode of the speaker as determinants of pronouncing a particular word with any form of force than others. This implies that, the degree of emphasis in the utterance of any particular word may not necessarily be based on an established rule or criteria (Mohammed, 2022).

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There is no doubt; the first language interference that results to misrepresentation and mispronunciation of the correct stress pattern in words and sentences by students of English in the universities creates a vacuum that needs to be filled so as to achieve the competency expected of all language students. It is the attempt to fill this gap and achieve the competency required by students of English in the universities that prompted this study.

In fact, the improvement of instruction has been the goal of meaningful curriculum programmes (Guskey, 2019). Although there are varieties of approaches to improving the instruction, in most cases, instruction can be characterized by the task of setting the objectives, teaching content based on the objectives and evaluating the performance. This process is indeed the most commonly used in most educational institutions in Nigeria, especially the universities. It is worthy to note that, there are several alternative approaches to what was currently obtainable in our citadels of learning. Individualized instruction is a typical example of such approaches. Individualized instruction comprises of a number of approaches such as: the competency based/ mastery instruction, the personalized instruction, the audio-tutorial instruction and the computer assisted instruction among others. Learners today are diverse in their academic needs, backgrounds and abilities. That is why, it is imperative that instructions should meet them where they are so as to maximize their learning potentials and mastery. One way to do this is to utilize individualized instruction of which competency-based approach is at the center stage. Competency based instruction refers to the use of strategies, resources and assessments to meet the needs of a particular learner. This process ensures that a learner is getting the proper guidance, flexibility and learning support to expand opportunities for academic growth (Davies, 2020).

Competency based instruction is an instructional strategy which maintains that learners must achieve certain level of mastery in a prerequisite content area before moving forward to learn the subsequent content area. In other words, competency-based instruction is a strategy of teaching and learning exercise expected to bring students to a level of mastery in the learning of any particular skill, content or subject area. Adepoju (2002) in Adeyemi (2018) maintained that competency-based instruction is designed towards making learners perform well on an academic task. Bergmann (2022) maintained that in a situation where a learner failed to achieve the designed mastery after the test, additional learning support will then be given as well as reviewing the process and the content after which, the individual learner will be tested again. This cycle continues until the learner accomplishes competency and may then move on to the next stage. The basic assumption of the competency-based instruction is that almost all learners can learn the essential knowledge and skills within a curriculum when the learning is broken into its component parts and presented sequentially (Adam, 2022). To implement this approach effectively, instruction should address a number of challenges. The first challenge is to divide the content and or skill into small units which can be presented sequentially using relevant functional and effective teaching strategies. The next step is to assess the learners themselves. Assessing the learners encompass their prior experience, interest and aspirations. The data obtained will help determine where in the sequence of the curriculum and the broken units, the instruction should begin. Effective assessment will enable you as the teacher to link the instructional objectives to the learning activities and the needs of the learners.

The next challenge will be how to address the variations in students learning. For those who quickly grasp concepts, you will need to promote learning by developing relevant enrichment opportunities. This will allow these students to be engaged in an appropriate higher level learning activities while, simultaneously allowing you to expand and extend the learning opportunities to those students who need more time to master the basics. To increase the effectiveness of the instructional process and subsequently the students learning, an instructor should engage in formative evaluation. Formative evaluation is an on-course frequent assessment of students learning that will enable adjustment of instruction to meet the individual needs of learners (Mamman, 2021). After series of on-course assessment, the approach then needs to prepare summative evaluation on each unit, content or objective. The result of the summative evaluation may likely reveal that some students still have not reach the mastery/competency level of the basic knowledge or skill within the time framework provided. In this situation therefore, you will need to develop creative ways for re-teaching and re-presenting alternative learning opportunities and or extending practice and strategies such as after school corrective instruction, peer or cross –age tutoring.

Competency based instruction is an instructional approach in which content, method and pace of the learning are based upon the abilities and interest of each learner. It is therefore a learner centered approach. Casey (2018) lamented that in the competency-based learning process, the curriculum content will be the same for all learners, but the individual learning profile and plan for each learner may vary. This is because each learner progresses through the material at a different speed and according to his/her own learning needs and abilities. In this approach, a learner might master content quickly or require longer time to master and progress through a given topic, skip topics that cover information already mastered or repeat topics when the need arises. The features of the competency-based instruction as identified by Ogan (2012) and Maggins (2022) are so encompassing and elaborate. In this approach, all learning experiences are clearly communicated to learners including long

term expectations such as graduation requirements and competencies; to the short-term expectations such as specific learning objectives for a unit or course as well as other learning experiences such as the expected competency performance levels of grading and reporting success. All forms of assessment are competency based and success is defined by the achievement of expected competencies and not relative measures of performance or student to student comparison.

Furthermore, formative assessment measures learning progress during the instructional process and its result are used for instructional adjustments, teaching practices and academic support. Summative evaluation on the other hand evaluates learning achievement and records students' level of competency at a specific time. Academic progress and achievement are monitored and are reported separately from work habits, character traits and behaviors such as attendance and class participation which are also monitored and reported. In the competency-based instruction, academic grades communicate learning progress and achievement to students and are used to facilitate and improve the learning process. Students are given multiple opportunities to improve their work when they fail to meet the expected standard or mastery. In this approach, students can demonstrate learning progress and mastery in multiple ways such as differentiated assessments, personalized learning options or alternative learner pathways. Students are also given opportunities to make contributions to the design of learning experiences and pathways (Telimoye & Georgina, 2015). Competency based instruction help to personalized learning experiences of students through individual assessment, feedback, and corrective and or enrichment exercises. The approach caters for individual differences of students. Each student can learn and progress at his/her own pace. The approach places premium on the learning process rather than the test scores. This help to improve the depth of knowledge, mastery and retention capabilities of learners. In the competency-based instruction, the amount of time (pace) designed for students to master a particular content is imperative. There are two basic extremes when pace of instruction is considered. The first is when someone other than the learner, usually a teacher controls the amount of time spent on learning the material. In this scenario, specific due dates are defined before instruction begins (Bergmann, 2022). This is currently the predominant model in most educational systems. The other extreme would be if the learner had exclusive control over the pace of instruction without time limit. However, between these two extremes are situations where control of the pace of instruction is shared or negotiated not necessarily equally, by the teacher and the learner.

It is also pertinent to stress that competency-based instruction has ways through which instruction is structured and managed. As theories of learning and instruction develop and mature, more and more considerations are given to the way in which learning occurs. In an attempt to account for the way that students learn, teachers may apply a combination of theories and principles in preparing instruction. This process can influence whether instruction is designed for one homogenous group or is flexible in anticipation of individual differences among learners. The instructional method in the competency-based instruction is usually designed to address individual learner characteristics. To put this in a clear picture, the instructional method can be considered in extremes. In the first extreme, one instructional method will be used for all students. On the other extreme, a specific instructional method is used for each individual student. Between the two extremes lie situations where learners are arranged into groups according to their characteristics. These groups can vary in size with the instructional method tailored to each group based on its uniqueness (Adam, 2022). Competency-based instruction help to bridge the gap between above average, average and below average students in the instructional process (Adeyemi, 2018, Gusky, 2019 & Beulah, 2022). This could be made possible by creating small units with clear objectives. That is, each section has clear objectives for completion and works for the prior section. It is usually in line with less to a more complex learning content. For example, in stress pattern, it starts with students' identification of the symbol(s) of the stress, the types of stress, then the correct pronunciation of the stress in words and sentences. In the competency based instructional process, students learning experiences are assessed before, during and after exposure to the learning materials. The pre-assessment will help determine learner's prior experience which has direct bearing to the topic under discussion. As the assessment is a continuous process, tests will also be given during the classroom interaction in an attempt to determine learner's mastery of the content being taught. This will enable the instructor to adopt or replace the pedagogy being employed. On the other hand, assessment after the instruction will provide the basis for learner's competency and whether they have mastered each stress pattern's correct pronunciation and can therefore proceed to the next or otherwise. It should be noted that, for a student to be classified as competent, he/she ought to have mastered a particular stress pattern by identifying its symbol and its correct pronunciation at 90% in the inter-language level (Casey, 2018). Inter-language is the level of proficiency a second language learner's speech approximate the target language. Students who were assessed below the competency level will then be exposed to corrective exercises and enrichment opportunities. These corrective exercises include more practice on the stress pattern or presenting it in a different way.

Based on the foregoing perspectives, it is endorsed that in any attempts that are geared at improving students' academic performance, the relevant instructional method can never be over emphasized. Method of instruction is highly considered as

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the process of classroom interaction (Dada, 2016) which to some extent contributes to the effectiveness or otherwise of any teaching learning process. In the act of learning, learners obtain content, knowledge, skills and develop work habit and practice the application of all these by demonstrating competency in real life situation; application that has bearing on performance. Performance represents a set of strategies for the acquisition and application of knowledge and skills through tasks that are meaningful and engaging to learners (Nnamdi, 2023). Teachers can therefore determine the extent to which learners acquire and mastered relevant curriculum content by assessing their performance.

Research findings have revealed incessant failure of students in English language especially, phonology of English (Bell, 2017; Wakawa 2017 & Kabir & Dada, 2021). The first semester results of forty eight B.A.Ed. English students in ENG 312 (Phonology of English) for 2021/2022 academic session in the Department of Arts and Social Science Education, Federal University Dutsinma revealed that only 5% of the candidates obtained 70% and above of the scores. This technically suggest that 95% of the candidates failed to reach competency level which requires 90% score and above. It is worthy to note the fact that these students were taught using language laboratory instruction. In this regard, attempts should be made to improve students' mastery that will in turn enhance their performance. On this note, this study assesses the degree to which competency-based instruction enhances performance in concept stress pattern among university undergraduate English students in Katsina state.

Objective of the Study

The objective of the study was to:

Determine the mean performance score of university undergraduate English students taught concept stress pattern using competency-based instruction and those taught using language laboratory instruction in Katsina state.

Research Question

The study answered the following question:

What is the mean performance score of university undergraduate English students taught concept stress pattern using competency-based instruction and those exposed to language laboratory instruction in Katsina state?

Hypothesis

The study formulated the following hypothesis:

There is no significant difference between the mean performance score of university undergraduate English students taught concept stress pattern using competency-based instruction and those exposed to language laboratory instruction in Katsina state.

Methodology

The study adopted a quasi-experimental research design with pre-test, treatment and post-test. Two universities were selected, one as experimental and one as control groups. The experimental group were taught concept stress pattern using competency-based instruction while, the control group were taught using language laboratory instruction. The population of the study comprises all the undergraduate B.A. Ed English 300 level students during the 2021/2022 academic session in Katsina state. One hundred and eighteen (69 Male and 49 Female) students constituted the population of the study. Eighty (40 Male and 40 Female) students were purposively selected as sample of the study. Stress Competency Performance Test (SCPT) was used as the research instrument. The instrument contains twenty-five multiple choice items. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was to test the reliability of the instrument. The instrument yielded reliability coefficient of 0.96; hence, reliable for this study.

At the initial stage, pre-test was administered to both groups to ascertain the entry learning experience of the participants. After which the groups were exposed to the treatment. The treatment was designed to cover the following units: identification of the symbols of stress, the types of stress, the correct pronunciation of each stress in words and the identification of each stress pattern in words and in sentences. Participants in the experimental group were tested after each unit for competency. They are expected to pass at 90% and above before they proceed to the next unit. Those that failed to obtain the minimum benchmark of 90% were exposed to corrective exercises and enrichment opportunities. After six weeks of treatment, a post-test was also administered. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research question while, t-test was used to test the hypothesis. Probability level of 0.05 was used to retain or reject the formulated hypothesis.

Results

Research Question

What is the mean performance score of university undergraduate English students taught concept stress pattern using competency-based instruction and those exposed to language laboratory instruction in Katsina state?

Table 1: Mean performance score of experimental and control groups

Group	N	\bar{X}	SD	Mean Gain.
Experimental	40	91.411	3.012	49.287
Control	40	42.124	4.341	

Table 1 revealed that there is a statistical difference in the mean score and standard deviation between the experimental and control groups in stress pattern. The experimental group has mean score of 91.411 and the standard deviation of 3.012, while the control group has mean score of 42.124 and the standard deviation of 4.341. A mean gain of 49.287 was calculated in favor of the experimental group. This finding implies that students taught stress pattern using competency-based instruction performed significantly better than those taught using language laboratory instruction

Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between the mean performance score of university undergraduate English students taught concept stress pattern using competency-based instruction and those exposed to language laboratory instruction in Katsina state.

Table 2: t-test analysis of mean performance score of experimental and control groups

Group	N	\bar{X}	SD	df	t-cal	t-crit	p-value
Experimental	40	91.411	3.012	78	25.37	2.58	2.58
Control	40	42.124	4.341				

Table 2 revealed the t-test analysis of mean performance score of experimental and control groups taught concept stress pattern using competency-based instruction and language laboratory instruction. The table revealed that P-value= 0.000 is less than the alpha 0.05. The t-calculated 25.37 is greater than the t-critical 2.58 at degree of freedom of 78. The hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between the mean performance score of university undergraduate English students taught concept stress pattern using competency-based instruction and those exposed to language laboratory instruction in Katsina state was rejected. This means that there is significant difference between the mean performance score of university undergraduate English students taught concept stress pattern using competency-based instruction and those exposed to language laboratory instruction in Katsina state. The difference is in favor of the experimental group.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study revealed that there is significant difference between the mean performance score of university undergraduate English students taught concept stress pattern using competency-based instruction and those exposed to language laboratory instruction in Katsina state. Students taught concept stress pattern using competency-based instruction performed significantly better than those taught using language laboratory instruction. This finding agrees with the findings of Ogan (2012), Telimoye and Georgina (2015) whom revealed that competency-based instruction enhances students' academic performance. In their separate findings, Haigar (2020), Larry (2020) and Ibrahim (2023) revealed that competency-based instruction facilitates learning of phonology of English and stress pattern in particular. After revealing the efficacy of competency-based instruction on students' academic achievement, Bergmann (2022) recommended that educational curriculum should be designed in such a way that sufficient time is allocated for individual student in order to attain mastery of the learning task. This study finding has also justified the findings of Adeyemi (2018), Gusky (2019) and Beulah (2022) which revealed that competency-based instruction bridged the gap between above average, average and below average students in the instructional process. This is evident in the mean performance score of the experimental group of 91.411.

Conclusion

This study has revealed that competency-based instruction is more effective than the language laboratory instruction in teaching concept stress pattern in universities in Katsina state. The study therefore concluded that competency-based instruction effectively enhances students' academic performance in concept stress pattern than the language laboratory instruction.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and the conclusion drawn, the study recommended that competency-based instruction should be employed in teaching concept stress pattern in universities in Katsina state and in Nigeria. This could be made possible through the following:

1. Strengthening and advancing the recommendation of the use of practical activities in the teaching and learning of phonology of English in the universities by the National Universities Commission (NUC) to be supplemented by demonstration of mastery as competency-based instruction had revealed to be achievable.
2. Constituting a committee of curriculum experts, language specialists and all other stakeholders in education to come up with an integrated curriculum design that will blend practical activities, language laboratory and competency-based learning in the Nigerian universities.

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Effect of Concept Mapping Instructional Strategy on Performance in Agricultural Science among Senior Secondary School Students in Kaduna State

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Abstract

The study was carried out to determine the influence of concept mapping method on the academic performance of agricultural science students in senior secondary schools in Kaduna State. The study has 2 specific objectives, with corresponding 2 research questions and 2 null hypotheses respectively guided the study. The Research design adopted for this study is pre-test post-test quasi-experimental design. The population for this research comprised of all the agricultural science students in the 2021/2022 academic session in all the government senior secondary schools in Kaduna State. Multistage Sampling technique was used in selecting both schools and students. Eighty (80) (40 male & 40 Female) SS II students were randomly selected using hat and draw technique. Forty (40) male and forty (40) female students were selected. The instrument used for data collection was a multiple-choice test consisting of a 30-item Achievement Test in Agricultural Science (ATAS) which was developed by the researcher. Simple descriptive statistics (means and standard deviations) were used to answer all the research questions and Data collected was then subjected to t-test statistics to determine students' academic performance under concept mapping method. All test null hypotheses were tested at 5% level of significance. Result indicated findings revealed that, students taught Agricultural Science using concept mapping method performed better than students taught using the conventional lecture method. Male students were found to perform better than their female counterparts in the concept mapping method instructional strategy. Concept mapping method should be adopted by agricultural science teachers as it enhances students' academic performance. Government should equip the schools with the necessary equipment and materials needed by teachers for effective utilization of concept mapping teaching method. Teachers should creative and use their initiative one using concept mapping method for better understanding by students and better academic performance.

Keyword: Concept Mapping, Instructional, Strategy, Performance, Agricultural Science

Introduction

Teachers are always looking for innovative ways and instructional methods to help students improve their outcomes in subject matter. Learning is a purposeful, conscious and complex process (Jones & Watson 2018). An important feature of learning is that it involves a complex interactive system including environmental, social, motivational, emotional and cognitive factors (Kamoru, 2021). Various teaching-learning strategies have been developed to accelerate learning process of students. Learning strategies evolve from the learning theories defining the role of teacher, students and the contents. In Nigeria, at present, mostly behavioural practices are in vogue in schools where students are passive and classroom environment is mostly teacher dominated (Baba, 2021). The effect of teaching methods on students' performance is receiving considerable attention from educators and researchers worldwide. What students learn is greatly influenced by how they are taught (Sani, 2017). Instructors teaching agricultural science have implemented a wide variety of teaching methods that fit different niches within the agricultural classroom. Muhammad, Abdullahi, Osman, Ali, Abu-Samah, Jumaat, Ashari and Umar, (2020), noted that there has been drastic reduction in the standard of students' performance at all levels of education in Nigeria in the past decades. The fall in the standard of education is traceable to many factors which are rooted in psychological and environmental factors. This fall in standard of performance at secondary level is incontrovertibly attributable to instructional methods adopted by teachers in schools. Sani (2017) stresses that learning through some methods is passive rather than active. Educators and researchers have repeatedly acknowledged the drawbacks of teaching with a strict lecture format.

Teaching methods according to Kamoru (2021) are the approaches, ways and strategies that a teacher adopts in conducting his lesson to a successful end. Muhammad, Abdullahi, Osman, Ali, Abu-Samah, Jumaat, Ashari and Umar, (2020)

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also defines teaching methods as the ways of teaching which involve a series of teacher directed activities that result into pupils' learning. Teaching methods comprise of principles and strategies used for instruction (Muhammad, Abdullahi, Osman, 2021). Teaching methods are the tools of the teacher for reaching the set goals and objectives. A concept map is a type of graphic organizer used to help students organize and represent knowledge of a subject. Concept maps begin with a main idea (or concept) and then branch out to show how that main idea can be broken down into specific topics. Concept maps are typically hierarchical, with the subordinate concepts stemming from the main concept or idea. This type of graphic organizer however, always allows change and new concepts to be added. They include **concepts**, usually enclosed in circles or boxes of some type, and **relationships** between concepts indicated by a connecting line linking two concepts. According to Muhammad, Mukhtar, Abdullahi and Hassan (2022), a concept map is a diagram showing the relationships among concepts. It is a graphical tool for organizing and representing knowledge. The concept map representation encodes propositions describing two or more concepts and their relationships, in implied natural language sentences. In educational settings, concept mapping exercises have been used to encourage students to actively construct an understanding of concepts and relationships within domains of interest (Ahmad, 2013). It was designed to support the learner's effort by externalizing concepts and propositions known to the student, making them visually apparent to facilitate their connection with newly acquired concepts. Concept maps have been used by teachers to assess students' understanding, by students to compare their knowledge and collaboratively renew their understanding, and by experts as a vehicle for modeling and sharing their knowledge. When created correctly and thoroughly, [concept mapping](#) is a powerful way for students to reach high levels of cognitive performance. Sani (2017) opined that, a concept map is also not just a learning tool, but an ideal evaluation tool for educators measuring the growth of and assessing student learning. As students create concept maps, they reiterate ideas using their own words and help identify incorrect ideas and concepts; educators are able to see what students do not understand, providing an accurate, objective way to evaluate areas in which students do not yet grasp concepts fully. Concept mapping is a valuable visual learning and thinking technique that helps students understand and communicate a concept and its connections between examples and ideas. Sani (2017) stated that, concept mapping is a valuable theory of learning that teachers can use to evaluate a student's level of understanding. A concept map is meant to be constantly changed, added to and reconstructed as new information and knowledge is learned (which is why it's usually easier to concept map using a computer); the goal is to have the student be able to explain each part of the concept map and their reasoning behind the concepts and connections they made.

Students' academic performance refers to students' achievement in the topic taught base on the stated objectives. The use of appropriate teaching method by the teacher helps to achieve this goal. Sani (2017) defines academic performance as the outcome of education which reveals the extent to which a student, teacher or institution have achieved their educational goals. Academic performance or achievement is commonly measured by examinations or continuous assessment (Sequeira, 2013). Considering the central role played by agriculture in the Nigerian economy, it is necessary to identify and apply teaching methods most appropriate for the subject in senior secondary schools. This is because, according to Daluba (2013), the objectives of agricultural science in secondary schools can only be attainable through effective instruction and motivation of students by agricultural science teachers. Abdulhamid (2013) also maintains that, for effective teaching to take place, the teacher must stimulate, encourage and maintain active participation of the students through the selection of appropriate teaching methods. This would require a balance between what is taught and how it is taught. Thus, successful teaching of agricultural science does not depend only on the teacher's mastery of the subject matter but also the teaching method employed.

The poor academic performance of students in agricultural science in both internal and external examinations has assumed a dangerous dimension. In light of this, agricultural science educators need to seek suitable ways of tackling the current mass failure if they are to halt the drifts of students to arts and social science subjects (Sani, 2017). Time has come when young men and women should learn in school how to maintain and improve the fertility of the soil, how to increase the yield of an economic plant and how to raise domesticated animals on a more economic basis. This is imperative because, school boys receiving lessons on agricultural science today will be the scientific farmers of the future. It is therefore the work of agricultural science teachers to teach students the scientific principles underlying the field of agriculture. According to Muhammad, et'al (2022), meaningful learning of principles depends on the ability of the pupils to recognize their relevance and their applicability to appropriate situations and then to apply them correctly. More so, the transfer of principles is a complex mental operation which cannot be left to chance. Students learning ability is greatly influenced by how they are taught. Instructors teaching agricultural science curricula have implemented a wide variety of teaching methods which fit different niches within the agricultural classroom (Abdulhamid 2013). Some methods of teaching are completely out of phase with background and local environments of the learners. Abdulhamid (2013), stressed that organizing for effective teaching in agricultural science is centered on certain factors such as what to teach, when to teach and how to teach. The teacher does not only teach the most

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relevant, meaningful and useful materials for specific students, he must also recognize and adopt a good and well-researched method of teaching that guarantees better understanding and also stimulates and motivates the students. Therefore, this study set out to investigate if the use of concept mapping method could yield a better performance of both male and female agricultural science students in senior secondary schools.

Objectives of the Study

The major objective of the study is to determine the effects of concept mapping method on students' academic performance in agricultural science in senior secondary schools in Kaduna State. Specifically, the study intends to:-

1. Determine the difference in the academic performance of in agricultural Science among senior secondary students taught using concept mapping method instructional strategy and those in the exposed to lecture method control group
2. Determine the difference in the academic performance in agricultural science of among male and female Agricultural Science senior secondary students taught using exposed to concept mapping method Instructional Strategy.

Research Questions

1. What is the difference in the academic performance of agricultural Science students taught using concept mapping method and those in the control group?
2. What is the difference in the academic performance of male and female Agricultural Science students taught using concept mapping method?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in the academic performance of Agricultural Science students taught using concept mapping method and those in the control group
2. There is no significant difference in the academic performance of male and female Agricultural Science students taught using concept mapping method

Methodology

The Research design adopted for this study is pre-test post-test quasi-experimental design. This design was suitable for this research as it allowed the researcher to collect data on students' academic performance using under the concept mapping instructional strategy on experimental group and lecture method and the on control group. To apply this design, the researcher gave the pre-test to students to determine their initial equivalence in all relevant aspects of the topic (Sheep and Goat Management systems) before exposing them to the treatment variables (concept mapping Method) after which post-test was taken administered. The population for this research comprised of all the agricultural science students in the 2021/2022 academic session in all the government senior secondary schools in Kaduna State. Multistage Sampling technique was used in selecting both school and students. One school was selected randomly from all the senior secondary schools in Kaduna State. The instrument used for data collection was a multiple-choice test consisting of a 30-item Achievement Test in Agricultural Science (ATAS) which was developed by the researcher. This is in line with Edinyang (2012) and Abdulhamid and Daluba (2013) who all adopted the same instrument in their studies. The test items were selected from livestock management system (sheep and goat). Each of the items had five (5) options, A-E. All instruments were pilot tested and were adjusted before administration. Data collection phase lasted for three weeks. Students were divided into two (2) groups; namely group A and B. Group A students formed the experimental group and were taught using concept mapping method. Group B formed the control group and were taught using traditional method. However, pre-test was given for both the treatment (group A) and the control (group B) group to test their initial equivalence before exposing group A to the treatment variable (concept mapping method). After the experiment, post-test was administered for both the treatment and the control groups. The exercise lasted for three weeks. Simple descriptive statistics (means and standard deviations) were used to answer all the research questions. Data collected was then subjected to t-test statistics to determine students' academic performance under concept mapping method. All null hypotheses were tested at 5% level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the difference in the academic performance of agricultural Science students taught using concept mapping method and those in the control group?

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Table 1: Difference in the academic performance of agricultural Science students taught using concept mapping method and those in the control group

Group	N	SD	X	Grade
Concept Map.	40	2.312	67	B
Control Group	40	2.503	48	D

Result in Table 1 above indicated that, students taught using concept mapping method performed better than students in the control group who were taught using traditional lecture method. The mean score of students in the concept mapping method is 67 which is greater than the mean score of students in the control group (48). The mean grade of students in the concept mapping method is 'B' while that of students in the control group is 'D'. This implies that, concept mapping method leads to better students' academic performance in agricultural science in senior secondary schools.

Research Question 2

What is the difference in the academic performance of male and female Agricultural Science students taught using concept mapping method?

Table 2: difference in the academic performance of male and female Agricultural Science students taught using concept mapping method

Group	N	SD	X	Grade
Males	20	1.902	68	B
Females	20	2.021	65	B

Table 2 presents the result of male and female students taught using concept, mapping method. The result revealed that, male students performed better than their female counterparts when exposed to concept mapping method. The mean score of male students is 68 while that of their female counterparts is 65 indicating that, male students performed better than their female counterparts. However, mean grade of male students is 'B' while that of female students is also 'B' indicating that, the difference in the academic performance of male and female agricultural science students taught using concept mapping method is not much.

Test of Null Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the academic performance of Agricultural Science students taught using concept mapping method and those in the control group

Table 3: t-test analysis of the difference in the academic performance of agricultural Science students taught using concept mapping method and those in the control group

Group	N	X	DF	t-cal.	t-crit.	Decision
Concept Map	40	67	78	3.21	1.9	rejected
Control Group	40	48				

The t-test analysis of the difference in the academic performance of agricultural science students taught using concept mapping method and those in the control group as presented in Table 3 indicated that, t-calculated (3.21) is greater than t-critical at the degree of freedom of 78 and at 5% level of significance. This implies that, there significant difference in the academic performance of Agricultural Science students taught using concept mapping method and those in the control group. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant difference in the academic performance of agricultural Science students taught using concept mapping method and those in the control group was rejected.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the academic performance of male and female Agricultural Science students taught using concept mapping method.

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Table 4: t-test analysis of the difference in the academic performance of male and female Agricultural Science students taught using concept mapping method

Group	N	X	DF	t-cal.	t-crit.	Decision
Males	20	68	38	1.82	2.0	retained
Females	20	65				

Table 4 presents the t-test analysis of the difference in the academic performance of male and female Agricultural Science students taught using concept mapping method. The Table revealed that, t-calculated (1.82) was less than t-critical (2.0) at the degree of freedom of 38 and 5% level of significance. This implies that, there is no significant difference in the academic performance of male and female Agricultural Science students taught using concept mapping method. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant difference in the academic performance of male and female Agricultural Science students taught using concept mapping method was retained.

Discussion of Findings

The results obtained from data analysis in this study shown that the use of concept mapping in instructional strategy in Agricultural science enhance better performance than the use of lecture method. This finding agrees with Sani (2017) and Kamoru (2021) who found that concept mapping facilitates the learning of scientific concepts. It is also clear from the results that male students performed significantly better than their female counterparts. The reason for this higher performance of male students could probably be that, the use of concept mapping enhanced in-depth and meaningful learning to them, which the corresponding effect showed higher performance. This finding is in agreement with the finding of Jones and Witson (2018) who found out that students taught biology with concept mapping scored significantly higher than the control group. The findings also agreed with Abdulhamid (2013) finding that concept mapping increased learning outcome and concept retention in science related areas. The result on the other hand disagreed with that of Muhammad, Mukhtar, Abdullahi and Hassan (2022) who found out that female student had improved performance than their male counterparts when exposed to learning through concept mapping. Consequently, upon these findings, therefore, concept mapping is significantly a very useful instructional strategy for increased meaningful understanding of difficult concepts and more meaningful internationalization of difficult concept in Agricultural science.

Conclusion

Base on the findings of this research work, the researcher concluded that: Concept mapping method has significant influence on the academic performance of agricultural science students in senior secondary schools in Kaduna State. There is no significant difference in the academic performances of male and female agricultural science students in the concept mapping method. The study revealed that there is statistically significant difference between the performance of students taught Agricultural science with concept mapping and those taught with lecture method in favour of students taught with concept mapping. This implies that Agricultural science teachers should be expose to training workshops and seminars on concept mapping strategy in order to update their skills of teaching concepts in Agricultural science since it has the capacity of enhancing students' performance. The study has a wider implication to teacher training institutions to as a matter of urgency in cooperate the teaching of graphic organizers which concept mapping is part of it in their teacher training schedules. This will enhance students' performance in science and national development since science and technology is at the for-front of nation building.

Recommendations

Base on the findings of this study, it was recommended among other things that:

1. Concept mapping method should be adopted by agricultural science teachers as it enhances students' academic performance.
2. Government should equip the schools with the necessary equipment and materials needed by teachers for effective utilization of concept mapping teaching method.
3. Teachers should creative and use their initiative one using concept mapping method for better understanding by students and better academic performance.

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Effect of Jig - Saw and Team - Teaching Strategies on Achievement and Retention in Chemistry among Secondary School Students in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State

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Abstract

This study investigated the effects of jig - saw and team - teaching strategies on chemistry achievement and retention among secondary school students in Ilorin west local government, kwara state. The study employed quasi experimental research design using pretest posttest non randomized non control group design. Population of study consists of all Senior Secondary School class two (SSII) chemistry students in Ilorin west Kwara State. The sample size of 210 (117 male & 93 female) chemistry students using an intact class of 3 out of 10 government secondary schools were randomly selected by lottery technique in Ilorin west local government. The instruments used for data collection was Chemistry Students Achievement Test (CSAT). The CSAT was validated by experts from University of Ilorin, Ilorin kwara State. Thus, the CSAT gave a reliability Coefficient of 0.933 using Guttman Split half reliability test. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer research questions raised and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 levels of significance. Findings from this study revealed that there was a significant difference between achievement of students taught chemistry using jigsaw strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method. Based on research findings for this study, it was recommended that students should be exposed to jig-saw instructional strategies frequently during Chemistry instructions so as to aid better achievement and retention in Chemistry among secondary school students.

Keyword: Jig-saw, Team teaching, chemistry achievement and retention.

Introduction

Science education is a field of study which involves producing a scientifically enlightened individual in the area of science and technology development. The importance of science education in any society cannot be overemphasized that is why any society that aspires to be great must pay adequate attention to the quality of science education. Science education is taught in most senior secondary schools in Nigeria as Biology, Physics and Chemistry respectively. Chemistry is one of the core science subjects' students are expected to pass before being admitted into higher institutions of learning in Nigeria to pursue science - based programs such as Medicine, Pharmacy, Engineering, Agriculture and Biochemistry (Bolaji, 2017). Despite the importance of Chemistry, West Africa Examination Council (WAEC) annual reports has shown that there is a decline in chemistry achievement over the years, which revealed failure rate increasing from 27.28% to 77.99% while the pass rate decreases from 50.95% to 10.00% respectively. Research findings show that students perform poorly on the concept Electrolysis (Adeoye, 2016 and Ifeanyi, 2017). Some research findings attributed students' poor achievement in Chemistry to lack of adequate mastery of chemistry content knowledge by teachers in some selected areas in Chemistry (Agu, and Odu, 2016). This implies that some chemistry teachers are not well - versed and competent enough in teaching some aspects of Chemistry. Moreover, Okeke (2015) and (Odogu and Oduguisi, 2017) attributed the cause of students' poor achievement in chemistry to interest. This implies that students' interest in the learning of chemistry may negatively influence the quality of learning outcome thereby lowering achievement. Some research findings also attributed the causes of poor achievement in Chemistry to students' ability levels (Agu and Odu, 2016). This may be connected to students' entry behavior or levels of exposure resulting to being low, medium or high ability levels respectively. This implies that, students within the low and medium ability levels may be at disadvantaged, therefore, the need to bridge the existing gap between the levels becomes necessary, as findings revealed divergent opinions (Okeke, 2015) and (Adai and Bayo, 2017). However, traditional methods of instruction have been the most commonly used instructional strategies in most Nigerian secondary schools and have been found to be inadequate for chemistry instruction (Okeke, 2015). Nevertheless, innovative teaching strategies such as team teaching and collaborative strategies are being employed to mitigate the inadequacies of these traditional methods.

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Team teaching is an instructional strategy involving groups of teachers working together in a well-structured platform for effective classroom delivery (Adai and Bayo, 2017). Collaborative teaching strategy involves students working together as a team by sharing ideas during problem solving with, little guide from the teacher (Okeke, 2015). Collaborative strategies among others includes Think Pare – Share, Three – step interview, Jigsaw (II) and Students Teams – Achievement Division (STAD). Thus, this research intends to investigate the effects of collaborative and team teaching strategies on achievement, ability levels and interesting Chemistry among senior secondary school students in Kwara state. Despite the importance of Chemistry, the WAEC chief examiners annual reports revealed a continued decline in Chemistry achievement as shown in Table 1 which revealed that from 2012 - 2018 failure rate increases from 27.28% to 77.99% while the pass rate decreases from 50.95% to 10.00% respectively.

Table1: May /June, 2012 – 2018, West Africa Examination Council (WAEC) Results.

Year	Total Sat	Total Credit A1 – C6	Total Pass D7 – E8	Total Fail F9
2012	349,936	178,274 (50.95%)	66,423 (18.71%)	47,913 (27.28%)
2013	380,140	170,670 (44.50%)	86,423 (22.73%)	11,448 (30.11%)
2014	391,160	165,265 (42.25%)	74,751 (19.11%)	151,144 (38.64%)
2015	401,723	178,164 (34.35%)	93,642 (23.31%)	129,917 (42.34%)
2016	403,528	158,465 (34.27%)	94,990 (23.54%)	150,072 (47.19%)
2017	411,356	150,145 (25.20%)	91,444 (15.80%)	169,766 (60.90%)
2018	464,853	46,488 (10.00%)	55,780 (11.99%)	362,585 (77.99%)

Source: WAEC Headquarter Yaba, Lagos state (September, 2018)

Also chemistry students do not perform well in the concept of Chemical reactions (Bolaji, 2017). Research findings attributed students' poor achievement in chemical reaction to the use of poor and inadequate instructional strategies (Odogwu and Oduguisi, 2017), lack of adequate mastery of chemical reactions by teachers (Agu, and Odu, 2016), lack of adequate interest to learning of chemical reactions or related problems among chemistry students (Okeke, 2015) and variations gender among students in chemistry achievement (Agu and Odu, 2016). However, traditional methods of instruction have been the most commonly used instructional strategies in most Nigerian secondary schools and have been found to be inadequate for chemistry instruction. Therefore, the need to seek for alternative teaching strategies becomes necessary. That is why the researcher intends to investigate the effects of jig - saw and team teaching learning strategies on chemistry achievement and retention among senior secondary school students in Ilorin west local government, Kwara state.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study are to determine the effects of:

1. Jig-Saw and Team-teaching instructional strategies on achievement in Chemical reactions among senior secondary school students in Ilorin west local government.
2. Jig-Saw and Team-teaching instructional strategies on retention in Chemical reactions among senior secondary school students in Ilorin west local government.

Research Question

The study will attempt to provide answers to the following research questions;

1. What are the effects of Jig-Saw and Team-teaching instructional strategies on achievement in Chemical reactions among senior secondary school students in Ilorin government?
2. What are the effects of Jig-Saw and Team-teaching instructional strategies on retention in Chemical reactions among senior secondary school students in Ilorin west local government?

Hypotheses

The following Null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 significant level.

1. There is no significant difference between achievement of students taught chemical reaction using Jig-Saw strategy and those exposed to Team –Teaching strategy among senior secondary school students in Ilorin west local government.
2. There is no significant difference between retention of students taught chemical reaction using Jig-Saw strategy and those exposed to Team –Teaching strategy among senior secondary school students in Ilorin west local government.

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Methodology

Quasi experimental research design, specifically, Pretest Posttest non randomized nonequivalent control group design. The population of the study consists 1620 (1124 male & 496 female) Class II Chemistry students. Sample size of 210 (117 male & 93 female) class II Chemistry students using an intact class of 3 out of 10 secondary schools randomly selected by lottery technique in Ilorin west local government area of kwara state were used for the study as shown in table 2.

Table 2: Sampled SSII Students in Ilorin West LGA

School	Group	Male	Female	Total
G.D.S.S, Air Port	Jig-Saw	45	29	79
L.G.S.S Osin Aremu	Team Teaching	49	40	89
Ilorin Grammar Sch. Ilorin	Control	23	24	47
	Total	117	93	210

Chemistry Students Achievement Test (CSAT), the CSAT was developed using blooms taxonomy of learning which covers the entire 4 sub - topics on the concept chemical kinetics as shown in table 3.

Table 3: Table of Specifications for Chemistry Students Achievement Test

Content Area	Remember	Understand	Apply	Analyze	Evaluate	Create	Total
Types of Reaction	13	11, 12	16	20	-	-	5
Chemical Kinetics	1, 14, 25	23	9	-	2	-	6
Factors affecting Reaction Rate	3, 5, 7	17	19, 24	21	6	-	8
Calculations /Theories	15	4	8	18	-	10, 22	6
Total Items	8	5	5	3	2		25

Source: Anderson and Krathworl in Bidemi, (2017).

The CSAT and marking schemes were validated by three experts from University of Ilorin, Ilorin Kwara State. The CSAT was pilot tested using an intact class of 63 class two 2018/19 Chemistry students from Omu Aran High School, Omu Aran, Kwara State. The same instrument was applied to the same group of students after an interval of two weeks (test-retest method). The reliability coefficient of 0.933 was gotten for CSAT using Guttman's Split half Correlation Coefficient reliability test. The CSAT was administered to the students in a normal class room setting for pretest scores. Experimental groups were taught the concept chemical kinetics using jig-saw and team-teaching instructional strategies, respectively while control group were taught using lecture method. A reshuffled version of the CSAT was then administered to the students to measure achievement. 2 weeks later, the CSAT was re - reshuffled and administered to the students as post – posttest to measure students' retention in chemical kinetics. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer research questions raised, analysis of variance (ANOVA) to analyze if pretest result was significant or not. Thus, Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 levels of significance. The statistical package for social sciences (version 23.0) was used to analyze data. Thus, the research lasted for six (6) weeks.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the mean achievement scores of students taught chemical reaction using Jig-Saw strategy and those exposed to Team teaching strategy in Ilorin west Local government area?

Table 5: Mean and Standard Deviation of Students achievement in Chemistry

Group	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Gain
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
Jig-Saw	74	27.45	3.12	42.04	4.61	14.59
Team teaching	89	25.82	3.87	42.76	4.17	16.94
Control	47	24.12	4.92	26.38	6.35	2.26

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Table 5, revealed a pretest result for jig-saw group having a mean achievement score of 27.45 with standard deviation of 3.12, while posttest result shows a mean score of 42.04 with standard deviation score of 4.61. Hence, had a mean gain score of 14.59. Similarly, pretest result for team teaching group revealed a mean achievement score of 25.82 with standard deviation of 3.87, while posttest result gave a mean score of 42.76 with standard deviation score of 4.17. Hence, had a mean gain score of 16.94, the control group pretest results revealed mean achievement score of 24.12 with standard deviation of 4.92, while posttest result gave mean achievement score of 26.38 with standard deviation of 6.35. Hence, mean gain of 2.263. These, results revealed that both jig-saw and team teaching had higher mean achievement score than control group, but team-teaching group had higher mean gain than jig - saw group. Thus, to find out how significant the difference was, analysis of covariance ANCOVA was used to test the null hypothesis from research question 1 raised as shown in table 7.

Research Question 2

What is the mean retention scores of students taught chemical reaction using Jig-Saw strategy and those exposed to Team teaching strategy in Ilorin west Local government area?

Table 6: Mean and Standard Deviation of Students Retention Rate in Chemistry

Group	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Gain
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
Jig-saw	74	42.04	4.61	55.27	2.37	13.32
Team teaching	89	42.76	4.17	58.18	2.53	15.42
Control	47	26.38	6.35	31.15	2.47	4.778

Table 6, revealed a pretest result for jig-saw group having a mean score of 42.04 with standard deviation of 4.61, while posttest result shows a mean score of 55.27 with standard deviation score of 2.37, had a mean gain score of 13.32. Similarly, pretest result for team teaching group revealed a mean score of 42.76 with standard deviation of 4.17, while posttest result gave a mean score of 58.18 with standard deviation score of 2.53, had a mean gain score of 35.42. The control group pretest results revealed mean achievement score of 26.38 with standard deviation of 6.35, while posttest result gave mean retention score of 31.15 with standard deviation of 2.47, had a mean gain score of 4.778. These, results revealed that both jig-saw and team-teaching strategy had higher retention score than control group, but team-teaching groups had higher mean gain score on retention than jigsaw groups. Thus, to find out how significant the difference was, analysis of covariance ANCOVA was used to test the null hypothesis from research question 2 raised as shown in table 8.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between mean achievement scores of students taught chemical reaction using Jig-Saw strategy and those exposed to Team- Teaching strategy in Ilorin west Local government area.

Table 7: Summary of ANCOVA Test Results of Groups with Achievement

Source	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F _{cal}	P _{value}
Corrected Model	9958.241 ^a	3	3319.414	14.685	0.000
Intercept	28667.327	1	28667.327	126.821	0.000
pretest	536.457	1	536.457	2.373	0.125
Group	8248.057	2	4121.028	18.244	0.000
Error	46565.573	206	226.046		
Total	373365.000	210			
Corrected total	56523.814	209			

Significant at P > 0.000

Table 7 revealed that $F_{(2, 206)} = 18.244$ and $P = 0.000$ at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that p value is less than 0.05 ($0.00 < 0.05$) which is significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis one was rejected. There is significant difference between jig-saw and team-teaching instructional strategy on senior secondary school student's achievement in the concept chemical kinetics.

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Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between mean retention scores of students taught chemical reaction using Jig-Saw strategy and those exposed to Team- Teaching strategy in Ilorin west Local government area?

Table 8: Summary of ANCOVA Test Results of Groups with Retention

Source	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F _{cal}	P _{value}
Corrected Model	36452.765 ^a	3	12150.92	245.976	0.000
Intercept	46541.824	1	46541.82	176.104	0.000
Pretest	162.211	1	162.211	0.614	0.434
Group	34294.971	2	17147.48	64.882	0.000
Error	54442.992	206	264.286		
Total	566991.000	210			
Corrected total	90895.757	209			

Significant at $P < 0.05$

Table 8 revealed that $F_{(2, 206)} = 64.882$ and $P = 0.000$ at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that p value is less than 0.05 ($0.00 < 0.05$) which is significant. Therefore, null hypothesis two was rejected. This means that there is significant difference between jig-saw and team-teaching strategies on senior secondary school student's retention in the concept chemical reaction.

Discussion of Finding

The findings of this study revealed that there is significant difference between achievement of students taught the concept chemical reaction using Jig-Saw instructional strategy and those expose to lecture Team-teaching strategy. The finding is in agreement with the findings of Okeke (2015), Odogu and Oduguisi (2017) which revealed significant difference jigsaw instructional strategy and achievement in concept chemical reaction among secondary school students.

Conclusion

Jig-saw and team-teaching instructional strategy improves secondary school students' achievement and retention in Chemistry.

Recommendations

Based on research findings for this study, it was recommended that:

1. Jig-saw and team-teaching instructional strategy should be adequately used frequently by teachers during Chemistry instructions to aid better achievement in Chemistry among secondary school students.
2. Jig-saw and team-teaching instructional strategy should be adequately used frequently by teachers during Chemistry instructions to aid better retention in Chemistry among secondary school students.

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Effect of Mastery-Learning Approach on Academic Performance in Mole Concept among Secondary School Chemistry Students In Gombe Metropolis

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Abstract

The study investigated effect of mastery learning approach on academic performance in mole concept among secondary school students in Gombe metropolis. The study employed quasi-experimental research design using pretest posttest non-randomized control group design. The population of the study consist of all Government Senior Secondary School class II Chemistry Students (2020/2021)1 academic session in Gombe metropolis, Gombe State. Simple random sampling technique by balloting technique was used to select 2 Schools in Gombe metropolis, Gombe State. A sample size of 85 (46 Male; 39 Female) class (II) students were selected for the study using an intact class. Two groups formed are Experimental Group and the Control Group. The instrument used Mole Concept Performance Test (MCPT) was validated and had a reliability coefficient of 0.78 using Pearson Product Moment Correlation. Two research questions guided the study with a corresponding hypothesis tested at 0.05 level of significance using t-test Inferential statistic. The finding revealed that there is significance difference in the academic performance of students taught using mastery learning approach and lecture method. Therefore, students in experimental group taught using mastery learning approach performed better than those in control group taught using lecture method. Based on findings, it was recommended among others that seminars, workshops and conferences should be organized by Educational Organizations such as Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN) for chemistry teachers to update them with the use of Mastery Learning Approach so as to improve the academic performance of students.

Keywords: Chemistry, Mole Concept, Mastery-learning, and Academic Performance

Introduction

Chemistry Education plays a vital role towards the advancement of science and technology of a nation. This was explained by Emendu (2014) that Chemistry Education is one of the major bedrocks for the transformation of our national economy and further buttressed that there is a positive relationship between chemistry education and chemical industry. By implication, the higher the quality of chemistry education, the more the number of chemical industries produced by a country and the better the economy of the country. Chemistry is an essential science subject and is one of the core science subjects in the Senior Secondary Schools (SSS) curriculum in Nigeria. Thus, Mole concept is an aspect of chemistry that involves mathematical skills in solving problems. Mole Concept has been identified in teachers' guide for new senior secondary school chemistry curriculum as a difficult Concept in Chemistry. As a result of its difficulty to comprehend. This was confirmed by Bamidele, Adetunji, Awodele and Irinoye (2013) who explained that chemistry students are deficient in the use of the Mole Concept and its applications. The West African Examination Council Chief Examiner's Report (2018-2022) recorded poor performance in chemistry which was attributed to use of inappropriate teaching methods by teachers and poor mathematical skills by students in some concepts of chemistry. In Gombe State, where this study was carried out, the situation is not very

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different. The analysis showed that students have problem with chemistry subject at the SSSCE and poor passing grades fluctuate within the years under consideration. Lack of adequate and frequent use of activity based instructional strategies have been identified as the major cause of poor performance in chemistry (Adeyemo & Babajide, 2014).

Mastery Learning is an approach which involves breaking down the topic to be learned into units for easy assimilation by students. It is a method that frequently monitors the students' progress through formative assessment in each unit of a lesson with the view of providing feedback and reinforcement. Adeyemo & Babajide, (2014) described mastery learning as a teaching strategy that involves a pre-specified criterion level of performance which students must master in order to complete the instruction and move on. Furo (2017) maintained that Mastery Learning is a model where students are expected to master a learning objective or goal, before the students can move on to the next goal. For example, in a class room situation where a teacher is to teach the concept Amount, the stated objective for the first unit will be (i) to define Amount (ii) give the unit for Amount and (iii) give the formula for calculating Amount, the students can only proceed to the next unit (solving problems on Amount) after formative assessment was given based on the stated objective and the student achieved 80% mastery. If on the other hand, the students did not achieve 80% mastery, an additional study time will be given for corrections which will enable the student to improve in the mastery in order to proceed to the next unit. This shows that in a mastery learning model, all students have equal chance to reach the mastery level only if given unlimited learning period. This shows that in a mastery learning model, all students have equal chance to reach the mastery level only if given unlimited learning period. Also supported by Mitee and Obaitan (2015) that Philosophy of mastery learning assert that virtually all students are capable of attaining a high degree of learning if given the needed time and appropriate learning conditions and that if teachers could provide these appropriate conditions, virtually all students could reach a high level of performance and the differences in their level of performance would vanish. Mastery Learning Strategy (MLS) can help the teacher to identify students' area of weakness and correct it thus breaking the cycle of failure. Mastery Learning Approach (MLA) can help the teacher to identify students' area of weakness and correct it thus breaking the cycle of failure. On the basis of this background, the study intends to investigate the effect of mastery-learning approach on academic performance among senior secondary school chemistry students in Gombe metropolis.

Poor performance in science subjects among senior secondary schools have been of concern to educationists and researchers. In Nigeria and other developing countries, stakeholders in science education are interested in finding out the cause of the incessant poor performance in chemistry among secondary schools. The West African Examination Council Chief Examiner's Report (2014-2018) recorded poor performance in chemistry which was attributed to use of inappropriate teaching methods by teachers and poor mathematical skills by students in some concepts of chemistry. This poor performance increased to 69% between 2018 and 2021. Studies such as Meheux (2017), Filgona (2017), Sor, Jamabo and Igwe (2017) have shown that several factors are responsible for this poor performance, common among all is the teacher, teaching aid and his teaching methods. So also, Bamidele, *et al.* (2013) identified mole concept and its application to Stoichiometry as a difficult topic perceived by chemistry students in secondary school. Therefore, the researcher intends to teach mole concept using mastery learning approach in order to improve the academic performance of chemistry students.

Objectives of the Study

This study has the following objectives which are to:

1. Determine the effects of mastery learning approach on chemistry students' academic performance in mole concept.
2. Determine differences in academic performance between male and female students when taught using mastery learning approach.

Research Questions

This study was guided by the following research questions which are as follows:

1. What is the difference in academic performance mean scores among chemistry students taught using mastery learning approach and those taught using lecture method?
2. What is the difference in the academic performance mean scores between male and female chemistry students taught using mastery learning approach?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the academic performance mean scores among chemistry students taught using mastery learning approach and lecture method.

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2. There is no significant difference between the academic performance mean scores of male and female chemistry students taught using mastery learning approach.

Methodology

This study adopted pre-test, post-test quasi-experimental-control group design. The population for this study consist of all SSII 2018/19 session government secondary school chemistry students in Gombe metropolis. For the purpose of selecting the schools, Simple random sampling technique using ‘balloting method was used to select two (2) senior secondary schools out of eighteen Senior Secondary Schools in the population. This was achieved by writing the names of each secondary school on pieces of paper, fold and pour them inside a container. One of the students was asked to hand-pick 2 papers and drops each paper on two different containers labeled EG and CG. The two schools selected forms the subjects of the study, that is, the Experimental and Control Groups, consisting of both male and female students. This method ensured that each member of the population had equal and independent chance of being selected. A sample size of 85 (46 male; 39 female) SSII chemistry students were sampled using an intact class, which is in line with the central limit theorem. Pretest was administered to all the groups before the treatment to determine the groups’ equivalence based on the ability of the students. The Mole Concept Performance Test (MCPT) designed by the researcher was used to measure students’ academic performance, it consists of 50 multiple choice questions with four options constructed to serve as pretest to ascertain equivalence of ability of subjects and as posttest to determine the effects of the treatments on ability to solve numerical problems in chemistry based on the Mole Concept. The items consist of 33 calculations and 17 theories on mole concept. The instrument MCPT was developed from past question papers of external examination bodies such as West Africa Examinations Council (WAEC) and National Examination Council (NECO) (1999-2019) and also practical chemistry textbook by Ojokuku. Each question was awarded 1 mark. The MCPT was validated by four lecturers and two experienced chemistry teachers in the secondary school who are seasoned examiners of WAEC and NECO, all corrections, suggestions and recommendation were noted. The reliability of the Mole Concept Performance Test (MCPT) was determined using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Formula, From the result obtained, r was calculated and found to be 0.78, indicating a strong positive relationship. Thus, the instrument MCPT is reliable to measure the academic performance of the study subjects. The Experimental Group students were taught mole concept using mastery learning approach while the control group students were taught the same concept using the lecture method. A posttest was administered to the two groups after six weeks of administering the pretest in order to determine the effectiveness of the treatments on the students. Data collected were statistically analysed. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and one-way Analysis of variance (ANOVA) to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance using SPSS version 23.

Results

Research Question One

What is the difference in academic performance mean score among chemistry students taught using mastery learning approach and those taught using lecture method?

Table.1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Students’ Academic Performance Scores Taught Using Mastery Learning Approach and Those Taught Using Lecture Methods

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference
Experimental	42	44.43	12.351	9.13
Control	43	35.30	6.964	

From Table 1, it can be seen that the mean score of experimental group is higher than the control group with a mean difference of 9.13. Therefore, there is a difference in the performance of students taught using mastery learning approach and those taught using lecture methods. This means that mastery learning approach enhances students’ academic performance in chemistry. However, to find out how significant the difference is, t-test was used in analyzing the scores.

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Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference in the academic performance mean score among chemistry students taught using mastery learning approach and lecture method.

Table 2: Posttest t-test of Students’ Performance Between Experimental Group and Control Group

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. error mean	Df	p-value	Decision
Experimental	42	44.94	12.351	2.826	83	0.001	S
Control	43	35.30	6.964	2.261			

* Significant at P < 0.05 level

Table 2 shows that the p - value observed was 0.001 at the degree of freedom of 83 and 0.05 level of significance. The p - value of 0.001 is less than the alpha value of 0.05 which is an indication that there is significant difference in the performance of students taught chemistry using mastery learning approach and that taught using lecture method. Based on the result of Table 2, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of chemistry students taught using mastery learning approach and lecture method is therefore rejected. There is significant difference in the performance of students taught using mastery learning approach and that taught using lecture method.

Research Question 2

What is the difference in the mean scores academic performance between male and female chemistry students taught using mastery learning approach?

Table 3: Posttest Mean and Standard Deviation of Students’ Performance According to Gender in the Experimental Group

Variables	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean Difference
Experimental Group	Male	37	44.41	10.303	0.04
	Female	32	44.45	14.555	

From Table 3, it can be seen that the mean scores of both male and female students taught mole concept using mastery learning approach in the experimental group is (44.41 and 44.45) respectively. Considering values obtained by both genders in the group, there is a difference in the performance of students taught using mastery learning approach based on gender. However, to find out how significant the difference is based on gender, student t test was used in analyzing the scores.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female chemistry students taught using mastery learning approach and lecture method

Table 4.4: Posttest t-test of Students’ Performance Between Male and Female Students in the Experimental Group

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. error mean	Df	p-value	Decision
Male	22	44.41	10.303	2.801	40	0.001	S
Female	20	44.45	14.555	2.810			

*Significant at P< 0.05 level

Table 4 shows that the p- value observed was 0.001 at the degree of freedom of 5 and 0.05 level of significance. The p- value of 0.001 is less than the alpha value of 0.05 which is an indication that there is a significant difference between the mean scores of male and female chemistry students taught using mastery learning approach. Based on the result of Table 4, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female chemistry students taught using mastery learning approach is therefore rejected. There is a significant difference between the mean scores of male and female chemistry students taught using mastery learning approach.

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Discussion of Findings

The objectives of this study were to investigate the effects of concept mapping strategy and mastery learning approach on reflective thinking and academic performance in mole concept among secondary school students' in Gombe state, Nigeria. The results are discussed as follows: The results from the research question on Table 1 and testing of hypothesis one on Table 2 indicated that there was a significant difference in the performance of students taught mole concept using mastery learning approach and lecture method. The result also revealed that there is a significant difference between use of mastery learning and lecture method.

The significant difference in performance is in favour of the students in the Experimental Group taught using mastery learning approach. This is in line with the findings of Filgona (2017), Mayanchi, Anya and Kainuwa (2018). The finding from this study indicated that mastery learning approach can enhance academic performance among students and yield better result than Lecture method. Students in the experimental group taught using mastery learning might have learnt meaningfully because of the sequential evaluation of students' progress in every unit of the lesson which is absent in the control group, students in the control group taught using lecture method are mere passive listener.

Results from the research question and testing of hypothesis two from Table 3 showed that there was no significant difference in the performance of male and female when exposed to mastery learning approach. This means that mastery-learning approach is an instructional strategy that is gender friendly as it gives equality in learning for both sexes. This result is equally in line with the result of Wambugu and Chaneiywo (2008), which revealed that there was no significant difference in the academic performance of male and female students when taught using mastery learning approach. This shows that both male and female students benefited equally when exposed to both mastery learning approach.

Conclusions

The study concludes that students taught mole concept using mastery learning approach was found effective in improving the academic performance compared to those taught mole concept using lecture method. Mastery learning approach is gender friendly since both genders showed improved academic performance when taught mole concept in chemistry

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study and conclusion reached, the following recommendations were made:

1. Lecture method in this research study has been found to be less effective in improving the students' academic performance. Teachers should therefore explore mastery learning approach into the teaching and learning of various topics in chemistry so as to enhance students reflective thinking and thereby improving their general academic performance.
2. Mastery learning approach has been shown to improve academic performance for both sexes; therefore, Teachers should actively involve male and female students in learning activities to avoid gender stereotyping so as to help create equal educational opportunities for both male and female learners.
3. The Federal government through its ministries and agencies like the Federal Ministry of Education (FME) and the Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC) Gombe branch should provide adequate funds for training of science teachers in-form of seminars, workshops and conferences that focuses on Concept-mapping and mastery learning approaches and other activity-based teaching strategies that are more effective in promoting academic performance.
4. Mastery learning approach is a teaching method that requires more time for the development of learning objectives along with corresponding formative tests and corrective activities and since the usual allotted time in the school timetable is inadequate for the effective implementation of either mastery learning approach or concept-mapping strategy, curriculum developers and planners should therefore create more time on the school timetable for optimum result

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Effect of Peer Review Technique on Performance in English Essay Writing among Secondary School Students in Odigbo, Ondo State

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Abstract

The purpose of this research was to investigate the effect of the Peer Review Technique on performance in English essay writing in Odigbo, Ondo State. Two research questions and two null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. A quasi-experimental research design was adopted for the study. Specifically, the non-randomized control group design. The study population consists of all Government Senior Secondary School class two (SSII) students in the 2021/2022 academic session. The sample for the study consists of 160 SSS2 students from two co-educational schools in Odigbo Local Government Area of Ondo State. The experimental group comprised 78 male and female students while the control group comprised 82 male and female students from schools located in rural and urban areas respectively. Both the experimental group and control group were given the same essay writing but the difference is that those in the experimental group were taught essay writing using the Peer Review Technique (PRT), while those in the control group were taught essay writing using the conventional method. The instrument used for data collection was the Essay Writing Achievement Test (EWAT). The data obtained from the trial tests were used to calculate the instrument's reliability using Kendall's formula. It yielded an index of 0.75. Mean was used to answer the research questions while ANCOVA was used to test the hypotheses at $P < 0.05$. From the results obtained, it was found that students in the experimental group had higher performance scores in essay writing than their counterparts who were in the control group. Based on the findings, it was recommended that English language teachers should adopt the Peer Review Technique in teaching essay writing.

Keywords: English in Nigeria, Peer Review Technique, gender, and essay writing

Introduction

The English language remains the cornerstone of education in Nigeria, serving as the primary medium of instruction from upper primary levels through secondary and tertiary education. It functions as the conduit for teaching all other subjects in the curriculum. The challenges of learning English as a second language are widely recognized, particularly in non-English speaking countries like Nigeria. Proficiency in English entails possessing both spoken and written skills for effective communication. As a colonial legacy from the British, English holds a significant position, evident in its status as a mandatory subject in Nigerian senior secondary schools. Across various spheres of Nigeria's development, the English language plays a pivotal role. Nearly all aspects of endeavors beyond individual pursuits necessitate the utilization of English (Olutola, Iliyas & Abdusalam, 2017). Despite the crucial roles attributed to the English language, a significant number of Nigerian students struggle to attain proficiency in its various skills, particularly in the domain of writing. A study by Patrick, Uloh-Bethels, and Ukwueze, (2020) highlights that the underwhelming academic achievements in English among students might be directly linked to their struggles with effective writing. This deficiency in writing skills consequently contributes to subpar performance not only in English but also across other subjects in both internal and external examinations. This trend continues to raise concerns about the broader educational landscape and the holistic development of students. Adding to this discourse, a recent study conducted by Akintunde and Angulu (2020) underscores the enduring nature of the challenges faced by Nigerian students in mastering English writing skills. The researchers found that despite efforts to improve language education, students still grapple with issues of coherence, organization, and grammar in their written expression. This persistent struggle not only affects their academic performance but also hinders their ability to effectively communicate and engage in various professional and social contexts. In the same vein, the performance of students in the English language has been witnessing a consistent decline at both junior and senior secondary school levels. This concerning trend is substantiated by the assessment of the WAEC Chief

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Examiners' Report (2020), which emphasizes that while the questions posed were generally well-suited to the student's abilities, their actual performance did not reflect the expected quality and simplicity of those questions. The report highlights that the students exhibited inadequate essay organization and a lack of conscious effort toward grammatical accuracy. This assessment underscores the observation that despite the accessibility of the questions, students struggled to effectively structure their essays and grappled with grammatical errors, ultimately contributing to their unsatisfactory outcomes.

Notably, the report also draws attention to the students' deficient grasp of the four essential language skills: listening, speaking, reading, and writing—as a significant factor influencing their subpar performance. This observation underscores the pivotal role of these language skills in holistic language proficiency. As such, there arises a compelling need to address these challenges by prioritizing the teaching and learning of essay writing within the framework of the English Language curriculum. Reinforcing the urgency of this matter, recent research by Akintunde and Angulu. (2020) delves into the persistent decline in English language performance among Nigerian students. The study identifies several contributing factors, including limited teacher training, inadequate teaching materials, and a lack of effective instructional strategies. These findings underscore the complexity of the issue and emphasize the necessity for a multifaceted approach to ameliorating the declining state of English language proficiency among students in Nigeria's secondary schools. In light of these insights, a comprehensive overhaul of English language education, particularly in essay writing skills, emerges as an imperative. By addressing the issues highlighted in both the Chief Examiners' Report and recent research, educators, and policymakers can collectively work toward fostering a more effective and enriching learning environment that equips students with the language skills necessary for academic and real-world success. Essay writing, a prevalent linguistic endeavor, serves as a means for individuals to articulate their contemplations on a specific subject (Idris, 2019). Guided by the topic and intent of the writing, this form of composition embodies a distinct content and structure. The author characterizes an essay as a concise written composition addressing a specific theme, highlighting the writer's thoughts through verbal expressions. It not only showcases the writer's proficiency in conveying concepts but also serves as a yardstick for evaluating the writer's intellectual acumen.

Furthermore, recent scholars have emphasized the enduring significance of essay writing in the English curriculum. Okika (2021) and Okon, (2022) underscore its revered status as a staple in exams, often carrying a substantial weightage of marks. This underlines the warranted investment of time and effort into honing essay writing skills. Importantly, the utility of essay writing extends beyond the confines of the English syllabus; it permeates into various subject domains where exam questions frequently assume the essay format. Consequently, students must adeptly tailor their responses to align with the specific essay writing techniques demanded by each question. Strengthening this perspective, Anidi, Obumneke-Okeke, Nwune, and Okwuduba, (2022) acknowledge the multifaceted nature of teaching essay writing. The authors emphasize the essential role of language teachers in providing guidance and control over the sentence structure within essays. This underscores the collaborative effort required to cultivate effective essay-writing skills among students. For second language learners, various impediments can impede students' academic progress. These challenges can be attributed to educators and their instructional approaches, the learning environment, and gender dynamics. In the research by Idris (2019) the absence of modern teaching resources to enhance instruction, inadequate coverage of curriculum content, teachers' limited capacity to deliver effective lessons, and students' struggles to absorb the taught material were identified as obstacles in the realm of English language education. It could be deduced that these same challenges extend to the teaching and learning of essay writing. As highlighted by Akinwumi (2017) essay writing is a notably intricate skill within language acquisition. The optimal approach to mastering this skill involves employing suitable methodologies and allocating substantial time daily for focused instruction. Consequently, the methods employed for its teaching tend to lack innovation and practical orientation, as noted by Nwosu (2017). There are many methods that could be used by teachers in English essay classes. Most teachers have been using the conventional method where the students are arranged in straight lines down and across the classroom. The teacher assumes that all the students in the class have equal knowledge or that they know little or nothing. He stands in front of the class and delivers his lessons. As the teacher dominates the lesson, the students' potentials are rarely used to the fullest and impatience rather than enthusiasm is generated (Nwosu,2017). For language learning, grammatical analysis and rote learning of grammatical rules, vocabulary acquisition, and translation from the target language to the learner's mother tongue and vice-versa are emphasized in the conventional method. The students work individually and are assessed individually. Only the best students are rewarded which forces students to work against each other so as to be the best. As a result of the shortcomings of conventional methods, the researcher intended to investigate the effect of peer review techniques on the achievement of students in English essay writing.

The Peer Review Technique (PRT), devised by linguist Charles James at Johns Hopkins University in 1990 involves collaborative assessment among peers, also known as "peer feedback". This approach entails students reviewing and evaluating

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Based on this disparity of findings on which gender performs better in language, it seems that the exact effect of gender on language performance is not clear; hence there is a need for further studies on the nature of students' performance by gender, especially in Nigeria. English language remains the cornerstone of education in Nigeria, serving as the primary medium of instruction from upper primary levels through secondary and tertiary education. It functions as the conduit for teaching all other subjects in the curriculum. The challenges of learning English as a second language are widely recognized, particularly in non-English speaking countries like Nigeria. Proficiency in English entails possessing both spoken and written skills for effective communication. As a colonial legacy from the British, English holds a significant position, evident in its status as a mandatory subject in Nigerian senior secondary schools. Across various spheres of Nigeria's development, the English language plays a pivotal role. Nearly all aspects of endeavors beyond individual pursuits necessitate the utilization of English (Olutola, Iliyas & Abdusalam, 2017). Despite the crucial roles attributed to the English language, a significant number of Nigerian students struggle to attain proficiency in its various skills, particularly in the domain of writing. A study by Patrick, Uloh-Bethels, and Ukwueze, (2020) highlights that the underwhelming academic achievements in English among students might be directly linked to their struggles with effective writing. This deficiency in writing skills consequently contributes to subpar performance not only in English but also across other subjects in both internal and external examinations. This trend continues to raise concerns about the broader educational landscape and the holistic development of students. Adding to this discourse, a recent study conducted by Akintunde and Angulu (2020) underscores the enduring nature of the challenges faced by Nigerian students in mastering English writing skills. The researchers found that despite efforts to improve language education, students still grapple with issues of coherence, organization, and grammar in their written expression. This persistent struggle not only affects their academic performance but also hinders their ability to effectively communicate and engage in various professional and social contexts. In the same vein, the performance of students in the English language has been witnessing a consistent decline at both junior and senior secondary school levels. This concerning trend is substantiated by the assessment of the WAEC Chief Examiners' Report (2020), which emphasizes that while the questions posed were generally well-suited to the student's abilities, their actual performance did not reflect the expected quality and simplicity of those questions. The report highlights that the students exhibited inadequate essay organization and a lack of conscious effort toward grammatical accuracy. This assessment underscores the observation that despite the accessibility of the questions, students struggled to effectively structure their essays and grappled with grammatical errors, ultimately contributing to their unsatisfactory outcomes. Notably, the report also draws attention to the students' deficient grasp of the four essential language skills: listening, speaking, reading, and writing—as a significant factor influencing their subpar performance. This observation underscores the pivotal role of these language skills in holistic language proficiency. As such, there arises a compelling need to address these challenges by prioritizing the teaching and learning of essay writing within the framework of the English Language curriculum. Reinforcing the urgency of this matter, recent research by Akintunde and Angulu (2020) delves into the persistent decline in English language performance among Nigerian students. The study identifies several contributing factors, including limited teacher training, inadequate teaching materials, and a lack of effective instructional strategies. These findings

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There are many methods that could be used by teachers in English essay classes. Most teachers have been using the conventional method where the students are arranged in straight lines down and across the classroom. The teacher assumes that all the students in the class have equal knowledge or that they know little or nothing. He stands in front of the class and delivers his lessons. As the teacher dominates the lesson, the students' potentials are rarely used to the fullest and impatience rather than enthusiasm is generated (Nwosu,2017). For language learning, grammatical analysis and rote learning of grammatical rules, vocabulary acquisition, and translation from the target language to the learner's mother tongue and vice-versa are emphasized in the conventional method. The students work individually and are assessed individually. Only the best students are rewarded which forces students to work against each other so as to be the best. As a result of the shortcomings of conventional methods, the researcher intended to investigate the effect of peer review techniques on the achievement of students in English essay writing. The Peer Review Technique (PRT), devised by linguist Charles James at Johns Hopkins University in 1990 involves collaborative assessment among peers, also known as "peer feedback". This approach entails students reviewing and evaluating each other's writing, encouraging active participation and dialogue (Okika 2021). Students adopt dual roles as both reviewers and writers, offering diverse perspectives and identifying errors. Unlike conventional one-way teaching, this technique nurtures self-awareness of errors and problem-solving. PRT enhances both spoken and written English proficiency, fostering standard English through teacher and peer guidance during the classroom review process. PRT is premised on Vygotsky's theory in 1978. The author deemed social interaction an essential element for cognitive learning and accorded great importance to learning in human thought development. To Vygotsky, learning is a cognitive activity that takes place in social interaction. By the same token, writing is a learning activity in which the writer learns best through interacting with his peer reviewers.

However, although there is a general belief that students' poor achievement in English essay writing could be traced to inappropriate methods of teaching adopted by teachers, it is likely that an intervening variable such as gender can also have some effects on the effectiveness of teaching method and learning outcome especially in English essay writing. Gender is

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There have been consistent reports of poor performance in the English language among Nigerian students over the years. Also, students' performance in the Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) in the English language over the years has not been commendable. Students' performance in essay writing at Senior School Certificate Examinations has been generally poor. This low level of achievement has been attributed primarily to poor teaching methods. The method often used by English language teachers is the conventional method. This method makes students passive listeners in the class. More so, the conventional method does not allow teachers to adapt learning to the level of students' understanding (Ogunyomi, 2014). The poor performance of students in English essay writing may also be attributed to poor knowledge of Standard English. Many students could not express themselves in Standard English. Most students go straight into answering the questions without properly understanding them. Some of them are not well prepared for the Examination. It is evident that the major weakness of the students could be their inability to express themselves very well in Standard English (Akintunde & Angulu, 2020). Although the use of peer review technique has been tried in subjects like chemistry, government, social studies, and typewriting. However, its effectiveness is yet to be determined in the study of English language essay writing, and narrative essay in particular. Also, no study to the best of the researcher's knowledge explored the effect of the peer review technique on performance in English essay writing among secondary school students in Odigbo, Ondo State.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study is to find out the Effect of the Peer Review Technique on performance in English essay writing among secondary school students. Specifically, this study is aimed at:

1. Finding out the performance of students taught essay writing using the Peer Review Technique and those taught using the conventional method.
2. Determining the performance of male and female students taught essay writing using the Peer Review Technique and those taught using the conventional method.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

1. What is the mean performance scores of students taught essay writing using the Peer Review Technique and those taught using the conventional method?
2. What is the effect of gender on the performance of students taught essay writing using the Peer Review Technique and those taught using the conventional method?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of students taught essay writing using the Peer Review Technique and those taught using the conventional method.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students taught essay writing using the Peer Review Technique and those taught using the conventional method.

Methodology

A quasi-experimental research design was adopted for the study. Specifically, pretest a posttest non-equivalent groups design was used. This design was considered appropriate because intact classes were used by the researcher in order to avoid disruption of the normal academic programme of the schools. There are seventeen public secondary schools in this area. They are all co-educational schools. Four of these are located in urban areas while thirteen are located in rural areas respectively. The population of the study comprised all Senior Secondary class two (SS2) students in 2021./2022 academic session in the seventeen government-owned secondary schools in Odigbo Local Government Area of Ondo State. The sample size for this study was 160 students comprising 78 male and 82 female students in Odigbo, Ondo, State. The study adopted a multi-stage

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sampling technique. A multi-stage sampling technique is a complex form of cluster sampling. It is one in which sampling is done sequentially across two or more hierarchical levels. The sampling technique was carried out in two stages. Purposive random sampling was used to select two schools from the local government (one in a rural area and one in an urban area) because the researcher had the freedom to select the schools that were appropriate for the study. The two schools that were selected by the researcher were fit for the purpose of the study because each of the schools is located in rural and urban areas respectively. The instrument for data collection was the Essay Writing Achievement Test (EWAT). This was adopted from WAEC's past questions. The essay Writing Achievement Test was only on narrative writing. The students were given an option to choose one of the six narrative essays. The researcher used the WAEC standard marking scheme. The minimum length expected in the essay was 450 words while the students were required to spend 45 minutes for the essay writing. The reliability of the instrument was established through trial testing on a group of 20 SSSII students using the Kendall coefficient of Concordance. The correlation coefficient of 0.71 was used as the reliability coefficient which showed that the instrument was relatively above average.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the mean performance score of students taught essay writing using the peer review technique and those taught using the conventional method?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of scores of students taught essay writing using peer review technique and those taught using conventional method.

Group	Number	Pre-test		post-test		Gain score
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Experimental	78	16.35	9.31	58.00	14.89	41.35
Control	82	16.28	5.87	43.46	12.40	27.18

Table 1 shows that the students who were taught essay writing using the peer review technique had a mean performance score of 58.00 with a standard deviation of 14.89 at the post-test while those who were taught the conventional method had a mean performance score of 43.46 with a standard deviation of 12.40. Mean gain scores of 41.35 and 27.18 for the two groups respectively imply that the students who were exposed to peer review technique achieved higher than their counterparts.

Research Question 2

What is the mean performance score of male and female students in English language essay writing taught using peer review technique?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of performance scores of male and female students in English language essay writing

Gender	Number	Pre-test		post-test		Gain score
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Male	82	15.06	9.08	45.46	15.32	30.40
Female	78	16.37	6.78	55.38	13.69	39.01

Table 2 revealed the mean performance scores of male and female students in essay writing. Male students had a post-test achievement mean score of 45.46 with a standard deviation of 15.52 while their female counterparts had a post-test achievement mean score of 55.38 with a standard deviation of 13.69. Gain scores of 30.40 and 39.01 for the male and female students respectively may have indicated that female students achieved higher than their male counterparts in English essay writing.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of students taught essay writing using peer review technique and those taught using conventional method.

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Table 3: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of the effect of peer review technique on performance in English essay writing

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	16300.356 ^a	8	2037.545	14.177	.000
Intercept	48636.700	1	48636.700	338.420	.000
Pre-test	2142.645	1	2142.645	14.909	.000
Treatment	3818.277	1	3818.277	26.568	.000
Treatment * Gender	285.649	1	285.649	1.988	.161
Group * Gender *	19.161	1	19.161	.133	.716
Error	21701.244	151	143.717		
Total	446850.000	160			
Corrected Total	38001.600	159			

a. R Squared = .429 (Adjusted R Squared = .399)

The analysis in Table 3 above shows that the probability associated with the calculated value of F (26.568) for the effect of peer review technique on performance in English essay writing is .000. Since the probability value of .000 is less than the .05 level of significance ($p < .05$), the null hypothesis was rejected. Thus, there is a significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught essay writing using peer review techniques and those taught using conventional methods in favour of the experimental group.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students in English language essay writing.

Table 3 shows that the calculated value of F (13.780) for the influence of gender on performance in English essay writing is .098. This implies that gender is a significant factor in the student's performance in English essay writing since $p > .05$ in favour of the female students.

Discussion of Findings

The evidence from this study shows the higher performance of students taught English essay writing with the Peer Review Technique may be a result of many factors. One such factor according to Ajiwoju (2015) is making learning an interactive process and active, where the learner is totally immersed in learning activities that interest and appeal to him. Also, the fact that instruction was conducted in small heterogeneous peer learning groups which pared way for individual attention and equal participation might have contributed to the improved essay writing performance in the treatment group. These findings are consistent with the findings of Okika (2021) and Nwosu (2017), who believed that learners' interaction ginged their interest in writing which consequently increased higher performance in essay writing.

The higher performance of female students may be as a result of interactions among the students. The findings agree with the findings of Ali (2016) and Ajiwoju (2015) which indicated that gender was significant in students' performance in the English Language.

Conclusion

Peer Review Technique has been found to be effective in promoting performance in English essay writing. The mean performance scores of the students taught with Peer Review were found to be higher. Also, the students taught with the Peer Review Technique were found to be more interested and motivated than those taught with the conventional method.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study;

3. Secondary school teachers should make use of the Peer Review Technique in teaching essay writing.
4. Teacher trainers in the various universities and colleges of education should incorporate the Peer Review Technique as a useful technique in second language teaching and learning and train the teacher trainees on how to use the technique.

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Effective Counselling and Parenting: Panacea for Total Development of an Adolescent Child in Nigeria

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Abstract

In terms of encouraging self-direction, social integration, emotional growth, and intellectual development, parental involvement through positive parenting is the most significant impact in a child's total development. Adolescent's well-being in the areas of mental health, personality development, psychosocial growth, and adaptive behaviour in society are all predicted by parental role modeling, which also creates an emotional environment that is conducive to good parent-child relationships. This paper examined effective counselling and parenting: panacea for total development of an adolescent child in Nigeria. The article discussed concepts of counselling and parenting. It addressed different parenting styles and compared them with positive parenting. The paper further highlighted obstacles to positive parenting, implication for professional counselling and recommendations.

Keyword: Counselling, Positive Parenting, Parenting Styles, Adolescents

Introduction

Character development in children happens over the course of several years rather than being something that just happens to them (Almuhajir, 2021; Atika et al., 2021). Beginning with the child's birth and development into an adult in the home environment, socializing with friends in game groups, attending school, and ending with the community (Prasanti & Fitrianti, 2018; Iltiqiyah, 2020). An important goal in the early learning process is the instillation of moral principles (Zamroni et al., 2021; Rozi & Maulidiya, 2022). Children are educated and disciplined to build character traits like responsibility, honesty, independence, etc. from an early age. The early formation of moral and ethical principles must take into account child development issues (Ramdhani et al., 2019). Today's parents face the same difficulties as always. As people face problems and implement daily routines in response to their children's demands, they grow into their parental roles and build their parenting abilities. Parental effectiveness is important in how parents behave while interacting with their kids and during the entire socialization process. Young children's care, physical protection, and physical, cognitive, and emotional growth are the parents' responsibilities. They also monitor the child's integration into society and encourage socially acceptable behaviour. The child's cognitive and psychosocial development is improved if the parents believe they are effective in their parental role (Loukia, 2019). Counselling is a beneficial profession for people of all ages: infancy, adolescence, maturity, and senescence. People of all races and walks of life have used counselling services and treatments for self-growth, self-restructuring, and self-development in families, marriages, government institutions, colleges, universities, companies, organizations, associations, and non-governmental entities. Counselling as a discipline encompasses a wide range of worldwide services to mankind, including educational, vocational, psychological, and personal information that is preventive, curative, restructuring, and generative in character (Killian, 2019). Therefore, this paper will be guided with concepts discussion such as parenting, parenting styles and obstacles to positive parenting.

Concept of Counselling

In the realm of guiding and nurturing, counseling emerges as a powerful tool that holds the key to addressing the intricate tapestry of parenting and the cultivation of character in children (Bishop, 2023). The journey of character development, a slow and steady voyage spanning years, is intricately woven by a multitude of threads, including the domestic ambience, social interactions, and community engagement (Fiehn et al., 2023). Amidst these, parents assume a role of paramount significance, sculpting the moral compass and character foundation of their offspring. Yet, the path they tread is often laden with the challenge of harmonizing their responsibilities (O'Donnell et al., 2022). Enter counseling, a vocation that extends its helping hand across age groups, from children and adolescents to adults, ushering them through the labyrinth of personal evolution, relationship intricacies, and the trials of parenting (Lenz & Lemberger-Truelove, 2023). Its purpose is resolute—to

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provide a scaffold of support, a compass of guidance, and a treasure trove of strategies to nurture constructive parenting paradigms, efficacious communication, and the blossoming of character traits (Juffer et al., 2023). Parenting stands as a symphony of commitment, one that orchestrates a child's emotional, physical, intellectual, and societal maturation (Witte, 2022). The art of effective parenting entails a methodical approach, one that plants the seeds of positive conduct and virtuous attributes from the earliest stages (Ubaidillah & Sholih, 2023). Diverse parenting styles, spanning from the authoritative to the permissive, cast their influence on a child's emotional intelligence, cognitive development, and social growth (Nyangoya, 2022).

Positive parenting thrives on gentle corrections and nurturing support, instilling not only self-assurance but also the art of problem-solving and the bedrock of wholesome relationships (Conkbayir, 2023). However, technological advancements and economic constraints are two issues that modernity brings with it that might have an impact on parenting (Sujarwo et al., 2021). It is within this backdrop that the beacon of professional counseling shines brighter than ever. It offers the compass to parents, helping them navigate the complex waters of family dynamics, surmounting the obstacles that bar the path to fostering positivity (Diamond, 2023). The scope of counseling's impact is profound and far-reaching (Kim et al., 2023). The realm of professional counselors is akin to a gardener tending to the soil of positive parenting techniques, tilling the ground for communication to flourish between parents and children, and sowing the seeds of character development strategies (Schauss et al., 2019). The integration of family counseling programs into educational institutions, coupled with parental workshops and discussion forums, serves as a bridge that connects educators and parents in a shared purpose (Kelty & Wakabayashi, 2020). In this tapestry, counselors don the mantle of educators, imparting the wisdom of positive parenting methods and providing the resources necessary for holistic growth in the realm of children and adolescents (Estiningsih et al., 2020). Beyond this, they recognize the intricate interplay between character development, academic triumph, and parental engagement, charting the course toward effective parenting that nurtures not only robust moral values but also paves the way for academic accomplishments (Clarke, 2023).

Concept of Parenting

Parenting is a vow to invest time, money, and your best efforts in a child's emotional, physical, intellectual, and social growth. Parenting is also thought of as raising a child in a structured way so that when the child arrives at school, he or she will perceive classroom activities as enhancing what they have learned at home. This will enable the child to better transfer knowledge and skills from home to school to improve academic performance. According to NTI (2009), positive transfer that supports academic achievement is achievable when knowledge and abilities gained in one learning environment—home, which is often a child's initial learning environment—are comparable to those in another context, like a school environment. Talib, Abdullah and Mansor (2011) claims that the household because of this determines a child's degree of academic achievement in school. Parenting is the art of carrying out the duty to raise and prepare children for productive lives. Parenting is a process of raising and nurturing a kid because it is an art. Psychologists like Coleridge (2009) and Talpur, Pathan, Shah (2012) have stated as much. They continued by saying that part of parenting is taking care of your child's academic progress.

Parenting is the process of raising a kid so that he will not be deprived of his education and other fundamental rights, regardless of the severity of the national economic downturn. It entails caring the youngster without overworking him so he may grow up strong and be able to handle his academic responsibilities. According to Yang, Kim, Laroche and Lee (2014), children who are overworked are frequently observed dozing off in class due to fatigue, which is detrimental to their ability to do well academically. Relationships, communication between co-parents, and the academic ideals that are supported and encouraged by both parents in a family are prominent among the elements that affect parenting generally. The benefits of consistent parenting and the values that both parents uphold, which set clear expectations for the child's academic success and other aspects of his behaviour, are similar to those of effective communication between parents and their children (Tompsett & Toro, 2010). All of these points out that parenting entails a variety of duties, including establishing guidelines for kids to follow, providing educational materials to ensure regular attendance at school, inspiring kids, especially when their spirits are low, and developing friendships with them, among other things. Children should be exposed to character development as early as feasible (Baharun, 2017). Character development is more important in the early years. Character building in early infancy is a crucial process that builds the foundation of human personality, hence failing to do so will result in the development of a troublesome personality in later life (Tanto et al., 2019). In order to develop character, one has to practice virtues both at home and at school (Maryam, 2018; Muali et al., 2021). The primary responsibility of parents in the education of their children is to provide primary education, fundamental attitudes, and fundamental skills, including religious education, personality, manners, aesthetics, affection, a sense of security, the fundamentals of following rules, and instilling habits (Cahyono et al., 2018; Munif

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et al., 2021). Furthermore, it is the responsibility of the family to impart values and conduct via what is taught in school. To put it another way, there is a connection between what is taught at home and what is taught at school. It is critical to establish a positive relationship between the school and the parents. Arif and Pratama (2019) given that education and parental care play an important part in the development of a kid's character, if a child receives strong character education at school as well as good habits at home, the child will have a positive attitude later in life (Atika et al., 2021; Almuhajir, 2021). Since the favorable attitudes these kids currently hold will gradually evaporate if the values being taught at the school do not have support from the home environment, schools can help their pupils gain a greater initial understanding while they are in school.

Parenting styles vs Positive Parenting

According to Piko and Balázs (2012), parenting practices have been linked to several elements of children's emotional, cognitive, social, and academic skills. Parenting practices are crucial to children's development. Parenting style was described by Poduthase (2012) as the attitudes that parents have toward their children. It is a collection or system of behaviours that outlines how parents and children engage in a variety of contexts and fosters productive interactional environments. The identification, growth, and development of a child's gifts and skills, as well as being familiar with social laws and norms from the parents' point of view are just a few of the many functions that parenting style provides. According to Moreno Méndez et al. (2020), parenting styles are linked to peer issues, problematic binge drinking, and general maladjustment problems. Zuquette et al. (2019) found a similar association between problematic parenting and binge drinking (Obimakinde et al., 2019). As one of the three main parenting approaches, authoritative parenting has consistently been linked to favorable outcomes, such as "psychosocial competence... maturation, resilience, optimism, self-reliance, social competence, and self-esteem;" Kuppens&Ceulemans (2019), as opposed to authoritarian parenting's negative outcomes, such as aggression, delinquency, anxiety disorders, stress, and general adjustment issues; Aduale, 2017; (e.g., depression, anxiety; Aduale, 2017; Kuppens&Ceulemans, 2019; Moreno et al., 2020; Williams et al., 2009; Wolfradt et al., 2003). In general, punitive parenting style has detrimental effects on the mental well-being of children (Zubizarreta et al., 2019).

Parental practices in Nigeria incorporate all parenting philosophies with a focus on deference to and adherence to parental directives (Akinsola, 2011 in Killian 2014). However, a lot of parents in Nigeria go along with this need for obedient behaviour and compliance with parental directives by being receptive, loving, caring, sensitive, and engaging in a two-way discussion with their children. Teenagers in Nigeria are able to regard their parents as authoritative at times and authoritarian at other times because of the parents' dual demands for compliance and attentiveness. According to research, many Nigerian parents use authoritative and authoritarian parenting techniques as well as their hybrids (Akinsola, 2010a in Killian 2014). As a result, it is hypothesized that adolescents who experienced permissive, authoritarian, or their hybrid parenting styles will report higher levels of social and performance anxiety than adolescents who experienced authoritative parenting. According to scholarly assessments, teenagers' social anxiety scores are significantly influenced by excessive parental supervision (Siegel & Welsh, 2014). A meta-analytic evaluation found that the parenting characteristic of control had a medium impact size and was not just related to children's social anxiety (McLeod, Wood, and Weisz, 2007). This relationship is often believed to be the result of authoritarian parents teaching their children that the outside world is a dangerous place where they need always be on guard. Furthermore, this idea contends that parents who exercise excessive control over their children deprive them of the opportunity to develop independent problem-solving skills. According to Saldana, J. (2012), this causes the teenager to experience a lower feeling of personal competence, which can subsequently result in social anxiety. An adolescent who experiences parental acceptance and warmth reflects more self-confidence outside the home compared to an adolescent from a home environment where rejection/cold relationships are the norm; such adolescent will manifest unsympathetic behaviours. Killian (2014) emphasizes parent-child relationship as one of the factors that enhance the child's confidence in himself or herself in pursuit of life-achievement goals, especially in the area of career and vocational choice.

Positive parenting is using gentle corrections rather than severe penalties to deal with undesirable conduct. Instead, parents actively meet their children's emotional needs via loving relationships, which may stop a lot of undesirable behaviour before it ever starts. Caley (2022) asserts that positive parenting simply encourages parents to "catch kids doing nice" and provide reinforcement that is more positive rather than concentrating solely on inappropriate conduct. Some parents worry that positive parenting is overly idealistic, contending that if parents don't teach their children understand and respond to unpleasant emotions, they won't learn how to do so later in life, which might be detrimental. However, according to psychologists, supportive parenting may boost kids' self-esteem and provide them the skills they need to make wise decisions. Additionally, it fosters their sense of self-worth, creativity, optimism, and interpersonal skills. When parents mess up and lose their temper, it's the perfect time to apologize to their kids and show them how to deal with mistakes Caley (2022).

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Obstacles to positive parenting

According to Lykken's (1997) investigation into the reasons and treatments for ineffective parenting, the high rate of unsocialized adolescents is mostly attributable to the level of ineffective, overloaded, or sociopathic parenting they have experienced. He continues by saying that with the absence of effective conventional approaches like the socialization of children through involvement in extended-family organizations, it is not entirely unexpected that there is such a high incidence of ineffective parenting. According to Lykken (1997:129–137), communities that still use this parenting style today generate children that develop successful consciences, empathy, compassion, and group collaboration, as well as reduced levels of intramural crime. According to the hypothesis, parents may feel less confident in their abilities to have a good impact on their children's lives as a result of heightened emotional anguish brought on by higher levels of economic strain brought on by reduced family income and uncertain employment situations. Any perceived or actual social-emotional support from friends or family tended to lessen the psychological consequences of these financial demands. Further, confident parents engage in numerous collaborative activities with their kids both inside and outside the house, according to Elder et al. (1995). In her article on reflective parenting, O'Brien (1996:238) makes the argument that parenting is such an important aspect of our children's lives that it must be properly planned and carried out. It is important to go back on one's reactions to assess if they were the most suitable in the given conditions and whether they best met the requirements of the kid. However, this capacity depends on the life lessons parents have learned throughout their lives as well as the parenting they have personally experienced. As a result, their capacity to satisfy the emotional and developmental requirements of their kid as well as to offer proper childcare will be greatly influenced by the quality of their own nurturing. The demands of a contemporary professional life and limited family time influence many parents. 2018 (Sanders) The 21st century demands that parents give their children, especially teenagers, a lot of their time, attention, and accessibility. However, given Nigeria's economic instability and political volatility, most parents struggle to strike a balance between job and family.

The difficulties of parenting have increased in recent years due to technical developments (such as information communication technology), social media, and media violence, which have taken time and attention away from parent-child activities and the passing on of cultural and moral values. Blondel (1998) argues that there is cause for concern if parents are unable to balance all these changes at home with respect to the values and ideas that the next generation of teenagers will adopt. The alterations that began in the previous several decades and appear irreversible, at least in the normal span, have already greatly shaped the physiognomy of the twenty-first century (Londel, 1998). Some of these advancements, like information and communications technology, are not inherently bad, but they frequently pose challenges in a variety of human endeavors, including families and homes. Ineffective communication, poor parenting, and challenging relationship patterns were all mentioned as the main problems for family connections by families. Recognizing family strengths before tackling issues might assist to strengthen connections within the family (Sanders, 2018).

The Role of Counseling in Enhancing Positive Parenting across Different Styles

Incorporating counseling into parenting practices brings positive outcomes for parents and contributes to the well-being of children (Finardi et al., 2022). Skilled counselors provide an unbiased perspective, helping parents understand their behavior and motivations (Eli et al., 2022). This self-awareness is essential for personal growth and improves parenting dynamics. Understanding fundamental principles of parenting helps parents align with their child's needs (Richards et al., 2022). Counseling offers support to parents facing challenges (Shepherd et al., 2020). Parenting can be confusing, but professionals offer guidance that validates efforts (Siverns & Morgan 2019). Counselors guide parents through conflicts, behavior issues, and emotions (Goldberg et al., 2021). They provide strategies that enhance discipline and empathy, building trust between parents and children (James et al., 2020). It is important to note that counseling is not one-size-fits-all. Families have unique needs, and counselors adapt their advice accordingly (Tokatly et al., 2021). This personalized approach increases the chances of positive change for parents. Counseling complements various parenting styles, helping parents create nurturing environments that foster their children's growth (Blewitt et al., 2021). Recognizing the value of counseling inspires parents to be proactive in nurturing their children's development (Suri & Chandra, 2021).

Implication for Professional Counselling

The relationship between the counsellor and the counsellee during counselling is supportive. It attempts to aid students in making a suitable adjustment to the curriculum by assisting them in resolving issues that hamper their academic success, whether they arise at home or at school. Thus, if schoolchildren want to achieve in their studies, professional counselling

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services must be disregarded. This supports Adewuyi's (2009) claim that professional counselling include consultation, debate, deliberation, exchange of values, and assisting to modify circumstances that are preserving people's issues by encouraging self-awareness in the individuals involved. A professional counsellor's duty in the school system to effectively enhance excellent performance in learners includes assisting parents of school children to understand how exploitative most of the parenting techniques that exist in their various homes are (Nwazor, 2006), the need to adopt positive parenting (technique), and what positive parenting entails in order to facilitate excellent academic performance in children. The pursuit of academic excellence is stated in the Nigeria National Policy on Education (2004:51) as "Educational services assist the implementation of educational policy, the achievement of policy objectives, and the advancement of educational system effectiveness." This is consistent with Anagbogu (2004), Onwuasanya and Okeke (2008), who stated in their various studies that the role of professional counselling in a school whose students perform poorly cannot be overstated. This means that when an effective professional counsellor is able to counsel with the parents of the students and uses his expertise to treat the students whose behavioural problems emanate from the home, using appropriate behaviour modification techniques, both the students and the parents benefit. Silsby (2012) identified issues such as low school attendance, lack of attention, negative self-concept, lesson inattentiveness, and unequal performance. Furthermore, Castaldi (2007) observed that a lack of school-based-family therapy is shown when a student's academic performance is low owing to parental and guardian failures. All of this implies the employment of proactive counselling strategies, such as school-based-family counselling and behaviour modification programs, parent fora, and others, to assist parents in adopting good parenting in their homes, aided by the home-visit strategy. School-based family therapy is a type of therapeutic strategy that relies on the guidance and information provided by a professional therapist who specializes in family difficulties. In order to reinforce positive change in the child, the professional counsellor integrates school counselling models to solve problems that affect a child's academic performance. Part of it is a home visit in which the counsellor goes into a counselling relationship with the parents at their home or workplace to discuss ideas on how to best assist a child in his academics. It enables parents to actively participate in any wise decisions and selections that their children are assisted in making with the school counsellor to ensure positive academic performance, such as decisions against tardiness, truancy, non-payment or late payment of school fees, lack of concentration, and others (Nwaoba, 2011). These techniques might be utilized to assist a child whose parents or guardians physically abuse him or her through overwork, child leasing, kidnapping, and other means that impair his or her success in school.

A professional counsellor may be able to impart knowledge by setting up parent forums at PTA meetings and open days at the school (Haruna, 2015). This will encourage parents to embrace excellent parenting practices and will provide them with the necessary motivation. Family counselling in schools includes instruction on family life. Through oral presentations, videos of positive parents and their kids, or speeches from invited resource people, a professional counsellor utilizes his expert knowledge to drill parents on the program of positive parenting/technique and to issue a clarion cry for its adoption in families. The professional counsellor also works with schoolchildren to promote positive behavioural change to ensure improved academic achievement utilizing behaviour modification programs that are therapeutic in nature, all the while using his knowledge to assist parents in adopting good parenting.

Conclusion

Children's character development requires a continuous and consistent procedure. Counsellors must collaborate closely with parents in order to support them as they build the character of their children via effective parenting initiatives. Establishing a link between the attitudes of kids at home and their behaviour at school. In order to include parents as partners in their children's education, schools get in touch with parents via parenting programs. As a result, parents may maximize their ability to affect how their kids turn out. By overseeing parental activities, schools may work with families to create and foster a sense of early childhood.

Recommendations

1. It is advised for counsellors to start family counselling programs at schools.
2. The necessity to embrace positive parenting (techniques) in raising children in homes should be the main topic of counsellors' lectures during PTA meetings and open days at schools. In other words, counsellors should step up their efforts to provide parents with enough knowledge on the kind of parenting that promotes children's exceptional academic success.
3. Governments (federal and state), non-governmental groups, and school authorities should consider supporting school counsellors so they may sometimes hold successful parent forums, workshops, and seminars on good parenting (method)

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at schools. They should provide enough money so that counsellors may buy the right teaching aids, including TVs, videos, posters, and other things, to really drive home the link between good parenting (method) and children's academic achievement.

4. Professional counsellors ought to be assigned to schools and given full practicing rights.
5. Instead of being limited to family counselling, the training program for professionals in counselling should be varied to include skills in school-based "family counselling for all counselling specializations."
6. Some school disciplines and courses, including social studies, health education, and civic education, should incorporate positive parenting.

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Effectiveness of Instructional Materials in Teaching and Learning of Letter-Word Recognition among Out-of-School Children in Kaduna: A Literature Review

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Abstract

It is very important to note that, the use of instructional materials is virtually necessary. This paper focused on qualitative study on Instructional Materials: Panacea for Effective Teaching and Learning of Letter-Word Recognition among Out-Of-School Children in Kaduna. The paper investigated the concept of out-of-school children and the concept of instructional materials. It looked into the importance of instructional materials in teaching and learning classification of instructional materials and their relevance to the teaching of letter-word recognition to the out-of-school children. The study discussed the criteria for guiding the selection of instructional materials to teach the out-of-school children. It highlighted the steps to be followed when using instructional materials to teach the out-of-school children. The paper provided the following areas as suggestions based on the conversations that have already taken place in this study in order to encourage instructors of out-of-school children to adopt the attitude of employing instructional resources. It maintained that education resource centers organize seminars to teach language instructors, and to evaluate students' learning proficiency outside of the classroom primarily in the north. Educational stakeholders should ensure the provision of instructional materials for daily letter-word recognition and to enhance visual-motor abilities in letter recognition for children not in school.

Keywords: instructional, material, letter-word, out-of-school, school-children

Introduction

Education has always been the cornerstone of all lasting national advancements. It is the tool that starts the race for optimal development, progress, and problem-solving across all sectors. Education must engage everyone and be successfully taught for it to be relevant in a nation (Alipour, 2014). All of these goals can only be reached by using effective teaching strategies and age-appropriate instructional resources when working with out-of-school children (Coomb, 2010). This study's focus is on the teaching materials and how they apply to children who are not in school. Because out-of-school children encounter these resources but are unaware that they aid in learning, it is necessary to make educating them practical through the use of instructional materials. In order to identify words and swiftly access their meanings, Out-of-School Children that should use effective word-recognition strategies are able to quickly and automatically transform the letters or spelling patterns of written words into spoken sounds (Vandervelden & Siegel, 1997). To focus on the meaning of what they are reading, Out-of-School Children should need to be able to rapidly and easily recognize words (Stanovich, 1986). Effective word-identification techniques will enable such children to deduce the pronunciations of words they have never seen in print as they get older and read increasingly complex books. It is critical that Out-of-School Children may learn to recognize words primarily by using their sound and spelling skills (Bay Area Reading Task Force, 1997; Beck, 1998). The chance to engage with bigger units, such as word families, spelling patterns, and onsets and rimes, should also be provided to Out-of-School Children. More complex word-identification techniques concentrate on reading multisyllabic words and structural analysis, which includes identifying root words, prefixes, and suffixes. Before they can sound out some basic words (like this and the), Out-of-School Children may be able to recognize them. It is important to educate Out-of-School Children how to use word-identification procedures to figure out words, even if some words are only presented as sight words. According to research by Smith et al. (in press) and Stein, Johnson, & Gutlohn (1998), there was insufficient representation in word recognition training and oral language skills instruction for Out-of-School Children. According to Stein et al., very few programs used an explicit phonics approach, and the majority of Out-of-School Children reading selections were inaccessible to them because they frequently did not match the terms that Out-of-School Children were learning during word-recognition training.

Although the word-recognition instruction to reading achievement is a much-debated topic, any enlightened discussion by advocates of such instruction emphasizes that it must be only a part of a total program of instruction (Snow, Bums, & Griffin, 1998). The main goal of such instruction is to help Out-of-School Children figure out the alphabetic system of written English and become comfortable with that system as they become readers (Lyon, 1998). The authors of *Becoming a Nation of Readers* (Anderson, Hiebert, Scott, & Wilkinson, 1985), written almost a decade ago, nicely described the goal, purpose, and limitations

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of phonics instruction: While there is substantial dispute regarding the relationship between reading achievement and systematic phonics and word-recognition training for Out-of-School Children (Snow, Bums, & Griffin, 1998). As Out-of-School Children become readers, the primary objective of this kind of training is to assist them in understanding the alphabetic system of written English and help them grow accustomed to it (Lyon, 1998).

Concept of Out-of-School Children

Children who are not enrolled in any school or who have left school at any point before finishing elementary education are considered out of school children (OoSC) (Aremu, 2008). Children who are not in school are quite diverse. Children who are living or working in urban areas, on streets, on railroad platforms, or on construction sites are examples of children who are not enrolled in school (Out-of-School Children). This category of learners might be employed as street hawkers, housekeepers, child laborers, wage employees, mechanics, rag pickers, or shoe shine boys. Other categories might include children involved in the sex trade, children whose parents move around in search of seasonal work, children from scheduled castes and tribes, children with special needs who may fall into any of these categories, and children who suffer disadvantage due to socio-cultural, economic, geographic, and linguistic factors. In addition to these, there are kids who attend minority community-run Madarasas (Islamic Education) for their education and study religious texts with little to no involvement in the standard curriculum. In a similar vein, there may be teenage females who have never attended school or who may have left early. Children who live in troubled neighborhoods or in challenging situations must also be found and supported in neighborhood schools. In order to close the achievement gaps and integrate these diverse groups of children into the general education system in the age-appropriate classrooms, specific efforts must be made to expose them to instructional materials (Wales, 2012).

The Concept of Instructional Materials

Instructional resources, educational technology, instructional technology, etc. are all terms used to describe instructional materials. In education, instructional materials are anything that a teacher uses during teaching to improve the learning process (Smith, 2009). According to Ehri & McCormick (1998), instructional materials are any hardware, software, or group of resources that teachers can use to facilitate teaching, learning, and leaving. Additionally, according to Aremu (2008), instructional materials are those that help teachers do their jobs more effectively and efficiently while also reducing the stress associated with teaching and learning for both the teachers and the students. Thus, children will play with letters and word games, and begin to learn how the system of print works. Here, they may begin to understand that the teacher read print from left to right, from the top of the page to the bottom, that capital letters begin sentences, that periods end sentences, and more. For that awareness of these concepts of print provides the backdrop against which reading or writing are acquired

Importance of Instructional materials in teaching and learning

The value of instructional materials lies in how they enhance learning by making it more engaging, applicable, and appealing (Stanovich, 1986). Additionally, they make it possible for both professors and students to actively and productively engage in class. According to Aremu (2008), instructional materials encourage active learning among students during the teaching and learning process. He added that it spares instructors' time and effort. Wales (2012) also noted that the use of instructional materials by instructors' aids in their efficient performance of their jobs. According to Smith, the value of instructional materials is that they facilitate learning for students by making information clearer, more vivid, and more engaging. The use of instructional resources, according to Coomb (2010), is advantageous to both the instructor and the student. This is because they allow teachers to care for each student's unique differences while also saving them time and energy. They particularly assist kids who lack certain abilities. The aforementioned ideas have demonstrated the critical significance instructional materials have in the teaching and learning processes of out-of-school children. For Aremu (2008); & Wales (2012), the following list of factors illustrates the significance of educational resources for a child who is not in school:

1. Instructional materials can encourage meaningful communication of interest among out-of-school children, which in turn facilitates efficient learning.
2. The use of instructional materials can strengthen retentive memory because the out-of-school child can readily see and observe which increases the rate of remembering.
3. Non-schooled children might be inspired to learn quickly by instructional materials.
4. For these children who are not in school, it can quickly facilitate the necessary target.

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5. The difficulty for the out-of-school children will decrease.
6. The use of instructional materials for educating the out-of-school children facilitates exposure to practical tasks.

Aremu (2008); & Wales (2012) elucidated that reading and writing instruction that focuses on the use and appreciation of written language includes activities that help out-of-school children to understand that print represents spoken language; to highlight the meanings, uses, and production of print found in classroom signs, labels, notes, posters, calendars, and directions; learn print conventions, such as directionality; to practice how to handle a book - how to turn pages, how to find the tops and bottoms of pages, and how to tell the front and back covers. Here, the lessons in word awareness will help out-of-school children to become conscious of individual words (e.g., their boundaries, their appearance, and their length).

Classification of Instructional Materials and their Relevance to the Teaching of Letter-Word Recognition to the Out-of-School Children

Wales (2012), classified Instructional materials into three: the audio, the visual and audio-visual Instructional materials.

Audio Materials

These are those instructional items that a teacher brings to class but that only the students can hear. They are instructional materials that exclusively appeal to the sense of hearing; they don't display images or produce motion. Radio, tape recorders, telephones, and other audio devices are examples of resources that some youngsters who are not in school are most familiar with.

Visual Materials

These may be characterized as the instructional tools that the instructor uses and that the student sees and notices. They are instructional resources that convey information to students primarily via visual means. The teaching of letter-word recognition can be done through a variety of visual materials. These consist of tangible items, written documents, images, fees, maps, globes, etc. All of these can be utilized to teach letter-word recognition to children who are not enrolled in school. For instance, printed alphabet cards can be employed as instructional materials to teach letter-word recognition. Names of streets, towns, and nations can be taught via maps and globes. Images of various species can be used to illustrate words. Because, listening skill is a major component of many classroom tasks that is essential to incorporate audio instructional resources into the process of teaching letter-word recognition. In addition to audio resources, a teacher may also employ audio-visual elements in the classroom, which may be seen and heard. They simultaneously engage the senses of sight and sound. According to studies, students only retain 10% of what they read, 20% of what they hear, and 50% of what they see and hear (Wales, 2012). This shows that the use of audio-visual instructional materials is crucial when teaching out-of-school students and would have a greater impact on them because out-of-school students are exposed to these materials in one way or another without being aware of their educational value.

Films, videos, television, computers, and other forms of audio-visual media are examples. Children who are not in school can learn letter-word recognition using audio-visual instructional resources (Mougbamiam, Rivera, & Francis, 2009). For instance, letters, words, and what they visually represent can be taught via video tape cassette on a television or a CD on a computer. Children who are not enrolled in school can readily internalize and envision a film that demonstrates the steps involved in teaching letter-word recognition or the linguistic alphabet for use in the future (Aremu, 2008).

Criteria for Guiding the Selection of Instructional Materials to Teaching the Out-of-School Children

It is important to note that not all instructional resources can be used in a class of out-of-school students, and this relates to the guiding principles that teachers might apply when choosing materials to educate this group of students (Mougbamiam, Rivera, & Francis, 2009). Therefore, the instructor in a letter-word recognition class must ensure that the instructional material he chooses meets the learning demands of these different types of students. The instructional resources may only be made applicable to the teaching process through this approach. When choosing instructional materials, Aremu (2008) suggests that a language instructor should take into account three factors.

1. The instructional materials' adequacy and appropriateness. This implies that the language instructor must ensure that the teaching materials are appropriate for the age of the out-of-school students as well as the topic being taught (letter-word recognition). If instructional materials do not meet the learners' expectations, they will not be effective. Additionally, it will be meaningless if the course materials have nothing to do with the topic or problem that has to be addressed.
2. Learning materials need to be appealing, transportable, and adaptable. These characteristics increase the instructional materials' relevance and efficiency when used to teach these varieties. Additionally, they design the instructional materials

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to be simple for the instructor to manipulate. If instructional materials are not made appealing, they may lose their worth or credibility in terms of stimulating the attention of children who are not in school.

3. The cost of the instructional materials must be planned for. The language instructor should make every effort to suggest and recommend instructional materials that the management of these classes of learners can pay since the instructional materials should be appropriate for the students' age levels.

Steps to be Followed when Using Instructional Materials to Teach the Out-of-School Children

It is important to remember that teachers should follow specific guidelines while using instructional materials to teach children who are not enrolled in school. These actions would improve the efficient use of educational resources in the classroom. The stages should thus be followed by the language instructor to ensure that the goal of employing instructional materials is successfully attained. Aremu (2008); & Mougbamiam, Rivera, & Francis (2009) concurred in maintaining steps that a language teacher should employ when using instructional materials to teach the out-of-school children through the following steps:

1. **Preparation:** This means that children who need training (teaching) should be identified by the teacher and the school management committee run by the relevant government, and such training should be organized as follows:
 - a) The instructional materials must be well crafted, developmentally appropriate learning materials that have been approved by the academic authority (syllabus).
 - b) Classes for the aforementioned letter-word recognition instruction must be held in secure residential facilities or on school grounds.
 - c) (c.) The length should be for a time that may be extended based on the stakeholder of the instructional presentation's evaluation of the learning process.
2. **Preparing the instructional Materials:** The language instructor is now expected to carefully review the instructional resources to ensure that they are complete, intact, and prepared for usage with these kinds of learners.
3. **Preparing the environment:** The language instructor is responsible for making sure that the area where the instructional materials will be utilized is free from distracting noise when using audio and audio-visual resources, and that the area is accident-free while utilizing language laboratories.
4. **Preparing the students:** Placement conditions are involved; in other words, since out-of-school children are of varying ages, the instructor must ensure that age-matched pairs are seated in order to achieve acts of preparedness.
5. **Evaluating the Instructional materials:** This draws the language teacher's attention to the need to ensure that the instructional materials used to teach letter-word recognition are accurate and pertinent to the needs of students who are not currently enrolled in school.

Conclusion

The discussions in this study have focused on the value of instructional materials in imparting letter-word recognition to youngsters who are not enrolled in school. The conversations made it abundantly evident that instructional materials not only offer a tangible foundation for conceptual thinking, but also boost the learning interest and permanence of learning in out-of-school children, encouraging the development of their self-ability. This study has also made it quite evident that instructional resources must be used to teach letter-word recognition, just like they are for teaching any other component of English. The study found that every course geared at children who are not in school needs instructional resources and that there is no course for these learners without them. It is expected of the language teacher to introduce phonological awareness, decoding, and sight recognition to the youngsters who are not enrolled in school. Letter-word recognition becomes automatic as a result of the gradual integration of these talents. Letter identification is the simplest definition of letter recognition. Before they can name, write, or sound out the letters, it is one of the fundamental abilities that elementary school-aged children must possess.

Recommendations

The following elements are suggested based on the conversations that have already taken place in this study in order to encourage instructors of out-of-school children to adopt the attitude of employing instructional resources.

1. Education resource centers, primarily in the North, should plan for the enforce strategies to ensure adequate availability manufacture of instructional materials at all levels of education to teach the children who are not in school the letters in their names and give them a lot of practice.

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2. Seminars, workshops and Conferences for to teach language instructors should be organized consistently how to evaluate students' oral reading proficiency outside of the classroom.
3. With the provision in item one, daily letter-word recognition promotion and promotion of visual-motor abilities in letter recognition for children not in school.

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Effects of Audio-Visual Aids on Academic Achievement in Computer Studies among Secondary School Students in North-West, Nigeria

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Abstract

The evolution of audio-visual aids has made it very possible for learners to become more involved in learning activity. This study investigates the effects of audio-visual Aids (AVA) on academic achievement in computer studies among secondary schools' students in North- west Nigeria. The research design adopted was quasi-experimental research design, specifically pretest posttest non randomized control group design, three research questions and corresponding hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study consists of all senior secondary school class two (SSII) computer students in North-West Nigeria during the 2022/2023 academic session. 700 (350 male and 350 female) students constitute the sample size of the study, this was arrived at using multi-stage sampling technique within all the seven states in North-west Nigeria. Computer achievement test (COMSAT) was used to collect data for the study. The COMSAT was validated and reliability coefficient of 0.05 was obtained using analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) reliability test. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions. The analysis indicated that AVA had significant effects on students' cognitive achievement in computer studies. Gender was a significant factor in the students' overall cognitive achievement in computer studies. Thus, it is recommended to use AVA in the teaching and learning of computer and audio-visual aids should be procured and distributed in all the secondary schools in North Western Nigeria.

Keywords: Audio-visual, teaching, learning, computer, school.

Introduction

The innovation in technology has revolutionized the 21st-century educational workforce, changing the way things are done and equip teaching staff with the requisite skills needed to become more productive and effective educators (Toliver, 2017). Malmi, Sheard, Kinnunen, Simon and Sinclair (2019) stated that computer studies is a programme of study designed to give the students a thoroughly but general grounding in the ways computers are used. Computer studies equips the students with knowledge, skills and competencies that will enable them to operate the computer efficiently. Over the years, students' response to computer studies especially in public schools has been poor and the reason seems to be that instructional materials specifically audio-visual materials may not have been used or properly utilized during instruction and this is a source of worry to the researchers considering its possible effects on students' achievement in the subject. The evolution of audio-visual materials aids has made it very possible for learners to become more involved in learning activity (Idris, Shamsuddin, Arome & Aminu, 2018). Meaningful learning is most likely to occur when information is presented in a potentially meaningful way that the information conveyed is made or presented in a way that the majority of what was taught remains permanent in the learners' memory. Similarly, Soumia, (2020) opined that Audio-Visual aids make students understand and retains what they were taught for long.

Bhardwaj (2020) defines Audio-Visual Aids as "training or educational materials directed at both the senses of hearing and the sense of sight, films, recordings, photographs, etc. used in classroom instructions, library collections or the likes".

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Audio-visual materials could also be defined as the supplementary materials which are used to facilitate learning; which include models, diagrams, and displays as well as, recently developed taped-recording devices, film and television. It is a combination of aural and vision or a merger of spoken words and related visual aids to affect permanent and relative change in behaviour as reflected in sound-image display in television, film-show, video and sponsored-talking books (Karami, 2019). According to Padhi (2021), audio-visual materials are instructional devices which are used to communicate messages more effectively through sound and visuals. Audio-visual materials help in stimulating the sensory organs like ears and eyes and facilitate quick comprehension of the message by the audience. These may be used for literate as well as illiterate people. Audio-visual materials are used to improve teaching, i.e. to increase the correctness, clarity, and effectiveness of the ideas and skills being transferred. They enable the learner to LOOK, LISTEN, AND LEARN; to learn faster, to learn more, to learn thoroughly and to remember longer. Ojetade and Aregbesola (2020) supported the above with their findings that reviewed that audio-visual material has significant effect on student's achievement in science. Ibe and Abamu (2019) also revealed that students that were exposed to lesson with audio-visual technological contents integrated achieve higher in test scores than the group not exposed to audio visual materials. Singh (2021) found similar results in their study. They found that audio-visual materials can make lessons easy to understand. Images that a student views on the screen can be easily comprehended and remembered than descriptive reading materials. The importance of audio-visual materials in the teaching and learning processes cannot be over emphasized.

According to Poonia (2020), the roles of audio-visual materials are provision of sensory experience which requires an adequate background of sensory experience, which implies new words and unfamiliar objects cannot be followed and understood properly unless they are attached to specific elements of one's experience; provision of substitutes for direct experiences which makes audio-visual materials to come to our aid at that time to facilitate understanding of new concepts, facts and symbols. Pictures, models and specimens and so on to be used as accurate and effective substitutes of direct learning experiences; supplement to direct experience by visiting a post office or a cotton textile mill, pupils can learn more about the postal system and about the manufacture of cloth if these direct learning experiences are followed by seeing a film or motion picture on the subject; Important motivators by possess vividness, clarity and dramatic appeal. Children enjoy looking at pictures, going to movies and listening to radio. These are the effective medium of holding the attention and to simulating new interests and activities among children; Effective aid to the slow learner by making them to understand more easily and remember the facts, gained through pictures, movies, models and radio etc. than gathered from abstract symbols and printed pages; More efficient learning by making them to remember the facts, thus learned, for longer period; Development of the power of imagination and observation that are much clearer and more effective than the verbal images, which makes learning more natural and easier. Hence, the study is to investigate the effects of the use of audio-visual materials on students' achievement in computer studies.

The absence of the use of audio-visual materials by the secondary school teachers is a contributory factor to level of achievement of secondary school students in computer studies, which may be attributed to lack of interest on the part of the learners. Soumia, (2020) opined that Audio-Visual aids make students understand and retains what they were taught for long. Despite the fact that educational aids have a lot of outstanding positive effect in teaching and learning, the use of conventional approach to instruction are still what teachers are using, which is not based in sense experience nor does it extend their experience. In view of all this, learning of such cannot be permanent. Yet, there is also evidence of non-availability and underutilization of audio-visual materials in schools, these has led to students lack of interest, attention and active participation in the teaching and learning exercise which might be responsible for the poor academic performance of students generally. These have greatly affected students' achievement in computer education. The problem now is will the use of audio-visual materials effectively improve students' achievement in computer studies?

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to find out the effects of audio-visual aids on academic achievement in computer studies among secondary students. The work specifically;

1. Determine the achievement scores of students taught computer studies using audio-visual aid and those exposed to lecture teaching method
2. Determine the mean achievement score of male and female students taught Computer Studies using audio-visual materials
3. Determine the interactive effect of method and gender on academic achievement in computer studies among secondary students

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Research Questions

Three research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What is the mean achievement scores of students taught computer studies using audio-visual aid and those exposed to lecture teaching method?
2. What is the mean achievement score of male and female students taught Computer Studies using Audio-Visual Aids?
3. What is the interactive effect of method and Gender on academic achievement in computer studies among secondary students?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference between mean achievement scores of students taught Computer Studies using audio-visual aids and those taught using conventional teaching method.
2. There is no significant difference between mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Computer Studies using audio-visual aids.
3. There is no significant relationship between gender and method on students' mean achievement scores in Computer Studies.

Methodology

The research design adopted was quasi-experimental research design, specifically pretest posttest non randomized control group design. The researchers sampled fourteen secondary schools in North West Nigeria. The population of the study consists of all senior secondary school class two (SSII) computer students in North-West Nigeria during the 2022/2023 academic session. 700 (350 male and 350 female) students constitute the sample size of the study. This was arrived at using multi-stage sampling technique within all the seven states in North-west Nigeria. The instruments for this research were Audio-Visual Package for Computer Studies Instruction (AVPCSI) for the treatment group and Computer Studies Conventional Instruction Package (COMSCIP) for the control group. The test instrument, Computer Studies Achievement Test (COMSAT) were subjected to both face and content validation. The treatment instrument, Audio-Visual Package for Computer Studies Instruction (AVPCSI) was properly scrutinized by an expert in Educational Technology. The research questions were analysed using mean and standard deviation. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha levels using the analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) on the post-test and pre-test scores as covariates. ANCOVA was deemed appropriate here because it served as procedure for controlling the initial difference across the groups as well as increasing the precision due to the existence of erroneous variables, thereby reducing error variance.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the mean achievement score of students taught computer studies using audio-visual aid and those exposed to lecture teaching method?

Table 1: Mean scores of students based on treatment

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Experimental Group	371	70	196	19.28	4.716
Control Group	329	42	157	14.00	3.630
Valid N (listwise)	329				

Table 1 shows that the use of audio-visual aids had a huge effect on the academic achievement of the students. The students in the experimental group who were taught using audio-visual aids had a higher mean achievement score (19.28) than their counterparts in the control group who were taught using the conventional teaching method (14.00).

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Research Question 2

What is the mean achievement score of male and female students taught Computer Studies using Audio-Visual Aids?

Table 2: Mean achievement score of male and female students taught using audio-visual materials (AVPCSI).

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Male	210	84	196	21.23	4.415
Female	161	70	168	16.74	3.864
Valid N (listwise)	161				

As evident in Table 2, the male students exposed to **AVPCSI** obtained a mean score of 21.23 with a standard deviation of 4.415, while the female students also exposed to AVPCSI obtained a mean score of 16.74 with a standard deviation of 3.864. The study reported that the male students exposed to Audio-visual Package for Computer Studies Instruction achieved better than their female counterparts exposed to the same treatment.

Research Question 3

What is the interactive effect of method and Gender on academic achievement in computer studies among secondary students?

Table 3: The interactive effect of method and gender on students' achievement in computer studies.

Group	Male	Female	Mean Difference (Method)
Experimental (AVPCSI)	21.23	16.74	4.49
Control (CTM)	14.04	13.95	0.09
Mean Difference (Gender)	7.19	2.78	

Table 3 shows that, the male students exposed to **AVPCSI** obtained a mean score of 21.23, while the female students also exposed to AVPCSI obtained a mean score of 16.74, they have a mean difference of 4.29. From the control group, those exposed to the Conventional Teaching Method (CTM), the male students obtained a mean of 14.04 and the female students obtained a mean of 13.95, with a mean difference of 0.09. Comparing the two results from method (AVPCSI and CTM), it is observed that those exposed to Audio-Visual Package for Computer Studies Instruction achieved better than those exposed to the conventional teaching method. The males from the experimental group also showed a remarkable measure of understanding more than the females. Their mean differences in gender are also evident. The male students from the experimental group obtained a mean score of 21.23 while their male counterparts in the control group obtained a mean score of 14.04 with their mean difference summing up to 7.19. This shows that the males exposed to AVPCSI achieved better than the males exposed to CTM. Comparing the mean difference of the females as well from the experimental group and the control group, the females from the experimental had a mean of 16.74 while the females from the control group had a mean of 13.95 with their mean difference summing up to 2.78. The females increase in achievement was evident but not as much as that of the males.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between mean achievement scores of students taught Computer Studies using audio-visual aids and those taught using conventional teaching method.

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Table 4: ANCOVA results based on method (treatment vs control)

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	1337.720 ^a	2	668.860	57.914	.000
Intercept	81.165	1	81.165	7.028	.009
Pretest	642.475	1	642.475	55.629	.000
Group	84.337	1	84.337	7.302	.008
Error	1120.280	97	11.549		
Total	30682.000	100			
Corrected Total	2458.000	99			

a. R Squared = .544 (Adjusted R Squared = .535)

In Table 4, the calculated F value is 7.302 with a significance of 0.008. The significance of F is less than the alpha level (0.05), which means that it is significant. Therefore, we reject hypothesis one and accept the alternative hypothesis. Therefore, there is a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught using audio-visual material and those taught using conventional teaching method.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Computer Studies using audio-visual aids.

Table 5: ANCOVA results showing the effects of gender on the mean achievement scores of the students taught computer using audio-visual materials.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	490.098 ^a	2	245.049	18.379	.000
Intercept	87.729	1	87.729	6.580	.013
Pretest	227.144	1	227.144	17.036	.000
Gender	171.759	1	171.759	12.882	.001
Error	666.657	50	13.333		
Total	20864.000	53			
Corrected Total	1156.755	52			

a. R Squared = .424 (Adjusted R Squared = .401)

As shown in Table 5, the calculated F value as 12.882 with a significance of 0.001. The significance of F is less than the alpha level (0.05), which means that it is significant. Therefore, we reject hypothesis two and accept the alternative hypothesis. Hence, there is a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught using audio-visual material as shown in table 2. The male students exposed to the use of audio-visual aids achieved higher than their female counterparts.

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Hypothesis 3

There is no significant relationship between gender and method on students’ mean achievement scores in Computer Studies.

Table 6: ANCOVA results showing the interaction of gender and method on the mean achievement of students in computer studies.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	1505.461 ^a	4	376.365	37.536	.000
Intercept	108.156	1	108.156	10.787	.001
Pretest	547.177	1	547.177	54.572	.000
Group	81.864	1	81.864	8.165	.005
Gender	75.173	1	75.173	7.497	.007
Group * Gender	85.089	1	85.089	8.486	.004
Error	952.539	95	10.027		
Total	30682.000	100			
Corrected Total	2458.000	99			

a. R Squared = .612 (Adjusted R Squared = .596)

As shown in Table 6 the calculated F value is 8.486 with a significance of 0.004. The significance of F is less than the alpha level (0.05), which means that it is significant. Therefore, we reject hypothesis three and accept the alternative hypothesis. Hence, there is a significant interaction between gender and method on students’ mean achievement in computer education.

Discussion of Findings

The study investigated the effects of audio-visual aids on academic achievement in computer studies among secondary school students in North -West Nigeria. The results revealed that the use of audio-visual material had a huge effect on the academic achievement of the students. The result of the analysis of covariance on the performance of students taught computer using audio visual materials and those taught with conventional classroom instruction indicated a significant difference in favour of the students in the experimental groups. The students in this group achieved very much better than those taught conventionally. This is in line with the findings of Nonso, Onyebuanyi and Promise (2022) whose study concluded that audio-visual materials are very important and useful in education because learners gain more understanding in terms of multiple impression recorded through the eye, ear, touch and other series.

The influence of gender on the academic achievement of students when taught with audio-visual instructional material was examined using hypotheses two and three. The result of the analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) showed significant gender difference for learners exposed to audio-visual instructional material. These findings showed that gender had influence on the performance of students in computer. Thus, it can be deduced that the use of audio-visual instructional material enhanced the achievement of both male and female students but the males achieved better.

The finding in Table 3 showed significant interaction between gender and method on students mean achievement in computer studies. the male students exposed to **AVPCSI** obtained a mean score of 21.23, while the female students also exposed to AVPCSI obtained a mean score of 16.74. They have a mean difference of 4.29. From the control group (those exposed to the conventional teaching method), the male students obtained a mean of 14.04 and the female students obtained a mean of 13.95, with a mean difference of 0.09. Comparing the results from the two methods (AVPCSI and CTM), it is observed that those exposed to Audio-visual Package for Computer Studies Instruction achieved better than those exposed to the Conventional Teaching Method. The males from the experimental group also showed a remarkable measure of understanding more than the females. Their mean differences in gender are also evident. The male students from the experimental group obtained a mean score of 21.23 while their male counterparts in the control group obtained a mean score of 14.04 with their mean difference summing up to 7.19. This shows that the males exposed to AVPCSI achieved better than the males exposed to CTM. Comparing the mean difference of the females as well from the experimental group and control, the females from the experimental had a mean of 16.74 while the females from the control group had a mean of 13.95 with their mean difference summing up to 2.78. The females increase in achievement was evident but not as much as that of the males.

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Conclusion

The results of this study demonstrated that audio-visual aids (AVA) were effective instructional technique for teaching computer studies. The results were in consonance with the result of research on the effectiveness of AVA for better student's achievement in science and mathematics carried out by Sutthikun, Poramatworachote, Unchai and Ketsiri (2023). It can therefore be concluded that a relationship exists between the use of audio-visual aids and achievement of students in computer studies. Results of the study also showed that there was a significant difference between male and female students' achievement in computer studies when exposed to the treatment. Furthermore, AVA can be used as an alternative instructional method to the conventional method of teaching the various topics in computer studies since it proved to be more effective. The study has therefore provided strong evidence of the usefulness of AVA in teaching and learning of computer studies.

Recommendations

From the results of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Audio-visual aids are not always readily available for the teachers to use despite the fact that most of them know how to manipulate them. They should be procured and distributed in all the secondary schools in North Western Nigeria.
2. Teachers should be encouraged to devise local improvised audio-visual aids for teaching computer studies.
3. Computer students should be introduced to audio-visual aid as a tool for meaningful learning.
4. Computer education researchers may replicate and improve upon this study by conducting it among larger sample size and at other educational levels in the nations' educational system.

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Effects of Mastery and Collaborative Learning Approaches on Performance in Concept Genetics among Secondary School Students in Katsina State

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Abstract

A paradigm and theoretical shift in instructional designs and teaching methodologies has been witnessed in the 20th and 21st centuries, where effective teaching approaches were designed to suit learners' disposition because, educators realized the ways students preferred to be taught is significant with respect to students' academic performance. The study therefore investigated the effect of mastery and collaborative learning approaches on performance in concepts genetics among senior secondary school students in Katsina State, using gender and self-concept as moderating variables. The study adopted $3 \times 2 \times 2$ pretest posttest randomized quasi experimental factorial design. The first and second experimental and the control groups were treated using mastery learning, collaborative learning and traditional lecture methods respectively. Genetics Performance Test (Cronbach $\alpha = 0.802$) and Students' Self-concept Questionnaire (Cronbach $\alpha = 0.661$) were used to collect data which were analyzed using ANCOVA. The results of the study revealed that, there is significant main effect of treatment (mastery and collaborative learning) on students' performance in genetics concept ($F_{1,96} = 27.513; p < 0.05$). However, the main and interaction effects of the treatments and moderating variables were not significant. Based on these findings, it was concluded that, mastery and collaborative learning approaches have equivalent effects on students' performance in genetics concept. It was also recommended that teachers of biology should expose students to collaborative learning strategies in other to encourage social interaction among learners and use formative evaluation and remedial activities to help the so-called weak students gain mastery of learning contents.

Keyword: Mastery Learning, Collaborative Learning, Gender, Self-concept, Performance, Genetics Concept

Introduction

A paradigm and theoretical shift in instructional designs and teaching methodologies has been witnessed in the 20th and 21st centuries. Effective teaching approaches tailored to suit learners' disposition were observed because educators realized the ways students preferred to be taught is significant with respect to students' academic performance. Mastery Learning Approach (MLA) is one of such teaching approaches postulated in the 20th century by Benjamin Blooms. MLA is an instructional model based on the assertion that, if students are given enough time and attention while using appropriate teaching methods, most students can master any learning objective (Guskey, 2022). In MLA approach, students must achieve a level of mastery between 80-90% on a knowledge test in prerequisite knowledge before moving forward to learn subsequent information. This means that, every student is given the chance to learn and achieve mastery level at his/her own pace. Therefore, MLA can be used to improve students' understanding of perceived abstract concepts like genetics. Empirical studies conducted on mastery learning revealed the potential of the teaching strategy to enhance students' performance. For instance, Adeniji, *et al* (2018) investigated the effect of mastery learning on senior secondary school students' achievement in circle geometry and revealed that students' achievement in Geometry was enhanced significantly. In another study, Cheta and Chidinma (2018) compared Mastery and Constructivist-Based learning approach and concluded that, mastery learning

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approach is a better instructional approach than constructivist-based learning. Nnorom and Uchegbu (2017) also finds out that, mastery learning approach is effective in enhancing students' achievement in biology. Another instructional approach which has now being emphasized in teaching is collaborative learning. Collaborative learning approach is a strategy of learning in which, learners interact in smaller groups with the objective to collectively understand concept (Anthony, *et al*, 2018). In collaborative learning approach, learners with different characteristics are aggregated into heterogeneous groups. Learners in a collaborative group work together, exchange ideas, knowledge, experience and foster team spirit and cooperation among themselves. The learners also solve any problem collectively and clarify any ambiguity in concepts. In this sense, learners have full autonomy on their learning while the teacher only serves as a facilitator of the learning process.

Collaborative learning is characterized by positive interdependence (Oyarole, 2016). In positive interdependence, learners in collaborative group perceive that success or failure depends on their collective group work (Kaliisa, *et al*, 2022). If the group performs well, every individual in the group performs well and vice versa. For this reason, the attainment of personal goals depends on active participation of everyone in the group for success of the entire group (Oyarole, 2016). Collaborative learning approach promotes interaction among students around appropriate tasks and increases their mastery of critical concepts (Haataja, *et al* 2022). When students relate with other students, they learn to explain, discuss and respect other's perspectives, which lead to greater understanding of the learning materials. The process of resolving differences in opinion in collaborative activities result in the development of higher levels of understanding (Troussas, *et al*, 2023). Anthony, *et al* (2018) compared collaborative, individualistic and demonstration learning strategies using 155 senior secondary school students as sample. The study revealed that, collaborative learning strategy is more effective in enhancing students' academic performance compared to individualistic or demonstration learning strategy. Iji, *et al* (2017) investigated the effect of collaborative instructional strategy on chemistry achievement using a sample of 216 students in senior secondary school chemistry in Benue State, Nigeria. The researchers revealed that, students in the experimental group have a significant higher mean score than those in the control group. Williams and Akpan (2017) and Oyarole (2016) revealed a significant effect of collaborative learning on academic performance in biology.

Researchers have developed interest on the main and interaction effects of students' personality traits and treatments on dependents variables. Self-concept is one of such students' personality traits that has repeatedly found to have influence on academic performance. Self-concept is the perception a person has upon him/herself. It is conceptualized as "self-identity" which involves a mental and conceptual awareness and persistent regard that a person holds about his/her own being (Perinelli, *et al*, 2022). Self-concept is a product of social interaction developed through interpersonal relationship and striving for consistency (Arens, *et al*, 2022). In this recent time, self-concept has now been used as a moderating variable (Carter & Vartanian, 2022; Caasi & Pentang, 2022) due to its possible interference in experimental studies involving students' academic skills. This is because, students with better academic self-concept tends to have confidence and better academic performance. Therefore, including self-concept as a moderating variable in experimental studies like this study will help to annul the effect of extraneous effect of self-concept. There is an increased interest in male and female students' participation in Science Education because of gender imbalance in science education (Ogunode, *et al*, 2023; Eyiuche, 2019). Gender has now mostly been included in empirical studies as moderating variables. Some previous studies have shown that, gender is a significant factor for students' performance in science with either male or female students outperforming the other (Cheta & Chidinma, 2018; Udo & Udofia, 2014). However, some studies showed that, gender has no significant influence on students' performance in science (Nnorom and Uchegbu, 2017; Olatoye, 2017; Lamidi, *et al*, 2015). This study therefore included gender as a second moderating variable.

Genetics, an aspect of biology, is the scientific study of heredity and variation among living things. Students perceive genetics as too abstract and difficult to learn (Agbowuro, *et al*, 2016; Agboghroma & Oyovwi, 2015). As such, students woefully fail questions on genetics aspect of Biology in external examinations (WAEC, 2019; 2018; 2017). Students' specific weakness as reported by WAEC Chief Examiner include inability to demonstrate crossing to produce offspring; wrong usage of genetic symbols and inappropriate use of technical terms to describe genetic process. It has been stated that, MLA and other constructivists' learning approaches such as collaborative learning approach are recommended to effectively teach biology, most teachers remain adamant and thus rely heavily on traditional method such as lecture (chalk and talk) method which promote rote learning and make the teaching of biological concepts less effective. Students' performance has always been the most vital yardstick for the measurement of the effectiveness of instructional approach and the school system. The level of students' performance is determined by the learning situation more of which depends on the instructional approach. For any instructional approach to be effective, it must improve the students' performance in concept learned and as well enhances application of learning experience to other similar concepts. The quest to discover effective instructional approach to enhance

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students' performance in biological concepts has been a long-time struggle. The dwindling students' performance in biology and the manner students respond to questions in different aspects of biology and genetics in particular have shown that, there is problem in the instructional approach in biology classrooms. Against this problem therefore, the study investigated the effect of mastery and collaborative learning approaches on students' performance in genetics concepts using selfconcept and gender as moderating variables.

Objectives of the study:

The objectives of the study are to:

1. Examine the main effect of treatment on students' performance in genetics concept.
2. Find out the main effect of gender on students' performance in genetics concept.
3. Determine the main effect of self-concept on students' performance in genetics concept.
4. Assess the interaction effect of treatment and gender on students' performance in genetics concept.
5. Examine the interaction effect of treatment and self-concept on students' performance in genetics concept.
6. Measure the interaction effect of gender and self-concept on students' performance in genetics concept.
7. Examine the interaction effect of treatment, gender and self-concept on students' performance in genetics concept.

Hypotheses:

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance;

1. There is no significant main effect of treatment on students' performance in genetics concept.
2. There is no significant main effect of gender on students' performance in genetics concept.
3. There is no significant main effect of self-concept on students' performance in genetics concept.
4. There is no significant interaction effect of treatment and gender on students' performance in genetics concept.
5. There is no significant interaction effect of treatment and self-concept on students' performance in genetics concept.
6. There is no significant interaction effect of gender and self-concept on students' performance in genetics concept.
7. There is no significant interaction effect of treatment, gender and self-concept on students' performance in genetics concept.

Methodology

This study adopted a 3×2×2 pre-test post-tests randomized quasi experimental factorial design. This design was adopted because the independent variables can be manipulated. Also, factorial design helped to check the main and interaction effect of independent and moderating variables on the dependent variable. The detail of the research design is clearly summarized in Tables 1 and 2:

Table 1: Randomized Quasi-Experimental Control Group Pre-test Post-test Design

Group	Pre-test	Treatment	Post-test
1 st Experimental group	O _{1ML}	X _{ML}	O _{2ML}
2 st Experimental group	O _{1Coll}	X _{Coll}	O _{2Coll}
Control	O _{1L}		O _{2L}

Key: O_{1ML} represents pre-test for mastery learning group (1st experimental group)
 X_{ML} represents treatment for Mastery learning group (1st experimental group)
 O_{2ML} represents post-test for Mastery learning group (1st experimental group)
 O_{1Coll} represents pre-test for collaborative learning group (2nd experimental group)
 X_{Coll} represents treatment for collaborative learning group (2nd experimental group)
 O_{2Coll} represents post-test for collaborative learning group (2nd experimental group)
 O_{1L} represents pre-test for control group method
 O_{2L} represents post-test for control group method

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Table 2: Randomized Pre-test Post-tests Factorial Design

Group	Male		Female		Total
	High Self-Concept	Low Self-Concept	High Self-Concept	Low Self-Concept	
ML	8	8	8	8	32
CL	8	8	8	8	32
Control	8	8	8	8	32
Total					96

Key: ML is Mastery learning group; CL is Collaborative learning group

The population for this study comprises 12,853 (6079 male and 6774 female) senior secondary three (SS3) students in Katsina Education Zonal Quality Assurance, Katsina State, Nigeria. Katsina Zonal Education consists of 25 secondary schools spread across three Local Government Areas: Katsina, Kaita and Jibiya Local Government Area. A multistage sampling technique was employed in selecting the respondents. A cluster sampling was used to select three schools, one school from each Local Government. The three schools were randomly assigned as experimental and control groups. A simple random sampling technique was used to select thirty-two students from each school. Thus, the total sample size of the study consists of 96 students. In this study, Genetics Performance Test (GPT), and Self-Concept Questionnaire (SCQ) were used to collect data. Genetics Performance Test (GPT) is a twenty-five (25) item multiple-choice objective questions developed by the researcher. The items in GPT were constructed reflecting five selected topics in genetics aspect of secondary school biology curriculum. These topics are: 1) Chromosomes as the basis of heredity; 2) Transmission and Expression of Characters; 3) Sex determination in human beings, 4) Sex linkages in human beings and 5) Application of the principles of heredity. Each question in GPT was scored one mark. Self-Concept Questionnaire SCQ is a researcher-developed fifteen (15) items, four-point Likert-type scale instrument calibrated with Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). For all positive items on the scale, SA was assigned 4 points, A was assigned 3 points, D was assigned 2 points and SD was assigned 1 point. The maximum and minimum obtainable points are 60 and 15 respectively. Scores below 37 were categorized as low self-concept while scores from 38 above were categorized as high self-concept.

The initial drafts of the instruments were validated by two experienced biology teachers and an expert in psychometrics to check the relevance, adequacy and structure of the items before the pretest. The content validity of GPT was ascertained following strictly the number of items per topic as specified in the test blueprint in table 3 below. The recommendations and suggestions made by the experts were used to modify the final draft of the instruments.

Table 3: Table of Specification of 25 items Genetics Performance Test (GPT)

Content	Weight	Remember	Understand	Apply	Analyze	Evaluate	Total
Chromosomes; the basis of heredity	22%	3	2	0	0	0	5
Transmission and expression of character in organisms.	26%	2	2	1	2	1	8
Sex determination in human beings	15%	0	2	1	0	0	3
Sex linkage in human beings	15%	-	-	-	1	2	3
Application of the principles of heredity	22%	1	1	2	1	1	6
Total	100%	6	7	4	4	4	25

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Item Analysis (Difficulty Index and Discrimination Power) of GPT

The items on GPT were analyzed by determining the Difficulty Index (d) and Discrimination Power (D) of GPT using the pilot sample performance. Items with difficulty index between 30 – 70% were accepted while items with difficulty index above 70% or below 30% was tagged too easy or too difficult respectively and reviewed accordingly. For Discrimination Power (D), items within the range of 0.7 – 0.3 were retained and used for the study while discriminating power outside this range were reviewed. The reliability coefficient of GPT and SCQ were determined using Cronbach alpha method of estimating internal consistency. The data from a pilot study conducted was used to determine the reliability of GPT and SCQ which was found to be 0.802 and 0.661 respectively. The data collected were analyzed using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). SPSS version 23 was used to carry out the analysis.

Results

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant main effect of treatment on students' performance in genetics concepts.

Table 4: ANCOVA of Effects of Treatment on Students' Performance in Genetics Concepts

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
Corrected Model	1831.842 ^a	12	152.653	7.242	.000	Sig.
Intercept	1543.916	1	1543.916	73.247	.000	Sig.
Pretest	132.907	1	132.907	6.305	.014	Sig.
Treatment	1159.847	2	579.923	27.513	.000	Sig.
Error	1749.492	83	21.078			
Total	37632.000	96				
Corrected Total	3581.333	95				

a. R Squared = .511 (Adjusted R Squared = .441); Sig=Significant ($p < 0.05$); NS=Not Significant ($p > 0.05$)

Table 4 shows the main effects of treatment on students' academic performance in biology. There is significant main effect of treatment on students' performance in genetics concepts ($F_{2, 96} = 27.513$; $p < 0.05$). This means that, the teaching strategies experimented has a significant effect in enhancing the students' performance in genetics concepts. As such, the null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant main effect of treatment on students' performance in genetics concepts is rejected.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant main effect of gender on students' performance in genetics concepts.

Table 5: Main Effects of Gender on Students' Performance in Genetics Concepts

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
Corrected Model	1831.842 ^a	12	152.653	7.242	.000	Sig.
Intercept	1543.916	1	1543.916	73.247	.000	Sig.
Pretest	132.907	1	132.907	6.305	.014	Sig.
Gender	29.429	1	29.429	1.396	.241	NS
Error	1749.492	83	21.078			
Total	37632.000	96				
Corrected Total	3581.333	95				

Sig=Significant ($p < 0.05$); NS=Not Significant ($p > 0.05$)

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In Table 5, there is no significant main effect of gender on students' academic performance in genetics concepts ($F_{1, 96} = 1.396; p > 0.05$). This means that, the teaching strategies experimented in this study has nothing to do with students' gender. Both male and female students can perform equally when these teaching strategies are used. The null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant main effect of gender on students' performance in genetics concepts is hereby retained.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant main effect of self-concept on students' performance in genetics concepts.

Table 6: Main Effects of Selfconcept on Students' Performance in Genetics Concepts

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
Corrected Model	1831.842 ^a	12	152.653	7.242	.000	Sig.
Intercept	1543.916	1	1543.916	73.247	.000	Sig.
Pretest	132.907	1	132.907	6.305	.014	Sig.
Selfconcept	3.693	1	3.693	.175	.677	NS
Error	1749.492	83	21.078			
Total	37632.000	96				
Corrected Total	3581.333	95				

Sig=Significant ($p < 0.05$); NS=Not Significant ($p > 0.05$)

Analysis in Table 6 shows that, there is no significant main effect of self-concept on students' academic performance in genetics concepts ($F_{1, 96} = 0.175; p > 0.05$). This means that, the students performed equally in genetics concepts irrespective of the level of their self-concepts. The null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant main effect of self-concept on students' performance in biology is hereby retained.

Hypothesis 4

There is no significant interaction effect of treatment and gender on students' performance in genetics concepts

Table 7: Interaction Effects of Treatment and Gender on Students' Performance in Genetics Concepts

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
Corrected Model	1831.842 ^a	12	152.653	7.242	.000	Sig.
Intercept	1543.916	1	1543.916	73.247	.000	Sig.
Pretest	132.907	1	132.907	6.305	.014	Sig.
Treatment * Gender	25.367	2	12.684	.602	.550	NS
Error	1749.492	83	21.078			
Total	37632.000	96				
Corrected Total	3581.333	95				

Sig=Significant ($p < 0.05$); NS=Not Significant ($p > 0.05$)

In Table 7, the two-way interaction effect of treatment and gender on students' performance in genetics concepts is not significant ($F_{2, 96} = 0.602; p > 0.05$). This means that, the efficacy of the teaching strategies experimented in this study does not depend on students' gender. Both male and female students performed equally when taught genetics concepts using MLA and CLA. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant interaction effect of treatment and gender on students' performance in genetics concepts is retained.

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Hypothesis 5

There is no significant interaction effect of treatment and self-concept on students' performance in genetics concepts.

Table 8: Two-Way Interaction Effects of Treatment and Self-concept on Students' Performance in Genetics Concepts

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
Corrected Model	1831.842 ^a	12	152.653	7.242	.000	Sig.
Intercept	1543.916	1	1543.916	73.247	.000	Sig.
Pretest	132.907	1	132.907	6.305	.014	Sig.
Treatment * Selfconcept	46.534	2	23.267	1.104	.336	NS
Error	1749.492	83	21.078			
Total	37632.000	96				
Corrected Total	3581.333	95				

Sig=Significant ($p < 0.05$); NS=Not Significant ($p > 0.05$)

Data analysis in Table 8 revealed that, the two-way interaction effect of treatment and self-concept on students' performance in genetics concepts is not significant ($F_{2, 96} = 1.104$; $p > 0.05$). This means that, the efficacy of the teaching strategies experimented in this study is independent on students' self-concept. Students with low or high self-concepts will perform equally when exposed to genetics concepts. The null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant interaction effect of treatment and self-concept on students' performance in genetics concepts is therefore retained.

Hypothesis 6

There is no significant interaction effect of gender and self-concept on students' performance in genetics concepts.

Table 9: Two-Way Interaction Effects of Gender and Self-concept on Students' Performance in Genetics Concepts

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
Corrected Model	1831.842 ^a	12	152.653	7.242	.000	Sig.
Intercept	1543.916	1	1543.916	73.247	.000	Sig.
Pretest	132.907	1	132.907	6.305	.014	Sig.
Gender * Self-concept	3.643	1	3.643	.173	.679	NS
Error	1749.492	83	21.078			
Total	37632.000	96				
Corrected Total	3581.333	95				

Sig=Significant ($p < 0.05$); NS=Not Significant ($p > 0.05$)

The two-way interaction effect of gender and self-concept on students' performance in biology in Table 9 is not significant ($F_{1, 96} = 0.173$; $p > 0.05$). This means that, the interplay between students' gender and their self-concept will not affect their performance when taught genetics concepts using MLA and CLA. The null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant interaction effect of gender and self-concept on students' performance in genetics concepts is therefore retained.

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Hypothesis 7

There is no significant interaction effect of treatment, gender and self-concept on students' performance in genetics concepts.

Table 10: Three-Way Interaction Effects of Treatment, Gender and Self-concept on Students' Performance in Genetics Concepts

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
Corrected Model	1831.842 ^a	12	152.653	7.242	.000	Sig.
Intercept	1543.916	1	1543.916	73.247	.000	Sig.
Pretest	132.907	1	132.907	6.305	.014	Sig.
Treatment * Gender * Self-concept	32.334	2	16.167	.767	.468	NS
Error	1749.492	83	21.078			
Total	37632.000	96				
Corrected Total	3581.333	95				

Sig=Significant ($p < 0.05$); NS=Not Significant ($p > 0.05$)

Result in Table 10 revealed that, the three-way interaction effect of treatment, gender and self-concept on students' performance in genetics concepts is not significant ($F_{2, 96} = 0.767$; $p > 0.05$). This finding clearly defines the efficacy of the teaching strategies experimented as independent on students' gender and self-concept. As such, the null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant interaction effect of treatment, gender and self-concept on students' performance in genetics concepts is therefore retained. In a nutshell, the main effect of the treatment on students' performance in biology is significant but the main and interaction effects of the moderating variables (gender and self-concept) on the students' performance in biology are not significant. The teaching strategies experimented in this study as a whole accounted for 51.1% of the variation in the students' performance in genetics concepts ($R^2 = 0.511$; $F_{12, 95} = 7.242$; $p < 0.05$) (Table 4). However, it is important to determine the significance of the mean difference in the students' performance since the three groups performed differently. This is why Table 11 is presented.

Table 11: Univariate Tests of Mean Scores of the Experimental and Control Groups

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
Contrast	1159.847	2	579.923	27.513	.000	*Sig.
Error	1749.492	83	21.078			

*Significant ($p < 0.05$)

In Table 11, there is significant mean difference in performance among MLA, CLA and the Lecture Method groups ($F_{2, 83} = 27.513$; $p < 0.05$). This means that, the three groups performed at different levels. By comparing the groups 2×2 pairwise will help revealed the group that produced the difference. Table 12 therefore shows the comparison among the groups.

Table 12: Pairwise Comparisons of Experimental and Control Groups

Treatment	(J) Treatment	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	Remark
MLA	CLA	-1.552	1.309	.717	**NS
	Lecture Method	7.714*	1.347	.000	*Sig
CLA	MLA	1.552	1.309	.717	**NS
	Lecture Method	9.267*	1.323	.000	*Sig
Lecture Method	MLA	-7.714*	1.347	.000	*Sig
	CLA	-9.267*	1.323	.000	*Sig

*Significant ($p < 0.05$); **Not Significant ($p > 0.05$)

In Table 12, there is no significant difference between MLA and CLA (Mean Difference = -1.552; $p > 0.05$). However, there is significant difference between MLA and Lecture Method (Mean Difference = 7.714; $p < 0.05$). Also, there is significant difference between CLA and Lecture Method (Mean Difference = 9.267; $p < 0.05$). It can therefore be inferred that, MLA and

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CLA are the causes of the difference produced in the students' performance in genetics concepts. As such, MLA and CLA are effective in teaching genetics concepts.

Discussion of Findings

The study revealed that, there is a significant main effect of mastery learning approach on students' performance in genetics concepts. This finding agrees with the findings of Adeniji, *et al* (2018) and Cheta and Chidinma (2018) that mastery learning approach has significant effect on students' academic achievement. Many other previous studies conducted on mastery learning also proved the efficacy of this teaching method (Mitee & Obaitan, 2015; Udo & Udofia, 2014). This finding is therefore not a surprise because the formative assessment used as diagnostic tool do not only help weak learners achieve instructional objectives but it also helps to bridge the gap between the students with high and low self-concept (Guskey, 2022). The study further revealed that, there is significant main effect of collaborative learning approach on students' performance in genetics concepts. This finding corroborates with the findings of Anthony, *et al* (2018), Iji, *et al* (2017) that collaborative learning approach has significant effect on students' academic achievement. Collaborative learning approach has been proved to be an efficient teaching method in some aspects in biology (Williams & Akpan, 2017; Oyarole, 2016). This finding is not shocking because, collaborative learning has been theorized as a group-based learning process where students can reach their level of potential development through positive interdependency which characterized the model. Both mastery and collaborative learning has equal effect on students' performance in genetics concepts. In collaborative learning, students are more involved in the learning process. They interact and share common goal of success. This process gives strength to the weak students and thus enhanced performance. However, in mastery learning, students are less involved. But the corrective measures and the enrichment activities used after diagnosing students' strength and weakness enhance students' performance. Students could attain their level of potential development with either learning by collaboration or by learning for mastery.

Another finding of this study is that, there is no significant main effect of gender on students' performance in genetics concepts. Also, there is no significant two-way interaction effect of gender and treatment on students' performance in genetics concepts. This finding corresponds with the findings of Olatoye (2017) that, gender has no main nor interaction effects on treatment. Since the main and interaction effect of gender with treatment are not significant, it means that, the treatment is gender friendly. The innate difference in gender is not based on aptitude but on the nature of chromosome an individual inherits before birth. This cannot be translated into the learning process.

The study further revealed that, one-way and two-way interaction effect of self-concept and treatment on students' performance in genetics concepts are not significant. This finding agrees with the findings of Olatoye (2017) that, self-concept has no main effect nor interaction effects on treatment. It has been asserted that, effective teaching strategies do not only influence students' academic performance (Williams & Akpan, 2017; Enohuan, 2015) but also influence students' enabling variables such as attitude, interest, motivation to learning/study habit and also self-concept (Ukor & Isah, 2015; Enohuan, 2015). In mastery learning, students' learning difficulties are identified through diagnostic evaluation and corrected using remedial programmes. In the collaborative learning strategy, students with low aptitude and/or low self-concepts are grouped with students with high aptitude and/or high self-concept. In these kinds of learning process, both low and high self-concept students can attain the level of potential development and perform well in schools. This is why the one, two and three-ways effect of treatment with moderating variables on the students' performance are not significant.

Conclusion

Students' mode of response to questions on genetics concepts and performance in biology as a whole has not been encouraging despite efforts being made to stimulate the intellectual skill and personal growth of the students in science. The major cause of the poor performances in biology is attributed to the use of inappropriate instructional strategies adopted by the biology teachers. However, this study provides an empirical support and credence to mastery and collaborative learning as efficient enough to raise students' performance beyond the present level. Both mastery and collaborative learning strategies facilitates students' performance better than the traditional lecture methods. Remarkably as these learning strategies are, gender and self-concept do not affect students' performance when they are used. It is revealed that, the treatment given to the three groups have significant effects on academic performance though, students in the mastery and collaborative learning groups performed higher than those in the control/lecture groups. It is hereby concluded that, mastery and collaborative learning strategy have significant effect on the students' performance in genetics concepts than the traditional lecture method.

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Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following are hereby recommended:

1. Teachers of biology should expose students to collaborative learning strategy in order to encourage social interaction, active engagement and positive interdependence among learners.
2. Also, teachers of biology should always use formative evaluation to identify areas where students have difficulties. This will help to alleviate the so-called weak students to gain mastery of learning contents.
3. Teachers should be encouraged and/or mandated to attend workshops and seminars to acquaint themselves with requisite skills to use mastery and collaborative learning approaches in classrooms.
4. Curriculum planners should design curriculum in such a way that, mastery and collaborative learning strategies can be used to fully implement biology curriculum.
5. Textbook writers should lay emphasis on students' activities that will promote the incorporation of collaborative learning strategy in biology textbook

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Effects of Virtual Classroom on Performance in Essay Writing among Private Senior Secondary School Students in Abuja, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study titled: 'Effects of Virtual Classroom on Performance in Essay Writing among Private Senior Secondary School Students in Abuja', adopted a quasi-experimental research design. Four research objectives, questions and hypotheses were developed for the study. The population comprised of all the eleven thousand, four hundred and seventy-five (11,475) Private Senior Secondary School II students during the 2021/2022 academic session in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. Fifty-five students were sampled for the study using the purposive intact class sampling technique. The study adopted test titled: Structured Expository Essay Writing Test (SEEWTE) for data collection. The instrument was piloted using split-half test method. The scores of the reliability test were analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient (PPMCC), and reliability index of 0.90 was obtained. Simple percentage, mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that virtual classroom is significant on students' performance in essay writing compared to those exposed to physical classroom. The study concluded that virtual classroom is effective in the teaching of essay writing. Based on this finding, the study recommended that school management should ensure that technological materials are adequately provided for the smooth and effective use of virtual classroom in teaching essay writing to students in private Senior Secondary Schools in Abuja and the country at large.

Keywords: Technology, Virtual Classroom, Physical Classroom, Essay Writing, Academic Performance, and Students

Introduction

The use of technologies in education has become a practice in many countries of the world. This innovation became known in many educational institutions around the world in the year 2020 when the outbreak of Covid-19 brought about a global shutdown in all sectors and activities that require physical interaction and contact. Thus, technology gained its relevance in education, especially in making teaching and learning stimulating, and taking over the stand of the traditional classroom approach (Matthew, 2022). Adding to the submission of Matthew, Godswill, et al. (2023) note that technology in education has the capacity to enrich teachers' teaching style and approaches, hence, making teaching and learning effective. With educational technology, classes become more interesting, more immersive and fully interactive. Technologies offer the possibility of switching to a blended learning method, or a flipped classroom, which have been proven to be successful in learning all language skills (listening, speaking, reading and writing). Moreover, they provide teachers with an infinite number of exercises and activities for different levels, which promote students' active participation in the English language classrooms. Additionally, they enable teachers and learners to learn within and outside the physical classroom, keep students motivated, evaluating students with tests and exams, and other administrative tasks, as well as allow students to be much more creative, innovative, and participatory in the classroom (Carey, 2020).

Over the year, the teaching and learning of English language have undergone many changes. These changes have been attributed to the desire of language education researchers to make the teaching and learning of English language effective in learners' development of language skills and their academic performance in them. At the start of the 16thc, the Grammar Translation Method dominated the language classroom. This approach aimed at developing grammatical rules and vocabulary in learners, as well as building the skill of reading and writing (Odumuh, 2020). While the above was advantageous in learners' understanding of grammar, vocabulary and reading, studies from Mayiwa (2017), Nathan (2019) and Maisamari (2019) have shown the inability for the approach to develop the skills of writing in learners. Thus, learners produce written text that are extensive but meaningless; as there is no link between what teachers and learners teach and learn respectively, and the authentic world. Therefore, the effects of this form of meaningless text produced by learners have been seen on students' performance in English language and essay writing in particular (Anderson, 2012). It becomes necessary thus, for language education

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researchers to search for a better language teaching approach that helps incorporate technological tools such as virtual classroom in teaching writing; in this case expository essay.

The communicative approach is a language teaching approaches that frames communication as the main goal of teaching and learning English language. This approach ensures that students can communicate effectively and confidently in real-life situations through student-to-student and student-to-teacher interaction via spoken, or written. Essentially, this approach aimed at making students to learn a new language by actually using the language to communicate with those around them. As an approach that promotes authentic use of language, the integration of reading, speaking, and writing are some of its core features, hence, making teaching and learning of English language interesting and purposeful. Another interesting aspect of this approach is the involvement of learners in groups; participating in the completion of authentic tasks and activities, aimed at meeting language needs and goals. Central to the above, is the use of language teaching materials and technology in teaching and learning writing (Godswill et al., 2023). Therefore, the researcher is motivated to incorporate the use of language materials, technology in particular to create authentic use of language in writing. Virtual classroom is one good example of the use of technology in teaching and learning writing (Yenus, 2017).

A virtual classroom is an online interactive platform or a teaching and learning environment where teachers and learners present learning materials and tasks with the aim of meeting educational goals. It is an online, live interactive classroom where activities such as teaching, learning, evaluation, presentation of materials, and grouping of learners take place. It is synchronous in nature; and allows students' active participation and promotes students-centered approach where learners can produce and present materials for class discussion and the general teaching and learning activities (Yenus, 2017). The use of Microsoft Teams, Google Classroom, Zoom, WhatsApp, Telegram, are some of the live, synchronous and interactive classroom platforms/channels that recent language experts propose for use in the teaching and learning of English language. Essay writing is an aspect of the English language where the skills needed to competently use the English language can be developed and enhanced in learners through virtual classroom.

Expository essay is one type of essay writing in English. It is the type of essay that requires a writer to logically present a subject or topic in a sequential manner. It involves the use of ideas in various paragraphs to develop a subject matter or topic. Thus, a good written essay requires the writer to develop a subject or topic to be discussed, contents to be developed, as well as supporting details that expand the ideas of the essay. According to Yenus (2017), the expository essay is popularly known as the process essay as it requires a careful presentation of a subject matter in a logical and sequential manner following an established pattern. Thus, he identifies the title, introduction, body and conclusion as the structure of an expository essay. Adding to the submission of Yenus, Godswill et. al (2023) identifies some vital ingredients of an expository essay. These include: content, language expression, organization and mechanical accuracy. In his postulation, the expository essay requires the writer to expose the readers to a good subject matter or topic using good and elevated language in an organized manner and paying close attention to grammatical components such as spellings, sentence structure, coherence and cohesion and punctuations. It is clear from the above that expository essay writing is that aspect of language skill that requires careful and effective teaching and learning. While many teachers may claim the use of best approaches and materials in teaching the expository essay writing, the researcher is motivated to find out if these approaches and materials are effective in the teaching and learning of the essay, considering poor performance of students in internal and external examinations where students are tested to write such essay.

For example, the researcher observes that students find it difficult to develop or create a suitable title of an expository essay. The effect of this is that appropriate subject contents that support the subject or title of the essay are difficult to develop by students. Again, the development of contents, main idea and supporting details at the paragraph level are other important skills learners find challenging in approaching an expository essay. The researcher in one of his assessment of students' external examination scripts observes that most students' essays lack subject content and main idea. The implication of this problem is that they find it difficult to organize details that support the ideas of a topic or subject. The researcher also notes that students find it difficult to write in simple, logical correct sentences, and appropriate use of words in context. These problems suggest that learners lack adequate skill for correct use of language in developing subject content in an expository essay. Another important area that motivates this study is learners' inability to organize the paragraph of their essays, and appropriate use of punctuations. Cohesion and coherence are two important aspects of an organized expository essay. However, the researcher observes that students' essays lack cohesion at the sentences level forming a paragraph, and coherence at the paragraph level forming the whole structure of a text or essay. Also, the researcher's interaction with other English language teachers in Secondary Schools across Nigeria has shown that students' lack the skills of English punctuations, especially in writing essay.

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Thus, students find it difficult to differentiate between colon (:) and semi-colon (;), they also misuse exclamation marks (!), hyphen (-), dash (–), full stop (.) and comma (,). Could it be that the materials and approaches use in teaching expository essay at the level of content, language expression, organization and mechanical accuracy are not appropriate and activity-based? While there is no empirical evidence to justify the above question, the researcher relies on the outcome of this study to justify the effect of using virtual classroom on students' performance in expository essay in private Senior Secondary School, Abuja. It has been established that communicative approach is an important aspect of virtual classroom; as the use of technology has been found to be an effective teaching and learning tool for promoting authentic use of language and making communication functional, purposeful and meaningful. Thus, Raymond (2017) identifies some authentic, simulative and interactive activities use in teaching expository essay writing, using virtual classroom.

The subject or title of an essay is the first part of the essay learners are exposed to. This is the area of in which the essay is set to address. It is the issue or topic the writer intends to write on. Teaching the subject or topic or title of an essay requires the understanding of different issues and areas of life. For example, the teacher may guide the learners to mention people, places, things and ideas they know. Doing this exposes the learners to various subjects and areas of life as well as their relevance to in human society. The teacher may also present a long list of events and ask students to choose the three that they have attended. They may also be guided to state three things that happen in each of the three events. Another way teacher could help learners understand the subject or topic of an essay is by guiding the learners to mention one discipline they would love to study. This will help the teacher guide the learners on how to structure the title or subject of an essay. Additionally, the teacher may also use pictures, images, or play recorded videos and audio on different careers for learners to make their choices. Thus, using virtual classroom will help the learners to understand and select their choice of career as well as have detail information about the content of the career. Also, teachers are flexible in the presentation of materials for the teaching of essay writing at this level (Moyo, 2022). Writing the introduction of an essay is another important aspect or skill to be developed in learners. This is one of the most important areas that the teacher is expected to develop in learners. The teacher is expected to provide appropriate activities for effective understanding of the introduction of an essay. The teacher may present five sentence hooks on different subject or topic and guide learners to identify the most appropriate for a given subject or topic of an essay. The teacher may present a short video on an interesting story and tasks student to produce one moral lesson, which is further turned to either a statement or a question, as sentence hook (Moyo, 2022).

Teaching the body of an essay requires the learners to understand the meaning of an outline and its uses in writing. It is the itemization of the main points or ideas to be discussed or explained in a text. It is a list of points or issues to be discussed about a subject or topic. In impacting this skill or knowledge via virtual classroom, the teacher may present an outline haphazardly and guide students to arrange them chronologically. This may be presented in text, pictures, motion images, video and audio materials. The implication of this activity is that it aimed at developing students' skill of content creation and development as well as elaboration of main points or ideas (Abiola, 2022). Other areas to be developed in learners include: grammar and language expression, punctuation marks and organization of the text. These areas can be developed through many class simulative activities, and group work. The teacher may present ten sentences on a given idea and guides learners to arrange them accordingly. He or she may also play a recorded video on a given topic and guide students to write a paragraph on the video. For punctuation marks, the teacher may present unpunctuated paragraph and guide students to punctuate it. For language expression, the teacher may present sentence stripes and guide learners to fix them in a given blank spaces of a paragraph. This will help develop in them the skill of language expression in essay writing using virtual classroom (Abiola, 2022).

This study is anchored on the Operant Conditioning Theory by B. F. Skinner. The theory is anchored on the principles of behavioural psychology especially with regard to how learning is achieved. The theory promotes reinforcement as a means of behaviour formation and modification. Essentially, behaviourists generally agree that learning is an enduring change in behaviour which results from the application of a stimulus to elicit a desired response. It is important to also clarify that an individual's behaviour is a result of learning. That is, when we internalize what we learn and are able to display it appropriately, that (skill, concept, idea, philosophy, etc.) which we have learnt become our behaviour (Raymond, 2017). Thus, the operant is said to be reinforced if the consequence increases the likelihood of the behaviour's occurrence. For example, a teacher may seek to reinforce learners' skill or demonstration of knowledge (behaviour) by offering a reward so as to reinforce those students' behaviour. A reinforce, therefore, is anything that strengthens the desired response. It could be verbal praise, a good grade, stickers, or a feeling of increased accomplishment or satisfaction. The theory also covers negative reinforcers — any stimulus that results in the increased frequency of a response when it is withdrawn (Raymond, 2017).

Relating this theory to the study, it helps the teacher to guide the learners in responding to essay writing, thereby producing what they have learnt. The outcome of the essay therefore determines the reward given to the learners by the teacher.

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If students' response to the essay is good, they get positive rewards like clap, treat, gift, marks, stickers, praise, etc. However, if their response to the essay is poor/bad, the learners attract negative reward. However, the theory aimed at retaining or sustaining good response to what is taught. Additionally, the theory is also useful in understanding the skills, strategies and channel (virtual classroom) to increase good academic performance as well as decrease poor academic performance in learners. It also dwells on teachers' approach in impacting knowledge in learners (Steven, 2020). For example, if a teacher wants to encourage students to answer essay writing questions in class the teacher praises the learners for every attempt (regardless of whether their answers are correct). Gradually the teacher will only praise the students that produce correct answers, and subsequently, only exceptional answers from learners will be praised and affirmed for continuation (Steven, 2020). Additionally, knowledge of success is also important as it motivates future learning. However, it is important to vary the type of reinforcement given so that the behavior is maintained. For example, the teaching and learning of essay writing is aimed at developing writing skills in learners for them to be able to understand the structure of an essay, identify a subject or topic of an essay, write a good introduction, body, and conclusion. Also, it is expected that learners understand and develop the skills of essay contents in line with the subject or topic, express their ideas in simple, clear and meaning coherent language, organize paragraphs in a sequential order, as well as use punctuations appropriately and other writing mechanics such as spellings, capital and small letters, and space (Raymond, 2017). Thus, this theory is relevant for the understanding of this study.

Many studies in language education have been carried out on the use of technologies in teaching various aspects of the English language and essay writing in particular. First, Davids (2013) conducted research on the influence of the use of ICT in teaching writing in some selected Junior Secondary Schools, Kaduna State. The study found that there is significant difference in the levels of appropriateness of the use of ICT in teaching writing and their experience and skills in ICT. The study recommended that ICT should be adequately deployed and used in teaching writing. Paulinus, Idongesit, and Nkasiobi (2016) carried out a study on the use of virtual learning on academic performance of JSS 1 student in English composition in Secondary School in Port Harcourt Local Government Area. The study revealed that there is significant difference in student's academic performance when virtual learning was used to teach English composition. Etukakpan, Maduka, and Christopher (2021) conducted a study on virtual classroom and academic performance of SSS II students in formal letter writing in Secondary Schools in Abak Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. The study showed that students exposed to virtual classroom performed better than those in conventional class in formal letter writing. Talal (2021) conducted a study on the effect of using Telegram application on improving writing skill for the students of English as a foreign language. The study discovered that there are statistically significant variations at the level of significance ($=0.05$) between the mean scores of the experimental group and the control group in the writing ability of post-test due to the use of Telegram in favour of the experimental group. Also, Telegram application had a positive impact on the users, since it helped the students save and record their writing and other learning materials. Anabela, Debora, Deborah, and Susan (2022) carried out a study on the use of virtual classroom in teaching writing in Primary Education (grades 6) in Australia: A National Survey. The study revealed that teachers do not provide the appropriate teaching tasks for the teaching of writing. Also, the finding indicated lots of problems affecting the use of virtual classroom: poor network, inadequate computer materials like laptop, smart phones, tablet, etc. Eka (2023) conducted a study on the use of Microsoft Teams for teaching writing in Junior High School in Surabaya. The study revealed that teachers lack the skills needed for using Microsoft Teams in teaching writing. Godswill, Ngozi, Cajetan, and Ngozi (2023) conducted a study on enhancing ESL students' academic achievement in expository essay writing using Digital Graphic Organisers: A Mixed-methods Research. The study found a statistically significant difference between students' mean achievement scores before and after exposure to digital graphic organizer charts when writing expository essays. Despite the above areas revealed in those studies, there are gaps that the present study is set to fill. Thus, the use of virtual classroom (WhatsApp) as a channel through which expository essay writing is taught, and students' performance in the treatment of content, language expression, organization, and mechanical accuracy will be filled in the present study. Also, while the above studies used virtual classroom platform as such as Telegram, Microsoft Teams, Digital Graphic Organizer, etc., the present study used WhatsApp as the virtual classroom platform for the teaching of expository essay writing.

The clamour for the use of technology in every aspect of human society has demonstrated its relevance in meeting man's needs. The 2020 Covid-19 global pandemic that led to the shutdown of the world is a push factor that moved almost all sectors of the world to embrace technology for the conduct of formal and informal businesses, church services, and even education. This trend has since brought about change in the instructional methods and materials used in teaching and learning. To support the above, several scholars (Sylvester, Paulinus, & Udom, 2016; Anekwe, 2017; Mojtaba & Mahsa, 2018) consider the use of virtual classroom (an aspect of technology) as an effective instructional method of delivering lessons to students in today's world, as it helps stimulate learners and ease the teachers of the burden of teaching using the physical method. However,

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empirical justification is needed to support these assertions. Thus, the researcher is interested in finding out the effects virtual classroom have on students' performance on essay writing.

The researcher observes that the instructional method and materials used in teaching English language essay writing has not given much impact on students' knowledge of the English language essay and performance. This can be seen from students' performance in external and international examinations, where examination reports show that students' poor performance can be traced to the difficulty, they face in essay writing. For example, Godswill, Ngozi, Cajetan, and Ngozi (2023) note that students find it difficult to create and develop the title and content of an essay. Other areas include: language expression, organization and writing mechanics. These aspects of the essay writing are challenging for learners, as they lack the skills needed in writing a good essay. While the traditional teaching method has not been effective in the teaching and learning of the above areas in essay writing, the researcher is interested in finding out the effects virtual classroom will have if used in teaching students essay writing skills. Thus, the use of virtual classroom in teaching title of an essay writing, construction and development of good sentences that guide what the writer produces in each paragraph, organization of paragraphs in text, appropriate use of language and writing mechanics, are the main motivating factors that drive the conduct of this study, with the aim of finding out the effects of the use of virtual classroom in delivering these skills to learners in private Senior Secondary Schools, Abuja, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

The purpose of this study is to examine the effect of virtual classroom on the performance in expository essay writing among in private Senior Secondary Schools students in Abuja, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are to:

3. find out the mean performance scores of students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of content using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom;
4. examine the mean performance scores of students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of language expression using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom;
5. evaluate the mean performance scores of students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of organization using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom; and
6. examine mean performance scores of students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of mechanical using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom.

Research Questions

1. What are the mean performance scores of students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of content using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom?
2. Does any mean gain score exist in the performance of students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of language expression using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom?
3. Will there be any mean gain score in the performance of students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of organization using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom?
4. What are mean performance scores of students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of mechanical accuracy using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in mean performance scores between students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of contents using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom.
2. There is no significant difference in mean performance scores between students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of language expression using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom.
3. There is no significant difference in mean performance scores between students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of organization using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom.
4. There is no significant difference in mean performance scores between students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of mechanical accuracy using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom.

Methodology

The quasi-experimental research design was used in this study. The experimental group were taught expository essay using virtual classroom (WhatsApp), while the control group were taught using physical classroom. The population comprised of all the eleven thousand, four hundred and seventy-five (11,475) private Senior Secondary School II students during the academic session in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. Two private Senior Secondary Schools were randomly sampled from

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the population, while the purposive intact class sampling technique was used to sample the students. The study adopted Structured Expository Essay Writing Test (SEEWT) as its instrument for data collection. The instrument was piloted using split-half test method. The scores of the reliability test were analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient (PPMCC), and the instrument has a reliability index of 0.98. The simple percentage, mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and t-test to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Additionally, the instrument was administered to the students by two research assistants, who were trained to carry out the function.

Results

Research Question 1

What are the mean performance scores of students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of content using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom?

Table 1: Mean score of students taught expository essay in the treatment of content using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom.

Group	Method	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain Score
			\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD	
Experimental Control	Virtual Classroom	26	6.21	2.32	16.88	2.64	10.77
	Physical Classroom	29	6.61	2.78	9.57	1.65	3.87
Mean Difference			0.50		6.41		6.71

Table 1 reveals the mean scores of both experimental and control groups which are insignificant. However, the post-test result showed that the students in the experimental group had a mean score of 16.88 with standard deviation of 2.64, while the control group had a mean score of 9.57 with standard deviation of 1.65. The result also shows that the experimental group had a mean gain of 10.77 while those in the control group had a mean gain of 3.87. The table showed that experimental group had higher and increasing mean effect of 6.71 on the students' performance in the content of essay writing. Therefore, students in the experimental group have outperformed those students in the control group.

Research Question 2

Does any mean gain score exist in the performance of students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of language expression using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom?

Table 2: Mean score of students taught essay writing in the treatment of language expression using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom

Group	Method	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain Score
			\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD	
Experimental Control	Virtual Classroom	26	5.93	2.03	17.58	3.69	11.66
	Physical Classroom	29	5.47	2.19	10.68	2.29	5.23
Mean Difference			0.49		6.93		6.45

Table 2 indicates the mean scores of both experimental and control groups. There is similar mean score for both groups in the pre-test, but for the post-test result, students in the experimental group had a mean score of 17.58 with standard deviation of 3.69, and the control group had a mean score of 10.68 with standard deviation of 2.29. The result also reveals that the experimental group had a mean gain of 11.66 while those in the control group had a mean gain of 5.23. The table therefore showed that the experimental group had higher and increasing mean effect of 6.45 on the students' performance in essay writing in the treatment of language expression. This showed that students in the experimental group have performed better than students in the control group in language expression of essay writing.

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Research Question 3

Will there be any mean gain score in the performance of students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of organization using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom?

Table 3: The mean performance scores of students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of organization using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom

Group	Method	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain Score
			\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD	
Experimental	Virtual Classroom	26	5.58	2.82	17.22	2.45	10.68
	Physical Classroom	29	5.67	3.25	9.49	2.17	3.87
Mean Difference			0.09		7.72		7.79

Table 3 shows the mean scores of both experimental and control groups which are insignificant. However, the post-test result shows that the students in the experimental group had a mean score of 17.22 with standard deviation of 2.45, while the control group had a posttest mean score of 9.49 with standard deviation of 2.17. The result also shows that the experimental group had a mean gain of 10.68 while those in the control group had a mean gain of 3.87. The table showed that experimental group had higher and increasing mean effect of 7.72 on the students' essay writing in the treatment of language expression. This showed that students in the experimental group performed better than students in the control group.

Research Question Four: What are mean performance scores of students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of mechanical accuracy using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom?

Table 4: The mean performance scores of students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of mechanical accuracy using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom

Group	Method	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain Score
			\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD	
Experimental	Virtual Classroom	26	5.94	2.04	18.59	3.69	11.65
	Physical Classroom	29	5.46	2.18	10.67	2.28	5.22
Mean Difference			0.48		6.92		6.44

Table 4 indicates the mean scores of both experimental and control groups. While there is similar mean score for both groups in the pre-test, the post-test result indicated that the students in the experimental group had a mean score of 17.59 with standard deviation of 3.69, and the control group had a mean score of 10.67 with standard deviation of 2.28. The result also indicates that the experimental group had a mean gain of 11.65 while those in the control group had a mean gain of 5.22. The table therefore showed that the experimental group had higher and increasing mean effect of 6.44 on the students' performance in expository essay in the treatment of mechanical accuracy. This indicated that students in the experimental group have performed better than students in the control group in mechanical accuracy of expository essay.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in mean performance scores between students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of contents using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom.

Table 5: t-test analysis of mean score performance of Experimental and control group

Group	Method	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t-value	P-value	Decision
Experimental	Virtual Classroom	26	17.58	3.69	115	15.229	.000	Rejected
	Physical Classroom	29	10.68	2.29				

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Table 5 shows that there was a significant difference in mean score performance between the experimental group taught expository essay in the treatment of content using virtual classroom, and the control group taught without it, as $t = 15.229$, $df = 115$, $P .000 < 0.05$. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in mean performance scores between students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of contents using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom is rejected for the alternate.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in mean performance scores between students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of language expression using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom.

Table 6: t-test analysis of mean score performance of Experimental and control group

Group	Method	N	X	SD	Df	t-value	P-value	Decision
Experimental	Virtual Classroom	26	17.58	3.69	115	12.214	.000	Rejected
	Physical Classroom	29	10.68	2.29				

Table 6 shows that there was a significant difference in mean score performance between the experimental group taught essay writing in the treatment of language expression using virtual classroom and the control group taught without it as $t = 12.214$, $df = 115$, $P .000 < 0.05$. Thus, the hypothesis which state that there is no significant difference in essay writing performance scores between students taught language expression in essay writing using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom is rejected for the alternate.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference in mean performance scores between students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of organization using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom.

Table 7: t-test analysis of mean score performance of Experimental and control group

Group	Method	N	X	SD	Df	t-value	P-value	Decision
Experimental	Virtual Classroom	26	17.22	2.45	115	16.171	.000	Rejected
	Physical Classroom	29	9.49	2.17				

Table 7 shows that there was a significant difference in mean score performance between the experimental group taught essay writing in the treatment of organization using virtual classroom and the control group taught without it as $t = 16.171$, $df = 115$, $P .000 < 0.05$. Thus, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in essay writing performance scores between students taught using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom in organization of essay writing was rejected for the alternate.

Hypothesis 4

There is no significant difference in mean performance scores between students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of mechanical accuracy using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom.

Table 8: t-test analysis of mean score performance of Experimental and control group

Group	Method	N	X	SD	Df	t-value	P-value	Decision
Experimental	Virtual Classroom	26	18.59	3.69	116	17.165	.000	Rejected
	Physical Classroom	29	10.69	2.28				

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Table 8 shows that there was a significant difference in mean score performance between the experimental group taught essay writing in the treatment of mechanical accuracy using virtual classroom and the control group taught without it as $t = 17.165$, $df = 116$, $P .000 < 0.05$. Thus, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in essay writing performance scores between students taught using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom in mechanical accuracy of essay writing was rejected for the alternate.

Discussion of Findings

Based on the analysis of the above data, the study found that virtual classroom is significant on students' performance in essay writing in the treatment of content, language expression, organization and mechanical accuracy in private Senior Secondary Schools, Abuja. This is justifiable based on the mean scores realized in the test administered to students taught content, language expression, organization and mechanical accuracy of essay writing. The study of Davids (2013), Paulinus, Idongesit, and Nkasiobi (2016), Etukakpan, Maduka, and Christopher (2021) and Talal (2021) whose studies on the use of virtual classroom on the teaching writing and students' performance also agree with the above finding. This therefore justifies that the use of virtual classroom in the teaching of essay writing and students' performance is significant. Additionally, the finding of this study also agrees with the findings of Anabela, Debora, Deborah, and Susan (2022), Eka (2023), and Godswill, Ngozi, Cajetan, and Ngozi (2023), as their findings also indicated significant effect of virtual classroom on students' performance in various aspects of writing in English language. Therefore, the use of virtual classroom should be promoted by concerned educational stakeholder for in the teaching of essay writing.

Conclusion

The importance of the use virtual classroom in teaching essay writing cannot be over emphasized as the findings of this study has justified its significant effect in teaching content, language expression, organization and mechanical accuracy as well as students' performance in the above areas. Based on this evidence as provided in the analysis of the study, the study therefore concludes that virtual classroom is effective in teaching essay writing and as its gives significant effect on students' academic performance.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

8. Government and school management should ensure that adequate technological materials for the use of virtual classroom and competent teachers are provided for the effective teaching of the content of essay writing to students. Teachers should also be supervised on their use of virtual classroom in teaching the content of essay writing, and students' response to the teaching processes should be monitored for effectiveness.
9. The teaching of language expression of essay writing via virtual classroom should be stimulating, as to engaging all learners in participating in the teaching and learning processes for effectiveness.
10. Teachers should ensure that appropriate examples and learning materials are provided for the teaching and learning of organization of essay writing. Thus, emphasis should be place of the unity of paragraph (cohesion and coherence).
11. Finally on mechanical accuracy, the teaching of grammatical components, with emphasis on punctuation marks as well as their use in achieving a good written essay should be inculcated in learners via virtual classroom.

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Forest Regulation and Forest Conservation ... (Unimtiang, et. al., 2023) DOI:

Forest Regulation and Forest Conservation Practice Among Farmers in Boki Local Government Area, Cross River State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The main purpose of this study was to investigate forest regulation and forest conservation practice among farmers in Boki Local Government Area, Cross River State, Nigeria. To give direction to this study, two research questions and null hypotheses respectively guided the study. The review of related literature was carried out base on specific objectives of the study. Survey research design was adopted for the study. The targeted population was all the farmers in Boki Local Government Area, Cross River State in 2023 farming season. Multi-stage sampling techniques was adopted in selecting six hundred and sixty-seven (667) respondents used for the study. twenty (20) items four-point scale questionnaire titled “education for forest regulation and forest conservation Questionnaire” (FRFCQ) was used for data collection. To test the hypotheses formulated for the study, simple linear regression statistical tool was used for data analysis. The hypotheses formulated was tested at .05 level of significance. The result of the finding revealed that forest regulation significantly influences forest conservation in Boki Local Government Area in Cross River State. Based on the findings it was recommended that forest regulation should be expanded and intensified in Boki Local Government Area in Cross River State.

Keywords: sustainable, forest management practices, forest conservation, farmers, Boki Local Government Area

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Introduction

Ministry of Lands and Environment noted that forest ecological system effect or degradation is created by the consolidation of an effectively substantial and expanding human populace, constantly expanding monetary development or per capita fortune and the application of asset exhausting and polluting technology. It occurs when forest natural resources are depleted and the forest environment is compromised in the form of extinction or drastic reduction of forest species, pollution in air, water and soil, and rapid growth in population of unwanted forests species (Ministry of Lands and Environment, 2022). Forest degradation is one of the largest threats that are being faced by Cross River State and Boki Local Government Area today. The United Nations International Strategy for Disaster Reduction characterizes forest degradation as the lessening of the limit of the earth to meet social and forest destinations, and needs. Forest degradation can happen in a number of ways. At the point when forests environments are wrecked or common assets are exhausted, the forest [environment](#) is considered to be corrupted and harmed (FAO, 2020). [Forest issues](#) can be seen by long term ecological effects, some of which can demolish whole environments (climate change). A forest is a unique unit and incorporates all the living and non-living components that live inside it. Plants and creatures are evident parts of the forest environment, but it also includes the things on which they depend on, for example, streams, lakes, and soils. The forest is to be protected without compromise from all stakeholders. Despite the sustainable forests management practices in place; in 2019 Cross River State had the highest rate of deforestation in the world, according to the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO, 2020). In 2005 12.2%, the equivalent of 11,089,000 hectares had been deforested in Nigeria. Between 2000 and 2020, Nigeria lost an average of 409,700 hectares of forest every year equal to an average annual deforestation rate of 2.38%. Between 2005 and 2019, in total Nigeria lost 35.7% of its forest cover, or around 6,145,000 hectares (FAO, 2020).

Forest ecosystems are important habitats for a vast number of species worldwide. These ecosystems are degrading faster than they are regenerating, due to the increased demand for natural resources and the continued application of non-sustainable practices by humans. In order to protect these important ecosystems, the designation of protected areas (PAs) has become the primary policy tool for forest conservation and the provision of ecosystem services nowadays. According to the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) approximately 10% of forests across the world are officially designated as protected areas (Dudley & Phillips, 2006). Presently, the country has different policies within sub-sectors of agriculture and the forest involved in land use. There is need for integrated planning and management of all our rural development programmes. This will reduce conflicts and guarantee better resources use. With the assistance of some international organizations including the FAO, World Bank, UNDP, ADB, DFID (ODA), Ford Foundation, etc. strategies have been formulated and developed for effective sustainable management of a number of forest reserves in the country (FAO & UNDP, 2021). Gizachew, Rizzi, Shirima and Zahabu (2020) found that most PAs were effective in reducing deforestation rates, even if there were important pressures in their surrounding lands. BujoczekZieba and Bujoczek (2000) found that the quality of forest habitats under strict and active protected status in the regions was enhanced relative to that of managed forests. Maruna, Crnčević and Milojević (2019) describe the historical context of forest planning and management processes and discuss how the concept of land use planning for urban forest protection was established in the country through the critical re-assessment of the institutional structure of land use planning in a post-socialist environment. In the Western Terai Region of Nepal, timber harvesting increased substantially three years after scientific forest management implementation in community forestry systems, even if mean timber volume was reduced for community forest users Maruna, Crnčević and Milojević (2019).

Despite the increase in policy initiatives such as those mentioned above, meeting biodiversity conservation targets remains problematic, as many areas face continuous pressures. In the study by Wade, Austin, Cajka, Lapidus, Everett, Galperin, Maynard and Sobel (2020) the authors estimated global trends in tree cover loss between 2001 and 2018. They found a remarkable loss of forested land inside PAs, and a similar pattern in temporal trends in forest loss in PAs compared to those of global forest loss. These challenges are expected to be further aggravated by the COVID-19 pandemic. The actual long-term impacts of the pandemic on environmental and socio-economic issues are expected to be extremely complex and will take several years to be thoroughly explored. A collaborative study by researchers and practitioners from European PAs is presented McGinlay, Gkoumas, Holtvoeth, Fuertes, Bazhenova, Benzoni, Botsch, Martel, Sánchez and Cervera (2020), with some initial findings on how COVID-19 has caused an increase in PA visitors, accompanied by an increase in irresponsible behaviours bringing additional challenges for management authorities. Laktić, Žiberna, Kogovšek, Pezdevšek and Malovrh (2020) analyze links and relations between different stakeholders during participatory planning processes of the Natura 2000 management program in Slovenia. A main direction proposed by the authors is that groups of stakeholders from different institutions and sectors must be further empowered in order to be included in such processes. Similar issues emerged in the study by Kimengsi, Bhusal, Aryal, Fernandez, M.V.B.C. Owusu, Chaudhary and Nielsen (2019) in Nepal; the authors

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highlighted the need to include underprivileged groups in co-management processes in the Annapurna Conservation Area who remain highly motivated to participate despite the current top-down approach. Furthermore, in the study by Pezdevšek Malovrh, Paletto, Posavec, Dobšinská, Đorđević, Marić, Avdibegović, Kitchoukov, Stijović and Trajkov (2019); the authors identify a lack of stakeholder engagement and participation as one of the main parameters negatively influencing the implementation of conservation policies in several EU and non-EU countries. In close relation to engagement and empowerment, trust in specific entities and organizations is another important factor that needs to be taken into consideration.

In the study by Referowska and Chodak (2020); the authors found that levels of trust towards foresters were high, leading to a favourable opinion for this specific group to have a more leading role in nature conservation policies. Forests provide a variety of goods to local communities such as timber, food, fuel, and pharmaceutical products. Nevertheless, the equitable distribution of benefits derived from forests among users remains unclear. In a study conducted in the Western Terai Region of Nepal, most of produced timber was distributed among middle- and high-class groups, while poor households had very limited access to these resources Bhusal, Karki and Kimengsi (2020). In Mount Cameroon National Park, near the Kayang forest, Akonwi and Majory (2020) found through an ethnographic study, that state regulations restricted to some extent access to natural resources for local communities. However, the authors identified alternative unofficial pathways, which allowed customary practices to take place, and access to resources was possible for local communities via informal processes. Common management activities aimed at reducing high deforestation rates in large PAs and connecting these areas through restored forest corridors at the landscape level were proposed as a main priority in the study by Gizachew, Rizzi, Shirima and Zahabu (2020) in connectivity of forests with corridors was also proposed to promote long-term persistence of sacred church forests in northern Ethiopia by increasing species dispersal rates and reducing human disturbance within forests Woods, Bitew Mekonnen, Baez-Schon, Thomas, Scull, Abraha Tsegay and Cardelús, (2020). Restoration of the structure and composition of remaining forest habitats and afforestation were proposed to be adopted in the Mississippi Alluvial Valley, as a small percentage of the forest patch area was currently protected (Elliott, Mini, McKnight and Twedt, 2020).

Following a more holistic approach, Ola and Benjamin [22] demonstrated in Western Africa, that both environmental protection and economic goals must be combined before effective environmental protection can take place. However, poverty alleviation targets must not be completely ignored, as many West Africans rely on forest and catchment resources to support their livelihoods (Ola and Benjamin, 2019). Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (FMARD, 2010), is in charge of articulating Agricultural Land Use and Practices Policy for the country. There is no Land Use Policy in the country. There is however, a Land Use Act. States are being encouraged to derive their legislation from the national framework. A national forest and wildlife law is being developed with the involvement of all stakeholders. There is no forest certification practice in the country. However, public involvement on forest certification is being articulated in the proposed revised policy which will encourage private sector and NGO participation. It is being proposed that a National Working Group (NWG) on Sustainable Forest Management (SFM) and certification be set up to finalize the criteria or indicators for Sustainable Forest Management in the country. The following activities promote the use of forest products in place of products made of non-renewable materials: low tariff on wood products, reasonable pricing of wood products, under valuation of forest products, high cost of non-renewable materials especially energy and value system and traditional beliefs - preference in taste for food/delicacy prepared with fuelwood (Ola and Benjamin, 2019).

Nigeria started implementing the National Forestry Action Plan (NFAP) in 1990 with the assistance of FAO and a grant of US \$690,000 from UNDP. In order to ensure the greatest commitment at the highest and at all levels of Government, the National Advisory Council, assisted by a National Technical Committee, was inaugurated in 1994. The project was concluded in 1995 and the final NFAP report has been submitted. The next stage is to use the report to canvass for international funding from donors to implement the action plans (FAO, 2020). From literature reviewed, forest degradation has different and diverse influence on agricultural productivity. For instance, high intensity of heat resulted to discomfort for both the farmer and farm resources. Few related studies on aware creation and forest conservation have been conducted in other parts of the world and they varied in their methodology. To the best of the researcher's knowledge, none of such studies focused on forest regulation and awareness creation were conducted in Nigeria or Cross River State. This study was therefore meant to fill the gap.

Climate change has increased the region temperature, reduced the air quality we breath, pollute water, caused flooding, changes in seasons, infrastructural decay; increased pests and diseases, reduced soil fertility and reduced crops yields over the years and farmers are blaming the supreme being for the changes in climate and seasons while they keep on exploring and exploiting the earth's resources. Unless climate change is tackled, all the "best efforts" to help this great country, to come out of food shortages could be to no avail. One of the biggest threats is growing climate unpredictability, which makes subsistence farming difficult. This study posed the following questions: are farmers aware that the earth's temperature is rising because of some of their

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farming activities?, are awareness strategies or sources of information that farmers in Boki Local Government Area obtain information are assessable to farmers?, are the farmers' in Boki Local Government Area applying the forest regulation, awareness creation to aid forest conservation?, does the sustainable forest regulation applied by government improve farm productivity and environmental safety?

Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study is to investigate forest regulation and forest conservation practice among farmers in Boki Local Government Area, Cross River State, Nigeria.

Research Question

The following research questions was raised to guide the study:

To what extent does forest regulation influence farmers' forest conservation practice?

Hypothesis

The following hypothesis was formulated to guide the study:

Forest regulation has no significant influence on farmers' forest conservation practice.

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study is the descriptive survey research design. Ndiyo (2005) defined survey research as a scientific experiment conducted on a large scale on a defined population to determine some desirable characteristic of a population. Survey research is research that is directed towards determining the nature of the situation that exists at the time of investigation. He describes that it is a type of research that studies large and small population by selecting and studying sample chosen from the population to discuss the relative incidence distribution, interrelation of sociological variables.

Survey research designs is therefore useful for opinion and attitude studies. The research area for this study was the entire Boki Local Government Area of Cross River State. Boki Local Government Area on the north is bounded with Boki Local Government Area, on the South with Etung Local Government Area, on the East by Ikom/Ogoja Local Government Area. The local government lies between longitude 8°22'E and 9°12'E of the Greenwich meridian and latitudes 5°5'N to 6°15'W of the equator. The local government area is known for promotion of cultural festival and tourist attraction that sustains the local government policy for peaceful co-existence among members of the society, talents discovery and arts exhibition.

Educationally, primary, post primary schools abounds in Boki Local Government Area. Boki Local Government Area land and forest are fertile for the cultivation of crops such as yams, cassava, groundnut, palm oil and palm wine. Travelling across the local government area, most communities display the stereotype of crops produced as a heritage that must be presented which encourages individuals to be productive citizens. The population of the study comprises all the farmers in Boki Local Government Area, Cross River State. There are sixteen thousand, seven hundred and thirty (16730) registered farmers in Boki Local Government Area, Cross River State during the 2022/2023 farming season. Female farmers dominate the population in the research area with 9030 while the males are 7700. The researchers adopted multi-stage sampling techniques to select the sample for this study. Simple random sampling again will be used to select wards used while accidental sampling technique will be used to administer the instruments to the number of subjects used as sample. To do this, names of Wards in Boki Local Government (stratum) will be written each in piece of paper, folded and put in a container and properly shuffle together. Those that picked yes will be used as respondents in the study while those that picked no will be dropped.

The sample size for this study was 667 male and female farmers from six (6) wards in Boki Local Government, Cross River State during the 2022/2023 farming season. The number of farmers selected was to obtain adequate representative samples of farmers from the Local Government Areas. All the selected wards in the LGA were used to ensure equal representation in the study. Out of the respondents selected for the study, 343 are female while 324 are male respectively. The instruments used for data collection was a set of survey questionnaire called "Forest Regulation and Forest Conservation Practice (FRFCPQ)". The questionnaire was divided into three sections A, B and C. Section A focused on the personal data of the farmers such as sex, age, local government area of farmer, educational qualification. Section B elicited information on the various climate change awareness strategies under studies while section C measure mitigation measures among farmers. To ensure the extent to which the instrument measured what it purports to measure, the Forest Regulation and Forest Conservation Practice (FRFCPQ) was developed by the researcher through extensive literature review. The instrument was first given to two lecturers in the department of Social Science Education to scrutinize for item relevance to the variables under consideration. While some items were merged few others were re-written for inclusion in the instrument as a result of the scrutiny. The instrument was validated by two experts in measurement and evaluation and finally it was examined by the project supervisor.

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The instrument was giving to experts in measurement and evaluation for validation. Finally, the supervisor certified the face and content validities of the instrument, coverage, appropriateness and consistency with the blue print of the instrument will be certified by the supervisor.

To ascertain the reliability of the instrument, a trial test was conducted in Akankpa LGA on 50 farmers drawn from the population who are not members of the sample to be used for the study. The single test reliability method was adopted. In this approach, the instrument was administered to the sample. The responses from the administration were correlated using Crombach alpha Coefficient statistic. The Cronbach alpha coefficient results showed a reliability coefficient ranging from 0.676 to 0.732 which indicated that the instrument was reliable enough to be used for this study. The researcher with the help of research assistant carryout the administration of the questionnaire in all the wards that were selected to participate in the study. There was prior notice given to all the heads of the villages selected notifying them about the researcher's intention to visit their village. The instrument was administered on the sample group under the closed supervision of the researcher and research assistants. The research assistants were trained of the techniques involved in the administration of the instruments. There are therefore asked to ensure individual farmers' concentration and also prevent exchange of information and discussion of any form among the subjects. Six hundred and sixty-seven (667) copies of questionnaire were administered, but six hundred and fifty-two (652) were properly filled and returned. The researcher developed a key, which served as a guide for coding the data collected for, analysis. The items on the questionnaire were sorted based on the variables measured. The total number of the responses ticked (✓) in each of the section covering all the variables under the study was added. The total scores for each section were recorded against these variables. Linear regression statistical technique will be use in the analysis. These scores will be recorded on the blank column as indicated by the researcher.

Results

Hypothesis 1

Forest regulation has no significant influence on farmers' forest conservation practice.

Table 1: Simple linear regression analysis of forest regulation and forest conservation practice among farmers (N = 652)

Model	R	R ²	Adj.R ²	Std error of estimate	
1	.180	.033	.031	4.16558	
Source of variance	SS	Df	MS	F	Sig
Regression	379.446	1	379.446	21.869	.000
Residual	11278.830	650	17.352		
Total	11658.276	651			

$p < .05$, $F = 21.869$; $df = 1, 650$,

The independent variable in this hypothesis is forest regulation while the dependent variable is forest conservation among farmers. Simple linear regression statistical tool was used for data analysis because both independent and dependent variables are measured continuously. The result of this analysis is presented in Table 1. The result of analysis presented in Table 1 showed that the predictor or independent variable (forest regulation) significantly influence the predicted variable (forest conservation among farmers). The predictor variable accounted for only 3.3% of the variance in forest conservation among farmers in Boki Local Government Area, Cross River State. This showed a very weak relationship between the predictor and predicted variables. Furthermore, the regression ANOVA revealed there was a moderate significant positive influence of forest regulation on forest conservation among farmers $F(1, 650) = 21.869$; $p < .05$. Based on this result, it was revealed that the more the forest regulation provided for local farmers, the better the conservation practices they would adopt to cope with the harsh effects of climate change in the localities. Again, if the forest regulation decline, the conservation practices adopted by farmers will also decline in the area of this study.

Discussion of findings

This section focuses on the discussion of the findings obtained in the study based on each hypotheses formulated to guide the study. The finding from analysis and testing of hypothesis one showed that the null hypothesis was upheld. This implied that forest regulation significantly influences forest conservation practice among farmers in Boki Local Government Area, Cross River State. This could be based on the assumption that there are very low forest regulations provided in the study

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area or that most forest regulation do not cover forest conservation practices among farmers in the study area. It is predicted that if the level of forest regulation increase, farmers will increasingly adopt positive conservation practices that would enable them cope with the effects associated with changes in climate. The finding of this study is in line with the finding of Dudley and Phillips (2006) which revealed that in order to protect these important ecosystems, the designation of protected areas (PAs) has become the primary policy tool for forest conservation and the provision of ecosystem services nowadays. According to the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) in Dudley and Phillips (2006) approximately 10% of forests across the world are officially designated as protected areas.

Conclusion

Forest management practices have become increasingly obvious especially in the area of this study. The need for people especially the rural inhabitants to develop forest conservation practices has become paramount in order to cushion the harsh effects associated with such changes. Environmental awareness has been identified as a viable tool that can be utilized to sensitize and build capacity for forest management. It has therefore become an issue of utmost consideration among various stakeholders to brace up and empower the vulnerable with requisite support that would enable them cope with the effects experienced as a result of climate change. This is because an uninformed or poorly informed individual lives in uncertainty and cannot save the environment from further degradation and damage. Hence, the need to raise a citizenry that is aware of and capable of participating actively in solving environmental problem and preventing the occurrence of new ones at all times.

Recommendations

Based on the findings obtained in this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Forest regulation should be expanded and intensified in the study area in order to enable farmers developed better and improved forest conservation.
2. Awareness creation should be used more effectively in sensitizing and building the capacity of farmers to be able to cope with and adopt positive and forest conservation among farmers.

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Guidance and Counselling: Panacea for Effective Classroom Delivery among Female Secondary School Students in Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper gives a qualitative analysis of guidance and counselling: panacea for effective classroom delivery among female secondary school students in Nigeria. The teaching profession is a profession in which the tutor needs to attain certain level of proficiency or expertise in order to deliver in the classroom effectively. This implies that the classroom holds a very important place in any system of education which needs to be properly managed. The low participation of girls in formal education is a pointer to the fact that a good number of Nigerian women live in a state of extreme deprivation in spite of their need in the area of national development. The paper concludes that despite the impressive goals and objectives of professional educators and educational policy makers, female secondary school students still face hard times and go through a lot of constraints and delivery crisis which militates against their personal development. The paper suggested that more emphasis should be incorporated in the learning and delivery process of teaching by training and retraining of teachers and encouraging teachers to develop their instructional skills and modern teaching practices in order to make them efficient and effective in the classroom. The paper also suggested that counselling services should be offered to both teachers and students which will in turn help manage classroom crisis.

Keyword: Female, Secondary School, Classroom Delivery, Guidance and Counselling and Classroom Instruction.

Introduction

The teaching profession is an art in which the tutor needs to attain certain level of proficiency or expertise in order to deliver in the classroom effectively. This implies that the classroom holds a very important place in any system of education which needs to be properly managed. In modern day Nigeria, the classroom management practices are intended for teachers to provide the necessary supports to make sure students are really learning. But if the teachers lack the ability to control and deliver knowledge to the students it might lead to crisis in classroom which will in turn affect the classroom delivery. Ogunwuyi in Onuma and Nwankwo, (2017) contends that teacher education should be nationally adopted as an agent of change and stability to promote equity and quality as well as serve as a launching pad for sustainable human development. Classroom delivery determines what a person eventually becomes academically. This goes to prove how indispensable the provision of adequate, suitable and child-friendly classroom is for secondary school children to achieve their goals (Nwankwo, Omebe & Anikeze, 2019). This reveals that the classroom occupies a very important place in any system of education. It also implies the need for proper classrooms delivery. Osakwe in Nwankwo, Omebe and Anikeze, (2019) reported that a conducive classroom delivery is needed to promote students' academic achievement in secondary schools. Given the above situation, there is the need for proper management of the available classrooms in secondary schools for quality and sustainability in the system. The molding of a teacher entails the professional training of teachers towards the achievement and improvement of teachers in areas of instructional skills and modern teaching practices which make them efficient and effective in the classroom. From an academic point of view, teaching and learning can only happen in an orderly classroom (Ogbonnia, 2020). The quality of

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classroom delivery will depend on the knowledge, preparation of the lesson and motivation of the teacher which can be influenced positively by the supervisory performance of a school administrator.

In recent times, the widespread poor achievement of students in most subjects taught at the secondary school level in Nigeria have elicited so much attention. While a number of studies have attributed the scenario to student-related factors such as peer influence, study habits, self-esteem, socioeconomic status among others (Ekpoto et al, 2021; Ekpoto et al. 2022); school-related variables such as lack of qualified teachers, conventional teaching methods, conducive classrooms, laboratories as well as, a look at innovative teaching approach might bring about the desired result that appears to have eluded the educational system in Nigeria (Ekpoto, et al. 2022). Classroom instructional strategies employed by a teacher in classroom content delivery could make or mar the expected outcome of teaching-learning no matter how versed he/she might be in the subject concerned. Quite often, most teachers utilise lecture method. Lecture method is a traditional (conventional) chalk-talk method that involves teacher delivery facts, ideas or contents to students (Ezeudu et al 2014; Ekpoto, et al. 2022). It inspires routine memorization and regurgitation of ideas or facts (Ezeudu & Gbendu, 2020; Ekpoto, et al. 2022). Studies have shown that lecture method, although, suitable for large class sizes and quick coverage of curriculum contents, is teacher-dominated and ineffective in attracting students' attitude towards learning (Ezeudu et al, 2014; Abidoye, 2015). To avert the ugly scenario occasioned by the monotonous use of lecture method in secondary school classes in Nigerian schools, there is urgent need for teachers to switch to the use of other innovative teaching styles (Ekpoto, et al. 2022). Universally, education is seen as the mainstay for women development. It is a focal point around which the quick development of economic, political, sociological and human resources of any country is unraveled. The quality of education of any nation determines the development status of that particular nation. The World Conference on education for all in Hakimi, (2017) pointed out that education is a fundamental right of all people, women and men of all ages throughout the world. One of the major issues catching the attention of Nigeria today is that of the education of women and the girl-child. Women play big roles in the development of any nation, be it Nigeria or the Western world. It is common knowledge that the female sex in many countries are the victim of educational inequalities (Adekola & Kumbe, 2016). Education is one important tool often used to measure the development of any nation, through knowledge acquired by members of the society to help them maximize their abilities in our ever-changing world. The need for classroom delivery in the empowerment of the girl child in Nigeria cannot be over emphasized as the basis for Nigeria's development. Egbo (2013) explained that the total development of a child can only take place in an environment suitable for teaching and learning. It is in realization of the above that all educational services which can propel teaching and learning in schools are given prominent attention by educational planners. Counselling services are part of the school educational services. It is believed that guidance and counselling services in school will develop, assess and improve educational programmes; promote teaching and competence.

The education of girls has the ability to bring alive and upgrade traditional skills as well as build confidence in girls in their pursuit for upliftment. Education empowers female secondary school students by improving their quality of life. It is the starting point for women advancement in different fields of human endeavor. It is also the basic tool that should be given to girls in order to fulfill their role as full members of the society. United Nations Funds for Population Activities in Adekola and Kumbe, (2016) observed that more than half of the illiterates in the world are women especially in Africa. United Kingdom Department for International Development (DFID) in Adekola and Kumbe, (2016) also recorded that almost two thirds of the population of the world are females and this accounts for the two thirds of the over one billion people experiencing poverty. It further noted that in the Pacific, Southern Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa 83% girls do not go to school. The New Partnership for African Development [NEPAD] in Adekola and Kumbe, (2016) reported a tragic situation where over 50% of the population of women in Africa are illiterate in the turn of the 21st century when knowledge is of utmost importance. The United Nations Educational, Scientific, Cultural Organization (Adekola & Kumbe, 2016) equally recorded that; girls are 60% of the 300 million children of school age who are not in school.

Classroom Delivery Crisis

According to the 1999 Nigerian constitution section 18 which ensures all citizens irrespective of their race, sex or gender are guaranteed equal rights which reflect the nation's commitments to equality while the national policy of Education in Akinbi and Akinbi, (2015) stipulates that every Nigerian should have a right to equal educational opportunities. The low participation of girls in formal education is a pointer to the fact that a good number of Nigerian women live in a state of extreme deprivation in spite of their need in the area of national development. This has robbed most Nigerian women of the opportunity to contribute fully to national development (Haruna, 2015). If there is crisis or challenges in the classroom delivery among female secondary school students, it will affect the learning outcome of the students, and the intended outcome will not be

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achieved (Akinbi & Akinbi, 2015). Education is largely seen in Nigeria as an indispensable tool which will not only assist in meeting the nation’s social, political, moral, cultural and economic aspirations but will also inculcate in the individual knowledge, skills, dexterity, character and desirable values that will foster national development and self-actualization (Orji and Maekae, 2013). Education is an experience that has a formative impact on the mind, attitude, or physical ability of a person. It is the whole episode of experiences in life through which an individual learns something new through formal, informal and non-formal learning. Classroom delivery has to do with what the teacher does to promote or direct teaching and learning in a particular subject in a school. Classroom delivery entails the act of ensuring that organized teaching and learning is effective in the classroom. This means that the through effective organization of the lesson by preparation of lesson notes, collecting of teaching aids, using of teaching strategies and timely utilization of the equipment to corroborate the teaching are very crucial to the success of classroom delivery. The lack of effective instructional delivery will affect students’ learning experience, subject mastery and performance in the subject being taught (Uthman & Mohammed, 2018). Ayeni in Uthman and Mohammed, (2018) posited that there is a significant relationship between teachers’ qualifications and delivery, and between teachers’ teaching experience and delivery. The study concluded that teachers’ delivery can be enhanced with a good qualification and experience in teaching, while the challenges that teachers experience in the tasks of instructional inputs and curriculum delivery require effective capacity development during service, so as to improve the quality of teaching in secondary schools and the overall quality of the education system.

Female Secondary School Students classroom delivery and National Development

The role of women in the developmental drive of every society calls for their empowerment at all levels. Women in Nigeria are bound to be backward compared to their male counterparts due to marginalization from many areas of life. Roseline, Arikpo and Justin in Yusuf, (2013) opined that educating and empowering the female folk as a way of boosting their capacity to make choices will help in liberating them from poverty and also transform the choices made into desired actions and outcomes. For women to live a better life they need to access opportunities so the need for a successful classroom delivery without crisis cannot be over emphasized. The guidance counsellor also plays a deep role in different areas of their lives such as areas of social awareness, psychological and culturally based counselling, which will enable them have knowledge to transform the world to their advantage. A closer look at the pattern of classroom delivery crisis and female secondary school student’s participation in education in Nigeria reveals abysmal low levels, in spite of all the laudable goals and objectives of education, Nigerian women still face hard time and go through a lot of constraints and inhibitions which militate against their personal and national development from time in memorial (Nzulumike & Oli, 2015). Another challenge that teachers experience is the lack of exposure and limited accessibility to modern instructional facilities. Secondary schools especially in the rural areas do not have access to information communication technology (ICT) which could help improve the shortage of instructional materials. As the world operates as a global village and increase awareness on the use of modern scientific approach in teaching and learning processes in schools (Tety, 2016).

The enrolment of girls in schools and the sustainability of classroom delivery by teachers in Nigeria still need improvement. Some states in Nigeria do better than others in the aspect of girl child school enrolment as well as education delivery to the girl child. The increase and adequate enrolment of rural girls in both primary and secondary schools will help rural communities alleviate poverty as well as foster their development.

Primary and Secondary Education Enrolment Available Data from Federal Ministries of Education is Shown in the Table below.

Table 1: Primary and Secondary Education Enrolment Data

Year	2014	2015	2016
Rate of Enrolment of Primary School Age Girls	48.6 %	47.4%	47.5%
Rate of Enrolment of Primary School Age Boys	51.4%	52.6%	52.5%
Rate of Enrolment of Secondary School Age Girls	45.9%	46.5%	46.0%
About 54% of Boys Enrolled in Secondary School Between 2014 - 2015			
Enugu State had the Highest Per cent of Girls Enrolment in Secondary Schools in both 2014 -2015 (55.4%)			
Abia State had the Highest Per cent of Girls in Secondary Schools in 2016			
Kebbi State Recorded the Lowest Per cent of Girls in Secondary School in 2014,2015 and 2016 (29.5%)			

Source: National Bureau of Statistics, 2018.

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Class room delivery and its impact on women in Nigeria can be traced to the coming up of poverty alleviations programmes in the country as a way by which the Nigerian Government boost the economy (Ibharhokanrhowa, 2016). If women are not educated then the nation will not grow. Mothers play a big role in the development of any nation. Most of the countries with higher class room delivery attain reasonable development. Poverty elimination strategies became imperative in Nigeria, consequent upon the increasing rate of poverty among Nigerians after the Nigerian independence in 1960. Report has showed that incidence of poverty in Nigeria in 1960 was about 15 percent only but in 1980 it had grown to 28 percent and by 1985 the extent of poverty was about 46 per cent. In 1996, it was noted that poverty incidence in the country was 66 per cent or 76.6 million people from the Nigerian population of 110 million (Ibharhokanrhowa, 2016). The availability of infrastructural facility is one of the biggest challenges teachers face as a crisis in classroom delivery in secondary schools in Nigeria. Infrastructural Physical facilities play important role in teaching and learning especially at the secondary school age when the sense of reasoning is still developing (Uthman and Mohammed, 2018). Igbo in Uthman and Mohammed, (2018) discovered that the quality of student learning was related to the quality of classroom instruction. Also, Kinutai and Zachariah in Igbo in Uthman and Mohammed, (2018) discovered that the quality of student learning was related to the quality of classroom instruction. Also, Kinutai and Zachariah in Uthman and Mohammed, (2018) study found positive correlation between the instructional supervision and students' academic performance. The quality of classroom delivery will depend on the knowledge, preparation of the lesson and motivation of the teacher which can be influenced positively by the supervisory performance of the school administrator (Uthman & Mohammed, 2018).

The main concern of government should be the formulation of policies that will encourage human capital development to make students an asset that will drive the economic state of the nation to prosperity (Ekundayo, 2015; Ogbonnaya, 2020). The availability of adequate school building, classrooms, chairs and other facilities are necessary to the attainment of objectives of an educational system. However, the increase in secondary school enrolment does not have corresponding increase in infrastructural development in the secondary schools. A common scene at the secondary school environment is that of half completed or dilapidated and overcrowded classrooms lacking basic equipment and facilities with unsightly and unhygienic toilet. If the enrolment of girls is poor in secondary schools due to inadequate, facilities, lack of trained teachers and other factors it will in turn affect girl's enrolment in secondary schools. Education facilitates is essential for quality learning all through life among people of any age group. It plays an important role in career growth as well as in personal growth of every individual. Thus, effective classroom delivery plus intelligence is the true goal of education (Onwuka, 2014; Ogbonnaya, 2020).

Classroom delivery management practices

Classroom delivery management is a process involving planning, organizing, coordinating, motivating and controlling the actions of learners and materials in order to achieve instructional objectives (Adzongo & Olaitan, 2019). The art of classroom delivery management encompasses all the functions of a classroom teacher in instructional procedure. Such activities include lesson planning and presentation, organization of the classroom facilities, coordination of learning activities, management of instructional materials and leading by example (Nwankwo, 2014; Adzongo & Olaitan, 2019). Classroom management practices also refers to the tactics the teacher employs in the classroom for better teaching and learning (Nwankwo, Omebe & Anikeze, 2019). These tactics of organizing the students in the class include: having better seating arrangements, co-ordinating their activities, monitoring their behaviours, ensuring effective learning process, providing instruction through interactive communication, getting feedback from students, preparing and utilizing instructional materials in facilitating learning, maintaining discipline among learners, evaluating learning outcome, serving as a role model, reinforcing their performance through motivational techniques, giving clear and simple directions, among others. Osakwe (2014) refers to classroom management practices as the tactics or methods adopted by teachers to ensure decorum in the classroom and thus create a healthy and conducive atmosphere for learning. Therefore, classroom managers must be abreast with these effective techniques and practices for effective teaching to take place and quality to be assured in education in Nigeria. The classroom must be arranged properly to accommodate the students, seats and tables, instructional materials and so on. It is also the responsibility of the classroom teacher most especially in secondary schools to make sure that the students are monitored while instruction is on, maintain good teacher/student relationship, communicate effectively for better understanding, and most importantly, make good use of reinforcement to motivate the students for better performance (Nwankwo, Omebe & Anikeze, 2019). For a class room teacher to deliver effectively he/she have to create a safe and effective learning environment for his/her students' quality education. Therefore, teachers should know how to apply strategies that will help students learn (Nwankwo, Mathew & Christiana 2019). Arguing further Zuckerman, in Nwankwo, Mathew and Christiana (2019:107) noted some of these practices as:

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1. Good classroom arrangement. To manage the few facilities provided for students' usage.
2. Use and applying of incentives to motivate students and provide counselling services for those with deviant behaviours.
3. Make rules and regulations that are simple and understandable and be consistent in applying them.
4. Plan the lessons using the scheme of work as a guide, and present lessons from known to unknown facts.
5. Delegate specific responsibilities daily to students and request for regular update and reports from such students.
6. Treat the students' cases justly and equally without bias/partiality-set up a positive behaviour for rewards and punishment system.
7. The teacher should serve as a role model for the students to emulate.

Counselling and Classroom Delivery

Guidance and counselling is a tool that helps in informing children and reforming them and their perception from negative ideas that is planted in them by their peers, the environment they live as well as their experiences. Counselling is a helping process in which a counsellor helps a person learn, understand themselves and their environment and be in a position to choose the appropriate type of behaviours that will help them develop, progress, grow, ascend, mature and step up, educationally, vocationally and socio personally, (Egbo, 2013). Hence there is a need for counsellor to assist the girl child in developing their perception through effective counselling therapies and help them resolve challenges. The school counsellor is expected to be a role model to the students, handle short comings and proffer counselling to students by assisting them to take the most appropriate decisions in life. In counselling, learning through sustainable positive classroom delivery is concern with the assistance given to the individual learner in her educational development and help reduce classroom delivery crisis as well as the development of their social, personal, and career or occupational choice. Akinade in Ebizie and Enajedu, (2016) defines guidance and counselling as a process of helping an individual become fully aware of his/her self and the ways in which he is responding to the influences of his/her environment. The effectiveness of classroom delivery through counselling also plays a big role in reducing the challenges female secondary school students and their teachers face in achieving a fulfilled learning achievement without challenges (Haruna, 2015). The core of the uplifting of the girl child is the ability to use their capabilities and opportunities to expand their wants and ability to control their own destiny (UNU-WIDER, 2014).

Conclusion

The paper concludes that in spite of all the laudable goals and objectives of professional educators and educational policy makers, female secondary school students still face hard time and go through a lot of constraints and delivery crisis which militate against their personal and national development. The paper also concludes that early history of education in Nigeria revealed that woman lacked easy access to formal education. Availability of infrastructural facility is another challenge that teachers and students face in the learning process. It also noted that classroom delivery challenges will affect the learning outcome of the students, and the intended outcome will not be achieved. The paper also concludes that in counselling, learning through sustainable positive classroom delivery is concern with the assistance given to the individual learner in order to help reduce classroom delivery crisis as well as development of their social, personal, and career or occupational choice.

Recommendations

The paper recommends the following:

1. More emphasis should be incorporated in the learning and delivery process of teaching and learning by the training and retraining of teacher and encourage teachers to develop their instructional skills and modern teaching practices in order to make them efficient and effective in the classroom.
2. Adequate infrastructural facilities should be provided to female secondary school students and their teachers in order to facilitate a conducive learning environment.
3. Teachers should build good relationship and communicate effectively for better understanding and most importantly, make good use of reinforcement to motivate the students for better performance which will help in fostering an effective classroom delivery.
4. Guidance counsellors should address female secondary school student's needs, the counselling interventions will help eliminate subtle and complex situation that hinder the learning process.
5. Counselling services should be offered to both teachers and students which will in turn help manage classroom crisis.

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Impact of Continuous Professional Development on Academic Staff Performance in Sokoto State University, Sokoto, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study delved into the impact of Continuous Professional Development (CPD) on the job performance of academic staff at Sokoto State University in Northwest Nigeria, focusing on teaching, research, and community service functions. Utilizing a cross-sectional survey design, data were systematically gathered from 216 academic staff members through a structured questionnaire survey. Various descriptive and inferential statistics, including regression analysis, were employed. The findings underscored the significant positive impacts of CPD on teaching ($R=0.322$; $R^2=0.104$; $F=24.822$; $p=.000$) and community service ($R=0.309$; $R^2=0.096$; $F=22.662$; $p=.000$) performance, emphasizing a favorable correlation between professional development initiatives and these aspects of academic responsibilities. However, the research identified a statistically insignificant impact of CPD on research performance ($R=0.116$; $R^2=0.013$; $F=2.920$; $p=.089$) within the academic staff at Sokoto State University. Thus, the study concluded that while CPD significantly enhances teaching and community service proficiency, its influence on research performance appears inconsequential in this academic context. The research proposed recommendations to optimize CPD program effectiveness at Sokoto State University, explicitly addressing challenges associated with research activities. By providing nuanced insights into the varied impacts of CPD on academic responsibilities, this study contributes to targeted interventions and strategies for comprehensive professional development in the academic sphere.

Keywords: Continuous professional development, Job performance, Academic staff, Teaching, Research and Community Service

Introduction

In the rapidly evolving landscape of 21st-century higher education, the performance of academic staff emerges as a decisive factor influencing the quality of education and research. According to Okollo (2021), Nigeria, akin to many nations, grapples with an array of challenges in its higher education system, marked by escalating demand for education, diminishing government funding, burgeoning student populations, escalating competition in teaching and research, and swift technological advancements. The spotlight on Continuous Professional Development (CPD) as a catalyst for enhancing academic staff performance has intensified in this milieu. CPD, characterized by continual learning and skill enhancement, empowers academic staff to fulfill their teaching, research, and community service roles adeptly. Acknowledged for its potential to elevate job performance, augment competencies, and keep professionals abreast of the latest developments, CPD is pivotal in the dynamically evolving realm of higher education (Suliman et al., 2020). Sokoto State University, situated in Northwest Nigeria, encapsulates the challenges and opportunities confronting higher education institutions in the country, characterized by concerns related to academic staff performance, reluctance to engage in CPD activities, and a lack of empirical understanding of CPD's impact (Okollo, 2021). This study investigated the relationship between CPD and academic staff performance in teaching, research, and community service at Sokoto State University. It aimed to provide valuable insights into the nuanced dynamics of CPD's influence within this context. It ultimately furnishes evidence-based recommendations to enhance CPD practices and academic staff performance, aligning with the evolving demands and challenges of higher education in Nigeria.

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The theoretical underpinning of this study rested on the human capital theory, originating from the realms of human resource management and education. This theory posits that investments in education and training significantly contribute to an individual's productivity and overall human capital (Sean et al., 2023). Given the indispensable roles played by academic staff in knowledge dissemination, research, and community engagement, aligning their knowledge and skills through CPD initiatives seamlessly resonates with the central tenets of the human capital theory, leading to improved job performance and productivity (McCowan, 2019). Conceptually, the study navigated two pivotal constructs within its context: academic staff performance and Continuous Professional Development (CPD). Academic staff performance encompasses the proficient fulfillment of teaching, research, and community service responsibilities, evaluated based on various criteria, including lesson planning, lecture delivery, assessment, research project supervision, and community service initiatives (Apolot et al., 2018). On the other hand, CPD extends beyond traditional training and education activities, embracing diverse learning methodologies such as training workshops, seminars, conferences, and e-learning programs (Suliman et al., 2020). The study adopts a comprehensive conceptualization of CPD, emphasizing its encompassing nature, including all-natural learning experiences and consciously planned activities benefiting individuals, groups, or institutions. This perspective recognizes CPD as a continuous process empowering academic staff to acquire knowledge, skills, and emotional intelligence essential for professional thinking, planning, and educational practice (Ellen et al., 2022).

Contextually, the study unfolds within the unique characteristics, challenges, and objectives of Sokoto State University, established in 2009, to increase access to higher education and preserve the region's cultural heritage. Challenges faced by the institution include academic staff performance issues, reluctance to engage in CPD activities, low staff morale, and a lack of empirical data on the impact of CPD (Muftahu. et al., 2016). Approximately 60% of academic staff at the university hold positions below the rank of Lecture 1, underscoring the need to enhance the capabilities and competencies of academic staff (Muftahu. et al., 2016). The university has implemented policies to develop teaching skills, pedagogical innovation, and research competencies among its staff. Research activities at Sokoto State University encounter financial constraints due to limited funding, compelling academic staff to initiate and conduct research with restricted resources. Community service, a university's core function, necessitates active engagement from academic staff to benefit the broader society (Muftahu. et al., 2016). The literature review contextualizes the study by reviewing previous scholarship on the link between CPD and staff performance in higher educational institutions. Noteworthy studies, such as those by Wati (2011), Blessing and Uzochukwu (2021), and Ozurumba and Amosoumo (2015), underscore the significance of CPD in enhancing the performance of academic staff. However, these studies also emphasize the need for a more comprehensive exploration of the impact of CPD on different facets of teachers' performance. Thus, this study employed the human capital development theory to investigate its effect on the teaching performance of academic staff at Sokoto State University.

Furthermore, the study aligned with Kasule et al. (2016) research, emphasizing the importance of professional development activities in enhancing job performance among teaching staff. The literature also highlights the role of human resource management (HRM) practices in building organizational culture and enhancing academic staff effectiveness. Effective evaluation methods, technological integration, and CPD programs are recognized as crucial factors in improving teaching quality, according to various studies such as Roberto (2022) and Peraz et al. (2018). Implementing effective evaluation practices and emphasizing comprehensive CPD programs emerge as critical elements for fostering a culture of continuous improvement among university academic staff. Studies by scholars like Ozurumba and Amosoumo (2015 and Ayedun et al. (2021) underlined the importance of enhancing teaching methods, pedagogical knowledge, and technological proficiency while stressing the necessity of establishing national standards to guide the professional development of academic staff. Overall, the literature underscores the need for well-structured, comprehensive CPD programs tailored to the specific needs of academic staff to improve their teaching performance and contribute to the overall development of higher education institutions.

The literature also delves into research exploring the impact of CPD on the research performance of academic staff in various higher education settings. For instance, Ozurumba and Amosoumo (2015) established a significant connection between staff development and academic staff productivity in terms of research. Blessing and Uzochukwu (2021) conducted a study on the influence of CPD on the research performance of academic staff in universities in Anambra State, emphasizing the need to understand the impact of CPD on the research performance of academic staff at Sokoto State University, located in the Northwestern part of the country. Research publications significantly contribute to the academic staff's productivity and career advancements, influencing social prestige and professional status. The proposed research aims to shed light on the challenges faced by academic staff in achieving research productivity at Sokoto State University, Nigeria. It underscores the role of CPD in overcoming challenges related to inadequate funding, lack of resources, and limited support, hindering research activities and productivity within the Nigerian education system. The literature also recognizes the existing gender disparities in research

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productivity. It stresses the importance of a comprehensive understanding of the various factors influencing academic staff development, including the impact of CPD programs and the broader institutional environment (Blessing & Uzochukwu, 2021). The proposed research seeks to underscore the significance of robust CPD initiatives in enhancing the research capabilities of academic staff and contributing to the advancement of the educational landscape in Nigeria.

Some scholars like Blessing and Uzochukwu (2021) have investigated the correlation between Continuous Professional Development (CPD) and the community service performance of academic staff in various settings. However, the limited attention given to community service due to time constraints is a prevalent issue. Studies emphasize that effective professional development should focus on enhancing knowledge bases such as content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge, and conceptual and procedural knowledge. Continuous Professional Development (CPD) enhances literacy standards, practical instruction, and academic performance. Quality professional development programs facilitate a shift in teaching practices and student outcomes. Capacity-building programs in Nigerian universities play a pivotal role in advancing the professional development of lecturers, enabling them to better cope with the demands of their roles. However, challenges such as inadequate funding, unstable academic calendars, corruption, weak leadership, security concerns, and insufficient infrastructure significantly impede the successful implementation of community service programs in these institutions (Okollo, 2021). The community service programs in Nigerian higher education institutions are designed to benefit surrounding communities and foster social and economic development. However, the challenges of inadequate funding, unstable academic calendars, corruption, weak leadership, insecurity, and insufficient infrastructure often impede the successful execution of these initiatives. Inadequate funding, particularly below UNESCO's (n.d.) recommended 26% budget allocation for education, has severely affected the capacity of universities to implement community service programs effectively. Moreover, the recurring issue of strikes, stemming from disagreements between the government and unions, disrupts the academic calendar and compromises the quality of education. Corruption within the administration further exacerbates these challenges, leading to mismanagement of funds and resources. Ineffective leadership and the persistent insecurity issue in Nigeria also hinder community service implementation, hampering educational institutions' overall development and performance.

In conclusion, this study aimed to illuminate the multifaceted dynamics in the relationship between CPD and academic staff performance at Sokoto State University. By investigating the impact of CPD on teaching, research, and community service performance, the study endeavored to provide evidence-based recommendations that can enhance CPD practices and academic staff performance within the unique challenges and opportunities of higher education in Nigeria.

Continuous Professional Development (CPD) is widely recognized for its crucial role in enhancing academic staff job performance in higher education institutions. Despite its significance in equipping new teachers and providing growth opportunities for experienced educators, there is a notable lack of comprehensive literature on the practical implementation and impact of CPD on academic staff performance, particularly in developing countries like Nigeria. Existing studies, such as those by Blessing and Uzochukwu (2021), Ofojebe and Chukwuma (2015), and Akuegwu et al. (2013), conducted within the Nigerian context, did not specifically focus on CPD practices in state universities or systematically investigate its direct effects on academic staff job performance. This knowledge gap posed challenges for evidence-based policy formulation, specifically tailored to the unique circumstances of state universities in Northwest Nigeria, including Sokoto State University. Consequently, this study aimed to address this gap by thoroughly investigating the practical implementation of CPD within Sokoto State University, unveiling the nuances of CPD practices and their direct impact on academic staff job performance.

Objectives of the study

The study aimed to achieve the following research objectives:

1. To evaluate the impact of CPD on the teaching performance of academic staff members at Sokoto State University.
2. To analyze the effect of CPD on the research performance of academic staff within Sokoto State University.
3. To assess the influence of CPD on the community service performance of academic staff at Sokoto State University.

Hypotheses

The study was set to test the following null hypotheses:

7. CPD does not significantly impact the teaching performance of academic staff at Sokoto State University.
8. CPD does not significantly impact the research performance of academic staff within the university.
9. CPD does not significantly impact the community service performance of academic staff at Sokoto State University.

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Methodology

This study utilized a cross-sectional survey research design based on Fraenkel and Wallen's framework, as Creswell (2018) outlined. The survey research approach involved gathering information from many respondents to formulate conclusions about the sampled population and generalize findings to the broader target population. A random sample of academic staff at Sokoto State University was employed to extrapolate results to the entire academic staff population. The cross-sectional design, as defined by Sefia (2016), involved collecting data at a single point, providing a cost-effective and expeditious study compared to longitudinal designs. Focusing on full-time academic staff, the study aimed to gather insights from 216 participants, categorized by academic ranks, to represent the diverse hierarchy within the academic staff. This specific focus on academic staff was justified, given their vital role in teaching, research, and community engagement at Sokoto State University. The study utilized Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) Table for sample size determination, resulting in a total sample size of 216 respondents from three faculties. The principal data collection method was a self-administered questionnaire, chosen for its efficiency in gathering data from a large sample within a short timeframe and its ability to ensure standardized responses. The positivist approach to data management involved IBM Statistics software for data processing and analysis, including descriptive statistics, t-tests, ANOVA, and multiple linear regression. In the next section, the results of the study are presented.

Results

Hypothesis 1

The first research hypothesis (H_1) was stated: "CPD does not significantly impact the teaching performance of academic staff at Sokoto State University". To explore this hypothesis, the researcher created an index to quantify continuous professional development (CPD) and another index to measure the teaching performance of academic staff (TP). Following this, a regression analysis was performed, with TP regressed against CPD. The results of this hypothesis test have been meticulously outlined and are presented in Tables 2(a) through (c). These tables provide a comprehensive breakdown and analysis of the statistical findings derived from investigating the association between continuous professional development and the teaching performance of academic staff.

Table 1: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.322 ^a	.104	.100	.19855

a. Predictors: (Constant), CPD

Table 2: ANOVA – Teaching Performance

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.978	1	.978	24.822	.000 ^b
	Residual	8.436	214	.039		
	Total	9.414	215			

a. Dependent Variable: Teachers' performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), CPD

Table 3: Coefficients - Teaching Performance

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.729	.133		20.552	.000
	CPD	.210	.042	.322	4.982	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Teachers' performance

Source of Data: Field

The results outlined in Table 1 illuminate the connection between continuous professional development and teaching performance scores. The data highlights a positive correlation with a coefficient of 0.332, indicating that an increase in continuous professional development corresponds to improving teaching performance. However, a deeper analysis is warranted to understand this relationship fully. The R square correlation index, with a value of 0.104, reveals that a one-unit change in

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continuous professional development leads to a 0.104-unit change in teaching performance, signifying a proportionate and positive impact on teaching performance for each incremental step in continuous professional development. Moving to Table 2), it provides an encompassing view by presenting the overall statistics of the model. This encompasses the F statistic and the overall significance of the model. With an F statistic value of 24.822, the model demonstrates its capability to elucidate the association between continuous professional development and teaching performance. The accompanying p-value of .000 signifies the statistical significance of the model. Thus, it can be confidently affirmed that continuous professional development significantly influences the teaching performance of academic staff.

Finally, Table 3 offers additional insights by identifying continuous professional development as a significant predictor of teaching performance. This assertion is corroborated by a standardized b-value of 0.322, a t-value of 4.982, and a p-value of .000. The standardized b-value signifies the strength and direction of the relationship. In contrast, the t-value indicates the statistical significance of this relationship. In this context, the positive b-value suggests a positive relationship, and the substantial t-value, alongside the very low p-value, further reinforces the idea that continuous professional development is a significant predictor of teaching performance.

Hypothesis 2

The study's second hypothesis (H2) was that “CPD does not significantly impact the research performance of academic staff within the university”. The researcher adopted a specific strategy to assess this hypothesis's credibility. They formulated an index, CPD, to quantify the degree of continuous professional development undertaken by academic staff. In parallel, they devised another index, RP, to measure the research performance of these academic staff members. Subsequently, the researchers performed a statistical analysis by regressing the RP index against the CPD index. This regression analysis sought to investigate the connection between continuous professional development and research performance among academic staff. The results of this hypothesis test, along with the relevant statistical findings, have been thoroughly documented in Tables 4, 5, and 6 within the research report. These tables serve as a comprehensive exposition of the outcomes, providing insights into whether continuous professional development has a significant impact on the research performance of academic staff, as postulated.

Table 4: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.116 ^a	.013	.009	.64638

a. Predictors: (Constant), CPD

Table 5: ANOVA - Research Performance

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1.220	1	1.220	2.920	.089 ^b
	Residual	89.410	214	.418		
	Total	90.630	215			

a. Dependent Variable: Research performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), CPD

Table 6: Coefficients - Research Performance

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.866	.432		4.317	.000
	CPD	.234	.137	.116	1.709	.089

a. Dependent Variable: Research Performance

Source of Data: Field

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The insights presented in Table 4 provide valuable information regarding the connection between continuous professional development and research performance scores. These findings reveal a positive correlation with a modest correlation coefficient of 0.116. To understand this relationship better, we examine the specific correlation index, denoted as R square, measured at 0.013. This figure suggests that a one-unit change in continuous professional development corresponds to a proportional 0.013-unit change in research performance. Shifting to Table 5, it offers insights into the overall model. Here, we encounter the F statistic, which furnishes us with crucial information concerning the significance of the entire model. Notably, the F statistic is 2.920, while the associated p-value is .089. This outcome suggests that continuous professional development has a meaningful impact on academic staff's research performance. However, the significance level falls just short of conventional thresholds. Lastly, Table 6 examines continuous professional development as a predictor of research performance. In this case, the standardized b-value is 0.116, the t-value is 1.709, and the corresponding p-value is .089. These results collectively indicate that while demonstrating a positive relationship, continuous professional development is not a statistically significant predictor of research performance within this context; thus, the null hypothesis was accepted and the alternate rejected.

Hypothesis 3

The third and last research hypothesis (H₃) stated, “CPD does not significantly impact the community service performance of academic staff at Sokoto State University.” To thoroughly investigate this hypothesis, the researcher employed a quantitative measure, CPD (Continuous Professional Development), to assess how academic staff engage in professional development activities. Simultaneously, another quantitative measure, CSP (Community Service Performance), was utilized to evaluate the academic staff's level of community service performance.

In order to assess the impact of continuous professional development (CPD) on community service performance (CSP), the researcher conducted a regression analysis. This analytical technique enables researchers to explore how changes in one variable (CPD) may predict changes in another (CSP). Essentially, it helps determine if there is a significant statistical connection between continuous professional development and community service performance among academic staff.

The outcome of the hypothesis test, aimed at scrutinizing the aforementioned null hypothesis, has been thoughtfully presented in Tables 7 through 9. These tables provide a comprehensive representation of the statistical results and their implications, shedding light on whether a significant association exists between academic staff's participation in continuous professional development and their subsequent performance in community service activities. The breakdown into Tables 7, 8, and 9 likely reflects various aspects or conditions under which this relationship was examined, providing readers with a nuanced understanding of the research findings. These findings are crucial in helping discern the potential impact of professional development activities on academic staff's broader community service endeavors.

Table 7: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.309 ^a	.096	.092	.46639

1. Predictors: (Constant), CPD

Table 8: ANOVA - Community Service Performance

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	4.929	1	4.929	22.662	.000 ^b
	Residual	46.550	214	.218		
	Total	51.479	215			

a. Dependent Variable: Community Performance b. Predictors: (Constant), CPD

Table 9: Coefficients - Community Service Performance

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.421	.312		4.554	.000
	CPD	.471	.099	.309	4.760	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Community Performance

Source of Data: Field

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The findings in Table 7 shed light on the correlation between continuous professional development and community service performance scores, revealing a positive association with a correlation coefficient of 0.309. Furthermore, the specific correlation index, R square, is recorded at 0.096, indicating that a unitary change in continuous professional development corresponds to a proportional 0.096-unit change in community service performance. Moving Table 8 provides comprehensive insights into the overall model, including the F statistic and its significance. This data unambiguously demonstrates that continuous professional development significantly influences the community service performance of academic staff, as evidenced by the substantial F-value of 22.662 ($p=.000$). Finally, Table 9 confirms that continuous professional development predicts teaching performance. This is emphasized by its standardized b-value of 0.309, a t-value of 4.760, and an exceptionally low p-value of .000, which underscore its robust impact on community service performance, thus making the null hypothesis rejected and the alternative hypothesis accepted.

Discussion of Findings

Teaching is the bedrock of higher education worldwide, profoundly influencing the quality of educational institutions. Recent research shows a strong link between Continuous Professional Development (CPD) and improved teaching performance among academic staff, affirming the significance of effective teaching in academic practice, as highlighted by Roberto in 2022. This pivotal teaching role meets societal expectations for professionalism and fosters an environment conducive to learning and professional growth. Acknowledged by Escribano et al. (2018) and others, teacher performance standards serve as crucial guidelines for educators, enabling effective knowledge dissemination and continual self-improvement. Insufficient pedagogical support can impede the assessment of student progress and hinder the identification of necessary changes in teaching practices, as Peraz et al. (2018) noted. Adapting to the evolving demands of globalization and standardization, universities must prioritize ongoing pedagogical and humanistic training for faculty members, as advocated by Garcia (2017) and Ustunluoglu (2016), to equip educators with the skills needed for effective student learning. Furthermore, the study stresses the importance of a comprehensive teacher performance evaluation process, echoed by Apolot et al. (2018) in validating teaching outcomes.

In the specific context of Sokoto State University, teaching performance is characterized by a holistic approach, encompassing aspects such as tailored incorporation of students' existing knowledge, smooth lesson transitions, strategic use of teaching aids, and cultivating an engaging learning atmosphere. Educators' proactive engagement with these components, along with their extensive use of teaching aids and thorough lesson preparation, underlines their commitment to effective pedagogy and comprehensive student comprehension. Establishing a robust ranking and rating system within the Higher Education (HE) sector heavily hinges on assessing research performance, a critical element. At Sokoto State University and other Nigerian state universities, the evaluation of research activities incorporates diverse methodologies, including publications, conference contributions, grants, and thesis supervision. However, this evaluation is notably affected by the prevalence of academic lecturers holding positions below the rank of Lecturer I, creating a challenging context for research advancement in northwestern Nigeria. In contrast, a study by Herry et al. in 2020 from Malaysia proposed strategies to bolster research performance in state universities, emphasizing key performance indicators (KPIs) and comprehensive assessment instruments. Numerous studies have investigated research performance, considering both personal and environmental factors. Personal elements like age, experience, and qualifications, alongside environmental factors such as research culture and access to funding, significantly shape research outcomes. Notably, research funding is pivotal in enabling researchers to enhance their productivity. Additionally, management factors, including university policies and KPIs, have a substantial impact on the research performance of academic staff, emphasizing the need to consider behavioral aspects. This echoes the findings of Mukhtar and Nurudeen's (2016) study, which identified motivational incentives, promotions, and recognition as influential factors impacting research performance.

Despite recognizing the transformative potential of research in academia, the report exposes a prevalent negative attitude towards research at Sokoto State University, indicating the necessity for enhanced training, motivation, and resource accessibility for researchers. Acknowledging research's pivotal role in fostering national socio-economic development, it is imperative to empower academic staff through practical research training and access to necessary resources, thus enabling them to contribute significantly to the university and society. This resonates with contemporary models such as the Kennedy and transformative action research models, emphasizing the multifaceted benefits of effective research performance for individual growth and societal progress. At the core of the institution's mission, the Community Services program is a crucial pillar, profoundly influencing the communities it engages with. Its implementation, tailored to the diverse needs of different communities within the Nigerian context, has yielded compelling results. Our assessment of community performance underscores the vital role of these services in delivering social and economic development to the communities, effectively

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addressing local challenges and fostering progress. This affirmation is reinforced by the research of Ogunode and Iroegbu in 2018 and the sentiments expressed by Ayedun et al. in 2021, highlighting the significance of institutional sustainability through the delivery of essential services.

The critical role of community services extends to its contribution to the broader framework of Nigeria's stable macroeconomic and political environment, as emphasized by Ekpo and Ayedun in 2018. Within the Nigerian context, universities are pivotal in driving socio-economic development, embodying the nation's growth model. This emphasis on higher education is rooted in the understanding that nurturing individual potential translates into advancements across various sectors, positioning effective university education as a valuable national asset, as explained by Ayedun et al. in 2021. In the context of professional development, the active participation of most of our academic staff in various academic development programs underscores their commitment to enhancing their expertise. This dedication not only enriches the educational landscape but also strengthens their ability to contribute meaningfully to the advancement of our society. While most of our academic staff enthusiastically participate in community development initiatives, it is essential to note that a minority chooses not to engage in such endeavors within their respective organizations actively.

Conclusion

The study findings and subsequent discussion lead to several key conclusions. Firstly, Continuous Professional Development (CPD) emerges as a significant enhancer of teaching performance among academic staff, as evidenced by a robust correlation coefficient of 0.322, an R-square value of 0.104, and a statistically significant F statistic of 24.822 (p-value: .000). Investing in CPD programs is thus recommended to bolster teaching effectiveness in academic settings. Secondly, CPD demonstrates a modest, albeit statistically insignificant, impact on research performance. Despite a positive correlation coefficient of 0.116, the R-square value of 0.013, an F statistic of 2.920 (p-value: .089), and a beta coefficient of 0.116 suggest that CPD influences research performance without being a reliable predictor, indicating a limited effect on research outcomes among academic staff. Lastly, the study concludes that CPD significantly enhances community service performance, supported by a correlation coefficient of 0.309, an R-square value of 0.096, and a statistically significant F statistic of 22.662 (p-value: .000). This implies that investing in CPD initiatives can effectively increase academic staff engagement in community service activities.

Recommendations

Based on the findings above, several key recommendations emerge. Firstly, there is a strong endorsement for prioritizing and investing in Continuous Professional Development (CPD) programs for academic staff, particularly concerning teaching performance. Academic institutions are advised to allocate resources towards workshops, training sessions, conferences, and other opportunities that enhance teaching skills and pedagogical knowledge. Secondly, while acknowledging the relatively modest impact of CPD on research performance, institutions should customize CPD programs to address research-related skills and activities specifically. This could involve organizing research methodology workshops, providing access to pertinent research resources, and creating collaborative research environments to support academic staff in achieving their research objectives. Lastly, due to the noteworthy positive impact of CPD on community service performance, academic institutions are encouraged to promote and facilitate community engagement opportunities for their staff actively. This may include establishing partnerships with local organizations, allocating resources for community outreach, and integrating community service components into CPD programs, ensuring academic staff's sustained involvement in socially impactful endeavors.

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Qualitative Study on Globalization and Learning of English as a Second Language at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

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Abstract

The phenomenon of globalization has brought about profound transformations in the landscape of English language pedagogy, particularly in non-native English-speaking countries like Nigeria. This paper explores Language pedagogy, English in a global world, and the implications of globalization on the teaching and learning of English as a Second Language (ESL) in secondary school in Nigeria. By addressing these key areas, Nigeria can better equip its learners to navigate the challenges and opportunities presented by globalization while preserving its linguistic and cultural heritage. This paper sets the stage for a deeper exploration of the recommendations and strategies essential for enhancing ESL pedagogy in the era of globalization.

Keywords: Globalization, English Language, Students, teaching and learning

Introduction

Globalization's influence on education has become a topic of increasing importance and research. As economies, cultures, and societies intertwine on a global scale, the significance of mastering a universally recognized language like English becomes undeniable. Integrating language teaching with the principles of globalization aids learners in not only communicating effectively but also in comprehending diverse cultures and perspectives, thereby promoting intercultural competence. According to Mohammed (2020), in his article "English Language and Globalization," English has evolved into a global lingua franca, being the primary medium of international communication, business, and technology. The demand for English language skills is intricately linked to the demands of a globalized world. Therefore, teaching English should encompass not only linguistic competence but also cross-cultural understanding and adaptability, preparing students for a world where interconnections and interactions transcend geographical boundaries (Omachonu, Abuh, & Alhassan, 2017). In the Nigerian context, the impact of globalization on English as a Second Language education is notable due to the country's diverse linguistic landscape and its participation in global markets. The challenge lies in equipping learners with the skills necessary to navigate this global landscape effectively. Innovative methodologies, such as project-based learning that encourages collaboration and problem-solving, can engage students in authentic language use while fostering a global mindset (Bamidele, 2023, Amadi, 2019, & Mahboob, 2018).

Concept of Globalization and English as a second language

Globalization has had a profound impact on the English language, transforming it into a global lingua franca. As people and information flow more freely across borders, English has emerged as the dominant language of international communication (Owolabi, 2016). This phenomenon is driven by several factors. Firstly, the economic dominance of English-speaking countries like the United States and the United Kingdom has contributed to the widespread adoption of English in business and trade. Additionally, the internet and the rise of global media have made English the primary language of the digital age, as most online content, from websites to social media platforms, is predominantly in English. As a result, English

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proficiency has become a valuable skill in many parts of the world, leading to a surge in English language education and learners worldwide (Altan, 2017). The globalization of English has not been without controversy. Dash and Gandhi, (2022) argue that the dominance of English can lead to linguistic and cultural homogenization, eroding the diversity of languages and cultures around the world. This concern is valid, as the spread of English can sometimes overshadow the preservation and promotion of indigenous languages and traditions. However, proponents of English as a global lingua franca argue that it fosters greater international understanding and collaboration, breaking down communication barriers in an interconnected world. English facilitates the exchange of ideas, knowledge, and cultural expressions, enabling people from diverse backgrounds to engage in meaningful dialogue and collaboration on a global scale (Alfarhan, 2016). In conclusion, globalization and the English language are closely intertwined. English has become the de facto language of global business, diplomacy, science, and the internet, reflecting the interconnectedness of our modern world. While it offers opportunities for communication and cooperation, it also raises concerns about linguistic diversity and cultural preservation. Striking a balance between the advantages of a global lingua franca and the need to protect linguistic and cultural diversity is a complex challenge for societies in an increasingly globalized era.

Globalization and English as a Second Language at Secondary School level

Language pedagogy, the art and science of teaching languages, plays a crucial role in equipping individuals with the skills and proficiency needed to communicate effectively in a foreign or second language. Effective language pedagogy encompasses a multifaceted approach that considers various aspects of language learning, including linguistic, cultural, and cognitive dimensions (Verplaetse, & Migliacci, 2017). One fundamental aspect of language pedagogy is understanding the principles of second language acquisition. Educators draw upon theories such as behaviorism, cognitivism, and constructivism to develop teaching methods that align with how individuals naturally learn languages. For example, the communicative approach focuses on real-life language use and interaction, emphasizing the importance of meaningful context and communication in the learning process. This approach encourages students to actively engage in conversation, problem-solving, and authentic language tasks to develop their language skills. Another essential component of language pedagogy is the selection of appropriate teaching materials and technologies. Effective pedagogy integrates various resources, including textbooks, multimedia tools, language software, and online platforms, to engage students and enhance their learning experience (Hyder, 2021). In recent years, digital technologies and online language learning platforms have become increasingly prevalent, offering learners opportunities for self-paced study and real-time language practice with speakers from around the world. Language teachers must adapt to these evolving tools and incorporate them into their teaching strategies to cater to diverse learning styles and preferences (Moin, Patra, Mitra, & Dutta, 2019). Assessment and evaluation are integral aspects of language pedagogy, allowing teachers to gauge students' progress and adapt their teaching methods accordingly. Assessments can be formative, providing ongoing feedback, or summative, measuring overall language proficiency. Effective language pedagogy uses a variety of assessment tools, such as standardized tests, portfolios, oral presentations, and peer evaluations, to comprehensively evaluate students' language skills (Todorova, & Todorova, 2018). These assessments not only guide instructional decisions but also empower learners to set goals and monitor their language development, promoting a more personalized and effective learning experience.

English has undeniably achieved the status of a global language, serving as a common means of communication internationally. This designation as a global language is earned when a language assumes a unique role acknowledged across the world, transcending borders and cultures. English, in particular, has been embraced by nations globally, resulting in English speakers being present in virtually every corner of the globe. With over 350 million native English speakers and an additional 430 million individuals using English as their second language, it has become a genuinely global means of expression (Chapelle, 2018). In our interconnected world, the necessity for a universal language for effective communication is evident. This global language facilitates international dialogue across various domains, including politics, economics, education, and private business, ensuring that individuals worldwide can connect, understand, and engage with one another effortlessly (Omachonu, & Offorma). Below are the roles English plays in the global world. English is of paramount importance in education, particularly for those aspiring to study at renowned institutions in English-speaking countries such as Australia, the UK, and the US. Students are acutely aware that a strong command of the English language is a prerequisite for pursuing academic excellence in these nations. To gain admission to world-class universities in these countries, they must successfully navigate standardized English proficiency tests like TOEFL, IELTS, PTE, and more. Undoubtedly, these assessments pose a significant challenge to candidates. However, conquering these tests opens the door to fulfilling their educational dreams and

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gaining admission to prestigious colleges or universities. The significance of English in the realm of technology cannot be overstated, as it remains a fundamental language for global innovation and progress (Rao,2019).

In today's interconnected world, English plays a pivotal role across various domains. The technical lexicon largely relies on English terminology, making it essential for staying updated on the latest global developments and discoveries through English-language journals and research reports. The internet's rapid expansion has fostered international interactions, and English has become the primary medium for cross-cultural communication, enabling people from diverse nations to understand each other (Jenkins, 2015). Proficiency in English is particularly vital in education, science, and technology, where specialists often require a global language for effective collaboration. Aspiring students aiming to engage with the world of information technology recognize the paramount importance of achieving the highest level of English proficiency in pursuing their careers.

English is commonly referred to as the international language of business, a title that resonates strongly in the current global landscape. With international trade continually forging new connections among nations, the significance of English in the business realm cannot be overstated. Beyond facilitating travel, English empowers individuals to effectively communicate and project themselves on the global stage (Gottlieb & Nguyen, 2020). In the context of worldwide business interactions, English serves as the bridge for expressing ideas and engaging with the international business community. Proficiency in this global lingua franca is indispensable, as it ensures seamless communication and avoids potential hurdles arising from language barriers when dealing with diverse stakeholders worldwide. English, as the most widely spoken language globally, assumes a pivotal role in fostering cultural exchange and global connections. Its ubiquity enables English speakers to immerse themselves in the rich tapestry of diverse cultures through translated literature and international cinema, thus transcending geographical boundaries and broadening their horizons (Omachonu, Abuh, & Alhassan, 2017). Furthermore, this shared linguistic thread weaves a seamless fabric among English-speaking nations, facilitating effortless communication and fostering stronger connections between countries, bridging cultural gaps, and promoting global cooperation. In essence, English serves as a catalyst for cross-cultural understanding and interconnectivity, promoting a more prosperous, more interconnected world.

Learning English offers a distinct advantage in the job market, as many employers prioritize language skills, particularly proficiency in English, due to the widespread involvement of companies in international dealings. During interviews, hiring managers often assess candidates not only based on their academic qualifications but also on their ability to effectively communicate in English. Clear and articulate expression is highly valued, even alongside outstanding educational backgrounds. Given the abundant opportunities to work with international organizations in today's global job market, individuals are striving to acquire English language proficiency. Once job seekers attain both oral and written communication skills in English, they gain access to job prospects worldwide. This trend is not limited to English-speaking nations, as even individuals from non-English-speaking countries like China and Japan are increasingly learning English to enhance their employment prospects in the global business landscape (Rao,2019). English has become the universal language of business in the modern globalized world.

Travel and tourism, bridging national and international realms, predominantly rely on English as the universal language. It serves as the common linguistic thread connecting international travel departments, agencies, and companies. When visiting foreign nations, effective communication is essential for engaging with local populations, making a shared language a necessity. English, as the international lingua franca, fulfills this crucial role, enabling tourists to explore any destination worldwide (Todorova, & Todorova, 2018). Recognizing its significance, international travel agencies prioritize recruiting individuals with proficient English communication skills to facilitate seamless interactions with tourists from across the globe. English is pivotal in global entertainment, notably in the film, television, and music industries. Hollywood, based in the United States, serves as the epicenter of these industries, using English as their universal medium to reach a worldwide audience. This choice enables them to promote their content globally, offering relief to people facing the strains and stresses of modern life. English-language entertainment encompasses a wide range, including cartoons, movies, TV shows, comics, and educational programs like Discovery, National Geographic, Animal Planet, BBC, CNN, Star Movies, and AXN. These channels not only entertain but also educate, aiding children and adults in improving their language skills, vocabulary, and knowledge. In essence, English not only entertains and informs but also serves as a key language in various fields, reflecting its ever-increasing global importance (Mohammed, 2020). Learning English has become essential, transcending regional and national boundaries.

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Implications for Teaching and Learning of English as a second language at secondary school level Education in Nigeria

Teaching and learning the English language in schools comes with several implications that educators and students should consider. These implications can significantly impact the effectiveness of language education. Sucharitha, (2022) and Hodges, Moore, Lockce, Trust, and Bond, (2020) consider the following implications for the teaching and learning of the English language in secondary schools in Nigeria:

1. **Cultural Sensitivity and Awareness:** Teaching English in secondary schools involves not only language skills but also an understanding of the diverse cultures and backgrounds of English learners. Educators should be culturally sensitive and promote awareness to foster inclusivity and respect among students.
2. **Multimodal instruction:** Recognizing that students have different learning styles, teachers should employ various teaching methods, including visual aids, audio resources, interactive activities, and technology, to cater to diverse learning preferences.
3. **Language Proficiency Goals:** Secondary schools in Nigeria must set clear language proficiency goals for students. These goals can be aligned with international language proficiency standards like CEFR (Common European Framework of Reference for Languages) to ensure consistency and measurable progress.
4. **Differentiated Instruction:** Recognize that students enter the classroom with varying levels of English proficiency. Differentiated instruction allows teachers to tailor their teaching to meet the individual needs of each student.
5. **Language Assessment and Feedback:** Regular assessment of language skills is crucial. Formative and summative assessments can help identify areas for improvement. Providing constructive feedback helps students understand their strengths and weaknesses.
6. **Integration of Language Skills:** English language teaching should focus on integrating all language skills – listening, speaking, reading, and writing. This holistic approach ensures that students can effectively communicate in real-life situations.
7. **Cultural Exchange Opportunities:** Encourage language learners to engage in cultural exchange programs, language immersion experiences, or interactions with native speakers to enhance language skills and cultural understanding.
8. **Use of Authentic Materials:** Incorporating authentic materials such as books, news articles, movies, and songs into the curriculum helps expose students to real-world language usage and enhances their language proficiency.
9. **Technology Integration:** Utilize educational technology tools and platforms to create interactive and engaging learning experiences. Online resources, language learning apps, and virtual classrooms can enhance language acquisition.
10. **Teacher Professional Development:** Teachers should undergo continuous professional development to stay updated with the latest teaching methodologies, language trends, and cultural nuances to provide high-quality language instruction.

Support for English Language Learners (ELLs)

Schools should provide additional support, such as English as a Second Language (ESL) programs or tutors, for ELLs to ensure they can successfully integrate into mainstream English-speaking classrooms.

1. **Assessment of Progress and Outcomes:** Regularly assess the effectiveness of English language programs to make data-driven improvements. Monitor students' progress and adapt teaching strategies accordingly.
2. **Parental Involvement:** Encourage parents to actively support their children's language learning journey by providing a conducive environment at home and participating in school-related activities.

Incorporating these implications into English language teaching and learning in schools can help create a more effective and enriching educational experience for students and better prepare them for communication in a globalized world.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the impact of globalization and English as a second language at the secondary school level in Nigeria is a multifaceted phenomenon that presents both challenges and opportunities. The increasing global interconnectedness has made English not only a crucial tool for communication and access to global resources but also a marker of educational and socioeconomic success. This necessitates a dynamic and contextually relevant approach to English language instruction, emphasizing not only language proficiency but also intercultural competence and critical thinking skills. While challenges such as linguistic imperialism and the digital divide must be addressed, the integration of technology and innovative teaching methodologies can bridge these gaps. Additionally, fostering a culture of inclusive and culturally sensitive language education

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is imperative to ensure equitable access and promote the diverse linguistic heritage of Nigeria. In navigating the complexities of globalization, educators and policymakers must continuously adapt and collaborate to empower English language learners to navigate the global landscape effectively while celebrating their unique linguistic identities.

Recommendations

To address the challenges posed by globalization and its impact on English as a second language at the secondary school level in Nigeria, it is essential to consider a multifaceted approach that encompasses both policy-level changes and classroom-level strategies. Here are several recommendations for improving the teaching and learning of English as a Second Language (ESL) in Nigeria in the context of globalization:

1. **Curriculum Revision:** The Nigerian educational system should comprehensively review its English language curriculum. The curriculum should be updated to reflect the evolving demands of globalization, emphasizing language proficiency, intercultural competence, critical thinking, and digital literacy. This can help learners use English effectively in a globalized world.
2. **Professional Development for Teachers:** Continuous professional development programs should be established for ESL teachers. These programs should focus on modern teaching methods, incorporating technology, and promoting intercultural communication skills. Teachers need to adapt to the changing needs of learners in a globalized world.
3. **Incorporate Technology:** Utilize technology to facilitate language learning. The integration of multimedia resources, online platforms, and language learning apps can make English language learning more engaging and accessible to learners. This approach aligns with the digital demands of the globalized world.
4. **Cultural Awareness:** ESL teachers should promote cultural awareness and sensitivity in the classroom. Globalization has brought people from diverse backgrounds together, and understanding different cultures is crucial for effective communication. Encourage learners to explore various cultures through language learning.
5. **Assessment Reform:** Rethink the assessment methods used in ESL education. Move away from rote memorization and focus on assessing practical language skills, communication abilities, and critical thinking. This shift will better prepare learners for real-world communication scenarios.
6. **Promote Multilingualism:** While English is essential, promoting multilingualism is equally important. Nigeria is a linguistically diverse country, and encouraging the use of indigenous languages alongside English can foster a sense of identity and inclusivity while supporting effective language learning.
7. **Global Partnerships:** Establish partnerships with institutions, organizations, and educators from English-speaking countries. Collaborative projects, exchange programs, and access to native English speakers can provide learners with authentic language experiences.
8. **Policy Support:** Advocate for policies that prioritize the importance of English language proficiency in Nigeria's globalization efforts. Adequate funding, infrastructure development, and clear objectives are vital to the success of English language pedagogy.

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Qualitative study on military and internal security operation in Nigeria: 2013-2023

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Abstract

The study examines military and internal security operation in Nigeria: 2013-2023. The study employed an exploratory approach and gathered data from secondary sources such as the Google and Google Scholar search engines, media, and academic and research groups that have conducted research on the subject. The study findings revealed that rural banditry, farmer and herders' conflicts, Boko-Haram, and succession of Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB) were major internal security in Nigeria. Also, excessive use of force, arbitrary arrest, degrading treatment of citizens and extra judicial killings were the military mode of operation during internal security. The study findings also revealed that training, orientation, strategy and tactics, and equipment were the major challenges of the military during internal security operation. The study concludes that the military is generally abusive and engaged in numerous predatory activities that violate the human rights of the populace and further their sense of insecurity. Despite that, the military's acceptance as the most powerful organ of the state with the superior coercive force to suppress the threats and violence posed by armed groups. The study recommended among others that there is a need for an improvement in military control as regard to human rights abuses by engaging the National Human Rights Commission to handles or comparable tasks as, an independent military investigator who is focused on military abuse problems would be more helpful.

Keywords: Internal Security, Military, Operation.

Introduction

A state's principal role is to safeguard its population against external aggression as well as internal violence and unrest. In liberal democracies, the police are usually in charge of this (Bigo, 2000; Lioe, 2011). However, as violence erupts and the security situation deteriorates in Nigeria, as in many African countries, governments frequently rely on the military to restore order and calm (Howe, 2001). This is largely due to the police's inability to contain violent disputes, particularly when citizens' security is endangered by armed organizations (Nwolise, 2007; Omede, 2012). As a result, Baker (2010) contends that most African police units are not adequately equipped or educated to deal with the problems posed by armed groups and internal armed conflicts. As a result, the government is frequently forced to utilize the military in an internal role since it is the only state instrument with the necessary coercive capacity to suppress violence, disorder, or insurgency (Peterside, 2014). The ability to contain such violence is a challenge that many African countries face in the twenty-first century. This is especially true when disputes intensify and the country devolves into internal strife (Okumu & Ikelegbe, 2010). Numerous elements can be attributed to the causes of these violent conflicts in Africa (Gurr, Marshall & Khosla, 2000; Sarkees, Wayman & Singer, 2003). These include excessive wealth disparity, ethnic and religious divisions being manipulated and exploited, greed, and a lack of judicial procedures to address these concerns (Collier & Hoeffler, 2002, 2004). Other issues include the government's failure to provide fundamental public goods, frustrations stemming from the marginalization of minority ethnic groups, and citizens' inability to obtain economic, political, or social privileges in society. Armed organizations typically exploit these situations, with the bulk of them motivated by political goals, economic intent, and extremist religious doctrines (Fearon & Laitin, 2003; Vre, 2010).

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The growth of these armed groups in various forms is now playing a significant role in international politics and security sector changes in the twenty-first century (Vinci, 2008).

Armed groups are commonly used as spoilers or troublemakers in state-building and peace-building attempts (Schneckener, 2006). They endanger citizen security and the supply of public goods by leveraging existing complaints and disturbing states' essential operations, eroding their legitimacy (Stewart, 2002, 2004). This is especially true when they undertake coordinated attacks on civilian groups, essential infrastructure, or state forces and gain control of areas of a state (Thompson, 2014). As a result, states resort to the military to aid police in preserving domestic security and containing the risks posed by armed groups. Using the military for internal security operations (ISOPs), also known as military help to civil authority (MACA), has its own set of difficulties. One is the training of military troops, which is not suitable for employment in an internal societal role. The military's concentration is on defense, war, and the infliction of collective violence, as opposed to the police, whose primary duty is law enforcement (Harris, 2003; Weiss, 2012). The military tends to dominate in collaborative units or as hybrid security forces with police and other civilian organizations. This is most common in jurisdictions with no constabulary forces or gendarmeries. In terms of command and control, hybrid forces comprised of joint police and military units pose various challenges. Military sociologists and other security strategists regard the military as a crucial tool for conflict de-escalation in order to reinstall peace and order (Von Bredow, 2006). The deployment of the military in an internal role in society has become the norm in several African states because "when violence breaks out, policymakers and society at large believe that the military should be brought in" (José & Rasmussen, 1999). This is the scenario in Nigeria, where the military is continually deployed to tackle the threat posed by civil war and armed groups seeking to destabilize the government (Omede, 2012; Dambazau, 2014). It is against this background that the study interrogated the military and internal security operation in Nigeria

Concept of military

A military also referred to as the armed forces as a whole, is a well-equipped, well-organized organization that is mainly designed for combat. Its members can usually be recognized by their distinctive military uniforms, and it is typically approved and kept by a sovereign state. One or more military divisions, such as the army, navy, air force, space force, commandos, or coast guard, may make up this force. Defence of the state and its interests against exterior armed threats is typically described as the military's primary duty. In general usage, the words "armed forces" and "military" are frequently used interchangeably, but in formal usage, the terms "armed forces" and "military" can refer to both the military and other paramilitary forces of a nation. Unaffiliated with a recognized state, irregular military forces come in many different shapes. Despite sharing many characteristics with regular military forces, they are less frequently referred to as merely military.

The military of a country may operate as a distinct social subculture with its own infrastructure, including homes, utilities, schools, logistics, clinics, judicial services, food supply, finance, and banking. Beyond combat, the military may be used by the government for other authorized and unapproved purposes, such as countering threats to internal security, managing population growth, advancing political objectives, providing emergency services and reconstruction, safeguarding corporate economic interests, providing national honour guards, and responding to natural disasters (Mark, 2009). Military service is a career that predates written history itself (Jordan, Kiras, Lonsdale, Speller, Tuck, and Walton). (2016). The strength and prowess of ancient antiquity's war commanders are depicted in some of the most enduring artworks. One of the turning moments in Pharaoh Ramses II's rule was the Battle of Kadesh in 1274 BC, which is commemorated in bas-relief on many of his monuments. A thousand years later, Qin Shi Huang, the first ruler of united China, was so resolved to demonstrate his military prowess to the gods that he ordered himself to be buried alongside an army of terracotta troops. Romans gave military affairs a lot of attention, leaving behind numerous treatises and works on the topic as well as numerous elaborately sculpted triumphal arches and victory columns.

Concept of internal security

The state's ability to carry out its duties depends heavily on internal security. Protecting life and developing laws that would improve citizen wellbeing are fundamental functions of the state. If law and order cannot be maintained, the state cannot fulfil its first fundamental purpose. Internal security is therefore a crucial component of national growth and security. Furthermore, the problem of internal security is so important to nations and national leaders that they are willing to risk everything in order to defend or protect the security of their countries. Walter Lippman noted that a country is safe to the degree that its fundamental rights—life, property, and liberty—are not at risk. Internal security also alludes to the necessity of ensuring the Nation-State's survival through the practice of diplomatic, military, and political authority. While outlining his grand

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strategy, President Olusegun Obasanjo stated that the main goal of national security should be to strengthen the Federal Republic of Nigeria, reduce crime and corruption, promote genuine development, progress, and growth, and enhance citizen welfare (Attah, 2006). The military services are typically given this duty. However, the internal component of national security never receives much attention or funding; the Nigerian government does not have any clearly stated internal security policies. It has depended on impromptu actions, a fire squad strategy, excessive use of force, road blockages, and persuasion that is frequently ignored. And this helps to explain why the nation's domestic security has become so fragile. For instance, despite the catastrophic effects of armed theft on Nigeria's socioeconomic development, the call for a national summit on internal security has not yet been included in national debate. Security generally refers to the absence of risks or dangers, safety, or the capacity of the State to uphold its core principles, safeguard its lawful interests, and improve the welfare of its citizens. As a result, threats to property and life, including those posed by armed robbers, Boko Haram attacks, civil unrest, roadblocks that imperil other drivers, and other diversions, are signs that there is a dearth of internal security.

Internal security, as used in this research, refers to actions taken by domestic security forces like the police, customs, and immigration services, among others, to limit threats to national security that originate domestically. These dangers frequently involve dangerous situations involving riots, protests, strikes, communal disputes, terrorism, and the like, which typically do not come under the military's constitutional responsibilities. (International Committee of the Red Cross United Relations with Armed and Security Forces, 2002). For instance, it is the responsibility of the Police to uphold the rule of law and order in the community. The Police Act's Section 4 lists the basic responsibilities of the police as upholding law and order, protecting people and property, and properly enforcing all laws and rules that fall under their purview. A nation's internal disputes are handled by Internal Security Operations (ISOPs). Conflicts between communities and ethnic groups, religion disputes, and most lately acts of terrorism in Nigeria have made participation in ISOPs necessary.

Theoretical framework

The research, which is based on the integration theory created by military sociologist Morris Janowitz, centers on the military's professional standing and shifting social position. He sees the military as a career with established boundaries, guidelines, and norms of conduct. (Janowitz, 1960). He claims that civilian control of the military can only be accomplished when the military is integrated into society and the political decision-making process. This ensures that the military stays deferential to the rule of law. To prevent the military from developing a subculture and running the danger of becoming a state-within-the-state, Janowitz suggests that similar civilian, social, institutional, and cultural norms must exist (Lambert, 2009). He makes a number of reasons for why it is important to guarantee civil authority over the military. One of these factors is the shifting nature of security issues, which has led to an increase in the use of the military in law enforcement capacities. As a result, the distinction between policing and military duties as well as between peace and conflict is blurred in a number of states where the military is used in a domestic capacity. He anticipated that the military would play a larger part in law enforcement and eventually serve as the backup source of final legitimate force (Janowitz, 1960). Due to this, it is essential that the military upholds and supports society's democratic ideals while also respecting the authority bestowed upon government leaders. The military will be more dedicated to accomplishing the political objectives of the state where it supports the democratic values of society. (Janowitz, 1977). Again, this depends on the relative strength of the armed and civilian spheres. This can be troublesome, particularly in weak and autocratic states where the military is dissatisfied with the civilian government and exerts excessive control over political decision-making. (Auma-Osoto, 1980).

Due to their internal role and significance in ensuring political stability and security, military officials who become more politically aware subject the state to the risk of domestic military involvement in politics. When the officer corps is unhappy with the decisions or actions of civilian political officials, it becomes more and more motivated to take political power. This is especially true in nations with weak political structures and organizations and nations where civilian dominance is not institutionalized. The modern military commander is oriented toward maximizing his impact in politics and/or policy, as noted correctly by Perlmutter & Bennett in 1980. Therefore, because military leaders are familiar with political decision-making procedures, it is simple to use the flaws and failures of civilian leaders to advance personal interests, unless this is restrained (Feaver, 2003). From a different perspective, although Janowitz's concept of constabulary forces seems pertinent given that it relates to the use of the military in constabulary duties, it ignores parts of civil-military relations that deal with the interaction of the military with the populace. This covers things like the prevalence of military errors and abuses, which have been seen in a number of domestic security and peacekeeping missions. Taking Nigeria as an example, since the nation's independence in 1960, the military has participated in a number of domestic security and law enforcement missions (Okoli & Orinya, 2013; Dambazau, 2014). Given that Nigeria has been governed by the military for about 29 years, it has also played a significant role

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in governance (Ojo, 2006; Omede, 2012; Adeakin, 2015). The military has not, however, internalized societal principles that support civilian authority, respect for the law, or democratic values. (Agbu, 2004; Amnesty International, 2015). According to how I interpret Janowitz, he disregarded how the military's expertise and military culture can militarize the state and impact how they carry out police-like duties.

Military abuses, militarism, the militarization of society, and the infringement of citizens' human rights and civil freedoms rank among the main objections to using the military domestically (Nwolise, 2007; Odoemene, 2012). Problems frequently occur because military instruction and battle orientation are inappropriate for use in law enforcement and crowd management (Weiss, 2012). Additionally, even though it can manage masses, the military is still primarily a force used to fight battles and is very different from the police (Weiss, 2012). Its fundamental and most crucial ability is the capacity to disable, destroy, and cause the adversary great suffering (Gray, 2007). This explains the many difficulties and inconsistencies encountered when it is used internally, particularly when using force is involved. This can have an impact on the military's credibility and connection with the populace in states where victims of military abuse and excesses are not entitled to legal recourse. This leads one to the conclusion that, particularly in authoritarian states or states with weak civic control agencies, neither the separationist nor the integration theories are adequate to explain domestic security.

The nature of internal security in Nigeria

Communal bloodshed, threats, and significant domestic unrest have persisted in Nigeria since it gained independence from Britain on 1 October 1960. Every region of the nation has been impacted (Odoma, 2014), frequently throwing it into chaos and endangering political safety as well as the delivery of necessary public products and services, such as security (Ujomu, 2015). Six geographic zones, each containing five or more States, split Nigeria. According to their physical location and population makeup, these regional zones show the spatial spread of all the States of Nigeria, including the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) Abuja. In the North Central and North West Zones, communal conflicts are widespread because religious and ethnic diversity is exploited by desperate politicians and numerous armed groups to cause a rift for political/economic gains (Osaghae & Suberu, 2005). This is made worse by ongoing attacks by herders (mostly nomadic Fulani) on the indigenous population, which is made up of Christians from numerous 'minority' ethnic groups. In the North-East Zone, where Muslim Hausa's and Fulani. Communal conflicts are widespread in the North Central and North West Zones as a result of numerous armed groups and desperate politicians using the diversity of religion and ethnicity to foment strife for political and economic gain (Osaghae & Suberu, 2005). This is worsened by incessant herders' (mostly, nomadic Fulani) attacks on indigenous population, comprising of Christians of numerous 'minority' ethnic groups. In the North-East Zone, where Muslim Hausa's and Fulani's dominate, religious fanaticism and terrorism pose the greatest security concerns for especially, the non-Hausa/Fulani Christian minority. In the South West Zone, criminal violence and electoral violence endanger security, economic and political equilibrium in the area. While serious security threats (the Biafra secession crisis, the Niger-Delta Militancy, the Boko Haram terrorism, and the communal violence and herdsman attacks in Plateau State) are currently raging in four of the six geopolitical zones, these challenges "have been worsening on a daily basis" since Nigeria returned to democratic rule (Dambazau, 2014: 65).

The Nigerian military and internal security operations

According to Elaigwu (2003), the Nigerian Military has played a significant role in crisis management in Nigeria ever since the country's freedom. He contends that three fundamental factors influence the strategies used by the Nigerian Military in domestic security operations: a) the use of minimal force principle; b) adversary weapons holding, his tactical methods, and habits; and c) the topography of the enemy's location (Elaigwu, 2003). On top of this, Elaigwu illustrates the limitations of military intervention in domestic crisis management by demonstrating how the dispatch of a military force in the Tiv division in 1960 was unable to prevent the outbreak of violence there in 1961. Further acts of violence between July and August 1964—which culminated in another military deployment in November 1964—were not deterred by a comparable use of military force in February 1964. He continues by saying that although Maitatsine was subjected to the entire weight of military might in Kano in 1980, neither this nor later displays of physical force were able to prevent incidents of this nature from occurring in Bullumkuttu, Rigasa, Jimeta-Yola, and Gombe in 1982, 1984, and 1985, respectively (Elaigwu, 2003). The recent past, however, is ignored because the research only covers the first 33 years of Nigeria's freedom. According to Akpan (2011), Nigerian history is rife with instances of the military being used to put down internal uprisings. When it interfered in the Tiv disturbance in 1964, the Nigerian military made its first known appearance in domestic affairs. Since then, in Akpan's opinion, Nigerian leaders have used the military in political situations even when there is no proof that such actions have been successful.

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He uses the Niger Delta as the most recent illustration of the use of the military as a crisis management tool. He comes to the conclusion that the Mad Man's Theory is satisfied by the excessive use of military force to previously considered disproportionate levels to a domestic crisis and the parties' objectives and contends that the military is unsuited for conflict resolution and crisis management in a domestic setting that requires political resolution (Akpan, 2011). Dode (2012) makes the case that members of the Nigerian Armed Forces have a history of conducting successful peacekeeping operations throughout the globe, citing Sierra Leone and Liberia as examples. However, their security and crisis management efforts in Nigeria do not appear to be following through on this track record. According to Dode, military actions taken to maintain domestic security in Nigeria have largely been ineffective in resolving civic unrest. They have primarily been employed to advance the interests of certain political leaders. Dode (2012) comes to the conclusion that encouraging the enlistment of military people to resolve civil disputes in a democracy is strategically risky. According to Animasawun (2013), the military's use for domestic security activities in strife areas of Nigeria is fraught with peculiar, frequently regionally specific difficulties.

Armed organizations in Nigeria, including the Odua People's Congress (OPC), the Movement for the Actualization of the Sovereign State of Biafra (MASSOB), the Movement for the Emancipation of the Niger Delta (MEND), Boko Haram, and organizations engaged in sectarian violence in Jos, are classified as terrorist organizations by Akpaotor and Oromareghake (2013). Ocheche (2013) distinguishes between three types of terrorism in Nigeria: state terrorism, group (ethno religious), and externally influenced terrorism. All of these types of terrorism have continued to pose a serious threat to Nigeria's stability. It is argued that the liberal political space created by Nigeria's return to democracy in 1999 was the floodgate that released these militant elements. He cites the NM operations in Odi and Zaki Biam in 1999 and 2001, respectively, as examples of domineering military operations that directly impact a large number of civilians (Ocheche 2013). In Nigeria, ethnic paramilitary activity that includes kidnapping hostages, killing people, setting buildings on fire, robbing people, raping people, and maiming people is frequently classified as group terrorism. These acts have been carried out by organizations like the Odua People's Congress (OPC), the Movement for the Actualization of the Sovereign State of Biafra (MASSOB), the Egbesu Boys, the Movement for the Emancipation of the Niger Delta (MEND), and the Bakassi Boys, among others. Terrorism that is externally affected occurs when terrorist acts are committed by people or organizations outside of Nigeria who have connections to or supporters there. Osakwe and Umoh (2013) look at the paradox that arises when Nigeria uses its military forces to fight terrorism. They point out that a key component of any counterinsurgency plan is ensuring the safety of the local and civilian people. Success in counterinsurgency, however, has frequently been arrested and given a dearth of specified within framework for the Nigerian Military. Confront, Build, and Transfer, which are carried out by a mixture of an attack force, a support force, and a security force, are the three concepts highlighted by the Nigerian Military as the cornerstone of any effective COIN. In order to face fortified strongholds and deny insurgents access to their havens, the military assault force is needed. Building the host society requires the support team. Then, in order to stop crime, transfer would be made to the public security troops. The Nigerian Army's discipline between 1960 and 1965 is examined by Osakwe (2013). The case made by Creveld (1990) and Huntington is used to support the idea of expertise. Half a decade after Nigeria gained freedom, Osakwe (2001) focused solely on the administration, instruction, and training of the Nigerian Army in his study of professionalism in the Nigeria military. Superlatives and variables like discipline, loyalty, corporations, patriotism, and bravery are simple to use to describe the factors that contributed to professionalism in the Nigerian Army during the time period under consideration. Upon their exit in 1960, the British colonial officials greatly diminished what would be considered expertise. The degree to which this was intentional didn't seem to be thoroughly investigated. The residue of colonization is identified by Ouédraogo (2014) as a major barrier to professionalism in Africa, extending the debate across the entire continent. Ouédraogo (2014) contends that African armies were "built from the ashes of colonial forces," inheriting the colonial militaries' racial biases that led to a lack of professionalism. To offset traditionally more powerful ethnicities, minority ethnicities typically made up the majority of the imperial military forces. The development of post-independence armies was significantly impacted by this early ethnic prejudice. Military commanders from these ethnic minorities frequently led the surge of coups d'état that toppled some of the first post-independence governments.

In their 2014 study, Lipede and Osakwe, they look at violent disputes and military deployment in Nigeria. They contend that by performing tasks like enforcement and fighting, the NM has overextended itself. According to Lipede and Osakwe (2014), by 2013, nearly thirty of Nigeria's thirty-six states had signed on to the "military save the state" plan. All domestic security initiatives supported by state governments came to be known collectively as Operation Mesa. He analyzes both intricate and simpler operations, such as Operation Restore Hope and Operation Iron Fence (highway military patrols to ensure the safety of highways). This is in opposition to the Nigeria Police Force, which is legally responsible for upholding internal security and maintaining law and order. Furthermore, Lipede and Osakwe (2014) contend that using the military for

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law enforcement functions degrades military expertise. He comes to the conclusion that regular forces, as demonstrated in pertinent past contexts and the context of Nigeria, have not been known to thwart insurgent activities. Between 2009 and 2014, Odu (2014) analyzes the difficulties faced by the Military Joint Task Force (JTF) in counterterrorism activities. In the 1999 constitution, the Nigerian Military was given a dual duty that included both suppressing insurrection and protecting Nigeria from foreign attack. Odu (2014) goes on to claim that institutional mechanisms are used to accomplish collaboration between the NM and other security organizations. According to the research, the JTF faces a number of fundamental challenges, including a lack of strategic direction for inter-agency collaboration, poor technological intelligence tools, a lack of capacity, organizational limitations, and low levels of public support.

Mode of Operation of the military during Internal Security Operations

The Nigerian military has frequently participated in peacekeeping missions abroad and has received praise for its honourable behaviour on those occasions; two prime instances are Sierra Leone and Liberia. Why not, when it comes to internal security operations, is a mystery! One persistent issue that is cited as a weakness is the heavy handedness and insensitivity to the nature and traits of areas that are controlled by civilians (Dode, 2012). The Nigerian military's involvement in domestic security activities is characterized by a number of traits, the majority of which are detrimental. Below is a discussion on some modes off operation:

1. **Excessive use of force:** Excessive force is generally defined as force that is beyond what a reasonable and prudent law enforcement officer would use in the given situation. Article 51(5)(b) of the 1977 Additional Protocol I to the Geneva Conventions forbids attacks that may be anticipated to result in incidental loss of civilian life, injury to civilians, damage to civilian objects, or a combination of these, which would be excessive in relation to the circumstances. There have been numerous allegations of excessive force being used by the military during domestic missions. The incident that is commonly referred to as the Odi Massacre serves as an example of this. a raid by the Nigerian military on the largely Ijaw-populated hamlet of Odi in Bayelsa State on November 20, 1999. The assault took place amid the Niger Delta conflict over native peoples' access to hydrocarbon resources and environmental protection. Twelve (12) Nigerian police officers were killed before the Massacre by a group of unruly teenagers close to the hamlet of Odi. On orders from the Federal government, the military attacked and raided the hamlet in what appeared to be an act of retaliation. The use of force in this assault was severe and extreme. Thousands of defenseless civilians, including women and children, were actually slain as a result. With the exception of the bank, the Anglican Church, and the Community Health Centre, every structure in the hamlet was obliterated, leaving it in an appalling state of ruin (Okoli & Orinya, 2013).
2. **Extra judicial killings:** Extrajudicial killings by the military have also been a feature of domestic security activities. In April 2013, the governor of Borno State, Kashim Shettima, claimed that a weekend confrontation between members of the Joint Task Force and insurgents in Baga resulted in the deaths of over 100 persons. The Red Cross reports that 187 people were slain in the fight, but the villagers claim they buried 185 victims (Ola, 2013). According to human rights watch, troops from the 23rd armoured brigade of the 3rd armoured division rounded up locals in Gbeji (in the Zaki Biam region of Benue State) during a military exercise that started on October 22, 2001, for what turned out to be a "ployed meeting." The soldiers forced the villagers to settle down on the ground, dividing them into men and women, and then opened fire on the males without discrimination (Human Right Watch, 2001). There have also been numerous allegations of extrajudicial executions carried out by the Nigerian military.
3. **Degrading treatment of citizens – rape, torture:** Soldiers reportedly extort citizens after intimidating them; it is now standard practice for soldiers to ask defaulting car drivers on the high way to do "frog jumps" as a form of punishment; women and girls are raped on a number of occasions whether or not during internal security operations; and soldiers reportedly extort citizens after intimidating them.
4. **Arbitrary arrest:** As an example, many young people were arbitrarily detained at Odi and Zaki Biam and falsely accused of planning the murder of security personnel, and several youths were detained at Onitsha and falsely accused of belonging to MASSOB (Okoli & Orinya, 2013). This is just one of many examples of how soldiers engaged in internal security operations detain people.

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Challenges of the military in internal security operations in Nigeria

The need for the military to adapt to the demands of domestic security operations is informed by the military's participation in civil operations. When working with civic activities, the military typically has trouble adjusting. The following are some places that have been identified as the root of these issues:

1. **Training:** Since the primary duty of the military is to protect the nation during times of war, as noted by the International Committee of the Red Cross United Relations with Armed and Security Forces (2002), military training is typically based on dealing the greatest amount of harm and destruction to their adversaries and defeating them in the shortest amount of time while adhering to the laws and regulations of armed conflict. Contrary to what is typically expected of troops in traditional conflict, internal security operations only call for caution and the use of minimal force. Because they are now preserving law and order among their own citizens in their own nation, the minimal force prerequisite is necessary.
2. The type of training that soldiers receive can be responsible for the military's arbitrary actions during domestic security missions. Therefore, the troops must receive the necessary instruction to manage internal activities. Lt. Gen. Onyeabo Ihejirika, the Nigerian Army's chief of staff, also recognized this reality, stating that the Nigerian Army must reorient its infrastructure training to accommodate for domestic security operations in support of civil authority (Utebor, 2010).
3. **Orientation:** This is a person's mind-set or point of view. According to a military perspective, any possible danger should be eliminated because it is an enemy. It's risky to operate internally with this kind of mentality. The defence used against internal "enemies" should be distinguished from the defence used against exterior attack.
4. The way the military is seen when asked to carry out domestic security missions is another problem. Some troops believe they have a loftier purpose than this, and some even believe they have been called upon because the police are unable and ineffective at upholding law and order. As a consequence, instead of assisting the civil authorities as required by section 217 of the 1999 Constitution, the military typically takes over police activities. The military ends up assuming the lead rather than assisting the police or other worried civic officials. This may lead to resentment and mistrust between the troops assigned to the interior operations and the police force participating in the operation. Unhealthy competition could result from this, which could ultimately compromise security efforts (International Committee of the Red Cross United Relations with Armed and Security Forces, 2002). The Nigerian Army has argued in favour of a unified method to coordinate Joint Task Force Operations in the nation because it would stop different heads of security agencies from enforcing order and reversing it (Radio Nigeria Ibadan Online, 2013).
5. **Equipment:** The soldiers engaged in domestic security activities frequently lack the necessary equipment. If their lives are in danger from a hostile mob, soldiers involved in internal operations who are only armed will surely use it. In Nigeria, a typical crowd can only have access to stones, not firearms. It will not be appropriate to use lethal tools, such as firearms, in this circumstance.
6. **Strategy and tactics:** Combat operations depend on military strategy and techniques. To achieve broad political and military goals, military actions are planned, coordinated, and generally led by strategy. By making quick choices about troop movements and the use of weapons in combat, tactics put strategy into action. In times of conflict, armies all over the globe utilize certain strategies and techniques. The goal, the attack, surprise, security, unity of command, economy of force, mass, and manoeuvre are some of the most frequently mentioned concepts. History records that the Allied forces ultimately concurred on the goal of defeating Germany first with a straight offensive against the European continent, providing a renowned example that exemplifies most of these principles. They successfully gathered their forces in England, misled Germany about the invasion's entry point, gathered information on the location of German forces, and launched the massive operation known as Operation Overlord under the combined command of Gen. Dwight D. Eisenhower (Military Strategy and Tactics, Accessed April 04, 2023) (<http://www.molossia.org/milacademy/strategy.html>).
7. Another strategy is the Envelopment stratagem, which involves the surprise apparition of enemy forces on a flank or from behind. If a force is surrounded, it can be starved of provisions or come under assault from any direction (Azinge, 2013).

Dealing with a hostile crowd of civilians in a riot situation requires a completely different approach from an attack on an enemy position in conventional warfare. There is a need to adapt to the smaller scale of operations and the tactical mobility required. It has been agreed that internal conflicts do not always require all these tactics that soldiers typically employ (International Committee of the Red Cross United Relations with Armed and Security Forces, 2002).

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Conclusion

According to the study, there are many different ways that contemporary conflicts and violence manifest, and these ways are frequently determined by the actors and their justifications for using violence. This means that both state and non-state actors perpetrate contemporary violence, and these non-state actors could take the form of a militia, an insurgent, terrorist groups, or organized criminal and transnational criminal organizations. The issue with armed group actions, as seen in Kaduna State, is that they are hard to put down, and the authorities are powerless to stop the spread of armed violence. Numerous African police forces that are understaffed and poorly prepared to deal with their dangers are overwhelmed by armed groups that use irregular, sustained violence against government forces and civilian organizations. As a result, many African countries now routinely use the military to quell the violence and conflicts that these organizations incite. This is the scenario in Nigeria, where several regions of the nation continue to experience incidents of persistent and ongoing violent conflict and violence. This is problematic, especially when the military is generally abusive and engaged in numerous predatory activities that violate the human rights of the populace and further their sense of insecurity. Despite the military's acceptance as the most powerful organ of the state with the superior coercive force to suppress the threats and violence posed by armed groups.

Recommendations

The study made the following recommendations:

1. Improved civic authority over the military is required at all levels of government. Compliance would increase if the National Assembly, who are the representatives of the people, increased its parliamentary supervision of the military and its adherence to the rules governing its tasks. The disclosure of the military's standards of engagement for all domestic security operations could also fall under this category. The advantage of this is that it will increase accountability, guarantee compliance, and function as the benchmark for evaluating the actions and performance of people assigned for each ISOP in society. Without it, it is challenging to decide which staff actions are acceptable, when force should be used against citizens, and to what degree force can be used against a riotous or protesting civilian group.
2. The function of an impartial military ombudsman who can successfully step in to address cases of military mistreatment is another crucial factor to take into account. While the National Human Rights Commission of Nigeria currently handles comparable tasks as an ombudsman, an independent military investigator who is focused on military abuse problems would be more helpful. In order to properly handle the issue, it is imperative to give the daily presence of the military in society and the high frequency of military misuse primary focus. Additionally, given that the military is on active duty in many regions of the nation, this action may help to increase public confidence in this government entity and raise its standing and authority.

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Revolutionizing Nigerian Social Studies Classrooms: The Impact of Team Teaching

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Abstract

This paper explores the concept of revolutionizing Nigerian social studies classrooms through the implementation of team teaching. With the aim of enhancing the learning experience and outcomes of students, team teaching involves collaboration among educators to deliver instruction. The paper examines various forms of team teaching, identifies the benefits it brings to the social studies classroom, discusses different types of team-teaching approaches, and addresses the challenges that may arise during implementation. Drawing upon existing research and educational practices, this paper provides valuable insights into the potential of team teaching to transform Nigerian social studies classrooms and offers recommendations for effective implementation

Keywords: Revolutionizing, Social Studies Classrooms, Team-Teaching

Introduction

Team teaching is revolutionizing social studies classrooms in Nigerian schools, transcending the limitations of traditional teaching methods. By embracing this collaborative approach, educators are empowering students to become active participants in their learning journey, developing critical skills for engaged citizenship. Grofčiková and Trníková (2022) citing Plank (2013) argued that teaching is about leaving safe environment of individuals and be able to take the risk of collaborating with someone else. As Nigeria navigates its complex social, cultural, and historical landscape, team teaching stands as a catalyst for transformation, shaping a new generation of informed and socially conscious individuals ready to tackle the challenges of the future. In Nigerian schools, social studies plays a crucial role in shaping young minds, fostering critical thinking, and developing an understanding of the complex social, cultural, and historical fabric of the nation. However, traditional teaching methods often fall short in engaging students, limiting their active participation and inhibiting comprehensive learning experiences. Enter team teaching – an innovative approach that is revolutionizing social studies classrooms across Nigeria and redefining the boundaries of collaborative learning. Team teaching is an instructional strategy that involves two or more educators working together to plan, teach, and assess students' learning outcomes. Bates (2019) argued that teachers have to learn how to work in team and develop soft skills and necessary collaborative skills. Colleagues who teach together in a team can build up professional bonds and can be a model for students. Unlike the traditional one-teacher model, team teaching harnesses the strengths and diverse perspectives of multiple educators, creating a dynamic and interactive classroom environment. Team teaching not only enhances students' understanding of social studies concepts but also nurtures essential skills such as critical thinking, communication, and teamwork skills that are vital for active citizenship in a complex and interconnected world. When teachers work collaboratively, and engage the students in teaching and learning, they can help students solve problems and comprehend more complex ideas (Marantz Cohen & Mule 2019; Maija, Tiinamaija, & Antti, 2023).

Team teaching promotes a student-centered learning environment where learners are actively involved in the teaching and learning process. Through collaborative discussions, debates, and group activities, students gain a deeper understanding of social issues, cultural diversity, and historical events. According to Grofčiková and Trníková (2022) collaborative work means

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that every team member contributes and shares the ideas, opinions, knowledge, is engaged and motivated to complete goals. It includes a willingness to solve problems, thinking creatively and critically, recognizing strengths and weaknesses, responsibility and adaptability team teaching encourages educators to leverage their individual expertise and diverse backgrounds. By combining their knowledge, skills, and teaching styles, teachers can provide a richer and more comprehensive learning experience. For example, one teacher may excel in delivering engaging lectures, while another may specialize in facilitating hands-on activities or technology integration. This diversity creates a dynamic classroom atmosphere that caters to various learning styles and promotes inclusivity, ensuring that every student has the opportunity to thrive academically. Also, team teaching offers educators the chance to share the workload, reducing individual stress and burnout. Research suggests that collaborative learning, such as team teaching, promotes active engagement, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills among students. According to a study carried out by Johnson, Johnson and Smith (2014) it was found out that team teaching fosters positive interdependence, individual accountability, and interpersonal skills development. In a similar study by Slavin (1996) it was found out that team teaching led to higher test scores, increased knowledge retention, and improved critical thinking abilities compared to traditional teaching methods. Team teaching also enhances and encourages Teacher professional development. This is supported by study conducted by Supovitz and Turner (2000) on cooperative learning and achievement: 'What we know, what we need to know'. The study found out that team teaching promotes a culture of collaboration among teachers, leading to increased job satisfaction and professional growth. Thus, revolutionizing the social studies classroom through team teaching offers numerous benefits, including enhanced learning experiences, promotes active engagement, improved academic achievement, and professional development opportunities for teachers. These rationales, supported by research and empirical evidence, provide a compelling case for implementing team teaching in social studies classrooms.

Theoretical framework

The theory guiding this paper is hinged on Burns (1978) transformational leadership. The trust of the theory is on the idea that effective leaders can inspire and motivate their followers to achieve higher levels of performance and morality. The emphasis on Burns' (1978) theory of transformational leadership are:

2. **Idealized Influence (Charisma):** Transformational leaders serve as role models and gain the trust, respect, and admiration of their followers. They set high moral and ethical standards and inspire followers to emulate them.
3. **Inspirational Motivation:** Transformational leaders articulate a compelling vision of the future and inspire their followers to achieve it. They use language that evokes strong emotions and enthusiasm.
4. **Intellectual Stimulation:** These leaders encourage creativity and innovation among their followers. They challenge the status quo, promote critical thinking, and create an environment where new ideas are welcomed.
5. **Individualized Consideration:** Transformational leaders show genuine concern for the well-being and personal development of each follower. They provide support, coaching, and mentoring to help followers reach their full potential.

Burns' theory of transformational leadership theory can be used to explain team teaching in social studies classroom by laying emphasis on the key elements of the theory, which include idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration. Team teaching, which involves multiple teachers collaborating and coordinating their efforts to deliver instruction, can benefit greatly from transformational leadership practices.

Empirical Perspectives to revolutionizing Nigerian Social Studies Classrooms: The impact of team teaching

There are empirical evidence to support the incorporation of team teaching approaches in the Social Studies Classroom as illustrated by the studies below: Onyeachu (2017) investigated Team Teaching Approach in Nigerian Schools: An Innovative Strategy for Effective Teaching and Learning. The study found that team teaching allowed for more individualized attention and engagement between teachers and students, resulting in improved learning outcomes. In a study on The Impact of Team Teaching Strategy on Critical Thinking Skills of Secondary School Students in Imo State, Nigeria. Okoye and Nwosu (2016) found that when students are exposed to multiple viewpoints and teaching styles, they are more likely to develop critical thinking skills, analyze issues from different angles, and engage in meaningful discussions. Similarly, in a study by Igwe (2019) on Team Teaching: A Panacea for Classroom Management Challenges in Nigerian Secondary Schools. Result showed that having two teachers in the classroom allowed for better classroom management, as they could share responsibilities and maintain a more orderly environment. Additionally, in a study by Adedoyin (2018) on Integrating Cultural Diversity in the Teaching of Social Studies in Nigeria: A Need for Collaborative Team Teaching. The findings highlighted that team teaching can help incorporate local perspectives and traditions into the curriculum, making it more relatable and meaningful for students.

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These empirical studies reviewed suggest that team teaching can have a significant positive impact on Nigerian social studies classrooms. It can improve teacher-student interaction, bring diverse expertise into the classroom, enhance critical thinking skills, aid in classroom management, promote cultural relevance, and support teacher professional development. To revolutionize Nigerian social studies classrooms, education policymakers and institutions should consider implementing team teaching as a viable pedagogical approach.

Objectives of the Study

The paper seeks to achieve the following objectives

1. To examine the concept of team teaching in the context of the Nigerian social studies classroom.
2. To explore the potential benefits and challenges associated with team teaching.
3. To analyze the impact of team teaching on student learning outcomes in social studies.
4. To propose strategies for successful implementation of team teaching in Nigerian schools.

Methodology

The paper adopts the following methodology: The researchers conducted a comprehensive review of existing literature on team teaching, social studies education, and educational reforms in Nigeria. The used in the paper include journal articles, books, and reports as well as engagement with experts in the field of social studies so as to gain insights into the impact of team teaching on student learning outcomes and teacher effectiveness.

Concept of Team Teaching for social Studies Classroom

According to Buckley (2000) Team teaching involves a group of instructors working purposefully, regularly, and cooperatively to help a group of students of any age learn. Maija, Tiinamaija and Antti, (2023) posits that team teaching can take any of the following:

12. Involves two or more teachers within the teaching and learning environment.
13. Can vary along a continuum of collaboration.
14. Facilitates a learning community by impacting on both teaching and learning.
15. Can be either formal or informal.

From the above, we can deduce that team teaching set goals for a course, design a syllabus, prepare individual lesson plans, teach students, and evaluate the results. They share insights, argue with one another. The concept of team teaching holds immense promise for our social studies classroom. Through harnessing the power of collaboration, teachers can create an educational experience that transcends the boundaries of traditional teaching, inspiring our students to become active, critical thinkers and global citizens.

Concept of Social Studies Classroom

Danladi (2005), conceptualized social studies education as a field of study of man and his activities in relation to his social, economic, political, cultural and physical environments in order to achieve understandings, skills, attitudes and values that are necessary for personal and societal development. This paper adopts the explanation provided by Danladi (2005), because the definition is in conformity with the main focus of team teaching i.e. positively changing student's attitude, knowledge and skills for the betterment of the society. Social Studies Classrooms: Are educational spaces where students learn about the various aspects of society, including history, geography, economics, politics, and culture. The classrooms provide students with a comprehensive understanding of the world, its history, and its diverse cultures, empowering them to become active and engaged citizens in an increasingly complex global society.

Forms of team-teaching for Social Studies Classroom

Team teaching is a collaborative teaching approach in which two or more teachers work together to plan, teach, and evaluate a course or a lesson. This approach is often used in social studies classrooms, where multiple perspectives and interdisciplinary approaches are valued. Sandholtz (2000) identified three forms of team-teaching configurations, namely: (1) Two or more teachers loosely sharing responsibility; (2) Team planning, but individual instruction; and (3) Joint planning, instruction, and evaluation of the learning experience. Other classifications of team teaching include:

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10. Co-teaching: In this form of team teaching, two or more teachers share responsibility for planning and delivering instruction to a group of students. According to Friend and Cook (2016), co-teaching involves "two or more professionals delivering substantive instruction to a diverse, or blended, group of students in a shared classroom space. Co-teaching can take many forms, including one teacher taking the lead while the other provides support, or both teachers taking an equal role in instruction.
11. Parallel teaching: In parallel teaching, the class is divided into two or more groups, and each teacher is responsible for teaching one group. According to Scruggs and Mastropieri (2014), parallel teaching "involves two or more teachers working with different groups of students simultaneously, usually in the same classroom". This form of team teaching can be especially effective for providing differentiated instruction or for addressing the needs of students with diverse learning styles.
12. Station teaching: In station teaching, the class is divided into small groups, and each group rotates through a series of learning stations, each led by a different teacher or instructional aide. According to Friend and Cook (2016), station teaching "involves the use of physical stations or centers in which students rotate through a series of activities". This form of team teaching can be effective for providing hands-on learning experiences and for engaging students in a variety of learning activities.

Benefits of Team Teaching for Social Studies Teachers

When teachers work collaborative, share and exchange ideas, they stand better chance to optimize their teaching strategies. Thus Pasetto, Barreiros, Corrêa and Freudenheim (2021) identified three benefits of team teaching for teachers, the benefit include:

1. Changing the teacher's mind set becomes more open in dealing with and solving every problem of learning social studies in the classroom so that it is easy to solve by frequently involving colleagues and friends of the same profession to get new ideas through focus group discussions.
2. The teacher can anticipate and periodically evaluate the achievement of standard competencies.
3. Being an effective place for resource sharing between involved stakeholders especially all parties internally and externally, resulting in a collective awareness that the progress and success of learning social studies is the responsibility of all stakeholders involved.

Other benefits include: Capacity building, developing positive self-esteem, and developing interpersonal competence. One of the key benefits of team teaching is its ability to create a student-centered learning environment, where students actively participate in the learning process.

Types of team teaching for Social Studies Classroom

Team teaching in the context of a social studies classroom involves collaboration between two or more educators who work together to plan, deliver, and assess instruction. This collaborative approach has several types or models that can be implemented depending on the goals and needs of the students and teachers involved. Some of the types of team teaching in the context of a social studies classroom include the following:

4. Parallel Teaching: In parallel teaching, the teachers divide the class into two or more groups and simultaneously teach the same content. Each teacher takes responsibility for a specific group, ensuring that all students receive instruction and support. According to Friend and Bursuck (2018) parallel teaching can be used to provide differentiated instruction or to reinforce concepts through additional examples or practice. 'Parallel teaching is an effective strategy in a social studies classroom for providing differentiated instruction and reinforcing concepts. By dividing the class into groups, teachers can address the diverse needs of students' (Friend & Bursuck, 2018).
5. Station Teaching: In station teaching, the classroom is divided into stations or learning centers where students rotate to engage in different activities or receive instruction from different teachers. Each teacher prepares and leads a specific station. This model allows for small-group instruction, independent work, and collaborative learning experiences. The station teaching model in social studies classrooms promotes active student engagement and provides opportunities for differentiated instruction. Students rotate between stations, engaging in various activities that cater to different learning styles and needs" (Friend & Bursuck, 2018).
6. Alternative Teaching: Involves one teacher working with a smaller group of students who require additional support or enrichment while the other teacher leads the main instruction for the rest of the class. This model allows for targeted instruction and individualized attention for students who need it. According to Tomlinson, Brimijoin and Narvaez, (2008)

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alternative teaching is an effective approach in a social studies classroom for providing targeted instruction. Thus, by dividing the class into two groups, one teacher can provide additional support or enrichment while the other teacher focuses on delivering the main instruction.

Additionally, a team can be single-discipline, interdisciplinary, or school-within-a-school teams that meet with a common set of students over an extended period of time. New teachers may be paired with veteran teachers. Innovation is encouraged, and modifications in class size, location, and time are permitted. Different personalities, voices, values, and approaches spark interest and keep attention (Maija, Tiinamaija, & Antti, 2023).

Challenges of Team Teaching for Social Studies Classroom

Team teaching can offer numerous benefits in the social studies classroom. However, it also presents certain challenges such as:

- a. **Time Management:** Time management is a significant challenge in team teaching, as coordinating schedules and planning lessons together can be time-consuming. (Ylönen, 2019)
- b. **Consistency in Instruction:** Maintaining consistency in instruction can be challenging in team teaching, as different educators may have diverse teaching styles and approaches. (Lund & Stenfors-Hayes, 2020).
- c. **Communication and Collaboration:** Effective communication and collaboration between team teachers are crucial, but challenges can arise due to differences in opinions, lack of coordination, or conflicts. (Shin & Turner, 2018)
- d. **Assessment and Grading:** "Developing consistent assessment practices and grading criteria can be challenging in team teaching, as educators may have varying perspectives on evaluating student performance. (Petersen, 2019)
- e. **Classroom Management:** Maintaining classroom management and discipline can be more challenging in team teaching, as students may test boundaries or become confused with multiple authority figures. (Kos, 2018)
- f. **Roles, expectations, experience and knowledge** are related to "the conflict that could arise if there is uncertainty or disagreement in the role of each team member. (Letterman & Dugan, 2004).

Impact of Team Teaching for Social Studies Classroom

Team teaching in the social studies classroom can have a significant impact on student learning and engagement. Below are some insights on the impact of team teaching:

1. **Enhanced Student learning:** Team teaching can lead to enhanced student learning outcomes, as it allows for a variety of instructional methods and perspectives.
2. **Improved Critical Thinking and Collaboration Skills** among students.
3. **Increased Student Engagement**
4. **Positive Classroom Climate:** Team teaching contributes to a positive classroom climate, fostering a sense of community and support among students and educators." (Kendall, 2020)
5. **Diverse Perspectives and Cultural Understanding:** Team teaching brings diverse perspectives into the social studies classroom, promoting cultural understanding and a broader understanding of historical events. (Wong, 2018).

Conclusion

In conclusion, team teaching has the potential to revolutionize Nigerian social studies classrooms by fostering a collaborative and dynamic learning environment. The analysis of various forms of team teaching has revealed that it encourages educators to share their expertise, experiences, and resources, leading to increased student engagement and improved academic performance. The benefits of team teaching extend beyond the classroom, as it promotes professional growth and development among educators, while also enhancing their job satisfaction. Furthermore, the exploration of different types of team teaching has demonstrated the flexibility and adaptability of this approach, allowing teachers to tailor their instruction to meet the diverse needs of students. By embracing team teaching and addressing the challenges associated with it, Nigerian social studies classrooms can be transformed into vibrant and interactive learning spaces that foster critical thinking, collaboration, and cultural understanding among students.

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Recommendations

The paper put forward the following recommendations:

3. Educational institutions invest in professional development programs for teachers to acquire the necessary skills and knowledge.
4. Collaboration among educators should be encouraged and supported through regular team meetings, mentoring, and peer observations.
5. Communication channels should be established to address any conflicts or concerns that may arise during the implementation process.
6. Policymakers should consider allocating resources and providing incentives to schools and educators that adopt team teaching practices.

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Theme-types and Thematic (Progression)... (Allagbe, et. al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10431599>

Theme-types and Thematic (Progression) Patterns in the Argumentative Essays by Second-Year English Major Students from the Université André Salifou

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Abstract

This paper aims at analyzing the Theme-types and Thematic (progression) patterns in the argumentative essays written by second-year English major students from the Université André Salifou (henceforth, UAS), Niger Republic. Drawing its theoretical underpinnings from Systemic Functional Linguistics (henceforth, SFL) and the descriptive mixed research method, the study randomly selected and examined 10 out of the 80 argumentative essays (i.e., 12.50%) written by the English as Foreign Language (henceforth, EFL) students enrolled in the second year (2020-2021). The findings revealed that 8 out of the 10 texts contain two Theme-types: Topical Themes and Textual Themes. They also showed that most of the Topical Themes are unmarked, suggesting that the subjects in the clauses occur in their usual slots. The marked Themes, though they exist in low proportions in the texts, proved that the texts are rhetorically well-organized. The use of Textual Themes in the texts exuded too that the texts are rhetorically well-organized. Again, the findings indicated that all the texts comprise two major Theme classes (a and b), the dominant type being Theme class (a), confirming once more that Topical Themes are placed in their usual slots. Finally, the findings unveiled that only two types of Thematic progression pattern were selected in the texts: Theme reiteration and the zig-zag pattern. In other words, the multiple-Rheme pattern is absent from the texts, indicating that the students still find it difficult to organize their texts. Hence, more efforts should be devoted to text creation and organization in the EFL writing class.

Keywords: Argumentative essays, Theme-types, textual meaning, thematic pattern, thematic progression pattern

Introduction

There is an increasing number of lexico-grammatical studies on student writing drawing on Systemic Functional Linguistics, (henceforth, SFL) which use the T-unit or the clause complex rather than the clause as the unit of analysis (see Ebrahimi and Ebrahimi, 2012 and Nguyen and Nguyen 2018, for instance). It must be made clear from the onset that such studies create confusion in the mind of student researchers in this field. To dispel this confusion, proponents of SFL have recently established that the central unit of any lexico-grammatical analysis is the clause (Eggs, 2004; Fontaine, 2013; Halliday and Mathiessen, 2014, etc.). In fact, these scholars posit that the clause encodes three strands of simultaneous meaning, namely: ideational meaning, the interpersonal meaning and the textual meaning. Ideationally, the clause is seen as representation; i.e., it encodes the speaker's or writer's representation of reality, involving particular processes, participants and circumstances. Interpersonally, the clause is seen as exchange; i.e., it encodes the speaker's or writer's action and interaction with the addressee, including Mood, Modality and Adjunct choices. Textually, the clause is seen as message; i.e., it encodes how the speaker or writer organizes language, the means s/he draws on to produce a meaningful message or text. To

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organize language and realize textual meaning, the speaker or writer, as systemic linguists cogently hold, needs to develop or deploy such text-forming resources as cohesion or cohesive devices, logical relations (taxis and logico-semantics), Theme and Theme progression (see Allagbé, Tankari and Maignero, 2021 and Allagbé, Tankari and Tchada, 2022, on the study of the first two in student writing). The current study is concerned with (the analysis of) textual meaning in student writing.

Fontaine (2013, p. 139) claims that “There is no more basic role for the clause than that of creating text. Every clause is either constitutive of a text or part of a larger text.” Further, she adds that “Within the clause, the main resource for creating text is referred to as Theme [...]” (Ibid.). Theme actually comprises two functional components: Theme and Rheme. Eggins (2004, p. 299) points out that “Theme is the element which comes first in the clause.” According to Halliday and Matthiessen (2014, p. 89), “The Theme is the element that serves as the point of departure of the message; it is that which locates and orients the clause within its context.” Concurring with the foregoing, Fontaine (2013, p. 140) observes that “Within the clause, Theme indicates the clausal element that the speaker [or writer] has selected as the starting point; a metaphoric peg on which to hang the message.” For Halliday and Matthiessen (Ibid.), “The speaker [or writer] chooses the Theme as his or her point of departure to guide the addressee in developing an interpretation of the message; by making part of the message prominent as Theme, the speaker [or writer] enables the addressee to process the message.” Acknowledging the foregoing, Fontaine (2013, p. 140) highlights the importance of the initial position of the clause in English. In that regard, she writes:

In English, the initial position of the clause is significant for a variety of reasons. For example, it often introduces the topic about which something is being said, it may indicate the relevance of the clause to the surrounding text, it may orient the message in a particular way, or it may mark a transition in the text. This is not to say that the thematic elements of the clause are more important than the rest of the clause but rather that they contribute directly and in a pivotal sense to the creation of text.

On the contrary, the Rheme is the part of the clause in which the Theme is developed (Eggins, 2004, p. 300, Halliday and Matthiessen, 2014, p. 89). Eggins (2004, p. 299) posits that Theme involves three major systems: choice of type of Theme, choice of *marked* or *unmarked* Theme, and choice of predicated or unpredicated Theme. There are three types of Theme: viz. Topical (or Experiential), Interpersonal and Textual. A Topical or Experiential Theme is the starting point of the clause to which a Transitivity function (participant, process or circumstance) is assigned. An Interpersonal Theme is the point of departure of the clause to which a Mood label (subject, finite, vocative, etc.) is given. A Textual Theme is a clause element occurring in Thematic position which can neither be assigned a Mood label nor a Transitivity label. A Textual Theme plays an important role of cohesive work by relating the clause to its context. There are two types of Textual elements, namely: continuity adjuncts (e.g. oh, yes/yea/yep, no/nope, well, etc.) and conjunctive adjuncts (e.g. and, then, but, yet, however, etc.). It must be noted that the aforementioned three Theme-types correspond to the three-metafunctional structure of the clause. It must be noted too that Topical Theme is obligatory in a clause, while Interpersonal and Textual Themes are optional (Nguyen and Nguyen, 2018, p. 87). A Theme which conflates with any other constituent from the Mood system is called a *marked* Theme. However, when a Theme conflates with the Mood structure constituent that typically occurs in first position in clauses of that Mood class, it is referred to as *unmarked*. In other words, a Theme is said to be *unmarked* when it is used in its usual/normal/expected Subject position/slot (Amoussou, 2016; Allagbé, Amoussou and Tchada, 2020). As for Theme Predication, it is defined as “a process used when the speaker/writer wishes to give emphasis to a constituent that would otherwise be emphasized, while maintaining the ‘real’ news, which is in the Rheme of the original clause” (Eggins, 2004, p. 316). There is also what is called a ‘multiple Theme’. This notion presupposes that we have a ‘simple Theme’. A simple Theme is formed when the Theme of a clause consists of only one single structural element (Halliday and Matthiessen, 2014, p. 92). The structural element is the obligatory topical Theme. But a multiple Theme indicates that there are several textual and/or interpersonal Themes occurring before the obligatory topical Theme (Eggins, 2004, p. 307).

The analysis of Theme in student writing is very important for two main reasons. First, this can help us gain an insight into how students select Theme to create cohesion and coherence within the clause and across the clause level. In this perspective, Halliday and Matthiessen (2014, p. 133) cogently argue that “In the Theme-Rheme structure, it is the Theme that is the prominent element. [...] by analysing the thematic structure of a text clause by clause, we can gain an insight into its texture and understand how the writer made clear to us the nature of his [or her] underlying concerns.” Second, the analysis of Theme in student writing can help us unveil how student writers introduce the topic at hand, develop and orient it by means of successive Thematic patterns indicating what systemic linguists’ term ‘Thematic progression’ or ‘method of development’ (Eggins, 2004). Eggins identifies three types of Theme (progression) pattern, namely: Theme reiteration, the zig-zag pattern and the multiple-Rheme pattern. According to this scholar, Theme reiteration is one basic way to keep a text focused (i.e.,

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cohesive) by simply reiterating an element. The zig-zag pattern, on the other hand, denotes a pattern in which an element which is introduced in the Rheme in use in clause 1 gets promoted to become the Theme of clause 2. In the multiple-Rheme pattern, she further explains, the Theme of one clause introduces a number of different pieces of information, each of which is then picked up and made Theme in subsequent clauses (Eggins, 2004, pp. 324-325).

Empirical research on the development, deployment and use of Theme-types and Thematic (progression) patterns in student writing has been carried out by linguists and language educators in a recent past. Ebrahimi and Ebrahimi (2012), for instance, explored Theme markedness in a corpus of 180 compositions written by 60 EFL students: 20 sophomores, 20 juniors, and 20 seniors majoring in Teaching English as Foreign Language (TEFL). To gather data from the three categories of participants, the researchers asked them to write three pictorial stories. Using Halliday's (1994) model of thematic organization and clause complexity as a unit of analysis, the written texts were examined to control the students' use of marked Themes, and find out whether there were any statistically significant differences among the three groups with regard to their use of marked Themes. The findings revealed that the three categories used a small number of marked Themes in their texts, suggesting that most of the Topical Themes occupy both Thematic and Subject positions. According to these scholars, Theme/Subject compliance is indicative of structural simplicity of students' writings with different academic experience. On the other hand, the low portion of the marked Themes identified in the students' written texts, they added, indicated that their writing is less argumentative in nature. Again, it was reported that the similarity of the number of marked Themes used in the three groups can be explained in terms of genre. However, the slight increase in the use of marked Themes moving from sophomore to senior group can be accounted for in terms of academic experience.

Nguyen and Nguyen (2018) also investigated the Thematic progression patterns employed in 20 academic IELTS sample essays from books published by Cambridge University Press and IELTS official websites with the band score of 9 written by highly successful test-takers. Using the descriptive method combined with qualitative and quantitative approaches, the researchers segmented the essays into T-units. A T-unit, according to Fries (1994) (cited in Nguyen and Nguyen, 2018, p. 89) is a clause complex which consists of an independent clause together with all hypotactically related clauses and words which are dependent on it. The aim of this investigation was to find out which elements were selected as Themes in the sample essays. From the findings, the scholars reported that a total number of 491 Themes was used in the essays. Topical Themes ranked first with a figure of 311 (i.e., 63.4%) followed by Textual Themes representing 144 (i.e., 29.3%) and Interpersonal Themes with a rate of 36 (i.e., 7.3%). They further noted that a large proportion of Topical Themes found in the essays are often heavily modified nominal groups and dependent clauses. They also indicated that the great number of Textual Themes employed in the essays revealed that the clauses therein are joined together logico-semantically. Likewise, they reported that the deployment of Interpersonal Themes allowed the writers to convey their personal judgment in the texts with a view to establishing an interaction between them and their readers. Again, they added that the writers' use of the few interpersonal themes gave their texts an impersonalized tone because academic writing is always formal in tone (Oshima and Hogue, 1991, p. 3); i.e., the academic writing style is objective rather than subjective, formal rather than colloquial in nature. Moreover, they quantified the rate of simple and multiple Themes in the essays. They deduced from the analysis that, out of the 311 Themes the writers employed, 149 (i.e., 47.9%) are simple and 162 (i.e., 52.1%) were multiple. The multiple-Theme structure identified in the essays is Textual[^] Interpersonal[^] Topical. They explained that multiple themes prove to play an important role in construing the writer's point of view and in helping the writer to organize the message and connect the ideas in the text. Therefore, multiple themes are more appropriate for IELTS essay writing in order to indicate a high level of English proficiency (Nguyen and Nguyen, 2018, p. 90).

In the same token, Anwar and Amri, (2020) analysed the types of Theme and the Thematic patterns used in the discussion texts written by the third year students of English Department of Universitas Negeri Padang. These researchers selected 20 students enrolled in the aforementioned institution in the 2018/2019 academic year, and asked them to write a discussion text based on one of the three topics suggested. Drawing on a descriptive qualitative method (a content analysis method), the texts discussion written by the selected students were examined. From the findings, the scholars reported that the texts are composed of clauses constituted by four Theme types: simple unmarked Topical Theme (SUT), simple marked Theme (SMT), multiple unmarked Theme (MUT), and multiple marked Theme (MMT). They further noted that the most frequently used type in the students' texts is SUT with a figure of 338/638 (i.e., 52.98%). It is followed by MUT with a number of 206/638 (i.e., 32.29%), SMT representing 71/638 (i.e., 11.13%) and MMT with a total of 23/638 (i.e., 3.60%). They also found out that the identified SUTs in the texts were deployed in the clauses located not only in the introduction and conclusion but also in the arguments, suggesting that both the pros and cons in the students' discussion texts are mostly presented in SUT clauses. The foregoing finding, they explained, is in contrast with the finding of a previous study (Rosa, 2007a) which argued that con

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arguments are more frequently presented in marked Themes. They also explained this contrast in terms of difference in writing: students or novice writers are less creative and pay less attention to the organization of ideas. In addition, these scholars reported that the students' texts are made up clauses including the following Thematic patterns: Topical, Textual^Topical, and Interpersonal-Textual-Topical. The most frequently used pattern in the texts is Topical with a figure of 409/638 (i.e., 64.11%). The foregoing pattern, they explained, is due to the dominance of simple Themes in the students' texts. It is followed by Textual-Topical representing 225/638 (i.e., 35.26%). This pattern, they indicated, is motivated by the absence of interpersonal Theme from the multiple Themes composed of two types of Themes. Next comes the Interpersonal-Textual-Topical pattern with a number of 4/638 (i.e., 0.63%). The preceding pattern, they noted, is motivated by the very small occurrence of interpersonal theme in the students' discussion texts.

Mustika, Nurdin and Sakina (2020) investigated Theme and Thematic Progression in students' Recount texts too. The study was conducted in a private senior high school in Bandung and comprised nine tenth grade students' recount texts classified into three different levels of achievement: low, middle, and high achievers. Employing a qualitative design, the researchers examined the texts with a view to unveiling how the students organize their ideas in their recount texts, from the perspective of Theme and Thematic Progression, and finding out the implication of the Theme and Thematic Progression used by the students for the flow of their texts. From the analysis, the researchers inferred that that Topical Themes are the most dominant type of Theme used by the students from all achievement levels with the total percentage 73.5%. They further indicated that that most of the Topical Themes were unmarked (57.69%). They also noted that the unmarked Topical Themes frequently used by the students in their descriptive texts are pronouns and nominal group complexes. Again, they observed that the unmarked Themes occur in form of referential items (i.e., it, this, that, etc.) and ellipsis. In addition, the scholars reported that marked Themes are quite frequently found in the students' texts. In fact, the marked Themes identified in all the texts represented 15.81%. As the analysis further exuded, marked Themes are the third frequent Theme used across the three levels of achievement with 10.81% in the high achievement, 23.38% in the middle achievement, and 15.22% in the low achievement. The analysis also indicated that the marked Themes occurring in the students' descriptive texts are mostly in form of adverbial groups and prepositional phrases which function as Adjuncts of the clauses. The researchers further reported that the second frequent Theme employed in the students' recount texts is Textual Theme with 26.07%, suggesting the students' ability to establish the cohesion of text. They also reported that interpersonal Themes are the least type of Theme found in the text with 00.43%, indicating that the students rarely employed modulation and modularization in their texts. The rare use of interpersonal Themes in students' recount text, they explained, is acceptable since it commonly occurs in the conversation form (such as in interrogative clauses, polarity answers, and vocative adjuncts) while conversation is rarely used in a recount text. In addition to the identification of Theme, they analysed the Thematic Progression patterns in the students' recount texts. The analysis revealed that the students used three of the four Theme Progression patterns, namely: Theme reiteration Pattern, Zig-zag Pattern and Multiple-Theme Pattern. The analysis also indicated that Theme reiteration patterns are the most frequent patterns realized by the students from all achievement levels with 57.06%, suggesting that the students succeeded in keeping the focus of their texts by repeating their thematic element(s). Theme reiteration patterns are followed by zig-zag patterns with 36.16%, implying that the students have been able to make a logical relation and elaboration in their texts. The least Thematic Progression patterns identified in the students' texts are the multiple-theme progression patterns with 6.78% from the total patterns, suggesting that the students have not been able to manage the organization of their texts.

Similarly, Na-on and Jaturapitakkul (2017) studied the research project abstracts written by Thai EFL engineering undergraduates with a view to unveiling how they construct their ideas therein. In fact, 39 abstracts (13 from each of the 3 departments: Computer Engineering, Civil Engineering, and Chemical Engineering) written by Thai students were collected for the analysis, and the thematic (progression) and rhetorical patterns therein were identified. The abstracts were extracted both from the university's online library system and directly from the respective departments. The abstracts were actually based on three criteria: 1) the year of publication was from the academic years 2010-2015, 2) the length of the abstracts was between 200-300 words, for the ability to see the TP patterns clearly when analyzed and 3) all the abstracts were written by students who enrolled in the International Program. From the analysis, the researchers deduced that the abstracts contained the three patterns: Constant TP, Linear TP and Split Rheme. Further, they noted that Constant TP (50.92%) ranked first, Linear TP (48.35%) second and Split Rheme (00.73%) third in the abstracts. They also compared the use of the TP patterns across the three departments. They observed that the Computer and Civil Engineering departments employed Constant TP the most frequently whereas the Chemical Engineering department used the pattern the least often. Among the three, only the Civil Engineering department did not employ any Split Rheme pattern in their writing. Following these findings, the researchers recommended that teachers should familiarize their learners gradually with the concept of cohesion, Theme, and Rheme and

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eventually the Thematic Progression theory as this will help them better understand their own writing along with its generic processes.

As the studies reviewed above clearly exude, the use of Theme and Thematic progression in student writing plays a very important role as it encodes cohesion and coherence therein. The aforementioned studies reviewed also indicate that no prior analysis of student writing in an EFL context has thus far been conducted. This is the research gap that this paper sets out to fill. The next section is concerned with the analysis of the Theme-types and Thematic (progression) patterns deployed in the selected written essays under study, and the discussion of the findings arrived at.

Objectives of the Study

The current paper is set against the background of the above-mentioned theoretical claims. It aims at analysing the Theme-types and Thematic (progressive) patterns in the argumentative essays written by second-year English major students from the Université André Salifou (henceforth, UAS), Niger Republic. In the academic year 2020-2021, eighty students enrolled for the second year and followed a 10-week writing course. At the end of the course, they wrote an argumentative essay on one of the two topics below:

1. Should students be allowed to use their smart phone in class?
2. Modern technology has made the world a better place to live in today.

Research Questions

In consonance with the above-stated research objectives, this study formulates the questions below which it intends to answer:

4. What kind(s) of Theme do second-year English major students choose or use in their argumentative essays?
5. What kind(s) of Thematic (progression) pattern do second-year English major students deploy in their argumentative essays?

Methodology

To reach the set goal of this investigation, ten (i.e., 12.5%) out of the eighty student essays were randomly selected: 5 on the first topic and 5 on the second one. These essays are numbered (Texts 1-5 are on the first topic whereas Texts 6-10 on the second one). This paper employs the descriptive mixed method research design which consists in describing, identifying and classifying the Theme-types and Thematic (progression) patterns in the students' essays. The identified Theme-types and Thematic patterns are first quantified and tabulated before the findings thereof are discussed.

Results

Research Question 1

What kind(s) of Theme do second-year English major students choose or use in their argumentative essays?

We begin this section with the analysis of Theme in the students' argumentative essays. Recall that these essays are ten in total and they are numbered Text 1 to Text 10. This analysis follows Eggins (2004) and Fontaine (2013). In Eggins (2004) and Fontaine (2013), the clause rather than the T-unit or clause complex is considered as the unit of any lexicogrammatical analysis. In line with this criterion, the 10 texts are first of all segmented into clauses, and then the clause constituents therein are rigorously described or identified in consonance with the theoretical framework outlined in the first section. Due to space limitations, the analysis proper is not displayed here. Only the statistics drawn from the study are reported instead. The Theme-types identified in the texts under study are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Frequency Distribution of Theme-types in the Texts

FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION OF THEME-TYPES IN THE TEXTS											
Theme-types		Text1	Text2	Text3	Text4	Text5	Text6	Text7	Text8	Text9	Text10
Topical	Marked	08	02	03	04	06	11	02	04	05	08
	Unmarked	33	24	30	40	48	44	26	35	36	16
Interpersonal		01	00	00	00	00	01	00	00	00	00
Textual		19	09	19	15	20	24	05	13	16	09
Total		61	35	52	59	74	80	33	52	57	33

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As the table above clearly shows, Text 1 contains a total number of 61 Themes. In this text, Topical Themes rank first with a figure of 41/61 (i.e., 67.21%), Textual Themes second with a count of 19/61 (i.e., 31.14%) and Interpersonal Theme third with a number of 01/61 (i.e., 01.63%). Thirty-three (1; 2; 4; 5; 6; 7; 8; 9; 10; 11; 12; 13; 14; 16; 17; 18; 19; 20; 21; 22; 23; 24; 25; 26; 27; 28; (29); (33); 34; 36; 38; 40 and 41) out of the 41 Topical Themes are actually *unmarked*, suggesting that the subjects in the clauses constitutive of the text are predominantly used in their usual/normal/expected positions/slots. The *unmarked* Themes found in Text 1 can be grouped into three categories: common nouns ('Cell phones' in clauses [1; 11; 13 and 41] and 'students' in clauses [5 and 32]), a relative pronoun ('where' in clause [19]) and verbal nouns or/and predicators ('to use' in clause [4]; 'to research' in clause [7]; 'to forget' in clause [8]; 'to look at' in clause [18], etc.). The aforementioned common nouns are anaphorically referred to in the text with the pronouns 'it' in clauses (2; 6; 9; 12; 14 and 38) and 'they' and its variant 'their' in clauses (15; 16; 17; 26; 28; (29); (33); 34; 36 and 40). The bracketed clauses in the foregoing denote ellipsis. This is to say, the *unmarked* Topical Theme in each of these clauses is not overtly given but implied. The *marked* Topical Themes identified in the text are of two types: single words ('anything' [31]; 'Physically' [32] and 'Moroly' (Morally) [35]) and groups of words ('In education' [3]; 'In sum' [30]; 'In sum up' [37]; 'for any work' (39) and 'For example, if their teachers give them a work' [15]). In clause (31), the writer has placed a Goal in Thematic position, suggesting that the Goal has been emphasized or given prominence in the clause. In contrast, in clauses (3; 30; 32; 35; 37 and 39), circumstances are placed in Thematic position, and by so doing they become foregrounded. According to Thompson (2004, p. 109 cited in Fontaine, 2013, p. 79), circumstances "encode the background against which the process takes place". In this perspective, Eggins (2004, p. 339) argues that the use of foregrounded Themes in a text is "[...] one realization of a careful written mode, in which the writer has planned the rhetorical development of the text to allow the foregrounding of Circumstantial information". It must be noted that what is foregrounded in clause (15) is a hypotactic structure or a dependent clause. By placing a dependent clause in Thematic position, the writer wants to make the text "[...] appear more spoken, as the frequent use of dependent clauses in Thematic position contributes to neutralizing the distinction between spoken and written language." (Ibid.). In other words, as Eggins (2004, p. 323) further explains,

Hypotactic structures such as these allow the writer to maintain a very congruent style: rather than building up the lexical density of the text, the writer exploits the strategy of grammatical complexity. However, the Thematic position of the dependent clause indicates an amount of pre-planning that is less common in spoken than written language. Thus the text is able to 'sound' like written language, while remaining accessible by maintaining its closeness to the spoken language.

Like *marked* Themes, the 11 Textual Themes (5; 6; 9; 11; 12; 14; 15; 20; 25; 26; 28; 29; 33; 34; 36; 38; 39 and 40) found in Text 1 somehow suggest that the text is rhetorically well-written. In fact, all the Textual Themes identified in the text are Conjunctive items, indicating thus that the text is more characterized by feats of written language. Some of the Conjunctive elements in the text are *because* in (5); *Thus* in (6); *and* in (9), etc. The only Interpersonal Theme 'MAYBE' (24) used in the text is a mood adjunct and expresses probability, adding an interpersonal meaning to the clause in which it belongs.

Unlike Text 1, Text 2 comprises 35 Themes, and these Themes are of two types: 26 (i.e., 74.29%) Topical Themes and 09 (i.e., 25.71%) Textual Themes. Twenty-four out of the 26 Topical Themes are *unmarked* (1; 2; 3; 4; 5; 6; 7; 8; 9; 10; 11; 12; 14; 15; 16; 17; 18; 19; 20; (21); 23; 24; 25 and 26), indicating that the subjects in the clauses are chiefly employed in their usual/normal/expected positions/slots. The *unmarked* Topical Themes in Text 2 fall into four groups: common nouns ('Cell phone' in clauses [1; 10 and 12] 'people' in clause [2] and 'students' in clauses [5; 8; 11; 15 and 17]), a relative pronoun ('which' in clause [16]); a nominal group ('the use of cell phone for the students in class' in clause [24]) and verbal nouns or/and predicators ('to facilitate' in clause [3]; 'to use' in clauses [6 and 9]; 'to by (buy)' in clause [18] and 'to forget about' in clause [26]). Three of the foregoing tokens ('Cell phone'; 'students' and 'the use of cell phone for the students in class' are referentially referred to in the text with 'it' (7 and 25) and 'they' (19 and [21]). While the pronoun 'it' is used in clause (7) to point back to 'Cell phone', it is employed in clause (25) to refer to the nominal group 'the use of cell phone for the students in class'. The pronoun 'they', on the other hand, is anaphorically used to point back to 'students'. The two *marked* Topical Themes in Text 2 are of only one type: prepositional phrases ('In this case' [13] and 'From what' [22]). As stated earlier on, the use of marked Themes in a text serves to foreground Circumstantial information in it, exuding thus that it is rhetorically well-planned. The use of Textual Themes in a text also shows that the text is well-planned. In fact, in Text 2, there are 09 Textual Themes, all of which are Conjunctive elements (*that* [2 and 24]; *In spite of* [4]; *because* [7]; *in order to* [14]; *So* [15 and 19]; *and* [21] and *but* [25]).

Text 3 encompasses 52 Themes. Like Text 2, this text contains only two Theme-types: 33 (i.e., 63.46%) Topical Themes and 19 (i.e., 36.54%) Textual Themes. Thirty out of the 33 Topical Themes are *unmarked* (1; 2; 3; 4; 5; 6; 7; 8; 10;

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11; 12; 13; 14; 15; 16; 17; 18; 20; 21; 22; 23; 24; 25; 26; 27; 28; 29; 30; 32 and 33). This reveals that the subjects in the clauses are mainly placed in their usual/normal/expected positions/slots. The *unmarked* Topical Themes found in the text can be classified into six groups: a common noun ('Cell phones' in clauses [1 and 32]); nominal groups ('the cell phone(s)' in clauses [7 and 25]; 'some/most of the people' in clauses [3 and 14] and 'The more concern' in clause [22]); nominalizations ('using a cell phone in class' in clauses [3 and 11]); an indefinite pronoun ('anything' in clause [23]), relative pronouns ('where' in clause [16]; 'who' in clause [21] and 'which' in clause [33]) and verbal nouns or/and predicators ('to allowed (allow)' in clause [5]; 'to use' in clause [6]; 'to do' in clauses [12; 18 and 29]; 'to make' in clauses [13 and 30]; 'to work' in clause [26] and 'to sue (use)' in clause [27]. The token 'Cell phone' is referred to in the text with the pronoun 'it' in clauses (8; [10]; 17 and 18). The three *marked* Themes identified in this text can be classified into two: single words (Generally [9] and 'whatever' [19]) and a group of words (or a transitional expression) ('To conclude' [31]). The use of these marked Themes in the text serves to encode Circumstantial information in it, showing that it is rhetorically well-organized. Likewise, the use of the 19 Textual Themes (all of them are Conjunctive items) in the text indicates that the text is well-organized. Some of the Textual Themes in Text 3 are *Even though* (2); *that* (3); *but* (4); *Thus* (7); *because* (8), etc.

In the same token, Text 4 counts 59 Themes distributed across two types of Themes: 44 (i.e., 74.58%) Topical Themes and 15 (i.e., 25.42%) Textual Themes. Forty out of the 44 Topical Themes are *unmarked* (1; 3; 4; 5; 6; 7; 8; 9; 10; 11; 12; 13; 14; 15; 16; 17; 18; 19; 21; 22; 23; 25; 26; 27; 28; 29; 30; 31; 32; 33; 34; 35; 37; 38; 39; 40; 41; 42; 43 and 44), specifying that the subjects in the clauses are predominantly employed in their usual/normal/expected positions/slots. The *unmarked* Topical Themes in Text 4 can be grouped into four categories: common nouns ('Cell phone' in clauses [1; 7; 19; 22; 31; 38 and 43] and 'student' in clauses [9; 16 and 39]); a nominal group ('A simple question during the course' in clause [26]); relative pronouns ('which' in clauses [8; (12); 20; 29 and 34]; 'that' in clause [28] and 'who' in clauses [32 and 35]) and verbal nouns or/and predicators ('to use' in clauses [6 and 44]; 'to cheat' in clause [10]; 'to answer' in clause [14]; 'to be' in clause [30] and 'to commit' in clause [40]). The common noun 'cell phone' is referred to with the lexical item 'This element' in clause (3). It is also pointed back to referentially with the reference item 'it' in clause (33). Likewise, the common noun 'student' is anaphorically referred to with the pronoun 'He' in clauses (11; 13; 15; 17; 18; 21; 23; 25 and 27). The four *marked* Themes in the text are 'by which' in clause (2); 'which' in clause (20); 'everytime (every time)' in clause (24) and 'From all what' in clause (36). While the first two are structural elements, suggesting the packaging of clause simplexes into clause complexes in the text, the other two are groups of words, unveiling time or frequency and transition respectively therein. The use of the 15 Textual Themes (all of which are Conjunctive items) proves that the text is well-planned too. Here are some examples of the Textual Themes identified in Text 4: *because* (4); *However* (15); *Since* (7); *if* (13); *Again* (16), etc.

Text 5 encloses 74 Themes. These Themes are shared by two Theme-types: 54 (i.e., 72.97%) Topical Themes and 20 (i.e., 27.03%) Textual Themes. Forty-eight out of the 54 Topical Themes are *unmarked* (1; 2; 3; 4; 6; 7; 8; 9; 10; 11; 12; 13; 14; 15; 16; 17; 18; (19); 20; 22; 23; 24; 25; 26; 27; 28; 30; 31; 32; 33; 34; 35; 36; 37; 38; 39; 40; 41; 43; 44; 45; 46; 48; 49; 50; 51; 52 and 54), displaying that the subjects in the clauses are mainly deployed in their usual/normal/expected positions/slots. The *unmarked* Topical Themes in Text 5 can be classified into six groups: common nouns ('Cell phone' in clauses [1; 14 and 40] and 'students in clauses [6; 10; 12; 23 and 37]); nominal groups ('some students' in clause [3] and 'Certain people' in clause [7]); nominalizations ('using cell phone by students in class in clause [8] and 'Researching' in clause [11]); relative pronouns ('who' in clause [4]; 'which' in clauses [(19) and 32] and 'that' in clause [43]); indefinite pronouns ('Some' in clause [48] and 'others' in clause [50]) and verbal nouns or/and predicators ('to communicate/find in clause [2]; 'to use' in clauses [13; 24 and 49]; 'to complete' in clause [18]; 'to do' in clause [27], etc.). It must be noted that the common noun 'Cell phone' is referred to in the text with the pronoun 'it' in clauses (17; 25; 26 and 54). Likewise, the indefinite pronoun 'others' is pointed back to with the pronoun 'they'. The foregoing denotes that the text embodies inter-clausal relations. The six *marked* Themes identified in Text 5 are 'Nowadays (Nowadays)' in clause (5); 'Nowadays' in clause (21); 'If the lecturer have (has) something...' in clause (29); 'In your cell phone' in clause (42); 'In condition' in clause (47) and 'To sum up' in clause (53). The use of these Themes indicates that the clauses in the text are rhetorically well-planned. The use of the 18 Textual Themes (all of which are Conjunctive items) also shows that the text is well-planned. The following are some of the Textual Themes identified in the text: *that* (6; 8; 12); *but* (9); *in that* (10); *by* (16); *Also* (17), etc.

Text 6 counts 80 Themes distributed as follows: 55 (i.e., 68.75%) Topical Themes, 24 (i.e., 30%) Textual Themes and 01 (i.e., 01.25%) Interpersonal Theme. Forty-four out of the 55 Topical Themes are *unmarked* (1; 2; 4; 5; 6; 7; 9; 10; 12; 13; 14; 16; 17; 18; 19; 21; 22; 23; 24; 26; 27; 28; 29; 30; 31; 32; 33; 34; 35; 37; 38; 39; 41; 42; 43; 44; (45); 46; 48; 49; 51; (52); 54 and 55), suggesting that the subjects in the clauses occupy their usual/normal/expected positions/slots. The *unmarked* Topical Themes in Text 6 fall into five groups: nominal groups ('(the) modern technology' in clauses [1; 5; 32; 51 and (52)];

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‘This question’ in clause [8] and ‘the time’ in clause [11]); an indefinite pronoun (‘everybody (everybody)’ in clause [4]); personal pronouns (‘we’ in clauses [10; (12); 14 and 16]; ‘I’ in clauses [17 and 18] and ‘you’ in clauses [22; 23; 29; 38 and 41]); relative pronouns (‘how’ in clause [7]; ‘who’ in clauses [19; 44 and 45]; ‘why’ in clause [30] and ‘which’ in clauses [35 and 48]) and verbal nouns or/and predicators (‘to live’ in clauses [2; 6; 33; 49 and 55]; ‘to go’ in clause [26] and ‘to inform’ in clause [37]). The eleven *marked* Themes found in this text are ‘Today’ in clause (3); ‘This question’ in clause (8); ‘the time’ in clause (11); ‘at that time’ in clause (15); ‘in our time’ in clause (20); ‘now’ in clauses (25 and 40); ‘in ancient time’ in clause (36); ‘all’ in clause (47); ‘In summary’ in clause (50) and ‘in this (these) cases’ in clause (53). The use of the foregoing Themes proves that the text is internally well-organized. Again, the use of the 24 Textual Themes (all of which are Conjunctive items) identified in the text exudes that it is internally well-organized. Some examples of the Textual Themes in Text 6 include *that* (4); *but* (7); *In order to* (9); *and* (11); *For example, when* (12); *before* (13), etc.

Unlike Text 6, Text 7 includes 33 Themes distributed as follows: 28 (i.e., 84.85%) Topical Themes and 05 (i.e., 15.15%) Textual Themes. Twenty-six out of the 28 Topic Themes are *unmarked* (1; 2; 3; 4; 5; 6; 7; 8; 9; 10; 11; 12; 13; 15; 16; 17; 18; 19; 20; (21); 22; 23; 24; 25; 27 and 28), indicating that the subjects in the clauses occur in their usual/normal/expected positions/slots. The *unmarked* Themes identified in the text can be grouped into four categories: nominal groups (‘Modern technology’ in clause [1 and 7] and ‘many people’ in clauses [20 and (21)]); common nouns (‘Technology’ in clause [15] and ‘People’ in clause [17]); relative pronouns (‘which’ in clause [3] and ‘what’ in clauses [12 and 22]) and verbal nouns or/and predicators (‘to live’ in clauses [5 and 28]); ‘to express’ in clause [9]; ‘(to) send’ in clause [11]; ‘to stand’ in clause [18]; ‘to be’ in clause [19] and ‘to paid (pay)’ in clause [25]). The nominal group ‘Modern technology’ is referred to anaphorically with the pronoun ‘it’ in clauses (2; 4; 6; 8; 10; 13; 16; 24 and 27). The two *marked* Themes identified in Text 7 are ‘With the advance (advancement) of new technology’ in clause (14) and ‘To conclude’ in clause in (26), exuding that the text is internally well-organized. In addition, the presence of the 5 Textual Themes (all of which are Conjunctive items) found in the text shows that it is internally well-organized. The Textual Themes found in Text 7 are *Even though* (6); *Then* (20); *or* (21) and *without* (23 and 29). The only Interpersonal Theme ‘OF COURSE’ (1) used in the text is a mood adjunct and expresses certainty.

Like Text 7, Text 8 contains a total number of 52 Themes. These are shared by two Theme-types: 39 (i.e., 75%) Topical Themes and 13 (i.e., 25%) Textual Themes. Thirty-five out of the 39 Topical Themes are *unmarked* (1; 3; 4; 5; 6; 7; 8; 9; 10; 11; 13; 14; 15; 16; 17; 18; 19; (20); 21; 22; 23; 24; 26; 27; 28; 29; 30; 31; 32; 33; 34; 36; 37; 38 and 39), indicating that the subjects in the clauses occupy their usual/normal/expected positions/slots. The *unmarked* Themes found in the text can be classified into five groups: nominal groups (‘Modern technology(ies)’ in clauses [1 and 6]; ‘some documents’ in clause [15]; ‘many people’ in clauses [18; 29 and 38]; ‘the world’ in clause [32] and ‘many companies and some working places (and) their workers’ in clause [33]); demonstrative pronouns (‘This’ in clauses [8 and 13] and ‘These’ in clause [22]); an indefinite pronoun (‘whatever (whatever)’ in clause [12]); personal pronouns (‘it’ in clauses [4; 5 and 9]; ‘they’ in clauses [7; 19 and 20]; ‘I’ in clause [36] and ‘you’ in clause [37]) and verbal nouns or/and predicators (‘to live’ in clauses [3 and 39]; ‘to browse’ in clause [10]; ‘(to) download’ in clause [11]; ‘to find’ in clause [16]; ‘to manage’ in clause [23]; ‘(to) use’ in clause [24] and ‘to stand’ in clause [26]). The four *marked* Themes found in this text are ‘Now adays (Nowadays) and at this age’ in clause (2); ‘what ever (whatever)’ in clause (12); ‘at (the) bank’ in clause (25) and ‘To sum up’ in clause (35). The deployment of the preceding Themes points out that the text is internally well-organized. Also, the deployment of the 13 Textual Themes (all of which are Conjunctive elements) shows that the text is rhetorically well-written. The Textual Themes found in the text are *First* (6); *and* (11; 15; 20 and 24); *Second* (17); *without* (21; 30 and 34); *Moreover* (25); *while* (27); *Last (by)* (28) and *when* (32).

Text 9 is similar to Texts 7 and 8 in that the 57 Themes it encompasses are distributed across two Theme-types: 41 (i.e., 71.93%) Topical Themes and 16 (i.e., 28.07%) Textual Themes. Thirty-six out of the 41 Topical Themes are *unmarked* (1; 2; 3; 4; 5; 7; 8; 9; 10; 11; 12; 13; 14; 15; 16; 17; 19; 20; 21; 22; 23; 24; 25; 26; 27; 28; 29; 30; 31; 33; 34; 35; 36; 38; 40 and 41), exuding that the subjects in the clauses occur in their usual/normal/expected positions/slots. The *unmarked* Themes in the text are of six types: nominal groups (‘people’s life’ in clause [8]; ‘The using of cell phones in order to listen to radio to get information even on your bed’ in clause [10]; ‘the using of technology’ in clause [11]; ‘The using of dictionary and others (other) grammatic (grammar) documents’ in clause [29] and ‘modern technology’ in clause [41]); common nouns (‘Technology’ in clause [1]; ‘computer’ in clause [12]; ‘Radio’ in clause [15] and ‘people’ [30]); a relative pronoun (‘which’ in clause [14]); an indefinite pronoun (‘someone’ in clause [25]); personal pronouns (‘It’ in clauses [3; 7 and 19]; ‘we’ in clauses [20; 21; 22; 26; 36 and 40] and ‘you’ in clauses [13; 16; 17 and 34]) and verbal nouns or/and predicators (‘to live’ in clause [4]; ‘(to) facilitate’ in clause [5]; ‘to enter’ in clause [23]; ‘to download’ in clause [24]; ‘to go’ in clause [33] and ‘to attend’ in clause [38]). The five *marked* Themes identified in Text 9 are ‘For these reasons’ in clause (6); ‘on the way of study’

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in clause (18); ‘Anywhere’ in clause (32); ‘For the kind of travel which need (needs) to pass a huge water’ in clause (37) and ‘To sum up’ in clause (39). The use of these Themes proves that the text is rhetorically well-planned. The use of the 16 Textual Themes (all of which are Conjunctive items) in the essay suggests that the essay is rhetorically well-planned too. Some of the Textual Themes found in the text include *and* (5); *that* (7 and 11, etc.); *First* (8); *by* (9); *Moreover* (12); *because* (13), etc.

Text 10 like the preceding texts (7; 8 and 9) comprises 33 Themes shared by two Theme-types: 24 (i.e., 72.73%) Topical Themes and 09 (i.e., 27.27%) Textual Themes. Sixteen out of the 24 Topical Themes are *unmarked* (2; 3; 4; 7; 9; 12; 13; 14; 15; 16; 18; (19); 20; 21; 22 and 23). This exudes that the subjects in the clauses occur in their usual/normal/expected positions/slots. The *unmarked* Themes in Text 10 can be categorized into six groups: nominal groups (‘Modern technology’ in clauses [1; 16; (19); 22 and 23]); a nominal clause (‘the knowledge he had accumulated’ in clause [6]); personal pronouns (‘it’ in clauses [3 and 20]); a common noun (‘Technology’ in clause [12]); relative pronouns (‘that’ in clause [9] and ‘which’ in clause [21]) and verbal nouns or/and predicators (‘to begin’ in clause [4]; (‘to introduced (introduce)’ in clause [7] and (‘to bring’ in clause [18]). The eight *marked* Themes found in the text are ‘With the dawn of 21th (21st) century’ in clause (1); ‘through all the periods’ in clause (5); ‘the knowledge’ in clause (6); ‘With the dawn of modern technology’ in clause (8); ‘with the age machinery’ in clause (10); ‘by which’ in clause (11); ‘by what’ in (17) and ‘with evolutive perspective’ in clause (24). The use of these Themes implies that the text is rhetorically well-written. The text also counts 09 Textual Themes, all of which are Conjunctive elements, indicating that the text is rhetorically well-written. The Textual Themes identified in Text 10 are *Even though* (2); *but* (3); *and* (6); *however* (10); *by* (13; [14] and [15]); *Second* (18) and *Finally* (22). After displaying the types of Themes, the second-year English major students choose in their argumentative essays, let us now look at the Thematic (progression) patterns that they deploy in their texts.

Research Question 2

What kind(s) of Thematic (progression) pattern do second-year English major students deploy in their argumentative essays?

The analysis of Thematic patterns follows the Theme classification proposed by Amoussou (2016). The Theme classification contains six classes (a, b, c, d, e and f). This classification has been chosen because of its attempts to categorize the grammatical intricacies of the composition of Theme in a more or less precise way useful for a practical linguistic analysis. In fact, because of the preceding reason, this classification has been adopted and used recently to study the stylistic dimension of the Thematic structure and Thematic features in literary texts (see Allagbé, Amoussou and Tchada, 2020 and Amoussou, Allagbé and Tchada, 2020b). It is hoped too that this classification will help unveil the Thematic patterns in student writing. This classification has been reworked recently by Amoussou (2021). The main change this scholar highlights in his recent study concerns Theme classes (e) and (f), which he failed to distinguish in his earlier work (2016) because of lack of insight then, as he puts it himself (p. 4). In his recent work (2021), he considers the two classes as classes of rankshifted clauses: defining and reporting ones (see p. 4 of the study for more details). The Theme classification is provided in the table below.

Table 2: Theme Classification

Theme classes	Structure/Composition of the Theme
(a)	‘Only a transitivity-label item or Topical Theme’
(b)	‘Textual element+ Topical Theme’
(c)	‘Interpersonal element+ Topical theme’
(d)	‘Textual element +Interpersonal element+ topical Theme’/‘Interpersonal element+ Textual element + Topical theme’
(e)	‘Structural element’
(f)	‘Textual element+ structural element/‘structural element+ Topical Theme’

The Thematic patterns found in the texts are provided in the table below.

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Table 3: Frequency Distribution of Thematic Patterns in the Texts

Frequency Distribution of Thematic Patterns in the Texts										
Theme class	Text1	Text2	Text3	Text4	Text5	Text6	Text7	Text8	Text9	Text10
a	20	15	11	20	30	26	21	26	24	11
b	19	10	19	15	20	22	05	13	16	09
c	01	00	00	00	00	01	00	00	00	00
d	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00
e	01	01	03	08	04	04	03	00	01	02
f	00	00	00	01	00	02	00	00	00	02

Table 3 indicates that Text 1 comprises four Thematic patterns: Theme class (a) (20/51 [i.e., 39.21%]); Theme class (b) (19/51 [i.e., 37.25%]); Theme class (c) (01/51 [i.e., 01.96%]) and Theme class (e) (01/51 [i.e., 01.96%]). As the analysis clearly exudes, Theme class (a) predominates over other Theme classes, suggesting once again the dominance of Topical Themes placed in their usual/normal/expected positions/slots. This indicates a written mode. Like Theme class (a), the three other Theme classes (b; c and e) contain clauses in which Topical Themes occur in their initial slots. While in Theme class (b) these Topical Themes are preceded by a Conjunctive element, exuding cohesive development, in Theme class (c), the Topical Theme is placed after an Interpersonal element or a Mood adjunct, encoding interpersonal meaning. The use of Theme class (b) shows clause complexing. Spoken language tends to use the dynamic pattern of clause complexing (Egins, 2004, p. 293). In contrast, in Theme class (e), the Topical Theme is a structural element, implying also the packaging of clause simplexes into clause complexes. Unlike Text 1, Text 2 only consists of three Thematic patterns: Theme class (a) (15/26 [i.e., 57.69%]); Theme class (b) (10/26 [i.e., 38.46%]) and Theme class (e) (01/26 [i.e., 03.85%]). Like Text 2, Text 3 encompasses three Thematic patterns: Theme class (a) (11/33 [i.e., 33.33%]); Theme class (b) (19/33 [i.e., 57.58%]) and Theme class (e) (03/33 [i.e., 09.09%]). Text 3 differs from Texts 1 and 2 with regard to the rate of Theme classes (b and e). Simply put, this text seems to include more Conjunctive and structural elements than the other two. Like Text 1, Text 4 incorporates four Thematic patterns: Theme class (a) (20/44 [i.e., 45.45%]); Theme class (b) (15/44 [i.e., 34.09%]); Theme class (e) (08/44 [i.e., 18.18%]) and Theme class (f) (01/44 [i.e., 02.27%]). This text differs from Text 1 in that it does not contain Theme class (c). It is also different from Text 1 because it includes Theme class (f). The only Theme class (f) found in the text is 'by which' in clause (2). Like Texts 2 and 3, Text 5 comprises Three Thematic patterns: Theme class (a) (30/54 [i.e., 55.55%]); Theme class (b) (20/54 [i.e., 37.04%]) and Theme class (e) (04/54 [i.e., 07.41%]).

Unlike the preceding texts, Text 6 encompasses five Thematic patterns: Theme class (a) (26/55 [i.e., 47.27%]); Theme class (b) (22/55 [i.e., 40%]); Theme class (c) (01/55 [i.e., 01.82%]); Theme class (e) (04/55 [i.e., 07.27%]) and Theme class (f) (02/55 [i.e., 03.64%]). Text 7 differs from Text 6 in that it has only three Thematic patterns: Theme class (a) (21/29 [i.e., 72.42%]); Theme class (b) (05/29 [i.e., 17.24%]) and Theme class (e) (03/29 [i.e., 10.34%]). This text differs from all the other texts because of the rate of Theme class (b) it includes. Unlike all the texts, Text 8 contains only two Thematic patterns: Theme class (a) (26/39 [i.e., 66.67%]) and Theme class (b) (13/39 [i.e., 33.33%]). Text 9, like Texts 2; 3; 5 and 7, comprises three Thematic patterns: Theme class (a) (24/41 [i.e., 58.54%]); Theme class (b) (16/41 [i.e., 39.02%]) and Theme class (e) (01/41 [i.e., 02.44%]). Like Texts 1 and 4, Text 10 incorporates four Thematic patterns: Theme class (a) (11/24 [i.e., 45.83%]); Theme class (b) (09/24 [i.e., 37.50%]); Theme class (e) (02/24 [i.e., 08.33%]) and Theme class (f) (02/24 [i.e., 08.33%]). It must be noted that all the texts look alike because none of them consists of Theme class (d). By the same token, the ten texts are similar in that they all contain the same types of Thematic progression pattern: Theme reiteration and the zig-zag pattern. The Thematic progression patterns discovered in the texts are indicated in Table 4.

Table 4: Frequency Distribution of Thematic Progression Patterns in the Texts

Frequency Distribution of Thematic Progression Patterns in the Texts										
Types of Thematic Progression Pattern	Text1	Text2	Text3	Text4	Text5	Text6	Text7	Text8	Text9	Text10
Theme reiteration Pattern	16	10	08	19	10	11	13	07	13	07
Zig-zag Pattern	03	01	04	09	09	05	01	04	03	04
Multiple-Rheme Pattern	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00
Total	19	11	12	28	19	16	14	11	16	11

The table above clearly shows that the dominant Thematic progression pattern employed in all the texts is Theme reiteration pattern. This pattern rates 16/19 (i.e., 84.21%) in Text 1, 10/11 (i.e., 90.90%) in Text 2, 08/12 (i.e., 66.67%) in Text

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3, 19/28 (i.e., 67.85%) in Text 4, 10/19 (i.e., 52.63%) in Text 5, 11/16 (i.e., 68.75%) in Text 6, 13/14 (i.e., 92.86%) in Text 7, 07/11 (i.e., 63.64%) in Text 8, 13/16 (i.e., 81.25%) in Text 9 and 07/11 (i.e., 63.64%) in Text 10. The dominance of this pattern indicates that the students have kept their texts focused (i.e., cohesive) by simply re-iterating the Thematic element in most of the clauses therein. As the table further indicates, the next dominant Thematic progression pattern in the texts is the zig-zag pattern. It represents 03/19 (i.e., 15.79%) in Text 1, 01/11 (i.e., 09.10%) in Text 2, 04/12 (i.e., 33.33%) in Text 3, 09/28 (i.e., 32.14%) in Text 4, 09/19 (i.e., 47.37%) in Text 5, 05/16 (i.e., 31.25%) in Text 6, 01/14 (i.e., 07.14%) in Text 7, 04/11 (i.e., 36.36%) in Text 8, 03/16 (i.e., 18.75%) in Text 9 and 04/11 (i.e., 36.36%) in Text 10. The presence of the zig-zag pattern here exudes that the student writers have been able to encode logical relations and elaborations in their texts. On the contrary, the table shows that the multiple-Rheme pattern is absent from the texts. This clearly indicates that the students still find it difficult to organize their texts. As Eggins (2004, p. 326) notes, “[...] the multiple-Rheme pattern often provides the underlying organizing principle for a text, with both the zig-zag and theme reiteration strategies being used for elaborating on each of the main thematic points.”

Conclusion

This paper has analysed the Theme-types and Thematic (progressive) patterns in ten (i.e., 12.5%) out of eighty argumentative essays written by second-year English major students from the UAS, Niger Republic, in the academic year 2020-2021. The study has employed the descriptive mixed method research design which consists in describing, identifying and classifying the Theme-types and Thematic (progression) patterns in the students' essays. The identified Theme-types and Thematic patterns were first quantified and tabulated before the findings thereof were discussed. In point of fact, the analysis has yielded some salient findings.

The findings reveal, for instance, that eight of the students' texts (2; 3; 4; 5; 7; 8; 9 and 10) contain two types of Theme, namely: Topical Themes and Textual Themes. On the other hand, only Texts 1 and 6 include the three Theme-types. As the analysis further indicates, a great number of Topical Themes are unmarked, suggesting that the subjects in the clauses occur in their usual/normal/expected positions/slots. The *unmarked* Themes in the texts range from three to six types. The *marked* Themes, though they exist in low proportions in the texts, prove that the texts are rhetorically well-organized. The use of Textual Themes in the texts also shows that the texts are rhetorically well-organized. In addition, the analysis of Thematic patterns points out that the texts encompass mainly two Theme classes (a and b). The dominance of Theme class (a) confirms once more the dominance of Topical Themes placed in their usual/normal/expected positions/slots, which is indicative of a written mode. Theme class (b) clauses are the next dominant Thematic pattern in all the texts, and since the Topical Themes in them are preceded by a Conjunctive element, their use contributes to the cohesive development of the texts.

Again, the analysis of Thematic progression patterns in the texts unveils the choice of two patterns: Theme reiteration and the zig-zag pattern. Theme reiteration is the most dominant type in all the texts, and its use proves that the students have kept their texts focused (i.e., cohesive) by simply re-iterating the Thematic element in most of the clauses therein. The use of the zig-zag pattern also unveils that the student writers have been able to encode logical relations and elaborations in their texts. However, the multiple-Rheme pattern is absent from the texts, indicating that the students still find it difficult to organize their texts. Hence, more efforts should be devoted to text creation and organization in the EFL writing class. To reach this goal, Jing (2015) suggests an instructional package meant to build students' meta-knowledge of cohesion and coherence and Theme/Theme progression (T/TP). This package can be tried out both in an ESL (English as Second Language) setting and an EFL setting. Future research could measure the impact of this package on students' writing skills.

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Evaluating the Implementation of 5P's Model in External Examinations of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) Theses at Makerere University, Uganda

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Abstract

This study investigated the effectiveness of applying the 5P's model in the external examination of PhD theses at Makerere University, providing crucial insights into its functionality. Utilizing a case study design, the research aimed to evaluate whether Makerere's external examination system achieves its objectives, adheres to prescribed principles and follows systematic procedures. The study also sought to determine the involvement of relevant individuals and performance metrics in the University's external examination processes. Data collection involved vital personnel in the external examination processes, including academic deans, deputy vice-chancellors, college principals, deputy college principals, and PhD program coordinators, through in-depth interviews. The findings indicated that while the external examination of PhD theses at the University achieves its intended purpose and aligns with established principles, there is a noticeable absence of robust mechanisms for monitoring the performance of PhD students and external examiners, leading to persistent delays in submitting examination reports. In response to these findings, the study recommends establishing robust systems at Makerere University to monitor the performance and progress of external examiners and PhD students consistently. This proactive approach is envisioned to streamline the external examination process, ensuring timely submissions and cultivating a culture of excellence in academic progress.

Keywords: External examination, 5P's Model, PhD Theses, Makerere University, Performance management

Introduction

In the realm of higher education, external examination stands as a globally acknowledged cornerstone within quality assurance mechanisms, playing a pivotal role in upholding academic standards (Darojat, 2018). However, this recognition is juxtaposed with a paradox that questions the alignment between the confidence placed in external examinations and persistent apprehensions regarding academic standards (Fisher-Ari et al., 2017). This paradox is particularly pronounced in the discourse at Makerere University, where debates have emerged regarding the retention or removal of external examinations from the institution's quality assurance system (Betts et al., 2019). The impetus for this research arises from the escalating skepticism among Makerere University stakeholders concerning the efficacy and relevance of external examinations. In response to ongoing discussions within the academic corridors of Makerere, this study aims to unravel the complexities of the debate by investigating the application of Pryor, et al.'s 5P model in the external examinations of PhD theses.

External examination, rooted in history since the early nineteenth century, has evolved into a mechanism for universities to demonstrate the credibility of their academic standards, a sentiment echoed by Bloxham (Houston, 2018). In African universities, including Makerere, external examining is a longstanding practice with historical ties to affiliations with European universities during their inception (Kasozzi et al., 2019). Despite Makerere's century-old history of practicing external examination, challenges persist, with complaints about delayed completion of PhD theses due to late submission of reports from external examiners (Viana et al., 2022). Pryor's 5P's strategic management model, emphasizing Purpose, Principles,

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Processes, People, and Performance, emerges as a strategic tool for effective organizational operation (GÜLENC & KOZAK, 2016). This model is selected for its potential to align the process of external examinations at Makerere University with practical strategies and defined organizational purposes.

Framed within Pryor's 5P's model, this study delved into the Purpose, Principles, Processes, People, and Performance aspects of the external examination function at Makerere University. Despite external examination being a pillar of ensuring academic excellence at Makerere University, its process is marred by inadequacies, including delayed submission of examiners' reports and questionable practices. Stakeholders have raised concerns about the necessity of external examiners, leading to debates on the process's continued relevance (Kabeba, 2010; Ndyabahika, 2019). Within the framework of Pryor's 5P Model, this study aims to explore and address these challenges. The primary purpose of this study was to examine the application of Pryor's 5P's strategic management model in the external examination processes at Makerere University. The specific objectives included examining the extent to which the external examination system achieves its intended purpose, assessing adherence to set principles and processes, exploring the involvement of relevant people, and evaluating the use of performance measurement in the external examination of PhD theses at the University.

Numerous scholars have extensively explored the practice of external examination in higher education and its relevance in various contexts. Medland (2015) conducted a study in the UK assessing the effectiveness of the external examination system in upholding standards and instilling stakeholder confidence. Findings indicated a need to enhance professionalism, examiner calibration, and role clarity across UK universities. The study also emphasized the need for home institutions to support and recognize academic staff as external examiners. This investigation aims to determine if Makerere University supports and recognizes its academic staff undertaking external examinations. Unegbu and Ezeobi (2017) explored the role of external examiners in maintaining academic standards in Nigerian universities, emphasizing their significance in quality control and curriculum development. Despite the prioritization of external examiners' reports at Makerere University, it remains unclear if the University aligns its external examination processes with the 5Ps of strategic management. Hannan and Silver (2004) delved into why academics willingly engage in external examining despite time demands, citing reasons such as reciprocity and information gathering, even without significant support from their home institutions. While previous studies demonstrate the role of external examination in maintaining standards and information gathering, this investigation seeks to understand its application at Makerere University in Uganda.

Furthermore, Gold Smith's (2020) study on external examining procedures at the University of London emphasized the need to adhere to guidelines for appointing external examiners. However, how the nomination and appointment processes occur at Makerere University remains unknown, prompting the current study. Scholars like Silver (2006) and Finch (2011) have investigated external examining processes, highlighting institutional variations. The researcher aims to explore Makerere University's external examination processes, comparing them with existing practices and recommending improvements. Loukkola and Zhang (2010) emphasized the crucial role of individuals' quality and commitment in the success of external examination processes. This study will investigate how the people involved in external examining at Makerere University contribute to its effectiveness using the 5P's strategic model. Research on external examination and performance measurement in various contexts, such as Godo, Olel, and Oanda's (2011) study in Kenyan private universities, indicated improvements. However, there is a gap in understanding how performance measurement aligns with strategic management at Makerere University. Therefore, this investigation aims to apply Pryor White's 5Ps strategic model to assess external examination at Makerere University in Uganda.

At Makerere University, the role of external examination is deemed critical for maintaining and safeguarding academic excellence. However, the administration of this process is confronted with a multitude of deficiencies, most notably characterized by recurrent delays in the submission of examiners' reports. Eyangu et al. (2014) observed consistent delays in returning students' research projects at Makerere University Business School, sometimes accompanied by incomplete examination reports. Concerns have been raised regarding external examiners deviating from university guidelines, resulting in the production of reports deemed invalid and unreliable. The Rwendeire Report (2017) shed light on an inequitable examination process, both internal and external, contributing to the suboptimal assessment of graduate student work.

Consequently, substantial questioning has emerged among stakeholders regarding the necessity of external examiners at the University, with some advocating for eliminating external examinations for graduate dissertations and theses (Kabeba, 2010; Ndyabahika, 2019). By scrutinizing these challenges through the 5Ps strategic management model framework, it can be hypothesized that these issues may stem from deficiencies within the 5Ps, particularly as they pertain to the external examination function. In light of this hypothesis, the present study seeks to assess the extent to which Makerere's external examination system accomplishes its objectives, adheres to stipulated principles, and follows systematic procedures.

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Additionally, the study endeavored to ascertain the involvement of relevant individuals and the utilization of performance metrics in the University's external examination processes.

Objectives of the study

The study aimed to achieve the following research objectives:

1. Evaluate the extent to which Makerere University's external examination system fulfills its objectives.
2. Assess the degree of adherence of Makerere's external examination system to prescribed principles.
3. Investigate the implementation of systematic procedures in Makerere's external examination processes.
4. Determine the level of involvement of relevant individuals in the University's external examination procedures.
5. Examine the incorporation of performance metrics in Makerere University's external examination processes.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent does Makerere University's external examination system achieve its objectives?
2. How well does Makerere's external examination system adhere to prescribed principles?
3. How are systematic procedures implemented in Makerere's external examination processes?
4. To what degree are relevant individuals involved in Makerere University's external examination procedures?
5. How are performance metrics incorporated into Makerere University's external examination processes?

Methodology

This qualitative inquiry, grounded in the interpretivist phenomenology of Edmund Husserl, delves into the utilization of Pryor et al.'s 5P model in overseeing the external examination of PhD theses at Makerere University. Informed by the belief that a profound understanding of a phenomenon emerges from those who have experienced it, interpretivism provides a fitting framework for unveiling the meaning inherent in the external examination experience. Aligning seamlessly with Husserl's transcendental argument, the epistemological stance views knowledge as socially constructed, guiding the research. Employing a case study design to test theoretical models, the study focuses on crucial university figures responsible for the external examination process. Data collection involves interviews and document reviews, utilizing thematic analysis to categorize responses based on the 5P model. The qualitative approach centers on a purposive sample of 18 participants strategically chosen to oversee the external examination process, applying thematic framework analysis to document reviews with Pryor et al.'s model as predetermined themes. Trustworthiness is ensured through face validity, engagement with supervisors for question clarification, and methodological rigor. Rigorous data analysis using ATLAS.ti v22 encompasses extraction, transcription, coding, and theme development, resulting in transparent reporting tied to study objectives. Ethical considerations prioritize consent, confidentiality, and anonymization. This comprehensive research methodology evaluated whether Makerere's external examination system achieves its objectives, adheres to prescribed principles, and follows systematic procedures. Drawing on key stakeholders' experiences, the detailed analysis and ethical considerations enhance the reliability and validity of the findings.

Results

Research Question 1

The first research question was: "To what extent does Makerere University's external examination system achieve its objectives?"

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Table 1: Views of Stakeholders on Whether the Management of External Examinations Achieves its Purpose

Theme Research questions	<i>Responses on Whether External Examination Achieves Purpose</i>	<i>Responses on Whether External Examination Does Not Achieve Purpose</i>
To what extent does Makerere University's external examination system achieve its objectives?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The external examination is a direct quality assurance measure. • Achieving the intended purpose yields • auditing • It avoids the inbreeding of similar knowledge. • Certification of original work • Comparability of the programs in other universities • Education management and echo system • external examination gives a broader perspective on knowledge • Enables Judgement of good supervision • independent analytical feedback • independent opinions • knowledge transfer • opportunity for peer review • perspectives of different supervisors • Quality assurance checks for both the supervisor • standard assessment • a more comprehensive range of context 	<p>No need for external examination at Makerere University</p> <p>Makerere University has the capacity and does not need external examination.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unprofessionalism <p>Inadequate payment of external examiners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the quality of reports is questionable • Unfair judgment <p>Very Unfair assessment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policies on external examination need urgent review

As summarized in Table 1, the responses indicated a consensus among respondents that the management of external examination at Makerere University serves its purpose. Participants identified vital benefits, including its role as a quality assurance measure, independent review, avoidance of inbreeding of knowledge, and judgment of good supervision. Quotes from respondents emphasized the fundamental role of external examination in assessing both the supervisor and the student, providing independent opinions, and certifying the originality of work. The findings also highlighted the importance of external examination in maintaining comparability with programs in other universities, offering independent analytical feedback, and serving as a quality assurance check for both the supervisor and standard assessment.

Research Question 2

How are systematic procedures implemented in Makerere's external examination processes?

Again, to answer these questions, key informants were posed this and other related questions. Some of their responses have been reported verbatim as follows:

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Fairness and objectivity in the work are critical principles of external examination. Objectivity means that the external examiner should stick to the guidelines and mark the candidates' theses without bias. In that case, the external examiner should be mindful of who supervised the work of which the student wrote the theses. On the other hand, the principle of fairness requires the external examiner to be just and considerate when assessing any candidate's work. For that matter, the examiner should not malice a candidate (**Interviewee 003**).

Timeliness is yet another principle that must be observed while conducting external examinations. Timeliness means that the time taken to assess a candidate's work must be reasonable and should not extend to cause the candidate or supervisors of the candidate anxiety. However, in practice, some examiners violate this principle. Even the University policy of leaving examiners to work within three months violates this principle. It is worse if some examiners submit their examination reports beyond the stipulated time. I know of external examiners who often take over six months to return the students' theses and reports. This is disheartening (**Interviewee 007**).

For both students and EE, it is crucial. For example, some topics change very first. For example, current Law governing constantly has emerging issues or policies. When you submit the report to the EE, new trends, topics/themes will emerge. For example, I remember a student petitioning DRGT, saying they appointed an external examiner who had issues with the student. Unfortunately, the Research and Higher Degrees Committee did not know about the conflict (**Interviewee 004**).

One of the principles of external examination is transparency. This involves all the parties involved in external examination to handle the examination process openly and clearly. Indeed, transparency should be exercised at all levels of the external examination process. For example, the selection of the external examiner should be done as stipulated by policy. In practice, however, the choice of certain external examiners has been questioned or challenged because how some are chosen leaves much to be desired (**Interviewee 011**).

According to the researcher, an external examiner should not be a person who has been closely involved in the internal workings of the school, for example, teaching for the past three years. If somebody has been in the school, he or she cannot immediately become an external examiner. Suppose such a person is appointed as an external examiner. In that case, he or she may not exercise the freedom and independence so much desired to carry out his or her work suitably (**Interviewee 006**).

These results shed light on the adherence of Makerere University's external examination system to the principles outlined in Pryor's 5Ps model. Key informants emphasized the criticality of fairness and objectivity in external examination, underscoring the importance of unbiased assessment aligned with guidelines. The principle of timeliness emerged as a concern, with some examiners exceeding stipulated time frames, causing anxiety for both candidates and supervisors. The dynamic nature of particular disciplines, such as Law, highlighted the necessity for agility in the examination process. Transparency, a fundamental principle, was underscored as essential at all stages, including the selection of external examiners. Concerns were raised about the criteria for choosing external examiners, with suggestions to avoid individuals closely involved in the internal workings of the school for the past three years to ensure the desired freedom and independence in their role. These insights provide valuable perspectives on the strengths and challenges within the current external examination practices at Makerere University.

Research Question 3

How are systematic procedures implemented in Makerere University's external examination processes?

To answer this question, responses were collected through interviews, focusing on processes and challenges involved in external examination. Table 2 presents the responses, outlining various stages of the external examination process, including submitting a letter of intent by the student, nomination of examiners by the Dean and Deputy Principal, allocation of internal and external examiners, and approval by higher degree committees.

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Table 2: Responses on the Processes in the External Examination

No.	Research question	Responses/ data on processes involved in the external examination
01	To what degree do the processes involved in external examination at Makerere University align with the framework provided by Pryor's 5Ps strategic management model?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Once the student submits the letter of intent, the process begins. • Dean writes to the deputy principal to nominate the examiner. • For Makerere University, two internal examiners and one external examiner are appointed. • The Dean writes to the principal; in this case, the principal is the final person to appoint the examiners. • The CHUSS, the deputy principal, appoint the PhD. • DRGT is first copied in immediately when the college appoints an external examiner. • Dean writes to the deputy principal to nominate the examiner. • For Makerere University, they appoints two internal examiners and one external examiner. • The Dean writes to the principal; in this case, the principal is the final person to appoint the examiners. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Stage I.- The first stage is for the student to complete their research an 2. Stage II - Consider the potential pool of examiners, choosing the person most suitable for doing the work dissertation. 3. Stage III - Selection of External Examiner: Involves some consideration from a pool of examiners, choosing the person more suitable for doing work. 4. Stage IV.- examination report. This results from the External Examiner instrument or reading the dissertation and assessing. 13. The department generates the need for the External Examiner. 14. After the nomination of the External Examiner, the names are taken to the higher degrees committee for approval. 15. The office of the Deputy Principal approves and appoints External Examiners after the committee's recommendation.

Interpreting the findings, the majority of respondents affirmed that Makerere University follows a sequential process for external examinations, emphasizing the need for approval at each stage. The first stage involves the student submitting a letter of intent, followed by the school board's research completion and the examiner's allocation. The process further includes the appointment of internal and external examiners, seeking approval from higher degree committees, and final approval by the Deputy Principal and Principal. Participants emphasized the importance of adherence to these steps to maintain the integrity of the external examination process.

Quotes from participants provided additional insights into the process, highlighting the role of the Directorate of DRGT upon the student's submission of a letter of intent and the initiation of the process when the student notifies the supervisor of readiness for examination. Some participants expressed the importance of considering a potential pool of examiners and the role of the Dean's office in communication.

While the study suggests that Makerere University generally adheres to external examination processes, it acknowledges process abuse, mainly due to issues such as poor remuneration leading to external examiners failing to submit reports. Additionally, the study points out that Makerere University does not conduct institutional induction for external examiners, contrasting with practices in other universities.

Research Question 4

What is the extent of involvement of key individuals in the university's external examination procedures?

A documentary review and interview revealed various university officers and groups, as illustrated in Figure 3, who manage external examinations for PhD theses at Makerere University.

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Table 3: Responses to Performance Measurements

Theme	Sub-themes	Responses	Sub-theme 1
Employment of performance measurements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ excel sheet to track progress ▪ appreciation letter by the deputy principal ▪ No systematic tracking mechanisms are in place for M&E ▪ keeping records ▪ monitoring and evaluation ▪ performance appraisal ▪ registrars sending reports and reminders ▪ sending score sheets ▪ CEDAT with follow-up tool ▪ a formal policy on issues of plagiarism 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Setting Policies • Tracking mechanism • Performance appraisal • Monitoring and evaluation 	

Table 3 categorizes the responses into themes and sub-themes, revealing that Makerere University employs various performance measurement methods. These include using Excel sheets to track progress, sending appreciation letters by Deputy Principals, and utilizing a follow-up tool in the College of Engineering, Design, Art, and Technology (CEDAT). However, a notable gap exists in the absence of systematic tracking mechanisms for monitoring and evaluation, and there is no formal policy addressing plagiarism issues.

The results indicate that Makerere University's performance measurement system for external examinations incorporates email communication, record-keeping, and performance appraisals. External examiners are motivated through appreciation letters. Nevertheless, the concerns of Deputy Principals and Deans underscore the need for increased recognition and remuneration for internal and external examiners. The study highlights the urgency of strengthening monitoring and tracking systems for all graduate programs, revising allowances for external examiners, and acknowledging the contributions of internal examiners.

Discussion of Findings

The outcomes derived from the external examination system at Makerere University agree with existing research in higher education. Medland's (2015) investigation in the United Kingdom (UK) accentuated the significance of augmenting professionalism, calibrating academic standards, and delineating roles in external examinations across universities (Medland, 2015). This parallels the current study's emphasis on the adherence to principles at Makerere University. Challenges delineated by Silver and Williams (1996), Gaunt (1999), and Sadler (2011) about national standards and comparability are resonant with the present study's exploration of adherence to principles, specifically Pryor's 5Ps model of strategic management. Difficulties identified in ensuring reliability in external examining, as articulated by Gaunt, mirror challenges identified in the current research, including process abuse and insufficient remuneration, causing delays and necessitating attention within the Makerere University context. Unegbu and Ezeobi's (2017) study on external examiners in Nigerian universities, emphasizing their role in maintaining academic standards and serving as impartial advisors, aligns with positive perceptions of external examination in the current study, substantiating a consistent theme of external examiners contributing to quality control and assurance. Hannan and Silver's (2004) examination of academics' willingness to serve as external examiners, despite competing demands, aligns with motivations suggested by the current study, emphasizing the value placed on reciprocity and information gathering, even in the absence of robust support from home institutions.

In response to the second research question, the examination of Makerere University's adherence to Pryor's 5Ps model for external examination unveils a substantial alignment between participant-perceived principles and official university documentation. As depicted in Figure 4.1, respondents recognize fundamental principles such as expertise, competence, excellence, professionalism, confidentiality, timeliness, and integrity as imperative in selecting external examiners. The scrutiny of Makerere University's graduate handbook reinforces these principles, accentuating external examiners' roles in evaluating instruments, student performance, and marking process reliability, aligning with Senate regulations. The literature review, citing further substantiates the positive impact of external examination practices in maintaining academic standards and ensuring educational quality and consistency. These findings align with the broader literature on external examining, including (Golden et al., 2020) emphasis on guidelines in appointing external examiners and the discourse on external examining practices in the UK and beyond, highlighting the diverse roles of external examiners. (Bloxham & Boyd, 2012) exploration of the purpose of external examining aligns with the current study's focus on principles and standards, emphasizing

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the importance of appointing examiners from institutions known for defending academic standards, contributing to a comprehensive understanding of effective external examination practices.

The investigation into the alignment of external examination processes at Makerere University with Pryor's 5Ps strategic management model reveals a comprehensive and step-by-step approach to the external examination process. The study delineates various stages (Wray et al., 2018), such as the submission of a student's letter of intent, the nomination of examiners by the Dean and Deputy Principal, the assignment of internal and external examiners, and the approval by higher degree committees. The responses indicate a well-regulated and structured process at the University, underscoring the significance of strict adherence to maintain the integrity of the external examination process. The literature review complements these findings by providing insights into external examining practices in diverse international contexts, such as the US and the UK. While the study suggests overall adherence to external examination processes at Makerere University, it acknowledges challenges like process abuse, remuneration issues leading to delays, and the lack of institutional induction for external examiners. These challenges align with broader concerns in the literature about upholding academic standards and the necessity for clear guidelines and support for external examiners, highlighting the need for continuous improvement in the University's examination practices.

The research findings on the alignment between individuals involved in the external examination process at Makerere University and the people component of Pryor's 5Ps model reveal a complex landscape marked by conflicts, interference, and procedural delays. The study identifies various university officers and groups responsible for managing external examinations, as outlined in Figure 1, but notes discrepancies between the designated roles and the actual practices. Conflicts arise from the interference of some officers, such as principals, in appointing external examiners contrary to university policy. Prolonged committee meetings and contested choices for external examiners further contribute to delays in the examination process. Recommendations include reinforcing adherence to university policies, providing training for relevant personnel, and promoting timely student compliance with submission procedures. The literature review supplements these findings by emphasizing the crucial role of individuals, especially the quality of external examiners, in determining the success of the external examination process (Bloxham & Price, 2015). Studies from various contexts highlight the importance of organizational culture and effective management practices in universities, aligning with the challenges at Makerere University. The study extends the existing literature by applying Pryor's 5Ps model to assess the external examination process, providing a unique perspective on aligning people with strategic management components (Kapaanda & Benedict, 2019).

The research findings on Makerere University's external examination, analyzed through Pryor's 5Ps strategic management model, indicate a varied landscape of performance measurement practices. The University employs diverse methods, including Excel sheets, appreciation letters, and follow-up tools in specific departments. Notably, there is a lack of systematic tracking mechanisms for monitoring and evaluation, and a formal policy addressing plagiarism is absent. The results suggest a need for enhanced performance measurement practices, emphasizing robust monitoring and tracking systems for graduate programs. The literature review provides valuable context, with studies from various countries highlighting challenges and improvements in performance measurement in higher education (Al-Hosaini & Sofian, 2015). The findings underscore the importance of recognizing and remunerating examiners and suggest potential improvements in the broader university performance measurement system (Maeda & Socha-Dietrich, 2021). The study aligns with previous research emphasizing the need for balanced indicators and participatory-oriented monitoring mechanisms. Overall, it calls for Makerere University to strengthen its performance measurement practices for external examinations, drawing on insights from international experiences and addressing specific gaps identified within the institution.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the examination of Makerere University's external examination aligns with prior research in higher education, emphasizing the importance of professionalism, academic standards calibration, and role clarity. The challenges identified, such as those related to national standards and comparability, echo broader discussions in the literature. The positive perceptions of external examination align with its recognized role in maintaining academic standards and serving as impartial advisors, as highlighted in studies from different contexts. The study's contribution lies in its contextualization within the 5Ps model, providing nuanced insights into the specific challenges and adherence to principles at Makerere University. The investigation enriches the existing literature, offering valuable perspectives on the intricacies of external examination practices and providing a foundation for continuous improvement.

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Recommendations

Based on the findings, Makerere University should continue reinforcing adherence to its policies and procedures, ensuring that external examination practices align with the principles outlined in Pryor's 5Ps model. Training relevant personnel involved in the external examination process could enhance clarity and efficiency. Additionally, measures to address conflicts and procedural delays, such as streamlining committee meetings and establishing transparent nomination processes, are essential for maintaining the integrity and timeliness of the external examination system. The University should consider instituting institutional inductions for external examiners and exploring mechanisms for addressing remuneration issues to mitigate delays. These recommendations aim to foster a more robust and effective external examination system at Makerere University.

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Qualitative Study on In - Service Teachers' Programme and Future Curriculum Implementation among Secondary Schools in Kaduna State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The paper assessed qualitative study of in - service teachers' programme and future curriculum implementation in secondary schools of Kaduna State. In - service training is important for a successful implementation and realization secondary education objectives in the study area. It remains the only option that allows every teacher to be re - trained and even acquire high knowledge on what would help to effectively implement school curriculum at this level of Nigeria' s education system. Secondary sources of data collection were adopted in this study. Of course, the paper was qualitative research in nature and have discussed the followings namely concepts of a teacher and teacher education, objectives of teacher education, future curriculum and implementation of secondary school curriculum viz-a-viz in - service teachers. Among the challenges teachers in Nigeria are faced with today includes poor self - study attitude and poor motivation which has beam a cog in the wheel of their professional growth. Absence of materials with which to work dampens the morale of teachers as also been identified as well as inability of some training institutions to develop in them skills and attitudes to explore avenues of updating their knowledge. A significant number of these teachers do not deem it necessary to set standards and device means of assessing their progress and failures with the view of making adjustments and innovations that can bring about improved performance. It thus concluded that in order to meet up with the future trend in the training of the learners, government at all levels should put on all necessary materials in place to educate our teachers who are the agent of change in the society. It recommended among others that government should make teacher education programme attractive in terms of provision of adequate facilities and other incentives that will revamp the entire programmes.

Keywords: Future curriculum, Implementation, In - Service Training, Secondary Education, Teacher Education

Introduction

Education is key for socio - economic empowerment and poverty reduction of a nation. It is thus the springboard for personal and societal progress and development (Omajoko, 2009). This means that for any meaningful progress and development to take place in any society, there should be a sound and functional system which will enhance personal and societal growth and development in all areas of human endeavour. In support of this, Odawn and Akpata (2008) believed that education is the key that unlocks the door to modernization. Teachers are the key factor that holds the key to this door. This implies that teachers are the agent of change in the society who can make the lofty ideas of the educational system a reality. The teacher translates the educational policies and programmes to bring about the needed changes in the society. In this respect, the learner is at the centre of all these and teacher on his part acts as the pilot of the educational process. The way the teacher thus interprets the curriculum will have a direct bearing on the level of training received after the pre - service training. Therefore, a well - trained teacher will bring about improved standard of education and consequently the general developmental process of the country. However, any teacher not trained via refresher course or what is referred to as in - service training would not be effective to implement the secondary school curriculum as much as is expected. This perhaps was the reason adduced that no education can rise above its teachers and that no nation can rise above its teachers. This paper will be of great benefit

to the classroom teachers in the implementation of school curriculum, guide parents on how to their children are fairing and for the government, on the need to fund teacher education programme and to encourage more teachers to go for in - service training to update their professional knowledge from time to time and to the policy makers, in their policy formation as regards to teacher education programme not only in Kaduna State but Nigeria at large.

In-Service Teachers at the Secondary Schools

It is not everybody that handles a chalk before the learners that is regarded as a teacher. A teacher is that person who is capable of making rational human and creative decisions regarding the teaching act. In essence, teachers are mediator of learning, controller of students' behaviour, act as parent substitute, judge of achievement, curriculum developer, interpreter and researcher as public servant. In all these, they require adequate knowledge and skills to be able to undertake specific assignment bequeath to them in the line of duty. This form of education can be obtained through what is known as in - service education. In - service education can simply be defined as the relevant courses and activities in which a serving teacher may participate to upgrade his professional knowledge, skills, and competence in the teaching profession. Therefore, it encompasses all forms of education and training given to a teacher who is already on the job of teaching and learning. In - service education is also referred to as continuing education that is designed for the retraining, reskilling and updating the knowledge of manpower. According to UNESCO in Osamwonyi (2016) continuing education can be regarded as the entire body of educational processes whatever the content level and method, whether formal or otherwise, whether they prolong or replace initial education in schools, colleges and universities as well as in apprenticeship, whereby persons regarded as adults by the society to which they belong develop their abilities, enrich their knowledge, improve their technical or professional qualifications or turn them in a new direction and bring about changes in their attitudes or behaviour in the two fold perspective of full personal development and participation on balance and independent social, economic and cultural development.

The quality of teacher's performance at his/her duty post as a professional is an important thing to discuss, considering its significant role in secondary school curriculum implementation as evident in student achievement (Canales and Maldonado, 2018). But this role cannot be separated from the educational context, student characteristics, and school factors (Ambussaidi and Yang, 2019). In addition, the ability of teachers to be confident, create a comfortable climate for students, maintain interaction and contact with students can increase student involvement in learning (Durksen, Way, Bobis, Anderson, Skilling and Martin, 2017). Obviously, the higher the comfort of the teachers with the school, the increase its influence on their performance in the school (Sebastian, Herman and Reinke, 2019). While the pressure experienced by a teacher in a school that is sourced from various things and aspects will certainly reduce performance (Erichsen and Reynolds, 2019). The low performance of students in secondary schools, dynamic society and its needs, continues changes in expectations about the quality and assessment of education, rapid changes in science and technology lead the school and teachers to face difficulties with this respect to parents and society. In fact, the issues for teachers and teachers' education to fulfill these requirements are continuing and complex (Moeini in Medard, 2017).

In-Service Teacher Education Programme

In - service teacher training has grown in importance and status and has developed as a global trend for decades. Public organizations like schools try to increase their capabilities by investing more in employees (teacher) training. Moreover, it encourages competency of employees (teachers) for both their own benefit and the benefit of others (Rodrigues in Medard, 2017). In a career system, initial training is of paramount in the effective and efficient work performance. The newly recruited employees enter into an establishment without specific expertise for the job (Fraser cited by Medard, 2017). In fact, initial training offers general preparation in public service delivery. Such training offers specific preparation for a new function after or before transfer or promotion. Although, it is clear that in - service training programmes for employee (teachers) on work performance are increasingly drawing attention in public organization in view of their under - performance (URT, 2012). The fact is, it is no longer sufficient to recruit and retains the best employees but, organizations have to impart skills and enhance their capabilities through learning, supportive environment and shared knowledge. The quality of employees through training programs is the major factors in determining long term success of public organizations.

"Teachers" in the educational process refers to the person who instructs and promote the teaching-learning processes. He assumes various capacities as educator, instructor, tutor, lecturer, counsellor and so on. Whereas, education on the other hand is defined as a tool used for the integration of individuals into the society so that he/she can achieve self - realization, develop national consciousness, promote unity and strive for social, economic, political, scientific, cultural and technological progress. Teacher education therefore is that aspect of education which deals with the acquisition of practical and applied skills

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in the teaching profession (Apeh, 2010). This means that teacher education can be viewed to as professional education of teachers towards attainment of attitudes, skill and knowledge considered desirable so as to make them efficient and effective in their work in accordance with the needs of the society at any point in time. A good teacher educational programme must assist the individual teacher to grow and develop as a person, provide him with the necessary skills and professional competence that will assist him to become not only an effective teacher but also enviable community leader that will be able to project into future in terms of new trends in teaching and learning process.

Future Curriculum at Secondary Education

Future curriculum is an attempt to project into the future based on the past and present events or happening towards the type of education the learners may receive in order to prepare them for the likely changes that may occur in the nearer future. It is a design or planning of the whole education programme for the betterment of a future society (Saedah and Mohammed, 2003). Therefore, future curriculum is developed today for tomorrow based on systematic forecasting of what the system should be. Siraj (2015) identified two (2) main elements of concern in future curriculum to include: identifying main events with high probabilities to happen in the future - related to education for future society; and forecasting on various analysis dimension which relates to education for future society which include analysis on socio-economic politics, human resources, energy sources, agriculture. Future curriculum emerged as a result of study on future probabilities within a certain time frame. Analysis as carried out to ascertain how particular phenomenon have affected the results of policy implementation or action taken by a country (Longstreet and Shane 2009). This implies that it is a systematic and technical study of the knowledge of past and present conditions with the aim of predicting and designing what would happen in the future. The aim according to Glenn and Garden (2008) as applicable to this work among others include to:

1. Assist policy makers and curriculum developers of institution and the country to outline action plans in order to avoid making false assumptions about the future curriculum of our schools.
2. Illustrate possibilities and choices about the future to aid policy makers and curriculum developers of institutions and country to their attempts to make critical decisions and
3. Explain probabilities of preferred futures. In a nutshell future curriculum is viewed as systematic discipline to study probable future within a certain time frame. More so, analysis is carried out to ascertain how particular situations and environment could be affected as a result of policy implementation.

In-Service Teachers on Implementation of Future Curriculum at the Secondary Schools

1. Information Acquisition

The inevitability of this strategy hinges on the premise that the wider the range of opportunities known to an individual, the wiser his choice will become and the wider the horizon of knowledge will be. Thus, as a professional, a teacher's learning (acquisition of current information) should continue throughout his life time. This is contrary to the assumption that teacher practically completed his systematic learning as soon as the coveted certificate is obtained. This strategy hinges on the assumption that the teacher's own systematic learning is only well started when he graduates from his formal programme of teaching training. Teacher education should aim at instilling the attitude of continuous learning throughout his life.

Emphasis of teacher education should be on assisting the student-teacher knows how to plan his own systematic learning. Concern of strategy is to help build up the learner's informational background as well assisting the teacher to develop the attitude, skills and abilities necessary to continuously increase and appraise his store of information while still on the job. The modern teacher needs and deserves adequate preparation to continue systematic learning following the completion of his formal course. Buttressing this necessity, Onuh (2009) posits thus:

There are many reasons why the modern teacher cannot afford to stop growing professionally once he gets on the job in the first place, stagnation may lead to grumping, unhappiness, and irritation... there is danger that continuous repetition of the same assignments and discussions will make the teaching job a boring one instead of the challenging one it can be.

Information acquisition can make teaching a very pleasant and exhilarating experience. It gives satisfaction to the teacher and serves as a model for the students to emulate. Learners quickly catch the enthusiasm of a teacher who is constantly growing in knowledge and in its use. Accordingly, professional magazines, journals and books offer an excellent resource for meeting the desire of a professional teacher who must keep abreast of current thinking in his field of specialization. Perhaps this is what informed Ogbe (2010) to postulate that: "For those who work on the growing edge of science.... Only a few months may elapse before something which was easily taken for granted must be unlearned or transformed to fit the new state of knowledge."

In the light of this, it behooves those who teach and use knowledge keep abreast with new knowledge in their fields. Through professional acquisition of information, teachers can find solutions to their professional growth, which if left unchecked may inhibit their professional growth in terms of facilitating learning.

2. Appraisal Technique

This strategy deals with the analysis and interpretation of all valid data and information about an individual for the purpose of understanding in terms of his interests, aptitudes, capability and personality. Through this device, an individual's assets and liabilities are understood. To set the stage for systematic change in activities that will culminate in improvement, it is desirable for the teacher to continually diagnose what he is doing why he is doing, and how it is succeeding. The assumption here is that the changes of happiness and success as a teacher enhanced by continuous self-diagnosis. Some of the potent approaches to embark upon in order to identify teacher's assets and liabilities for the purpose of teaching are: comparative check on personal efficiency using one teaching method versus efficiency in using another method, voluntary and continuing colleague discussion or seminar by teachers of a particular course, visiting a colleague class for the purpose of evaluating and improving personal performance, self-constructed evaluative questionnaire or check lists to be filled by students and soliciting the assistance of supervisors in evaluating personal teaching.

3. Evaluation Strategy

Following a period of functioning, any professional would want to ascertain the degree of success or failures. Systematic evaluation in the classroom has long been seen as the exclusive responsibilities of the teacher. Such control of evaluative processes has resulted to extreme students dependence on the teacher for evaluative activities. It has led to learner being equipped to evaluate for learning purpose which involve practice in setting up goals, diagnosing needs through measurement, and in planning future activities.

4. Interpersonal Relationship

It has been assumed by too many teachers that the only measure front for improvement of professional activities was in the classroom. The current thinking is that there are many key areas outside the classroom where potentialities are bound for professional enhancement. For instance, an atmosphere of cooperation among teachers and attitudes sharing ideas and materials can enhance the art teaching. In fact, interpersonal relationships are skills that individuals need to become competent helpers (Abah, 2009). Teachers are facilitators of learning. They need interpersonal relationship skills to mature professionally. Abah (2009), remarks that most difficult problems in living are interpersonal in nature. It becomes necessary therefore to help individuals develop the skills needed for establishing and maintaining effective interpersonal relationship. For any successful teaching-learning and/or implementing situation, the individuals concerned must have a well - developed repertory of interpersonal skills. Teachers need the skills to learn about themselves and others because they are teachers of others and not just part of the curriculum. Abah (2009) contend that the starting point for education is the need for self - development as a person. This enables the teacher become someone who is competent to help others develop.

Challenges of Pre - Service Teachers in the future Curriculum Delivery at Secondary Schools in Kaduna State

A good number of practicing teachers in Nigeria today possess poor self - study attitude. Their dispositions towards research leave much to be desired. This can be attributed to the wrong notion that learning ends at graduation and that knowledge thus acquired is sufficient to allow for maximum performance on their jobs. To such teacher, knowledge is not dynamic, hence to engage in further search for current information is a mere waste of time. The problem is further compounded by the inability of some training institutions to develop in them skills and attitudes to explore avenues of updating their knowledge. Thus, the majority of today's teachers erroneously think they have acquired enough for life in the college. This general apathy towards self -improvement extended to workshops, seminars and conferences. Hardly to teachers avail themselves of these opportunities to acquire professional skills for optimal performance. The result is stagnation in professional growth which should not be allowed into the 21st century. There is a general lack of basic skills in self - appraisal by teachers. A significant number of teachers do not deem it necessary to set standards and device means of assessing their progress and failures with the view of making adjustments and innovations that can bring about improved performance.

Equally noticed today is the wrong perception of learning as teacher curriculum centered is opposed to child - centered, Hence the child's interest and needs plays a secondary role in guiding the course of teaching - learning in most schools. Education should be seen as child - centered and all teaching - learning activities should revolve around this philosophy. Ability to make realistic decision is an important asset to any individual. Unfortunately, many teachers are handicapped to train students for decision-making processes. To such teachers, decision-making is an exclusive responsibility of the adult on behalf of the

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child. The child therefore grows up ill - equipped to make realistic decision and accept responsibility for whatever the aftermath would be.

Record keeping systems of contemporary teachers leave much desired. Professional teachers should be able not only to acquire data but also, competent enough to store, retrieve and utilize such data for decision making and assessing personal growth in their profession. Closely allied to the above is the poor and unprofessional practice of continuous assessment by some teachers. Many have not come to terms with the implications of continuous assessment. Worst still, a significant number of teachers are ill-equipped to continuously assess students. Cognitive, as opposed to psychomotor and effective domains inclusive appears to be the only area of assessment. Even then, continuous assessment ought to be teacher-oriented and not just for labeling students. An area that has constituted a cog in the wheel of professional growth of teachers is motivation. Absence of materials with which to work dampens the morale of teachers, hence hindering their desire to improve themselves professionally. Teachers need motivation, recognition and appreciation to grow professionally in the practice of teaching. Against the backdrop of the current professional status of the teacher, counseling strategies are advanced to improve the practice of teaching by professional teachers in the 21st century (Ogbe, 2010).

Conclusion

Future curriculum is very vital in policy making and curriculum development at all educational level of an institution and country in general. In order to embrace new education policies and implementation of curriculum content for future delivery, there is the need for restructuring of teacher education programme in Nigeria to significantly prepare educators. Since teachers that are Nigerian educators are agents of change in the society. There is every need to train and retrain them in order to meet up with the future trends in the training of the learners, government at all levels should put on all necessary materials in place to educate our teachers who are the agents of change in the society.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion, the following recommendations were made:

1. Teachers should be trained and retrained from time to time in the area of school activities' assessments and evaluation in order to take advantage of the past and current trends in teaching and learning process to project into the likely future changes in the needs of the learner and society;
2. Curriculum planners and educational policy makers should provide a structure for teachers in their different disciplines the correct instrument for assessing and evaluating their learners with view of changes in the curriculum; and
3. Teacher education programmes should be adequately funded, in order for the pre-service and in-service teachers should be acquainted with necessary skills in assessing and evaluating students' academic progress in view of currents trends in teaching and learning process in relation to future changes in learners and society needs.

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Impacts of Women Librarian's Participation in Community Development Projects in Zaria Metropolis of Kaduna State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the impact of women's librarian participation in community development projects in Zaria Metropolis, Kaduna State, Nigeria. Two research questions were posed to guide the study. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The population of the study was 260 women Librarians in Zaria Metropolis, Kaduna State. The sample of the study was 176 women librarians selected through a purposive sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire developed by the researchers. The instrument for data collection was validated by three experts. The consistency of the instrument was ensured using Cronbach Alpha with a reliability co-efficient of 0.86. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. A mean score of 2.53 was used as a decision rule. The findings revealed the factors that hinder women librarians' participation in community development projects, range from poor financial status, cultural limitations on women, and gender base in project selection. The findings also revealed strategies for effective implementation of women librarians' participation in community development projects, which ranges from encouraging women librarians' participation in development activities to ensuring authentic participation and maintaining cordial relationships with women. It was recommended that women should be given equal rights and opportunities to participate in the decision-making process

Keywords: Women Librarian, Gender, Community development projects.

Introduction

Before the 21st century, Nigeria women were restricted by custom, standards and religion in the society. The elevated degree of ignorance among women further deteriorates the mishap. Also, women were thought of as the main really great for child-bearing and support, food readiness and taking care of the entire relations, to centered on cultivating and unimportant business, (Kay & Higuera, 2019). Further stated, women most significant stores come from the current enlightening mores which consign the women to the kitchen and distribute them the place of housewife or mother. Routinely, the portrayal of women has been that of a wife/spouse or mother while their obligation was to really focus on the man and nothing too. In International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA) (2019) reported that, out of a rough 2.4 billion oppressed individuals on the planet more than 66% are women. Further explanation made sense that women hopeless destitution in demands for sufficient food, water and medical services. Also, women need" admittance to the basic assets of credit, land, and inheritance. Considering the above mentioned clearly, women are denied decisions and potential open doors and decision-making both at home and locally is immaterial. In most piece of Nigeria, similar to North-West Nigeria, women are not approved to take part or participate in some community/local development projects/undertakings or exercises in the society. Enemuo, (2011) found that the standard of women is collectively and politically avoided from partaking in community development projects, arranging/decision-marking, and dynamic cycles. Research by Imhabekhai, (2019) posits that women

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who address an impressive extent of the all-out populace in Nigeria are illiterates. In support, Gbenga and James, (2019) affirmed that women procure not as much since they are in fields that are less fundamental and less compensated which additionally denies them from taking part in community development projects. It further explained that the absence of dynamic power influences women politically in society.

Without a doubt, Ike, (2015) reported that women need to get consent from their husbands/spouses to go to an exercise or work outside the home. They were not given the option to cast a ballot in a few delicate situations, community denied them the open doors, for example, they needed the dynamic ability to take interest on an equivalent premise with men. One of the presumptions behind the development is that everybody has something to add to the existence of the community. From this guess, it becomes relevant that women who comprise an enormous extent of Nigeria's populace could add to the existence of their community (Asogwa, 2019). Also, difficulties militating against the participation of women in community development projects for example absence of the executives' expertise, clashes, literacy/obliviousness, misappropriation of societal assets, unfortunate carry out of open assets, pay off and debasement among the partners, absence of preparation systems, absence of co-activity among partners and community pioneers, absence of managerial abilities, unfortunate responsibility, unfortunate initiative abilities, deficient exposure, orientation segregation, absence of women association, and self - centered interest of certain pioneers (Ewelum & Madu 2016). It depends on these difficulties that the review plan to give an outline about a few calculated systems like community development that could assist with tending to the above challenges by women librarians. Women librarians emerged as the Association for the Welfare of Women Librarians in Nigeria (AWWLIN) order wise referred to as AWLIN in 2013. This was for the purpose of consolidating the unity of the entire Women Librarians, archivists, and Information Scientists in Nigeria as a body of practitioners in the profession. Also, promoting their welfare in order to contribute positively and effectively to the utilization of the educational, cultural, and information resources of Nigeria and to enhance the dignity of women in Nigeria. This came with the birth of the Kaduna State AWLIN in 2019. However, the fact that the Association of Women Librarians in Nigeria (AWLIN) Kaduna State Chapter had to form, organize, and hold conferences, seminars and workshops on community development projects and gender empowerment, AWLIN had suggested and agreed that Nigeria women are not adequately empowered in their societies and aware of the needs for women to participate in community development projects in order to empower the girl child and women. So that they could be strong and resourceful, able to give their maximum contribution to develop Kaduna state and Nigeria as a whole. The participation of women librarians in community development projects is a means to achieve the goals of development, by uniting all women interested in Librarianship, Archivist and Information Scientists establish and develop libraries, information and resource centers, readership promotion and bridge the digital divide, collaborate with Non-Governmental organizations (NGOs) and other stakeholders in the implementation of global and regional commitment for girls and women empowerment/initiatives through gender awareness, more efficient economy-wide policies. AWLIN Kaduna State Chapter has also been contributing to the achievement of economic growth and helping in identifying the social goals, of the communities or societies which it's empowering. More so, initiating the participation of women increases in decision-making at all levels.

Community development is the course of progress that works on the existence of individuals in the community. As per Huberman, Tom, and Laura, (2014) characterized community development as a cycle which includes subjectively and quantitatively changing individuals, their current circumstance, values and social cycles. This infers that for any significant developmental projects to take place, all kinds of people should take an interest. From the abovementioned, obviously community development requires the endeavors of residents both physical and material, (Kelly and Caputo, 2016). It is on this ground that women were perceived as one of the gatherings in the society whose endeavors are profoundly required for the development of community projects. Ewelum and Mbara, (2015) characterized community development as development advance a better living for the entire society. Functionally, community development can be characterized as the cycle by which a community come all in all likewise works helpfully toward finding goals to the difficulties that impact their local communities. It is vital to understanding the outline of community development since it helps in rural development, advancement of educational centres/schools/instructive focuses and their libraries, improvement of wellbeing in the community, agricultural growth and the improvement in the general expectations for everyday comforts of individuals at the local community level. Subsequently, a bunch of people residing commonly in an exact spot, for example, a region made up of a community. Significantly, UNDP. (2018) proposed that to personality any community development projects which could works on the existences of the community have attributes which are widespread, for example, getting affects by all individuals impacted by change, regard nearby information and utilize neighborhood ability, assemble neighborhood limit, that is long heave community maintainability relies upon creating human and social capacities and compelling, straightforward correspondence. Considering the above affirmation, it basic to express that there is, no community development projects that

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can be effectively achieved without the dynamic association and cooperation of women in such society. On this position, it becomes fundamental for the help of women cooperation in community development project through activation.

Rally is one of the fundamental procedures of community development project. Rally can be characterized as an endeavor to bring both human and non-human together to embrace formative exercises or project to accomplish reasonable advancement. In Ajayi and Otuya, (2016), assembly is the most common way of placing individuals into status for dynamic help or of stimulating the interest and cognizance of a gathering in a programme, which would be good for them. There is a presumption that, the expected members have not become mindful of the presence, the goals or the benefits to be gotten from the program. Kelly and Caputo, (2016) as he would like to think noticed that rally and refinement of the community empowers the supporters of the project to have the amazing chance to examine exchange and answer questions which on the off chance that not treated at beginning phase will later mischief the venture. United Nations Development Programmes (UNDP), (2016) noticed that rallying includes making consciousness of specific issues existing community and which need earnest consideration. Functionally, rally subsequently, is giving sufficient information concerning a programme items and items to get the help and cooperation of individuals in the programme. Huberman, Tom and Laura, (2014) noticed that most development revolved around individuals and to this end perhaps of the most tireless worry being developed writing is about ways individuals might rally for given programs or for the goal of given issues that encroach on development itself. In this way, obviously any community which neglects to foster the abilities and useful gifts of her kin and to successfully rally and use such abilities to change the community economy could not be able to accomplish genuine turn on of the developments. To that end, rally is significant for compelling implementation of any community development projects.

However, other strategies for powerful implementation of proof based women librarian's cooperation in community development projects as placed by UNDP Women, (2018), incorporate the followings: to get solid authority, to lay out a conventional design, to draw in different associations, community pioneers, and occupants, to guarantee bona fide support and shared navigation, to guarantee legitimate and useful jobs for youngsters, to foster a common vision, to direct a necessities evaluation, to make a well thought out course of action, to carry out commonly building up systems, to think up a gathering pledges procedure, to lay out compelling channels for interior correspondence, to teach the community women, to direct process and result assessments, and to assess the community preparation exertion independently. Also, according to Huberman, Tom and Laura (2014) and UNDP, (2016) who reported that, Women librarians could play a vital role in improving access to information in their communities among women about the importance of women's participation in community development projects. Such as helping to create and manage community schools or public libraries, provide literacy training and facilitate access to digital resources, promote gender equality and advocate for women's rights, challenge gender discrimination and stereotypes, engaging women librarian's in decision-making processes as it can affect their community development project, building supportive networks for women can connect, share experiences and ideas, and provide mutual support for each other, assist to promote health education, provide access to health resources, and advocate for health policies that benefit women and their families, encourage collaboration among women, other community members and stakeholders which may assist them to build strong partnerships and promote collective action towards achieving common goals, assist in promoting community dialogue and facilitate community-based initiatives, lead to improvements in democratic governance and the protection of human rights, celebrating the successes of women, their achievements and contributions to community development, can also lead to a vital economic benefits to the development of their communities (IFLA, 2019).

Therefore, community development projects will be sustained by creating opportunities for women's continued participation in community development projects. Ewelum and Madu (2016) and Ugwu, (2010) likewise proposed strategies for development for women librarian's interest in community development projects, which include: assembling women for social change, security of finished projects, satisfactory use of accessible resources, giving the connection between the community and the government, non-governmental organizations or donors, goals of struggles and conflict as they emerge in the communities, empowering women interest, being developing exercises, guaranteeing that women air their perspectives, including women in checking and assessment of undertakings, testing improper way of behaving or outer factors, overseeing and raising of assets through various sources, keeping up with cheerful relationship with women, prioritization of community needs, giving sufficient information to the women assuming requirements emerge, taking on straightforward authority among the women, including women in settling community issues, coordinating authority preparing for pioneers, incorporating women in developing projects, development of imposing associations, and utilization of incorporated rustic turn of events (Ike, 2015).

More so, an efficacious rally emphasizes public involvement to generate fresh concepts and resources inside the community. Therefore, this calls for the involvement of women librarian's in the project's decision-making, planning and execution. Also by employing women librarian and others in community women or

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initiatives, activation encourages residents to take part in community development projects. Women librarian’s active involvement could assist any community development initiatives as they undertake success. Furthermore, this can promote self-assistance and makes best use of available human and material resources for community development projects for effective execution of community development projects by women librarians in Zaria metropolis, Kaduna State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study:

The objectives of this research are:

1. Identify the problems that hinder the effective implementation of women librarian's participation in community development projects.
2. Assess the strategies for effective implementation of women librarians’ participation in community development projects.

Research Questions:

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the problems that hinder the effective implementation of women librarian's participation in community development projects?
2. What are the strategies for effective implementation of women librarians' participation in community development projects?
 - a. projects?

Methodology

The researcher adopted descriptive survey design. The study was carried out in Zaria Metropolis, Kaduna State, Nigeria. The population of the study was 260 women librarians in tertiary institutions libraries from Zaria Metropolis, Kaduna State, Nigeria. The sample of the study was 260 women librarian's using purposive sampling technique. Research instrument for data collection was structured questionnaire developed by the researcher. Research instrument for data collections was subjected to content and face validated by experts, among which was Measure and Evaluation, Librarians and Community Leaders. Consistency of the instrument was ensured using Cronbach Alpha method which yielded reliability co-efficient of 0.82. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. A mean score of 2.42 was used to make decision. Also criterion mean of 2.34 was used for decision.

Results

Research Question One:

What are the problems that hinder the effective implementation of women's participation in community development projects?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviations on Problems that Hinder Effective Implementation of Women Librarian's Participation in Community Development Projects

S/N	Items Statement – Problems	M	SD	Decision
1.	Traditional imitations/norms/religion	2.89	0.44	Agreed
2.	Lack of education/Illiteracy/ignorance	2.85	0.44	Agreed
3.	Lack of rallying strategies/ management know-how/Intercultural competence	2.72	0.45	Agreed
4.	Lack of co-operation between stakeholders/community capacity	2.71	0.45	Agreed
5.	Embezzlement of public fund/non-priority nature of projects/poor accountability	2.60	0.45	Agreed
6.	Lack of interest and involvement in participation	2.82	0.45	Agreed
7.	Poor leadership skills/ selfish interest of some leaders	2.91	0.44	Agreed
8.	Politically excluded/not given right to vote	2.66	0.46	Agreed
9.	Inadequate publicity and communication networking before and during the project	2.58	0.46	Agreed
10.	Miserable poverty/poor financial status of women	2.68	0.45	Agreed
11.	Gender equality/good for child bearing/house keeping	2.76	0.45	Agreed
12.	Conflicts/insecurity	2.70	0.45	Agreed
Cumulative		2.57	0.45	

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The result of data collected in respect to research question on in Table 1 revealed that all the items from 1 - 12 were agreed to be the problems that hinder effective implementation of women librarian's participation in community development projects. This is because all the items have mean responses above the criterion mean of 2.50, which indicates positive responses to the items, with a cumulative mean response of 2.57 and a standard deviation of 0.45 respectively. More so, respondents accepted that, all items in table 1 were problems and challenges that hinder effective implementation of women librarian's participation in community development projects.

Research Question Two:

What are the Strategies for Effective Implementation of Women's Participate in Community Development Projects?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviations on strategies for effective implementation of women's participate in community development projects

S/N	Items Statement - strategies for effective implementation	M	SD	Decision
1.	Women enlightenment and education and sustainable developments	2.99	0.43	Agreed
2.	Encouraging women participation in development activities	2.89	0.44	Agreed
3.	Involving women in monitoring and evaluation of community projects	2.79	0.45	Agreed
4.	Providing access to adequate information needs among women on community development project	2.69	0.45	Agreed
5.	Improvements in democratic governance and the protection of human rights	2.58	0.46	Agreed
6.	Success celebration and barriers as they maintaining cordial relationship among women	2.73	0.45	Agreed
7.	Ensuring genuine participation of women librarians in decision-making	2.76	0.45	Agreed
8.	Organizing leadership training for leaders and transparent leadership among the women	2.71	0.45	Agreed
9.	Building supportive networks for women to connect, share experiences and ideas and provide mutual support for advocacy activities	2.88	0.44	Agreed
10.	Incorporate women librarians in community development projects,	2.67	0.45	Agreed
	Aggregate Mean	2.77	0.45	

The research question two presented in Table 2 revealed in items 1- 10 were accepted by the women librarians as the strategies for effective implementation of women participate in community development projects such as; women enlightenment and education and sustainable development, encouraging women librarian’s participation in development activities, involving women in monitoring and evaluation of community projects, providing access to adequate information needs among women, improvements in democratic governance and the protection of human rights, success celebration and barriers as they maintaining cordial relationship among women, ensuring genuine participation of women librarians in decision-making, organizing leadership training for leaders and transparent leadership among the women, building supportive networks for women to connect, share experiences and ideas and provide mutual support for advocacy activities, assimilate women librarians in community development projects.

Items in Table 2 were with a total mean score of 2.77 and 0.45 standard deviation respectively. Therefore, they respondents accepted that all the items on the table were indication of acceptance on the strategies for effective implementation of women librarians participate in community development projects in Zaria metropolis of Kaduna State Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

Findings on research question one revealed in Table 1 as problems that hinder effective implementation of women's participation in community development projects. Result of data analyzed revealed that all the items in table were accepted by the respondents as challenges that hinder effective implementation of women librarian's participation in community development projects. Problems range from Traditional imitations/norms/religion, Lack of education/Illiteracy/ignorance, Lack of rallying strategies/ management know-how/Intercultural competence, Lack of co-operation between stakeholders/community capacity, Embezzlement of public fund/non-priority nature of projects/poor accountability, Lack of interest and involvement in participation, Poor leadership skills/ selfish interest of some leaders, Politically excluded/not given

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right to vote, Inadequate publicity and communication networking before and during the project, Miserable poverty/poor financial status of women, Gender equality/good for child bearing/housekeeping and Conflicts/insecurity.

At a close look this finding of the study is in consonant with the findings revealed that the current finding shared direct relationship with the findings of Imhabekhai, (2019) which revealed that there was mainstream of women- are communally and politically excluded from participating in community development projects, planning arid decision-making processes. Findings of Enemu, (2011) also revealed women librarians who represent a considerable proportion of the total population in Nigeria as illiterate which also one of the factors that hinder effective implementation of women's participation in community development projects, finding in agreement with Ewelum, and Madu, (2016) revealed that lack of decision-making power affects women librarian politically in community development project participation. More so, it was revealed that a lot of community development projects were started and abandoned before competing them as a result of insufficient funds while available funds were not properly utilized due to corruption, embezzlement and lack of transparency among stakeholders and leader.

Findings on research question two revealed that, the results in Table 2 revealed strategies for effective implementation of women librarian's participation in community development projects. These strategies range from Women enlightenment and education and sustainable development, Encouraging women librarians, participation in development activities, Involving women in monitoring and evaluation of community projects, Providing access to adequate information needs among women, Improvements in democratic governance and the protection of human rights, Success celebration and barriers as they maintaining cordial relationship among women, Ensuring genuine participation of women librarians in decision-making, Organizing leadership training for leaders and transparent leadership among the women, Building supportive networks for women to connect, share experiences and ideas and provide mutual support for advocacy activities and Assimilate women librarian's in community development projects.

Finding is in line with a study conducted by IFLA. (2019) which revealed that strategies for improving women librarian's participation in community development projects, which include: rallying of women for social change, protection of completed projects, adequate utilization of available resources, resolutions of conflicts and disagreement as they grow in such communities, encouraging women participation in development activities, ensuring that women air their views, involving women in monitoring and evaluation of projects, maintaining cordial relationship with women, providing adequate information to the women if needs arise, involving women in resolving community issues, and assimilate women in development projects. Finding is also in agreement with that of Kelly and Caputo, (2016) that rallying and creating awareness in the community enables the sponsors of the project to have the opportunity to discuss dialogue and answer questions which if not answered at earlier times which may affect the project in later time. It also agrees with that of UNDP. (2018) that, rallying in the rural areas involves using such strategies as mass media like town criers, video, posters, and pamphlets to motivate women and win their acceptance for change and development as well as involving the participants in the formation, implementation and evaluation of the community projects. This finding is in agreement with the finding of UNDP. (2016) that the organizing launchings, encourage community organization and ensuring sound leadership are also strategies for enhancing community development projects as stated.

Conclusion

From the finding of this study, it can be seen that, community leadership remains the mechanism by which individual's efforts are enabled to follow the continual swapping of energies and fulfillment for the instant community development projects. Therefore, in the process of bringing about attractive social changes in Zaria communities, a number of challenges persevere thus retarding the pace at which development is achieved. Such challenges can be ameliorated through some potential strategies that have been suggested in this research. Emphasizes are imperativeness on rallying, as the most basic strategies of community development projects which the concepts of rallying and community development were discussed. Research revealed that rallying is an essential aspect of engaging women librarians in community development projects because it supports meaningfully to the attainment of community development projects.

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Recommendations

The aim of this study was to investigate the impacts of women librarian's participation in community development projects in Zaria metropolis, Kaduna state, Nigeria based on the findings the following recommendations were made:

1. Women librarians should strive to identify and address the barriers that prevent women librarians from participating in community development projects. Such as cultural and social norms, discrimination, and lack of access to education and resources. Strive for equal rights and opportunities to participate in community development projects in the decision-making process. Providing community development training for community-based women to equip them with the knowledge and skills of community development projects to help them participate in their communities can lead to economic empowerment. Women librarian leaders should adopt transparent leadership to avoid women's doubt in their leadership role. As they may call on government to encourage felt-needs projects by providing financial assistance to communities' projects that are most significant. Also advocate for women's rights, challenge gender discrimination and stereotypes. Such enables women acceptance of participatory approach to community development projects and be optimistic for efficient rally of women in community development projects.
2. Women librarians should promote community education, mostly for girls and women as community development projects. Such can be done by sponsoring the educational programmes and resources. Participation in education sectors can aid in social economic subsidy and decrease in poverty and conform-ability. Make an effort to organize rallies that should include other community women to ensure active participation in development projects. By so doing solid collaboration and common goals will be achieved. Build supportive networks for women to connect, share experiences and ideas, and provide mutual support which includes women's groups, and counselling. Seek for political rights of women so as to be given the right to vote and be voted for in some sensitive positions in the communities and protection, human rights, and democratic governance. And improving access to information in their communities among other women about the importance of women's participation in community development projects. Such can help establish and oversee the affairs of the community libraries, arrange for information literacy training, and ease access to digital resources.

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